

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute

Volume 4: No. (2), June , 2021

President of the Journal : Prof. Dr. Ahmed Abd El Mageed

Editor –in-Chief : Prof. Dr. Shaaban Abd-Rabou

Secretary of the Journal

Prof. Dr. Shaaban Abd-Rabou

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Noha H. Ahmed

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Dr. Samah S. Ibrahim

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Dr. Gamal M. Hassan

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Editorial Board Abroad

Dr. Alvin M. Simmons, FRES

Research Entomologist
USDA, ARS, U.S. Vegetable Laboratory
2700 Savannah Highway
Charleston, SC 29414
USA

Prof. Dr. Dong Chu

College of Plant Health and Medicine
Qingdao Agricultural University
No. 700, Changcheng Road
Chengyang, Qingdao, Shandong 266109
CHINA

Dr. Doo-Sang Park,

Korean Collection for Type Cultures (KCTC),
Microbiological Resource Center,

Korea Research Institute of Bioscience & Biotechnology (KRIBB), 125 Gwahangno,
Yuseong, Daejeon 305-806,
SOUTH KOREA

Dr. Gregory A. Evans

USDA/ APHIS/ PPQ c/o Systematic Entomology Laboratory
Bldg 005, Room 137,
BARC-WEST 10300 Baltimore Ave.
Beltsville, MD 20705
USA

Prof. Dr. Hassan Ghahari

Department of Entomology
Science & Research Campus
Islamic Azad University
Poonak – Hesarak
Tehran
IRAN

Dr. HDR. Hélène Delatte

UMR "Peuplements Végétaux et Bio-agresseurs en Milieu Tropical"
CIRAD-3P 7, Chemin de l'IRAT
Ligne Paradis
97410 Saint Pierre
La Réunion
FRANCE

Egyptian Editorial Board

Prof. Dr. Mohamed Ibrahim Abdel Mageed

University of Ain Shames
Faculty of Agriculture,
Cairo,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mohamed Gomaa Abbass

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Aly Soliman

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Aly H. El-Sherbiny

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Eman Radwan

Central Agricultural Pesticides Laboratory,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Magdy Welson

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mahmoud El-Naggar

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Mohammad Hendi

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Prof. Dr. Talal Elabbassy

Plant Protection Research Institute,
Agricultural Research Center,
Dokki , Giza ,
EGYPT.

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute *is* an official journal of the Plant Protection Research Institute, *Agricultural* Research Center. It includes original research papers on basic and applied research in all aspects of plant protection. In additions to original research papers, also published reviews and scientific notes or short communications on critical issues relevant to plant protection. Subject areas include, but are not restricted to the following fields: Field pests, vegetable, aromatic, medicinal and ornamental plant pests, orchard pests, locust and grasshopper, beekeeping sericulture, spray technology, alternatives methods of control pests, survey and classification of agriculture pests and new biocontrol technology pests

Abbreviation of the Journal: Egypt. J. of Plant Prot. Res. Inst. `

Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute
Volume 4: No. (2), June , 2021

Contents

- 1- **Ahmed, Abdel-Monem Taha; Marwa, A. M. Abd-Allah and Maha, A. M. Tantawy (2021):** Susceptibility of the potato tuber moth *Phthorimaea operculella* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) to the *Autographa californica* multicapsid nucleopolyhedrovirus. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 157-167. **157-167**
- 2- **Omnia, M. N. El-Sahn (2021):** Population fluctuation of the floridana scale insect *Lindingaspis floridana* (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) on *Ficus benjamina* under greenhouse conditions in Cairo Governorate . Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 168 –181. **168 –181**
- 3- **Ahmed, Abdel-Monem Taha and Youssef, R. Hassan (2021):** Possibility for laboratory mass rearing of the potato tuber moth *Phthorimaea operculella* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) through simplified steps and procedures. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 182 –192. **182 –192**
- 4- **Hamdy, H. Mahmoud (2021):** Effect of soil type on the insect population associated with onion plants, with special attention to onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) and crop yield. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): **193 –205**.
- 5- **Majid, Navaeian; Hamid, Sakenin; Angélica, Maria Penteado-Dias; Najmeh, Samin; Reijo, Jussila and Shaaban, Abd-Rabou (2021):** On a collection of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) of Iran. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 206–217. **206–217**
- 6- **Atif, M. El-Hady and Amany, S.M. Abou-Lila (2021):** Influence of mobile phone radiation on brood area, pollen gathering and inoculation virgin queen in honeybees *Apis mellifera* (Hymenoptera: Apidae) colonies. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 218–221. **218–221**
- 7- **Amal, E. Marouf; Ghada, E. Abd-Allah and Marwa, M. Shalaby (2021):** Effect of propolis extracts and *Bacillus thuringiensis* on leafminer fly *Liriomyza sativae* (Diptera: Agromyzidae). Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 222–229. **222–229**
- 8- **Nabil, M. Ghanim; Reda, A. El-Sharkawy and Wafaa, M.M. El-Baradei (2021):** Influence of mixing ammonium acetate and di-ammonium phosphate on their attraction to the peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* (Diptera: Tephritidae) under field conditions. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 230–239. **230–239**

Continued

- 9- **Samy, S. El-badawy; Sahar, Y. Abdel-Aziz; Ahmed, A. Elhefny ; Ahmed, Abdel-Monem Taha and Elham, A. Khalifa(2021):** Antifeedant effects of two plant extracts of (*Bidens pilosa* and *Rumex dentatus*) and neem oil on certain stored grains insects. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 240–252. **240–252**
- 10- **El-Maghraby, M. M. A. ¹ and Abdelatef, G. M. (2021):** Performance of *Schistocerca gregaria* haemocytes in response to entomopathogenic fungi *Metarhizium acridum* and *Beauveria bassiana* single and mixed infections. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 253–260. **253–260**
- 11- **Rezk, M. ; Ahmed, S. Abdel-Aty and Rasha, S. Abdel-Fattah (2021):** Impact of certain insecticides with different mode of action on the California red scale *Aonidiella aurantii* (Hemiptera-Diaspididae) on orange under local conditions in Egypt. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 261–274. **261–274**
- 12- **Manal, S. Ismail; Nadia, H. Habashy; Aida, K.F. Iskandar; Marguerite, A. Rizk and Mona, M.A. Ghallab (2021):** Seasonal abundance of true spiders inhabiting perennial shrubs and evergreen herbs. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 275–289. **275–289**
- 13- **Hanim, M. Soliman and Yasmin, A. Fergani (2021):** Dissipation of chlorpyrifos-methyl and lufenuron in and on tomato fruits infested with the cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) under the field conditions. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 290–298. **290–298**
- 14- **Khalifa, E. A.; Salah, S. and Risha, E. M. (2021):** Impact of the thrips-borne tomato spotted wilt virus infestation on some cucurbitaceous plant yield, Egypt. Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 299–310. **299–310**
- 15- **Ammar, A. E. and Salloum, W. (2021):** Evaluation of three different spraying volumes produced from two variables technique against tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and cotton aphid *Aphis gossypii* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) infesting marrows plants. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 311–321. **311–321**
- 16- **Mohamed, Hassan A. Soliman and Hend, Sh. Ghareeb (2021):** Molluscicidal effect of ammonium nitrate and some biopesticides on the brown garden snail *Eobania vermiculata* (Gastropoda: Helicidae). J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 322–340. **322–340**
- 17- **Hemat, Z. Moustafa; Mervat, A. Kandil and El-Bassouiny, H. M. (2021):** Genetic profile characterization of *Earias insulana* (Lepidoptera:Noctuidae) in Egypt. J. Plant Prot. Res. Inst., 4 (2): 341–351. **341–351**

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Susceptibility of the potato tuber moth *Phthorimaea operculella* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) to the *Autographa californica* multicapsid nucleopolyhedrovirus

Ahmed, Abdel-Monem Taha¹; Marwa, A. M. Abd-Allah² and Maha, A. M. Tantawy²

¹Central Laboratory for Organic Agriculture, Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt.

²Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 15 /1/2021

Accepted: 18/ 3 /2021

Keywords

Potato tuber moth (PTM), *Phthorimaea operculella*, *Autographa californica* multicapsid nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) and baculoviruses.

Abstract:

The *Autographa californica* multicapsid nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) pathogenicity was investigated for the potato tuber moth (PTM) *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Infection of PTM with AcMNPV viral concentration of 2.5×10^5 PIB/ml resulted in up to 6.25 % mortality, 14.3 % less active and partially paralyzed larvae and about 14.7 % absent or not found larvae compared to the control, and assumed to be died at their very early larval instar. Observation of infected dead larvae under optical microscope revealed presence of cubic polyhedral inclusion bodies (PIBs) in different insect cells. Hybridization of extracted and digested DNA from partially paralyzed infected PTM larvae, with specific AcMNPV nucleic probe, proved the identity of the AcMNPV used in PTM infection.

Introduction

The cultivated potato, *Solanum tuberosum* L. (Solanales: *Solanaceae*), is one of the most important vegetable crops for human nutrition worldwide (Flanders *et al.*, 1999). In Egypt as in many other countries worldwide, potato crop represents one of the main vegetable cash crops. Among serious insect pests that attack potato crop, the potato tuber moth (PTM) *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), represents one of the most dangerous pests that accompanying plant from seedling to harvest stages and storage period (Westedt *et al.*, 1998), leading to severe effects on potato yield quantity and quality. PTM is widely distributed in both subtropical and temperate regions and attacks wide range of variable host plants, including

tobacco, eggplant, and tomato (Fenemore, 1988 and Sporleder *et al.*, 2004).

For decades, the PTM control has relied upon the use of several traditional synthetic insecticides, leading to rapid development of resistance to a wide variety of insecticides, and increasing tuber infestation rates as well (Clough *et al.*, 2008). Recently, biological control for PTM using bioinsecticides and bio-agents have gained more attention, and efforts have been exerted to evaluate them against PTM in both field and storage (Sileshi and Teriessa, 2001; Agamy, 2003 and Mandour *et al.*, 2009).

To reduce infestations in stores, the soil bacterium *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) and the second

member of *baculoviridae*, the *granulovirus* that named PhopGV, were used by farmers worldwide and have been proved effective in reducing PTM infestations (Von Arx and Gebhardt, 1990) and has been applied to control larval populations in the field and stored potatoes in Peru, Bolivia, Colombia, and Ecuador (Raman *et al.*, 1992 and Moscardi, 1999) and Zeddami *et al.* (1999) summarized tropical and subtropical locations worldwide from which the PhopGV were isolated.

Although several studies have demonstrated the potential of this virus to control PTM under both field and storage conditions (Raman *et al.*, 1987; Reed and Springett, 1971; Von Arx and Gebhardt, 1990; Ben Salah and Aalbu, 1992; Lagnaoui *et al.*, 1997; Das *et al.*, 1998 and Hanafi, 2005), however, several authors stated that PTM has exhibited a strong potential to develop resistance to PhopGV (Briese and Mende, 1981, 1983; Briese, 1982 and Sporleder, 2003). Briese and Mende (1983) observed a 140-fold increase in LD50 following exposure of larvae to PhopGV over six generations, two decades later, Sporleder (2003) also reported high levels of resistance in a PTM population exposed to the virus for 12 generations. Beside emergence of PTM resistance to the virus, the PhopGV like other member of *granuloviruses*, is highly specific to the insect host from which it was isolated except certain of its isolates that were found able to infect other insect species belong to Gelechiidae (Zeddami *et al.*, 2013).

Nucleopolyhedroviruses (NPVs) that represents the first member of *Baculoviridae* were intensively studied and commercially exploited for insect pest control due to their host specificity and safety to other plants and animals, and their infectivity to a wide range of insect pest species (Hussain *et al.*, 2019). Among these viruses, the two

NPVs *Autographa californica* and *Anagrapha falcifera* were found to have a relatively broad host spectrum and have been shown to infect as many as 30 different lepidopteran species from as many as 10 separate families (Adams and McClintock, 1991), therefore, they were registered in the USA and field-tested at a limited scale, showing their potentiality against a variety of crops infested with pests belonging to a number of genera, including *Spodoptera* and *Helicoverpa* (Boguslaw Szewczyk *et al.*, 2011).

Finally, as the use of alternative environmentally safe means for controlling insect pests is highly recommended and encouraged in organic agriculture and other safe food production systems. Hence, considering the importance of PTM as a key insect pest and based on earlier studies that revealed that *Autographa californica* multicapsid nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) was able to multiply *in vitro* on an established cell line derived from *P. operculella* embryos (Lery *et al.*, 1998), therefore, the pathogenicity of AcMNPV to PTM *in vivo* was examined as a primary work aims to evaluate possible potentialities of other available baculovirus isolates to be employed in PTM control programs.

Materials and methods

1. Virus:

An AcMNPV strain was previously obtained as a gift from Dr. Croizier (INRA, France). To conserve the initial properties, the virus strain was regularly multiplied in the laboratory on the pink boll worm *Pectinophora gossypiella* (Saunders) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) (Vail *et al.*, 1972). The polyhedral inclusion bodies (PIBs) were isolated as follow; using a sterile pestle and mortar, the collected infected larvae were homogenized in 50 mmol/l Tris.Hcl and 2 mmol/L sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS), pH 7.8, and filtrated

through a cheese cloth, then the filtrate was centrifuged at 1000 x g for 2 minutes to remove the larger particles. Finally, the obtained suspension was purified by centrifugation through a 30%-70% sucrose gradient for 20 minutes at 25,000 x g. then band containing the purified PIBs was removed to a clean centrifuge tube, then diluted by completing the its volume with 50 mmol/l Tris. Hcl and re-centrifuged. A pellet containing PIBs was re-suspended in sterile distilled water, observed through phase contrast optical microscope, counted using a haemocytometer then stored at 4 °C for further investigations.

2. Insect rearing:

The PTM used in this study were derived from a PTM colony maintained at the Plant Protection Research Institute (PPRI) that is affiliated to the Agricultural Research Center, Egypt. At the beginning, received pupae were kept under laboratory conditions of 27 ± 1 and L16:D8 photoperiod as described by Zeddami *et al.* (2013). For PTM egg production, disinfected pupae were sexed, then transferred to adult box at 1:1 ratio (Male: female) then adult box was covered by a circular piece of white paper (or filter paper), sitting on top of a black fine mesh net fitted tightly over the opening with an elastic band and the box was provided with 10% honey solution, as a source of feeding for emerged adult, through a tissue paper soaked in the honey solution. Papers containing PTM laid eggs were cut off into sections, of 100 eggs each, and then kept in plastic ventilated cylinder boxes for further use under the same controlled conditions. By the appearance of larval dark head capsules, the eggs were surface disinfected in 10% sodium hypochlorite for 1 minute, rinsed in distilled water, dried on filter paper, then transferred to small potato tubers at a ratio of (2gr

potato per 1 PTM larva) and incubated at same conditions until pupation. Finally, new formed pupae were regularly used to re-initiate PTM new laboratory rearing cycles.

3. Larval infection:

To examine the pathogenicity of extracted AcMNPV PIBs produced on *P. gossypiella*, the polyhedral suspension were mixed with triton-X100 at final concentration of 0.1% and used as infectious suspension, then small round potato tubers calculated as 2 gr potato per one PTM larva, were covered with the infectious suspension then treated tubers were air dried and placed inside a small ventilated plastic containers. Finally, PTM eggs with black head capsules, prior to hatch, were placed on contaminated tubers and incubated in plastic boxes at 27°C and observed every other day. For control treatment, larvae were feed on potato tubers treated with sterile distilled water mixed with triton x100 0.1%, and larvae were observed for viral infection and resulted mortality up to 14 days post inoculation.

4. Examination of AcMNPV infected PTM larvae through optical microscope:

Smears from dead and abnormal dissected AcMNPV infected PTM larvae were prepared and stained with methylene blue, then examined using the oil immersion lens of the optical microscope to detect presence of PIBs.

5. Preparation of non-radioactive nucleic probe and hybridization:

A cloned fragment that concludes the polyhedrin gene, gift from Dr. Croizier (INRA, France), was used for the detection of AcMNPV genome among total extracted DNA from partially paralyzed and abnormal infected PTM larvae by applying a non-radioactive Dig DNA labeled nucleic probe which prepared according to the supplier protocol. The sensitivity of the prepared nucleic polyhedrin probe was

tested using different amount (Dilutions) of extracted AcMNPV DNA. For AcMNPV viral DNA detection, a randomly chosen individual representing dead, abnormal, and partially paralyzed PTM larvae were separately homogenized in TE buffer (0.01mmol/l Tris and 1mmol/l EDTA pH 8.0 then diluted up to 1/100. Then 10 μ l of diluted total insect DNA were subjected to the DNA dot blot hybridization with the prepared labeled probe.

6. Extraction and analysis of AcMNPV infected PTM total larval DNA:

The total insect DNA of abnormality, and partially paralyzed infected PTM larvae was separately extracted using techniques derived from Malone and McIvor (1995) as follow: Larvae were grinded in a buffer consisting of four parts of the homogenization solution (100mM/l NaCl, 200 mM/l sucrose, 10mM/l EDTA, and 30 mM/l Tris. HCl pH 8.0) and one part of lysis solution (250 mM EDTA, 2.5% SDS, 500mM/l Tris. HCl , pH 9.2) and incubated for 30 min. at 65°C. Proteinase K was added to a final concentration of 1 μ g /ml. Then the suspension was incubated at 37°C for 3 hrs. Then potassium acetate was added to final concentration of 3 mM and the suspension incubated at 0 °C for 30 min. the final suspension containing total DNA was centrifuged in a microfuge for 1 min. at 13000g to remove insect cellular fragments and the DNA was precipitated with 2 volumes of 100 % glacial ethanol. Total infected larval DNA was digested to completion with *Pst*I endonuclease and electrophoretic mobility through 1% agarose gel was realized according to Maniatis *et al.* (1989), then separated digested DNA was transferred to a nitrocellulose membrane and immobilized by UV-cross linking.

Finally, southern blot hybridization was realized according to Southern (1975) and Solanas and Escrich (1997), using the prepared DIG- labeled probe based on polyhedrin cloned sequence.

Results and discussion

As existence of a plant crop with a single economically important pest is unlikely to occur, developing of a complex multi species-baculovirus formulations that are able to control several pests simultaneously is highly recommended and require continuous search among available baculovirus species (Or isolates) to find the most effective one (s) for each pest in each region (Santiago Haase *et al.*, 2015). The *Autographa californica* multicapsid nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) is a reference model for viral genetic research, biotechnological applications and biological control of several insects and can cause pathogenicity for a large number of lepidopteran species belonging up to twelve families and often representing important pests and wide geographically ranges (Groner, 1986). This virus can be laboratory mass produced and several of its host can be reared industrially on artificial diets (Vail *et al.*, 1972).

Preliminary trails to infect PTM larvae with AcMNPV at 10⁴PIB/ml revealed neither appeared viral infection nor late disease symptoms, however, increasing the viral concentration to 2.5x 10⁵ PIB/ml resulted in up to 6.25 % mortality, 14.3 % less active and partially paralyzed larvae beside about 14.7 % absent or not found larvae compared to the control, and assumed to be died at their very early larval instar (Table 1).

Table (1): Infectivity of *Autographa californica* multicapsid nucleopolyhedrovirus to potato tuber moth *Phthorimaea operculella* larvae when applied at 2.5×10^5 PIB/ml. Percentages of dead, less active and partially paralyzed abnormal larvae were counted based on alive larvae obtained from the control.

N° of Rep.	N° of tested PTM	N° of Dead Larvae 2nd & 3rd instar	N° of abnormal aged larvae	Total dead and abnormal Larvae	N° of Alive	N° of absent Individuals	N° of individuals based on control	% of Dead	% of abnormal aged larvae	% of Total dead & abnormal	% of absent Individuals
1	200	8	26	34	101	25	160	5	16.25	21.25	15.625
2	200	13	20	33	107	20	160	8.125	12.5	20.625	12.5
3	200	9	23	32	102	26	160	5.625	14.375	20	16.25
Control	200	0	0	0	160	0	160	0		0	0
MEAN								6.25	14.375	20.625	14.7916667
total PTM	800	30	69	99							

Examination of discharged body fluid from dead PTM individuals through optical microscope, showed the presence of polyhedral inclusion bodies of nucleopolyhedro type similar to the used one for infection (Figure 1). However, examination of partially paralyzed and abnormal larvae by optical microscope, didn't give a clear configuration on the viral infection due to the limited amount of observed PIBs therefore, a Dig-labeled nucleic probe based on the AcMNPV polyhedrin gene sequence, was prepared and found to have detection sensitivity up to 5ng of viral DNA. Subjecting randomly chosen PTM larvae that represent dead, partially paralyzed, less active and abnormal larvae to dot blot hybridization with the prepared nucleic probe, revealed the presence of AcMNPV viral DNA in testing larvae of different categories (Figure 2).

Concerning the PTM partially paralyzed, and less active and abnormal larvae, the total insect DNA was extracted, digested with *Pst*I

endonuclease then subjected to southern blot hybridization to confirm identity of the produced virus that multiplied at low rate in partially paralyzed larvae. The fact that PTM larva is a small sized insect, it was difficult to use standard techniques for extraction, purification and analysis of the viral DNA. To minimize the viral DNA loss, extraction steps were reduced by elimination of purification steps based on centrifugation as described in the original protocol and the total insect DNA was also extracted and caused interference with electrophoresed viral endonuclease restricted fragments, therefore, obtained fragments (bands) were directly transferred and hybridized the with AcMNPV polyherdin nucleic probe. In this way, it was possible to reveal a viral infection from infected larvae and to prove the identity of the multiplied AcMNPV in PTM larvae (Figure 3).

Figure (1): Micrograph of different tissues prepared from *Autographa californica* multicapsid nucleopolyhedrovirus infected PTM larvae and observed under optical microscope using oil immersion lens. Arrows indicate the formed polyhedral inclusion bodies .

Figure (2): Dot blotting on nitrocellulose membrane with various total DNA extracted from *Autographa californica* multicapsid nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) (B1, B2 and B3) used as positive control, and from healthy and non infected PTM larvae (A1, A2 and A3) used as negative control. Numbers from 1 to 9 represent total DNA from randomly chosen dead, abnormal, and partially paralyzed larvae showing different level of AcMNPV DNA presence.

Figure (3): Southern blot hybridization using labeled *Autographa californica* multicapsid nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) polyhedrin probe:
 (A): Ethidium bromide stained gel after electrophoresis of *Pst I* digested total DNA extracted from AcMNPV infected potato tuber moth *Phthorimaea operculella* (PTM) (1) and from non-infected (Healthy) PTM larvae (2) Arrows indicate DNA fragments size.
 (B): *Pst I* digested total DNA extracted from AcMNPV infected PTM (1) and from non-infected (healthy) PTM larvae (2) hybridized with the dig-labeled polyhedrin nucleic probe.

The obtained *in vivo* low pathogenicity of AcMNPV for PTM that fed on virus contaminated tubers was not correlated with the *in vitro* multiplication obtained with the same virus on different *P. operculella* cell lines resulting in high titers of the virus (Lery *et al.*, 1998). This contradiction between *in vitro* and *in vivo* results could be due to one or more of the following reasons; firstly, the fact that no artificial diet is available for PTM laboratory rearing, presented a big barrier that hinders the accurate determination of viral lethal dose. The insect behavior may also have certain effects because newly hatched larvae may be exposed early, during their crawling on tuber surface, to an optimum number of polyheda during the first hours after hatching and may die during this early stage, this probability could participate in explaining reasons for absence of about 14.7% of PTM larvae from treated replicates compared to the actual number of PTM larval individuals obtained from the non treated replicate (Control), while other larvae that penetrate the tubers and their ingested viral particles were not sufficient to initiate a lethal infection could explain the resulted abnormal and partially paralyzed aged larvae. The fact that death occurred on 1st and 2nd larval instars, while only abnormalities were found in advanced larval instar also could be due to the existence of different levels of susceptibility among different larval instar to the viral infection, and among the insect population itself.

In this regard, Sporleder (2003) found that susceptibility of PTM larvae to PhopGV decreases rapidly with larval age, and Salama *et al.* (1995) reported that the virulence of the bacterium *Bt* is similarly host age dependent. Finally, this phenomenon could be simply related to the used viral

dose in relation to larval behavior. Carrera *et al.* (2008) stated that precise evaluation of Baculoviruses biological activity by the usual droplet method is not appropriate for boring insect larvae like the potato tuber moths because it remain on plant surfaces for a limited time that could not exceed several minutes before penetrating the substrate and get protected from viral inoculums on tuber surface. Also, when PhopGV biological activity was evaluated by immersing PTM eggs or the potato tubers in viral solutions, Sporleder *et al.* (2005) and Zeddami *et al.* (1999) found that both methods didn't allow the precise determination of the granule concentration presented on the potato surface and high variability between experiment's data were obtained.

In conclusion, baculoviruses could represent an attractive solution to supplement and/or in certain cases replace chemical insecticides in IPM programs and several insect viruses, mainly belongs to Baculoviridae were registered as bio-insecticides to control pests in crops, forests, and pastures worldwide (Xiu-lian and Hui-yin, 2007). The NPVs are commonly isolated from infected insects collected from the fields. In case of PTM, only granulovirus was isolated and successfully used, however, resistance to the virus has been recently documented. Therefore, the presented work aimed to initiate regular investigation for other possible potent baculoviruses that could overcome certain baculovirus technical application problems in field such as their relative slow speed of action, their restriction and specificity to their insect host, and relatively low virulence particularly for advanced larval instars. So, this work could propose a possibility to obtain a naturally recombinant candidate that expressing the advantages of narrow host range,

the PhopGV, and the speed of killing of AcMNPV.

References

- Adams, J.R. and McClintock, J.T. (1991):** Baculoviridae, nuclear polyhedrosis viruses Part 1: Nuclear polyhedrosis viruses of insects. In Atlas of Invertebrate Viruses; Eds. ,Adams, J.R. and Bonami, J.R.; CRC Press: Boca Raton, FL, USA, Chapter 6: 87–180.
- Agamy , E.A. (2003):** The inundative release of *Trichogramma evanescens* West. as biocontrol agent against the potato tuber moth, *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller). Egyptian J. biol. Pest Contr., 13: 101–104.
- Ben Salah, H. and Aalbu, R. (1992):** Field use of granulosis virus to reduce initial storage infestation of the potato tuber moth, *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller), in North Africa. Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment, 38: 119–126.
- Boguslaw Szewczyk; Marlinda, Lobo de Souza; Maria, Elita Batista de Castro; Mauricio, Lara Moscardi and Flavio, Moscardi (2011):** Baculovirus biopesticides, Pesticides - Formulations, Effects, Fate, Prof. Margarita Stoytcheva (Ed.), ISBN: 978-953-307-532-7, In Tech, Available from: <http://www.intechopen.com/books/pesticides-formulations-effects-fate/baculovirus-biopesticides>.
- Briese, D. T. (1982):** Genetic basis for resistance to a granulosis virus in the potato tuber moth, *Phthorimaea operculella*. J. Invertebr. Pathol., 39:215–218.
- Briese, D. T. and Mende, H. A. (1981):** Differences in susceptibility to a granulosis virus between field populations of the potato moth, *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Bull. Entomol. Res., 71:11–18.
- Briese, D. T. and Mende, H. A. (1983):** Selection for increased resistance to a granulosis virus in the potato moth, *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). Bull. Entomol. Res., 73: 1–10.
- Carrera , M. V. Z.; Zeddani, Jean-Louis; Pollet, Andre; Lery , Xavier and Miguel Lopez-Ferber (2008):** Evaluation of the *per os* insecticidal activity of baculoviruses by a nebulization method. Insect Pathogens and Insect Parasitic Nematodes, [OBCIwprs Bulletin, 31: 40-43.
- Clough, G.; De Bano, S.; Rondon, S.; David, N. and Hamm P. (2008):** Use of cultural and chemical practices to reduce tuber damage from the potato tuber worm in the Columbia Basin. HortScience, 43: 1159–1160.
- Das, G.P.; Lagnaoui, A.; Salah, H. B. and Souibgui, M. (1998):** The control of the potato tuber moth in storage in Tunisia. Tropical Science, 38: 78–80.
- Fenemore, P. G. (1988):** Host-plant location and selection by adult potato moth, *Phthorimaea operculella* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae): a review. Journal of Insect Physiology, 34: 175–177.
- Flanders, K.; Arnone, S. and Radcliffe, E. (1999):** The potato: genetic resources and insect resistance. In: Clement, S.L. and Quisenberry, S.S., Editors. Global Plant Genetic Resource for Insect Resistant Crops, 207–239.

- Groner, A. (1986):** Specificity and safety of baculoviruses. In : The biology of baculoviruses, Editors : Granados, R. R. and Federici, B. A. , CRC Press, Inc., pp.276 .
- Hanafi, A. (2005):** Integrated management of potato tuber moth in field and storage. Potato in Progress: Science Meets Practice (ed. by Haverkort, A.J. and Struik, P.C.), pp. 203–210. Wageningen Academic Publishers, Wageningen, The Netherlands.
- Hussain, B.; Sivakumar, G.; Kannan, M.; War, A.R. and Ballal, C.R. (2019):** First record of nucleopolyhedrovirus infecting brown-tail moth larvae, *Euproctis chryorrhoea* (L.) (Lepidoptera: Lymantriidae) in India. Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control, 29(11), <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41938-019-0117-9>.
- Lagnaoui, A.; Ben Salah, H. and El-Bedewy, R. (1997):** Integrated management to control potato tuber moth in North Africa and the Middle East. CIP Circular, 22: 10–15.
- Lery, X.; El-Tarras, A.; Abol-Ela, S. and Giannotti, J. (1998):** Yield and activity of *Autographa californica* nucleopolyhedrovirus and *Phthorimaea operculella* granulosis virus in cloned and uncloned cell lines of *Phthorimaea operculella*. Cytotechnology, 26: 103-110.
- Malone, L. A. and McIvor, C.A. (1995):** DNA Probes for two microsporidia, *Nosema bombycis* and *Nosema costeytrae*. J. Invertebr. Pathol., 65:269-273.
- Mandour, N.S.; Sarhan, A.; Ghanem, M. and Atwa, D. (2009):** Effect of certain bioinsecticides on the infestation rate and biological aspects of *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) in store. Agric. Res. J., Suez Canal Univ., 9: 109-116.
- Maniatis, T.; Fritsh, F.E. and Sambbrook, J. (1989):** Molecular cloning: A laboratory Manual. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, Cold Spring Harbor, N.Y.
- Moscardi, F. (1999):** Assessment of the application of baculoviruses for control of Lepidoptera. Annu. Rev. Entomol., 44:257-289.
- Raman, K. V.; Alcazar, J. and Valdez, A. (1992):** Biological control of the potato tuber moth using *Phthorimaea* baculovirus. Int. Potato Cent. Lima, CIP Train. Bull., 2: 27.
- Raman, K.V.; Booth, R.H. and Palacios, M. (1987):** Control of potato tuber moth *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller) in rustic potato stores. Tropical Science, 27: 175-194.
- Reed, E .M . and Springett, B. P. (1971):** Large-scale field testing of a granulosis virus for the control of the potato moth (*Phthorimaea operculella* (Zell.) (Lep.: Gelechiidae). Bulletin of Entomological Research, 61: 223–233.
- Salama, H. S.; Ragaiei, M. and Sabbour, M. (1995):** Larvae of *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zell.) as affected by various strains of *Bacillus thuringiensis*. J. Appl. Entomol., 119: 241–243.
- Santiago Haase ; Alicia, Sciocco-Cap and Víctor, Romanowski (2015):** Baculovirus insecticides in Latin America: Historical Overview, Current

- Status and Future Perspectives, *Viruses*, 7: 2230-2267.
- Sileshi, G. and Teriessa, J. (2001):** Tuber damage by potato tuber moth, *Phthorimaea operculella* Zeller (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) in the field in eastern Ethiopia. *Int. J. Pest Manage.*, 47: 109-113.
- Solanas, M. and Escrich, E. (1997):** An improved protocol to increase sensitivity of Southern blot using dig-labelled DNA probes. *Journal of Biochemical and Biophysical Methods*, 35(3):153–159.
- Southern, E. M. (1975):** Detection of specific sequences among DNA fragments separated by gel electrophoresis. *J. Mol. Biol.*, 98: 50-517.
- Sporleder, M. (2003):** The Granulosis of the potato tuber moth *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller): Characterization and prospects for effective mass production and pest Control. *Advances in Crop Research 3*, Margraf Verlag, Weikersheim, Germany.
- Sporleder, M.; Kroschel, J.; Huber, J. and Lagnaoui, A. (2005):** The granulovirus PoGV in its host *Phthorimaea operculella*. *Entomol. Exp. Appl.*, 116: 191-197.
- Sporleder, M.; Kroschel, J.; Gutierrez Quispe, M. R. and Lagnaoui, A. (2004):** A temperature-based simulation model for the potato tuber worm, *Phthorimaea operculella* Zeller (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). *Environ. Entomol.*, 33: 477–486.
- Vail, P.V.; Jay, D.L.; Hunter, D.K. and Staten, R.T. (1972):** A nuclear polyhedrosis virus infective the pink boll worm, *Pectinophora gossypiella*. *J. Inverteber. Pathol.*, 20:124-128.
- Von Arx, R. and Gebhardt, F. (1990):** Effect of a granulosis virus and *Bacillus thuringiensis* on life table parameters of the potato tuber moth, *Phthorimaea operculella*. *Entomophaga*, 35: 151–159.
- Westedt, A.L.; Douches, D.S.; Pett, W. and Grafius, E. J. (1998):** Evaluation of natural and engineered resistance mechanisms in *Solanum tuberosum* L. for resistance to *Phthorimaea operculella* Zeller. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 91: 552–556.
- Xiu-lian, S. and Hui-yin, P. (2007):** Recent advances in biological control of pest insects by using viruses. *China Virologica Sinica*, 22 (2):158-162.
- Zeddami, J.L.; Lery, X.; Gomez-Bonilla, Y.; Espinel-Correal, C.; Paez, D., Rebaudo, F.; Lopez-Ferber, M. (2013):** Responses of different geographic populations of two potato tuber moth species to genetic variants of *Phthorimaea operculella* granulovirus. *Entomol. Exp. Appl.*, 149: 138-147.
- Zeddami, J.L.; Pollet, A.; Mangoendiharjo, S.; Ramadhan, T.H. and Lopez-Ferber, M. (1999):** Occurrence and virulence of a granulosis virus in *Phthorimaea operculella* (Lep.: Gelechiidae) populations in Indonesia. *Journal of Invertebrate Pathology*, 74: 48–54.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Population fluctuation of the floridana scale insect *Lindingaspis floridana* (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) on *Ficus benjamina* under greenhouse conditions in Cairo Governorate

Omnia, M. N. El-Sahn

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 8 /1/2021

Accepted: 12/ 3 /2021

Keywords

Population fluctuation, *Lindingaspis floridana*, biotic and abiotic factors and Egypt.

Abstract:

The results showed that the floridana scale insect *L. floridana* total population infesting *F. benjamina* trees in the greenhouse in El-Zohreya Botanical Garden, Cairo Governorate was higher in the 1st year (2015-2016) than 2nd year (2016- 2017) with mean of total population 84.53 and 64.10 individuals/10 leaves, respectively. *L. floridana* total population recorded 3 peaks of abundance in both years. The highest peak was recorded in mid-October 2015 with 196.84 individuals/10 leaves with corresponding maximum, minimum and relative humidity 30.90, 21.33°C and 76.70%, respectively. While, the lowest population was noticed in mid-July 2015 with 21.63 individuals/10 leaves with corresponding maximum, minimum and relative humidity 31.97, 21.80°C and 73.90%, respectively. The highest rate of increase was in July 2016 with 1.75. Also, the upper surface was more preferable to the insect than the lower one. *L. floridana* recorded 3 overlapping generations in both studied years where the longest one was 180 days and recorded in summer generation 2016 while the shortest one was 75 days in winter generation. The population of the associated parasitoid was relatively low. It recorded 3 peaks each year, the mean of the immature stages population was higher in the 2nd year than the 1st year with 10.19 and 8.43 individuals/10 leaves, respectively. The highest rate of parasitism was recorded in 1st April 2016 with 22.62%. But, the lowest rate of parasitism was recorded in September 2015 with 2.17%. The effects of corresponding abiotic and biotic factors were studied. Results revealed that, maximum and minimum temperatures independently had an insignificant effect on the total population of *L. floridana* on 1st and 2nd generations, but they gave a highly significant effect on the 3rd generation. While the relative humidity alone had an insignificant effect in both years and during the 3 generations. Whereas, the effect of the presence of associated parasitoid alone was significant in the 2nd generation in both years and in the 3rd generation it was insignificant relation. In case of, the effect of combined abiotic and biotic factors, it varied between significant and highly significant effect in both years which indicate that it effects of combined factors is more efficient on the population of *L. floridana* than each independent factor.

Introduction

The floridana scale insect *Lindingaspis floridana* Ferris (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) is a polyphagous armored scale insect belonging to Order Hemiptera, Superfamily Coccoidea, Family Diaspididae with worldwide distribution. It was first found in Florida 1921 (Miller *et al.*, 2005). It is believed to be originated in Asia, but has invaded many tropical and subtropical regions of the world. It is listed as a harmful insect by Japan, Korea and Costa Rica. It infests many horticultural plants like mango (Bakr *et al.*, 2009 and Attia and Radwan, 2013) and olive, fig and ornamental plants (ScaleNet, 2021). The scale insects feed on plant sap, and infestations cause leaves to turn yellow as their condition deteriorates. It sucks a great amount of sap, leading to dryness of the leaves and defoliation. Heavy infestations can result in stunting and death of leaves and dieback (Ezzat and Nada, 1986 and Hassan *et al.*, 2012).

L. floridana was found severely infesting Hawaiian fig *Ficus benjamina* trees (Family: Moraceae) in El-Zohreya Botanical Garden, Cairo Governorate. It is an ornamental plant used as outdoor and indoor plants commonly known as weeping fig, benjamin fig or ficus tree, native to Asia and Australia. It can reach 30 meters tall in natural conditions. The infestation causes leaf malformation and the presence of insects on the leaves of an ornamental plant decreases the marketing value of the plant and that is a big loss to the producers and exporters. Also, a parasitoid was found associated with *L. floridana*. Abd-Rabou (2001) stated that there are two parasitoids associated with *L. floridana* in Egypt, which were *Aphytis lingnanensis* Compere and *Encarsia citrina* (Craw) (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae). The aim of this research

is to study the population fluctuation of *L. floridana* infesting *F. benjamina* trees and its associated parasitoid and the effect of corresponding abiotic and biotic factors to detect the most suitable time for insect control.

Materials and methods

1. Sampling procedures:

The seasonal abundance of *L. floridana* on *F. benjamina* was studied throughout two successive years (2015-2016) and (2016-2017) in a glass greenhouse in El-Zohreya Botanical Garden, Cairo Governorate. The selected trees did not receive any chemicals or pesticide treatment before or during the sampling procedures. Samples were taken biweekly of 5 leaves replicated 4 times and collected randomly from the trees. The samples were kept in plastic bags and transferred to the laboratory for examination. Inspection of leaves was conducted by the aid of stereomicroscope binocular to detect the different alive stages of *L. floridana* (Nymphs, adult females and gravid females). Also, the population of *L. floridana* was detected on both surfaces of leaves upper and lower surfaces. In addition, immature stages (Larvae and pupae) of a parasitoid were found associated with *L. floridana* and were counted in each sample. The rates of increase in the population density were calculated by dividing the total number of alive populations in any count over the total numbers of the previous one Bodenheimer (1951). Half monthly mean numbers of both *L. floridana* and its associated parasitoid different stages were smoothed by using three figures running mean.

2. Rates of parasitism:

The rate of parasitism was calculated according to the formula of Orphanides (1982).

Number of parasitized scale insects

$$\text{Rate of parasitism} = \frac{\text{Total No. of parasitized and non-parasitized scale insects}}{\text{Total No. of parasitized and non-parasitized scale insects}} \times 100$$

3. Number of generations and annual durations:

Number and durations of annual generations were detected on ficus trees in Cairo Governorate for *L. floridana* throughout two successive years (2015-2016) and (2016-2017). The annual generations were estimated from data of the accumulated half monthly counts of mean alive immature stage, according to Jacob Formula (Jacob, 1977).

4. Effect of abiotic (Weather factors) and biotic factor (Accompanying parasitoid):

The main studied weather factors were mean maximum, minimum temperatures and mean percentages of relative humidity 2 weeks earlier were measured inside the greenhouse, with the aid of a hygrometer throughout the two successive years. In addition, the effect of the presence of the parasitoid as biotic factor in the total population of *L. floridana* was studied.

5. Statistical analysis:

Statistical analysis procedures were implemented in two steps, the first one to investigate the effect of each factor individually by applying simple correlation formula and regression coefficient, (r) was used as a measure of significance. The second step by applying C-multiplier Formula (Fisher, 1950) to investigate the effects of abiotic and biotic factors on the total population of *L. floridana*. The factors were studied individually and as a group. The changes of the population density expressed as percentages of explained variance (E.V.%) and the variance ratios (F values) were used as measure of significance in combination with each other. All calculations were

carried out using Microsoft office Excel program ver. 2016.

Results and discussion**1. Population fluctuation of *Lindingaspis floridana* infesting *Ficus benjamina* trees in Cairo Governorate:**

A study was conducted to inspect the population fluctuation of *L. floridana* different stages for 2 successive years (2015-2016) and (2016-2017) in a glass greenhouse in El-Zohreya Botanical Garden, Cairo Governorate. The results illustrated in Figures (1 and 2) showed the following:

1.1. Nymphal stage:

In the 1st year (2015-2016) nymphal stage recorded 2 peaks of abundance; the 1st peak was 19.82 nymphs/10 leaves in 1st May 2015, while the 2nd one was higher with 68.82 nymphs/10 leaves in mid-October. In addition, it was clear that, nymphs were found in their lowest population in March and from June to August months. On the other hand, in the second year (2016-2017) *L. floridana* recorded 4 peaks of abundance in 1st March, 1st May, 1st July and mid-November with 54.10, 52.49, 22.29 and 34.85 nymphs/10 leaves, respectively. Also, the most depression population was found on mid-August with 7.49 nymphs/10 leaves.

1.2. Adult females:

Data graphically illustrated in Figures (1 and 2) showed that adult female population was higher in the 1st year than 2nd year with averages 33.80 and 17.00 adult females/10 leaves, respectively. It recorded 4 peaks in 1st year, the highest one was recorded in mid-October 2015 with 88.35 adult

females/ 10 leaves. The other peaks recorded 16.47, 25.68 and 16.36 adult females/10 leaves in 1st March, 1st May and mid-February 2016, respectively. While, the lowest peak was recorded on mid-July with 8.78 adult females/10 leaves. Furthermore, in the second year, the insect recorded 3 peaks in 1st May as in the 1st year with 34.17 adult females/10 leaves, the other 2 peaks were lower in population with 16.48 and 29.92 adult females/10 leaves in 1st July and mid-November, respectively. The adult female population declined gradually in August, September 2016 and February 2017.

1.3. Gravid (Ovipositing) females:

Gravid females recorded 3 peaks in the 1st year (2015-2016), it started with a peak in the beginning of the year with 32.02 gravid females/10 leaves in 1st March 2015, then it recorded another two peaks in mid-November and mid-February 2016 with 46.48 and 44.28 gravid females/10 leaves, respectively. Furthermore, gravid females populations declined in the period between mid-May till the beginning of September. However, in the second year it recorded 2 peaks in 1st August and mid-October with 23.95 and 20.13 gravid females/10 leaves. The lowest population of gravid females was recorded on 1st of February 2017 with 6.57 gravid females/10 leaves.

1.4. Total population:

It was obvious that the total population was higher in the 1st year than 2nd year with mean of total population 84.53 and 64.10 individuals/10 leaves, respectively. In addition, the total population of *L. floridana* recorded 3 peaks of abundance in both years. In the 1st year, the highest peak was recorded in mid-October 2015 with 196.84 individuals/10 leaves. While the other 2 peaks were 65.66 and 107.85 individuals/10 leaves in 1st May and

mid- February 2016, respectively. On the other hand, the lowest population of *L. floridana* was in mid-July 2015 with 21.63 individuals/10 leaves. Also, in the second year the total population of *L. floridana* recorded 3 peaks, the highest one was the 1st peak with 112.56 individuals/10 leaves in 1st May. The other 2 peaks were 56.32 and 82.39 individuals/10 leaves in 1st July and mid-November, respectively. In addition, the lowest population was noticed in mid-June and 1st February 2017 with 32.23 and 28.35 individuals/10 leaves, respectively.

In the 1st year the highest rates of increase, which indicate the most preferable time for the insect were recorded in mid-August and the beginning of September with 1.67 and 1.59 with an average maximum and minimum temperature and average relative humidity were 35.43, 25.42°C and 71%. While the lowest rates of increase were in mid-May, mid-July and 1st December with 0.62, 0.61 and 0.68 with an average maximum and minimum temperature and average relative humidity. 28.12, 17.76°C and 74%. During the second year, the highest rates of increase were in 1st July and mid-October with 1.75 and 1.40 with an average maximum and minimum temperature and average relative humidity 31.62, 21.75 °C and 78%. On the other hand, the lowest rate of increase was in mid-June with 0.38 with maximum and minimum temperature and relative humidity 21.24, 19.78°C and 62%.

In addition, in a study to determine the most infested surface of the leaves with *L. floridana* different stages. The results illustrated in Figure (3) showed that upper surface was the most infested surface with the insect different stages in both years with mean no. of total population 48.19 and 39.13 individuals/10 leaves while the lower surface were 36.41 and 25.00

individuals/10 leaves, respectively. From the previously mentioned results it can be concluded that, the highest numbers of *L. floridana* immature and adult stages was detected in October 2015 with 68.82 and 88.35 individuals/10 leaves. Therefore, the highest number of total populations was detected in October with 196.84 individuals/10 leaves. While the highest number of gravid females was observed in November with 46.48 gravid females/ 10 leaves. On the other hand, the lowest population of *L. floridana* was in mid-July 2015 with 21.63 individuals/10 leaves. The highest rate of increase was in July 2016 with 1.75. Also, the upper surface was preferable to the insect than the lower surface.

The obtained results are partially in agreement with Swailem *et al.* (1980) who found stated that heavy infestations of *Lindingaspis rossi* (Mask.) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) on *F. benjamina* in Giza and Zagazig regions. Also, they found that the most abundant numbers of immature stages recorded in November, January and May in Giza and January, April and June in Zagazig. While the peaks of adult stage were recorded in September, November and January in Giza and January, July and September in

Zagazig. In addition, total populations reached a large peak in autumn and early winter and a small one in spring and early summer; Danzig and Pellizzari (1998) stated that *Lindingaspis*

ferrisi McKenzie (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) is known from China, Taiwan, Egypt, India and Pakistan on the upper surfaces of leaves. Tawfik and Mohammad (2001) stated that, *Hemiberlisia lataniae* (Signoret) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) had four population peaks during the year on *Morus alba* in Giza Governorate. El-Sahn and Sadek (2014) found that *Chrysomphalus aonidum* (L.) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae) infesting *Dracena* shrubs was carried out under greenhouse conditions recorded 4 peaks during 1st year of investigation the highest one was in 1st of November 2010 (50.7 insects/ leaf) with maximum and minimum temperature (27.60°C, 17.35°C) and average relative humidity (79.83%). While in the second year it recorded 3 peaks of population; the highest peak was in mid of June (112.5 insects / leaf) with maximum and minimum temperature (32.20°C, 21.35 °C) and average RH. (71.70%).

Figure (1): Population fluctuation of *Lindingaspis floridana* different stages infesting *Ficus benjamina* trees in Cairo Governorate throughout 2015-2016 with the corresponding main weather factors.

Figure (2): Population fluctuation of *Lindingaspis floridana* different stages infesting *Ficus benjamina* trees in Cairo Governorate throughout 2016-2017 with the corresponding main weather factors.

Figure (3): The distribution of total population of *Lindingaspis floridana* on the upper and lower surfaces of *Ficus benjamina* trees leaves during two successive years.

2. Durations and number of generations of *Lindingaspis floridana*:

The results illustrated in Figure (4) showed that, *L. floridana* recorded 3 overlapping generations in both studied years 2015-2016 and 2016-2017.

2.1. In the first year:

2.1.1. 1st generation (Spring generation) started from mid-March 2015 till 1st August with 135 days, with corresponding average temperature and relative humidity 23.24°C and 68% .

2.1.2. 2nd generation (Summer generation) was the shortest one which recorded 90 days started from mid-July till mid-October 2015. (Average temperature and relative humidity 28.82°C and 71%).

2.1.3. 3rd generation (Autumn and winter generation) recorded 135 days from 1st October 2015 till mid-February 2016 (Average temperature and relative humidity 19.17°C and 77%).

2.2. In the 2nd year:

2.2.1. 1st generation (Spring generation) started from 1st of March 2016 till 1st of June with 90 days (Average

temperature and relative humidity 23.44°C and 64 %).

2.2.2. 2nd generation (Summer generation) started from mid-May 2016 till mid-November with 180 days (Average temperature and relative humidity 26.65°C and 72%).

2.2.3. 3rd generation (Autumn and winter generation) was the shortest one started from 1st of November 2016 till mid-January with 75 days. (Average temperature and relative humidity 15.65°C and 76 %). From the previously mentioned results it can be concluded that, *L. floridana* recorded 3 overlapping generations in both studied years where the longest one was 180 days and recorded in summer generation 2016 while the shortest one was 75 days in winter generation.

From the previously mentioned results it can be concluded that, *L. floridana* recorded 3 overlapping generations in both studied years where the longest one was 180 days and recorded in summer generation 2016 while the shortest one was 75 days in winter generation.

Figure (4): Number and durations of generations of *Lindingaspis floridana* during two successive years 2015-2016 and 2016-2017.

The obtained results were in agreement with (Hassan, 1993) who stated that *H. lataniae* which is a principal scale pest of *Ficus* sp. trees and other ornamental recorded two to four generations per year in Egypt, where the first generation crawlers appearing from mid-June to mid-July and second generation crawlers appearing in September. Gill (1997) in New Zealand who stated that *L. rossi* recorded one generation per year on Monterey pine, but there are up to three per year in Egypt. El-Sahn and Sadek (2014) found that *C. aonidium* infesting *Dracena* shrubs in green house had three generations in both years.

3. Population fluctuation of the associated parasitoid with *Lindingaspis floridana*:

From the present study it was found a parasitoid associated with *L.*

floridana infesting *F. benjamina* trees inside the greenhouse in El-Zohreya Botanical Garden, Cairo Governorate. The population of the parasitoid was relatively low, as shown in Figure (5). It recorded 3 peaks each year, the mean of the immature stages population was higher in the 2nd year than the 1st year with 10.19 and 8.43 individuals/10 leaves. In the 1st year, the highest population of the immature stages population was in mid-December 2015 with 16.12 individuals/10 leaves. The other two peaks were recorded in 1st March 2015 and 1st June with 5.38 and 5.26 individuals/10 leaves, respectively. In the 2nd year the highest population was recorded in mid-March with 27.54 individuals/ 10 leaves. While the lower peaks were 5.01 and 6.12 individuals/10 leaves in 1st August and 1st December 2016

Figure (5): Population fluctuation of the associated parasitoid of *Lindingaspis floridana* infesting *Ficus benjamina* trees two successive years 2015-2016 and 2016-2017 in Cairo Governorate.

4. Rate of parasitism of the associated parasitoid:

The results illustrated in Figure (6) showed that the highest rate of parasitism in the 1st year was recorded in mid-January with 18.57%. Whereas, the lowest rate of parasitism was recorded in September 2015 with 2.17% While in the 2nd year the highest rate of parasitism was recorded in 1st April 2016 and 1st February 2017 with 22.62 and 16.12%, respectively. For the lowest rate was in October with 3.83%.

From the previously mentioned results, it can be noticed that the population of the associated parasitoid was relatively low. It recorded 3 peaks each year, the mean of the immature stages population was higher in the 2nd year than the 1st year with 10.19 and 8.43 individuals/10 leaves, respectively. The highest rate of parasitism was recorded in 1st April 2016 with 22.62%. But, the lowest rate

of parasitism was recorded in September 2015 with 2.17%. These results agree with Swailem *et al.* (1980) who mentioned that, the average rates

of parasitism of *L. rossi* were 8.9 and 13.3% for *F. benjamina* in Giza and Zagazig and 13.2% on *Jasminum azoricum* in Giza.

Figure (6): Rate of parasitism of the parasitoid associated with *Lindingaspis floridana* infesting *Ficus benjamina* trees in two successive years 2015-2016 and 2016-2017.

5. Effect of abiotic (Weather) and biotic (Parasitoid) factors on the total population of *Lindingaspis floridana*:

It was important to study the different factors affecting the fluctuation of the total population of *L. floridana* scale insect *L. floridana* in Cairo Governorate during the two successive years (2015-2016) and (2016-2017). Each year under investigation was divided into three generations to detect the effect of abiotic factors (Weather factors) and biotic (Associated parasitoid). Results in Tables (1 and 2) showed the following:

5.1. Effect of abiotic (Weather) factors on population of *Lindingaspis floridana*:

The effect of three weather factors (Maximum, minimum temperatures and relative humidity) was studied in the total population of *L. floridana* in Cairo Governorate during the two successive years (2015-2016) and (2016-2017) and it was taken into consideration the effect of weather

factors two weeks earlier from the starting date of sampling.

5.1.1. The effect of mean maximum temperature on the total population of *Lindingaspis floridana*:

In the 1st year, it was clear that the effect of maximum temperature on the population of *L. floridana* was negatively insignificant in both 1st and 2nd generations with $r=-0.673$ and -0.437 , respectively. While, the effect on the 3rd generation was positively highly significant with $r=0.789$. In the 2nd year, the effect of maximum temperature was insignificant in both 1st and 2nd generations with $r=0.083$ and -0.607 , respectively. However, the relation was positively highly significant in the 3rd generation with $r=0.885$.

5.1.2. The effect of mean minimum temperature on the total population of *Lindingaspis floridana*:

In the 1st year the relation between the mean minimum temperature and the total population of *L. floridana* was the same as in Maximum temperature where the

relation was negatively insignificant in the 1st and 2nd generations with $r = -0.805$ and -0.273 , respectively. As in, the 3rd generation the relation was positively highly significant with $r = 0.813$. In addition, the effect of minimum temperature was negatively insignificant in both 1st and 2nd generations with $r = -0.143$ and -0.727 . But, in the 3rd generation the relation was positively highly significant with $r = 0.916$.

5.1.3. The effect of relative humidity on the total population of *Lindingaspis floridana*:

The mean relative humidity showed an insignificant relation with the mean of the total population of *L. floridana* in both years and in the 3 generations as well. Where it recorded negatively insignificant relation in 1st and 3rd generations with $r = -0.523$ and -0.105 , respectively. But it gave a positively insignificant relation in 2nd generation with $r = 0.176$. Almost the same was recorded in the 2nd year with negatively insignificant effect in both 1st and 2nd generations and positively insignificant in the 3rd generation with $r = -0.153$, -0.175 and 0.031 , respectively.

5.2. Effect of biotic (Associated parasitoid) factor on population of *Lindingaspis floridana*:

In the 1st year, the effect of the presence of the associated parasitoid with *L. floridana* varied from a generation to another where the relation was positively significant in the 1st generation with $r = 0.500$. While in the 2nd generation the effect was negatively insignificant with $r = 0.956$. In the 3rd generation it gave a negatively insignificant relation with $r = -0.668$. In the 2nd year, the effect of the associated parasitoid was positively insignificant in the 1st and 3rd generations with $r = 0.444$ and 0.186 , respectively. On the other hand, the 2nd generation, recorded a significant relation with $r = 0.673$.

5.3. The effect of the combined abiotic and biotic factors on the total population of *Lindingaspis floridana*:

Results in Tables (1 and 2) showed that in the 1st year (2015-2016), the combined effect of the three weather factors and the parasitoid on the population of *L. floridana* was highly significant in the three generations where the explained variance (E.V.%) recorded 97.70, 93.42 and 84.29%, with F values = 137.05, 7.10 and 6.71, respectively. Furthermore, in the 2nd year the combined effect recorded almost the same as in the 1st year where explained variances in the 1st generation was significant with 64.16% and F value = 0.89.

While, the combined effects in the 2nd and 3rd generations were highly significant with E.V. = 95.54 and 99.9% and F values = 42.80 and 1710.20. From the previously mentioned results we can conclude that, maximum and minimum temperatures independently had an insignificant effect on the total population of *L. floridana* in both 1st and 2nd generations, but they gave a highly significant effect on the 3rd generation. While the relative humidity alone had an insignificant effect in both years and during the 3 generations. Whereas, the effect of the presence of associated parasitoid alone was significant in the 2nd generation in both years and in the 3rd generation it was insignificant relation. In case of, the effect of combined abiotic and biotic factors, it varied between significant and highly significant effect in both years which indicate that the effect of combined factors is more efficient on the population of *L. floridana* than each independent factor. These results agree with Williams and Watson (1988) who found that *L. rossi* has been reported from many tropical countries and some temperate areas. Also, Moursi (1999) stated that the temperature had a significant effect on the development of

the *C.aonidum*. El-Sahn and Sadek (2014) found that the maximum, minimum temperature and relative humidity had negative significant

exponential relationship regression on different alive stages of *C. aonidum* inside the greenhouse in Cairo Governorate.

Table (1): Statistical analysis for simple correlation and multicapsid regression to investigate the effect of abiotic and biotic factors on *Lindingaspis floridana* total population during 3 generations in the 1st year (2015-2016).

Factors	Simple correlation	Regression values				“F” value	Explained variance %
	“r”	“b”	s.e.	“t”	Prob.		
1st generation							
Max. temp.	-0.673	-2.39	1.53	-1.57	0.18	52.94**	97.70 %
Min Temp.	-0.805	-0.30	1.60	-0.19	0.86		
RH%	-0.523	-1.90	0.34	-5.62	0.00		
Parasitoid	0.500*	0.34	0.73	0.46	0.67		
2nd generation							
Max. temp.	-0.437	5.98	20.88	0.29	0.80	7.10	93.42
Min Temp.	-0.273	2.06	18.62	0.11	0.92		
RH%	0.176	3.26	3.39	0.96	0.44		
Parasitoid	0.956**	22.93	5.36	4.28	0.05		
3rd generation							
Max. temp.	0.789**	-4.32	13.90	-0.31	0.77	6.71	84.29
Min Temp.	0.813**	16.67	15.13	1.10	0.32		
RH%	-0.105	2.81	1.52	1.85	0.12		
Parasitoid	-0.668	4.56	2.74	1.66	0.16		

* Significant relation

**Highly significant relation

Table (2): Statistical analysis for simple correlation and multicapsid regression to investigate the effect of abiotic and biotic factors on *Lindingaspis floridana* total population during 3 generations in the 2nd year (2016-2017).

Factors	Simple correlation	Regression values				“F” value	Explained variance %
	“r”	“b”	s.e.	“t”	Prob.		
1st generation							
Max. temp.	0.083	8.53	9.15	0.93	0.45	0.89	64.16
Min Temp.	-0.143	-23.83	36.61	-0.65	0.58		
RH%	-0.153	-3.86	6.85	-0.56	0.63		
Parasitoid	0.444	-3.26	8.66	-0.38	0.74		
2nd generation							
Max. temp.	-0.607	-3.28	2.27	-1.44	0.19	42.80	95.54
Min Temp.	-0.727	0.48	2.72	0.18	0.86		
RH%	-0.175	0.70	0.39	1.79	0.11		
Parasitoid	0.673*	4.06	0.49	8.28	0.00003		
3rd generation							
Max. temp.	0.885**	-2.96	0.34	-8.65	0.07	1711.20	99.9
Min Temp.	0.916**	8.63	0.38	22.44	0.03		
RH%	0.031	-0.98	0.06	-15.60	0.04		
Parasitoid	0.186	4.99	0.28	17.70	0.04		

* Significant relation

** Highly significant relation

References

Abd-Rabou, S. (2001): An annotated list of the Hymenopterous parasitoids of the Diaspididae (Hemiptera: Coccoidea) in Egypt, with new records. *Entomologica*, 33(1999): 173-177.

Attia, A. R. and Radwan, S. G. (2013): On the scale insects infesting mango trees and their parasitoids at Qaluobia Governorate, Egypt. *Egyptian*

Journal of Biological Pest Control, 23(1): 131-135.

Bakr, R. F. A.; Badawy, R. M.; Mousa, S. F.; Hamooda, L. S. and Atteia, S. A. (2009): Ecological and taxonomic studies on the scale insects that infest mango trees at Qaliobiya Governorate. *Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci.*, 2 (2): 69- 89.

Bodenheimer, F. S. (1951): *Citrus entomology in the Middle East with special references to Egypt, Iran, Irak, Palestine,*

- Syria, Turkey (No. BOD 634.3 (BR 533)). Dr., W. Junk, Publishers.
- Danzig E.M. and Pellizzari G. (1998):** Diaspididae. In: Catalogue of Palearctic Coccoidea (F. Kozár Editor), Plant Protection Institute, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Budapest, 172-370.
- El-Sahn, O.M.N. and Sadek, I.I. (2014):** Impact of certain climatic factors on population of *Chrysomphalus aonidum* L. infesting *Dracena* Shrubs under green house conditions. Journal of American Science, 10(12s):31-36.
- Ezzat, Y. M. and Nada , S. M.A. (1986):** List of super family Coccoidea as known to exist in Egypt. Boll. Lab. Ent. Agr. Filippo silvestri, 43: 85-90.
- Fisher, R.A. (1950):** Statistical methods for research workers. Oliver and Boy Ltd., Edinburgh, London. 12th ed.; 518.
- Gill, R. J. (1997) :** The scale insects of California. Part 3: the armored scales (Homoptera: Coccoidea: Diaspididae). California Department of Food and Agriculture Technical Series in Agricultural Biosystematics and Plant Pathology, 3: 307 .
- Hassan, N. A.; Radwan, S. G. and El-Sahn, O. M.N. (2012):** Common scale insects (Hemiptera:Coccoidea) in Egypt. Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci., 5(3): 153 -160.
- Hassan, N.A. (1993):** Survey and toxicological studies on citrus diaspine scale insects and their parasites in Egypt. Ph.D. Thesis, Fac. Sci., Ain Shams University.
- Jacob, N. (1977):** Un mode mathematic pentra stabilirea limitelor economic de toleranta an atacului moliilor fructelor inlupte integrate. Analele I.C.P.P.15.
- Miller, D. R.; Miller, G. L. ; Hodges, G. S. and Davidson, J. A. (2005):** Introduced Scale Insects (Hemiptera: Coccoidea) of the United States and Their Impact on U.S. Agriculture. Proc. Entomol. Soc. Wash., 107(1):123-158.
- Moursi, K.A. (1999):** Studies on the natural enemies of scale insects infesting some fruit trees. Ph.D. Thesis, Benha Branch, Zagazig University .
- Orphanides, G. M. (1982):** Biology of the California red scale, *Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell) (Homoptera, Diaspididae), and its seasonal availability for parasitization by *Aphytis spp* in Cyprus. (Bbiological citation): Boll. Entomol. Agraria Filippo Silvestri, 39: 203-212.
- ScaleNet (2021) :** A literature-based model of scale insect biology and systematics. García Morales M, Denno BD, Miller DR, Miller GL, Ben-Dov Y, Hardy NB. (Eds.) .Database. doi: 10.1093/database/bav118. <http://scalenet.info> .
- Swaleem, S. M.; Awadallah, K. T. and Shaheen, A. A.(1980):** Abundance of *Lindingaspis rossi* Mask. on ornamental host plants in Giza and Zagazig regions, Egypt (Hemiptera-Homoptera: Diaspididae). Egypt Bull Soc ent Egypte, 60:257–263.
- Tawfik, M. H. and Mohammad, Z. K. (2004):** Ecological studies of two scale insects (Hemiptera, Coccoidea) on *Morus alba* in Egypt. Bollettino di Zoologia Agraria e di Bachicoltura, 33: (3): 267-273.

Williams, D.J. and Watson, G.W.
(1988): The Scale Insects of the
Tropical South Pacific Region.
Part 2. The Mealybugs
(Pseudococcidae) CAB

International, Wallingford, 257.

Possibility for laboratory mass rearing of the potato tuber moth *Phthorimaea operculella* (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) through simplified steps and procedures

Ahmed, Abdel-Monem Taha¹ and Youssef, R. Hassan²

¹Central Laboratory for Organic Agriculture, Agricultural Research Centre, Giza, Egypt.

²Packaging materials Department, National Research Centre, 12622, Dokki, Cairo, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 10 /1/2021

Accepted:25/ 2 /2021

Keywords

Potato tuber moth,
Phthorimaea operculella, laboratory mass rearing and bio-control agents' production.

Abstract:

Insects, laboratory rearing is a prerequisite for any works related to fundamental or applied entomology, the number of needed individuals either for small experiment or for mass production of a biological control agent, is one of the main aspects to be considered. The potato tuber moth (PTM), *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), represent one of the major threats for potato production worldwide and generally laboratory reared in many labs worldwide, using the same concept and principals. In this work, a validated simplified system for PTM mass production under laboratory conditions is presented. The presented fabricated rearing unit aims to maximize production of germ free PTM stages with optimal use of available infrastructure, equipment, labors, and at the same time, minimizing risks of potato pathogens spread among PTM rearing containers or boxes.

Introduction

Insect laboratory rearing is essential for securing testing, insect materials needed for either ecological and/or biological studies, developing and mass production of biological control agents including natural enemy or production of sterile insect for release programs. A lack of proper planning and well-designed equipment in an insect rearing and harvesting program can result in wasted money, labor, and time, leading to failure of a research or control program (Hsin and Wayne, 1988 and Rameswor and Chuleui, 2011).

The potato tuber moth (PTM) or tobacco split worm, *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae), is an indigenous pest that originated in tropical mountains of South America (Hristina *et al.*, 2016). It

attacks and accompanying potato and other solanaceous plants, that grown and found in over 90 countries and distributed in temperate and subtropical climates regions, such as tomatoes, eggplants (*Solanum melongena* L.), peppers (*Capsicum* spp.), tobacco, and wild solanaceous plants like jimson weed or datura (*Datura stramonium* L.) (Alvarez *et al.*, 2005). Most economic damage that occurs to potato tubers under storage conditions are attributed to PTM larval feeding and their boring tunnels and deposit excreta in tubers, resulting in the unfit of tuber for either local consumption and/or for exportation (Malakar and Tingey 2006 and Rondon, 2010).

Among semi-artificial diets described in insect laboratory rearing, few diets were reported for PTM and

request quite well defined and precisely weighing chemicals, and mixing of a large number of components that surely present high costs (Badegana and Ngameni, 2000; Gleave *et al.*, 1998 ; Sharaby and Saleh, 1985 and Singh and Charles (1977) however, Kashyap *et al.* (2008) stated that testing of all these published diets gave negligible to very low rates of larval survival.

The applied conventional PTM laboratory rearing approach worldwide is essentially relay on potato tubers as a main source for larval feeding and both PTM mature and immature stages are kept in closed ventilated containers or boxes that regularly supplied with potato tubers and kept under controlled weather conditions. Application of these conventional rearing procedures for the insect mass rearing may require much space, precautions and effective measures of temperature and relative humidity to suppress disease outbreaks and surely are labor-intensive therefore, the objective of this work was the design and development of a practical laboratory potato tuber moth rearing unit (PTMRU) that permit easier observation, dealing with different PTM stage, and a practical harvest of a particular PTM stage, when needed for further purposes. During the course of this work, we examined the proposed simplified PTMRU to ensure minimal handling intervention and consequently, reducing risks of disease spread, if occur, labor cost, and duration and efforts needed for the regular daily work.

Materials and methods

1. Origin and maintenance of *Phthorimaea operculella* colony:

The PTM moths used in this study were derived from the laboratory colony of *P. operculella* maintained at the Plant Protection Research Institute which is affiliated with the Egyptian Agricultural Research Center. At the beginning, the PTM individuals were

conventionally reared according to procedures described by Jordao *et al.* (2010), under controlled conditions ($25 \pm 1^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 14hrs photoperiod). To facilitate pupae harvesting the technique was slightly modified so the pupation was formed in the provided corrugated carton strips of about 1.2 cm in width, which were prepared by longitudinally cutting of corrugated carton boxes, sheets, which traditionally used for packaging, then the strips were placed among and on potato tubers in part (B) of the designed and fabricated PTMRU as it will be explained later. For transferring PTM pupae to adults' box, carton strips were longitudinally opened (Tear apart) as shown in (Figure 1 C and D) and liberated pupae were surface disinfected in 0.3% sodium hypochlorite solution for 1 minute, rinsed in distilled water, dried on filter paper and finally sexed.

For egg production, sexed disinfected pupae were transferred to adult box in 1:1 ratio (Male: female) then the adult box was covered by a circular piece of white paper (Or filter paper), sitting on top of a black fine mesh net fitted tightly over the opening with an elastic band. To ensure contact of the used white paper with the fine black mesh, a piece of cork and slight weight were used as shown in Figure 2 (A, B and C). The PTM moths were provided with 10% honey solution as a source for adult feeding through a rolled tissue paper that is placed at the internal extremity of U-shape drinking straw and soaked via capillarity with the honey solution.

Papers containing collected PTM produced eggs, as shown in Figure (3), were surface disinfected in 0.3% sodium hypochlorite solution for 1 minute, rinsed in distilled water, dried on filter paper, then kept in plastic ventilated cylinder boxes for further use under the same controlled conditions.

Finally, cut papers with counted PTM eggs with black head capsules were transferred to the potato tubers surface-drilled at the rate of two grams potato per one PTM larva and new formed pupae were used for re-initiation of the new PTM rears cycle regularly.

2. The potato tuber moth rearing unit (PTMRU) description:

The whole unit was made from available house hold commercial plastic tools for the kitchen. As shown in Figure (4), it consists of two parts A and B. The part (A) is designed for capturing PTM adults (Moths) and their source for feeding, and even egg production if desired. This part is composed of two plastic cylinders. The 1st plastic cylinder (ca) contains one inlet hole and is freely placed, inside the 2nd plastic cylinder (cb) that contains number of holes equivalent to a number of sectors in part (B) of the PTMRU. The cylinder (ca) is placed inside the cylinder (cb) to create a form- fit seal with it to open or close the inlet holes and to prevent moths from exiting the cylinder (ca) and backing to any sector of part (B). The formed moths coming from different sectors of part (B) can be captured either selectively (from one selected sector) by simply turning the cylinder (ca) around its axe and adjusting its inlet holes to the chosen sector outlet open, or collectively (from all sectors at the same time) by pulling cylinder (ca) up so all the inlet holes of the cylinder (cb) is allowed to function at the same time, and a common recipient for PTM moths coming from all sectors is formed as shown in Figure (5).

All inlet holes in the two cylinders of part (A) are precisely aligned with each other and with outlets of all potato tubers sectors located in part (B). The part (B) is designed to receive clean, disinfected and surface, drilled potato tubers for infestation with newly hatched PTM neonates regularly.

This part (B) is divided into sectors (S) or parts using plastic sheets and each sector is provided with an external lateral hole that is closed with a cover containing a window of fine muslin (0.1m) for ventilation, and used to facilitate regular observation, manipulation and daily works, and reduce risks of possible spread of diseases among used potato tuber, if occur, all over the rearing unit Figure 4 (B, C and D).

Results and discussion

In the presented work, we designed, fabricated and examined a simplified PTM rearing unit (PTMRU) that aims to maximize production of different PTM individuals needed for further laboratory studies and/or for production of particular biological control agents or pathogen, through a simple approach based on arranging potato tubers in separate parts (Sectors) to ensure reduction of manual interference, spread of potato diseases, financial cost for infrastructures and labor, and time required for mass production of a certain germ free PTM stage.

In the conventional rearing procedures described by many authors worldwide, the PTM laboratory rearing is essentially based on almost the same concept of preparing a main rearing box, made of suitable material and covered by fine mesh gauze with zips at different positions to facilitate manipulation, and a common system for receiving formed pupae in either sand or sawdust layers by placing an additional separated recipient under the main rearing box. Normally these labs should be supported with extra facilities such as CO₂ containers or freezer to subdue or sedate moths .

In the present work, we report a simple PTMRU that shows practical and useful. The unit minimizes manual interfering leading to prevention of physical damage to any of the insect

stages, at the same time it allows rapid observation and manipulation of PTM rearing cycle, including, capturing of adult moth by orienting them to egg laying box (Adult box), harvest of pupae, if needed for further investigations or for egg production, by simply collecting corrugated carton strips placed in part (B). In this respect, it worth to mention that even larval individuals that preferred to build their cocoons and to pupate inter (Among) tubers or elsewhere within its rearing sector, are not considered wasted because potato tuber sector located in part (B) are directly opened on part (A) which is designed for capturing the PTM moths and getting benefit from most formed PTM moths.

Advances of the proposed model:

The Part (A) that is designed for capturing PTM adults (moths) either selectively or collectively. Presence of the two cylinders (ca and cb) of the part (A) with their precisely aligned inlet holes permitted a faster and controlled capturing of PTM moths. Beside its function of capturing PTM moths, the part (A) can be directly used for PTM egg production by simply attaching an adult box that provided with black fine mesh net and a feeding source as shown in Figure (2D). Concerning the design of the prepared adult box either for direct capturing of emerging PTM moths from the PTMRU or for receiving formed PTM pupae in the corrugated carton stripes and production of PTM elsewhere, in both cases, the bottom of this box can be easily opened or closed for either introducing new formed PTM pupae or for cleaning and discarding of dead moths and pupae cadavers, so, different steps, efforts and time required for transferring PTM moths from the PTMRU to another adult box are considerably minimized.

Regarding source of adult feeding, the fact that used honey

solution for feeding moths is supplied externally by using a U shape drinking straw as shown in Figure 2 (A, B and C), allowed PTM moths to be fed through the soaked rolled tissue paper placed at the internal extremity of the same U shape straw, with minimum PTM moths escape, handling and time waste.

The fact that (B) part is divided into sectors(Sections) using plastic sheets as previously shown in Figures (4 and 5), and each sector is provided with a window for ventilation, it helps on one hand, in minimizing risks for disease spread among the whole amount of the used tubers due to raised humidity or infected ones, and also facilitate manual manipulation and /or interference, when needed, for each sector separately, and replacement of consuming or expired tubers with new ones without affecting the running rearing cycle in other sectors. Furthermore, dividing tubers into sectors permits, managing the production rate of different PTM stages easily through controlling and managing time intervals for tuber infestation per sector (Section) with PTM neonates accordingly, number of producing pupae or adults or even eggs is continuously controlled. The cover of each sector lateral hole with ventilated windows was designed for two purposes; firstly, allowing continuous ventilation and air exchange all over the sector, secondly, it permits manual interference when needed.

Regarding pupae formation, the use of corrugated carton strips placed among potato tubers in the part (B) of the PTMRU, considerably facilitate and reduced required manual interference and at the same time, minimized sources for contamination and additional required materials for pupae formation, such as sterilized sand or saw dust, sieves and separated recipients for pupae formation as

applied in conventional PTM rearing methods elsewhere worldwide. In our work, the formed pupae can be easily detected by a simple observation of cocoons filaments that plug the corrugated carton stripes' holes as shown in Figure 1 (A and B), then the PTM pupae can be easily liberated from their cocoons by longitudinal tearing the carton strips apart as shown in Figure 1 (C and D).

The dimensions, in terms of height and diameter, of part (A) and part (B) of our PTMRU described here are modifiable depending on one hand, on purpose and volume of PTM production, and on the other hand space availability for units' arrangement. In this regard, the PTMRUs can be arranged either vertically or horizontally according to available place and equipment. In case of arrangement of several units vertically,

the part (A), can be modified by using a long cylinder with the same described system for inlet holes to serve as a common recipient for adult capturing from each level (Part B), when a large number of adults are needed as for example in the sterile insect release program (Figure 6).

Finally, the PTMRU's two main parts and their subparts could be easily disassembled, cleaned and disinfected with no need for intensive labor or extra time and the whole unit is made from available house hold commercial plastic tools for the kitchen and in case of need, it could be manufactured from durable autoclaveable materials and the same concept (Model) of this work can be adopted and/or inspired for rearing other insect species that yet hard to find a practical rearing method for them.

Figure (1):Harvested potato tuber moth (PTM) pupae formed in the provided corrugated carton strips (A and B), and liberation of formed PTM pupae by tearing apart the carton strips (C and D). Arrows indicate formed cocoon filaments (cf).

Figure (2): (A) Shows adult box for potato tuber moth (PTM) egg production. The plastic box is covered by a circular piece of white paper (w) sitting on top of a black fine mesh net (b) that fitted tightly over the box's opening with an elastic band (e), then a piece of cork (c) and slight weight(r) were used to ensure contact between the placed white paper and the fine black mesh.

(B and C) Show feeding of PTM moths on nutritive solution 10% honey solution (hs) via a rolled tissue paper (tp) placed at the internal extremity of U-shape drinking straw (u).

(D) A simplified figure for adult box designed to be attached to part (A) of the potato tuber moth rearing unit (PTMRU) and used for either capturing and transferring of PTM moths for further work, or for direct production of PTM egg as well. The upper opening (uo) can be easily closed with the screw led or cap, or simply covered with black fine mesh net for egg production as previously described. The down opening (bo), can be easily opened for either introducing new formed PTM pupae or for cleaning and discarding of the dead moths and pupae cadavers.

Figure (3): Potato tuber moth eggs produced on the provided white paper.

Figure (4): 3 D modeling of the PTMRU's parts: (A) Shows part (A) with its two plastic cylinders and their respective inlet holes. (B, C and D) Shows the upper cover or lid, a view for the internal sectors, and circular cover with fine muslin that is used to close lateral sector hole, respectively. (E) Assembled part (B) of PTMRU. (Refer to text for details of assembly).

Figure (5): 3D modeling of the potato tuber moth rearing unit (PTMRU) part (A) and its subparts (cylinder a (ca) that placed inside cylinder b (cb) and their respective inlet holes), and illustration of different positions for the two cylinders inlet holes depending on desired potato tuber moth (PTM) capturing mode.

(A) The two cylinders (ca) and (cb) with their respective inlet holes.

(B) Illustration of positioning of (ca) and (cb) cylinders among different sectors (S) of PTMRU's part (B).

(C) Positions of (ca) and (cb) cylinders inlet holes when PTM moths are captured selectively (From one sector). Note that the signs (+) and (-) denote allowed or not allowed access respectively, for PTM moths from sector(S) to the part A cylinders.

(D) Positions of (ca) and (cb) cylinders inlet holes when PTM moths are captured collectively (From all sectors at the same time). Note that, when the collectively capturing mode is desired, the (ca) is pulled up so it doesn't appear in the illustration).

Figure (6): (A) 3D modeling for disassembled parts and subparts of PTMRU (Arrows indicate directions of assembly or disassembly of the rearing unit). (B) Vertical arrangement of several PTMRUs with an elongated cylinder that serves as a common part (A) for capturing PTM moths.

References

- Alvarez, J.M.; Dotseth, E. and Nolte, P. (2005):** Potato tuber worm a threat for Idaho potatoes. University of Idaho Extension, Idaho Agricultural Experiment Station, Moscow, ID.
- Badegana, A.M. and Ngameni, P.H. (2000):** Rearing of potato tuber moth *Phthorimaea operculella* Zel. (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) in the laboratory, biological parameters and the influence of sugar levels in the feeding of adults. *Tropicultura*, 18: 23-25.
- Gleave, A.P.; Mitra, D.S. ; Markwick, N.P. ; Moris, B.A.M. and Beuning, L.L. (1998):** Enhanced expression of *Bacillus thuringiensis* cry9Aa2 gene in transgenic plants by nucleotide sequence modification confers resistance to potato tuber moth. *Molecular Breeding*, 4: 459-472.
- Hristina, K.; Fernando, C. and Bill, L. (2016):** The main pests on Solanacea crops in zone 1 of Ecuador. *New Knowledge Journal of Science* , 5: 1.
- Hsin, C. and Wayne M. G. (1988):** Mass rearing and harvesting based on an age-stage, two-sex life table: A potato tuberworm (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) case study. *Environ. Entomol.*, 17(1): 18-25.
- Jordao, A. L.; Nakano, O. and Janeiro, V. (2010):** Adult carbohydrate feeding affects reproduction of *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). *Neotropical Entomology*, 39(3):315-318.
- Kashyap, S.; Chakrabarti, S.K. ; Pattanayak, D.; Chandran, K. P.; Gautam, D. C.; Chandla, V. K. and Naik, P.S. (2008):** A modified artificial diet for rearing potato tuber moth *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller). *Potato J.*, 35 (3 - 4): 141-146.
- Malakar, R. and Tingey, W.M. (2006):** Aspects of tuber resistance in hybrid potatoes to potato tuber worm. *Entomologia Experimentalis et Applicata*, 120:131-137.
- Rameswor, M. and Chuleui, J. (2011):** Rearing methods of potato tuber moth, *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae). *Korean Journal of Soil Zoology*, 15(1-2): 53-57.
- Rondon, S.I. (2010):** The potato tuber worm: A literature review of its biology, ecology, and control. *American Journal of Potato Research*, 87:149-166.
- Sharaby, A. and Saleh, M.R. (1985):** On the biology of potato tuber moth, *Phthorimaea operculella* Zeller, on semi-artificial diets. *Bulletin De la Societe Entomologique D' Egypte*, 65: 345-50.
- Singh, P. and Charles, J.G. (1977):** An artificial diet for the larvae of potato tuber moth. *New Zealand Journal of Zoology*, 4: 449-451.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Effect of soil type on the insect population associated with onion plants, with special attention to onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) and crop yield

Hamdy, H. Mahmoud

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 15 /1/2021

Accepted: 22/ 3 /2021

Keywords

Onion, soil type, *Thrips tabaci*, population and yield.

Abstract:

The onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) is a major pest of onion in Egypt. The present studies were carried out at Assiut Governorate throughout the two successive onion growing seasons (2016 / 2017 and 2017 / 2018) on onion plants in three different types of soil which are clay soils, silty soils and reclaimed sandy soils to determine the main pests of onion, their occurrence time and associated predators in addition, to further studies of *T. tabaci* in different soils during both seasons. Also, the effect of someone compound on population of *T. tabaci* and onion yield. Results obtained showed that 15 insect pests and 4 insect predators were present in onion plants. As a general observation, *T. tabaci* was the major and most economically important insect pests threatening onion plantations in the fields. Infestation with thrips prevailed from January until May in three different soils. Significant variation in the total yield of soil type was observed in the two successive growing seasons of study. The silty soil gave the highest total yield and followed by the clay, while the sandy soils gave the lowest total yield. Application of someone compounds increased the yield more than untreated plants in different soils during two seasons.

Introduction

Onion (*Allium cepa* L.) is an important field crop cultivated in all over Egyptian regions for fresh green onion or onion bulbs. Onion plantations as well as bulbs during the storage are eventually subject to considerable insect infestation which effected in the crop quality and quantity (Mahmoud, 2008). Onion plantations usually suffer insect attacks throughout their different growth stages from immediately after transplanting in December until harvest-time in May. During this period onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman

(Thysanoptera: Thripidae) dominates as the most destructive threat. According to the statistics of the Ministry of Agriculture and Land Reclamation the total area cultivated onion in Assiut Governorate in 2019 exceeded 3464 feddan.

Literature on the insects associated with onion plantations in Egypt refer to El-Sherif (1971) and Haydar and Sherif (1987) at Giza; Abd-El-Fattah (1980) at Giza and Sohag; El-Bolak *et al.* (1990) at Giza and Assiut ; Abd-El-Wahab (2004) , El-Gendi (1998), Sabra *et al.* (2007), at Fayoum

and Kafr-El-Shiekh; Mahmoud (2008), El-Sherif and Mahmoud (2008 a and (2008 b); Amro *et al.* (2009) at Assiut and Awadalla *et al.* (2011) at El-Mansoura.

Abroad, literature refers to Thiramurthi *et al.* (1989), Gupta *et al.* (1991) and Satinder *et al.* (2019) in India; Ahn *et al.* (1991) in Korea; Szwejda (1998 and 2005) in Poland; Ciociola-Jr *et al.* (2002) in Brazil; Duchovskiene (2003) in Lithuania; Chernenko and Chernenko (2004) in Ukraine; Mesic and Baric (2004) in Croatia and Gebretsadkan (2017) in Ethiopia.

The present work aims to determine the occurrence time of main onion pests and their associated predators and also to study the population of *T. tabaci* on two cultivars at three soil types and the effect someone chemical compound in *T. tabaci* and yield income of onion in three different soil types during 2016 / 2017 and 2017 / 2018 seasons in Assiut Governorate.

Materials and methods

1. Survey of insect pests and associated predators on onion plants:

Survey of insect pests associated with onion plants at open field, was carried out in farmers fields cultivated with the commonly planted onion cultivar (Giza 6 Mohassan) at different localities at Assiut Governorate from early January until May in 2016 / 2017 season. Random samples of 40 plants were carefully pulled off from selected fields in the morning (Between 6 and 8 a.m.). Sampling plants were carefully introduced into cloth bags the transferred to the laboratory for inspection. In addition to the plant samples, 40 full-length double-net strokes were also taken across the two diagonals of randomly selected parts of the examined onion. Net catch was killed in an ordinary cyanide jar, then

transferred through both plant samples and net-sweeps were carefully examined for identification. In the case of uncertain taxonomic identification, the suspected specimens were conveyed to the appropriate specialist of Insect Classification Research Department at the Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, for proper identification.

2. The population abundance of the onion thrips *Thrips tabaci*:

These experiments were carried out in three different types of soil which are clay soils, silty soils and reclaimed sandy soils by onion farmers and the agricultural research station farm in Arab-Al-Awamer in Assiut Governorate using the commercial variety (Giza 6 Mohassan) during two successive seasons 2016 / 2017 and 2017 / 2018.

These experiments were carried out during survey studies of the pests associated with onion plant. Also, to determine population abundance of the main insect pests in the three types of soil under study. Approximately 1/6 feddan for each soil type was divided into four plots (Replicates) and transplanted with healthy onion seedlings by late November. A random sample of 10 plants was taken from each replicate at quarter-monthly intervals, thus making a total sample size of 40 plants from the whole experimental field, from the beginning of January until the beginning of May. All plots were left to grow normally, and no control measures were applied until harvest-time. Sampled plants were introduced into clean cloth bags, then transferred to the laboratory where they were examined for the occurrence and count of thrips (Larvae and / or adults) associated with onion plants. Data were analyzed with analysis of variance (ANOVA) test.

3. Effect someone chemical compound on *Thrips tabaci* in three

different soil types in relation to the onion yield:

The study was executed in three different types of soil at selected farmer fields and the agricultural research station farm in Arab-Al-Awamer planted with the commonly grown onion cultivar (Giza 6 Mohassan) during the two seasons 2016 / 2017 and 2017 / 2018. For each season, an area of 425 m² from both soil types was divided into four plots (Replicates) and transplanted with onion seedlings by late November. Two applications were applied at 30 days approximately. The first application was on 2 and 4 February and the second application on 2 and 4 March in two the seasons, respectively. The use of the chemical compound was [Carbosulfan (Marsal

25 % WP) 2,3-dihydro-2,2-dimethylbenzofuran- 7 yl (dibutylaminothimethyl carbamate) at the rate of 150 gm. / 100-liter water].

To evaluate the reduction percentage of *T. tabaci* infestation caused by each compound, 5 plants was picked up from each replicate and transferred to the laboratory wherein they were examined for the occurrence of thrips larvae and / or adults. The samples were examined before spray and consequently after 7, 14, 21 and 28 days of application. Reduction percentage in thrips infestation was calculated according to Henderson and Tilton (1955) equation. The reduction in weight estimated by using formulae:

$$\% \text{ Increase weight} = \frac{\text{Weight of onion bulbs in sprayed plots} - \text{weight of onion bulbs in unsprayed plots}}{\text{Weight of onion bulbs in sprayed plots}} \times 100$$

Results and discussion

1. Survey and occurrence time of onion pests and associated predators:

Data presented in Table (1) reveals 19 species belonging to 17 families and 7 orders. Among these species 15 were pests belonging to 14 families and 5 orders and 4 predators belonging to 4 families and 4 orders were recorded in onion plants during the 2016 / 2017 season at Assiut Governorate. Abd-El-Fattah (1980) surveyed 21 insect species on onion plants, El-Bolok *et al.* (1990) found that onion plantations are inhabited by a variety of insects belonging to 38 genera from 23 families and 9 orders, Thiramurthi *et al.* (1989) reported 10 species of insects on onion flowers, Ahn *et al.* (1991) surveyed the insect pests in onion fields, Szwejda (1998 and 2005) identified 23 insect species from onion fields, Ciociola *et al.* (2002) gave notes on the insect pests of onions, Duchovskiene (2003) reported 11 insect species from onion plantations and Mesic and Baric (2004) listed the

dipterous pests associated with onion plants.

Also, on the other hand, data in Table (1) showed that, the onion thrips *T. tabaci* recorded the main insect pests attacking onion plants throughout the whole onion growing season. Such observation seen to coincide with the findings of El-Sherif (1971), Khalil *et al.* (1971), Haydar and Sherif (1987), Abd-El-Wahab (2004), Sabra *et al.* (2007), Mahmoud (2008), El-Sherif and Mahmoud (2008a and 2008b), Amro *et al.* (2009) and Awadalla *et al.* (2011) who agreed that *T. tabaci* is a dominant insect species in onion plantations in Egypt. Some other studies referred to *T. tabaci* as a major pest in onion plantations in India (Thiramurthi *et al.*, 1989 ; Gupta *et al.*, 1991 ; Maher and Shafiq (2014) and Satinder *et al.*, 2019); Korea (Ahn *et al.*, 1991), Poland (Szwejda, 1998 and 2005); Brazil (Ciociola *et al.*, 2002), Lithuania (Duchovskiene, 2003); New York (Elaine *et al.*, 2014), and Ethiopia (Gebretsadkan, 2017).

As seen in Table (1), survey results revealed the rare occurrence of only four predator species mostly by early spring. These predators are the dragonfly *Hemianax ephippiger* (Odonata: Aeschnidae), the aphid lion *Chrysoperla carnea* (Steph.) (Neuroptera: Chrysopidae), the syrphus

fly *Syrphus corollae* Fabricius (Diptera: Syrphidae), the eleven spots beetle *Coccinella undecimpunctata* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae). All these predators occurred as adults only, except for *C. undecimpunctata* which occurred as both larvae and adults.

Table (1): A systematic list of the insect pests and predators associated with onion plants in the fields at Assiut Governorate during 2016 / 2017 onion growing season.

No.	Species	Stage (s)	Frequency of occurrence	Period of occurrence
P E S T S				
1	<i>Thrips tabaci</i> Lind. (Thysanoptera : Thripidae)	A and L	C	Jan. – May
2	<i>Aphis gossypii</i> Glover (Hemiptera : Aphididae)	A and N	Fe	Mar. – May
3	<i>Empoasca discipiens</i> Paoli (Hemiptera : Cicadellidae)	A and N	Fe	Mar. - Apr.
4	<i>Lyperosia minuta</i> Bezzi (Diptera : Muscidae)	A	Fe	Feb. - Apr.
5	<i>Eumerus amoenus</i> Loew. (Diptera : Syrphidae)	L and P	Fe	May
6	<i>Actia crassicornis</i> (Meigen) (Diptera : Tachinidae)	A	Fe	Feb. - Apr.
7	<i>Bemisia tabaci</i> (Gennadius) (Hemiptera : Aleyrodidae)	A	Fe	Feb. - Apr.
8	<i>Melanagromyza cunctans</i> (Meigen) (Diptera : Agromyzidae)	A	Fe	Jan. - Mar.
9	<i>Ephydra macellaria</i> Eggr (Diptera : Ephydriidae)	A	Fe	Feb. - Apr.
10	<i>Hydrellia griseola</i> Fallen (Diptera : Ephydriidae)	A	Fe	Feb. – Mar.
11	<i>Melieria nigratarsis</i> Becker (Diptera : Otitidae)	A	Fe	Mar. - Apr.
12	<i>Lepidocentinus insertus</i> Handschin (Collembola : Entombryidae)	A	R	Mar.
13	<i>Delia alliardia</i> Fonseca (Diptera : Anthomyiidae)	A	R	Mar.
14	<i>Carpophilus hemipterus</i> Linne (Coleoptera : Nitidulidae)	A	R	Mar. - Apr.
15	<i>Sitona lividipes</i> Fahrs. (Coleoptera : Curculionidae)	A	R	Mar. - Apr.
P R E D A T O R S				
1	<i>Hemianax ephippiger</i> Selys. (Odonata : Aeschnidae)	A	R	Feb. - Apr.
2	<i>Chrysoperla carnea</i> Steph. (Neuroptera : Chrysopidae)	A	R	Mar. - Apr.
3	<i>Syrphus corollae</i> Fabricius (Diptera : Syrphidae)	A	R	Mar.
4	<i>Coccinella undecimpunctata</i> L. (Coleoptera : Coccinellidae)	A and L	R	Mar. - Apr.

N = Nymphs L = Larvae P = Pupae A = Adults C = Common (More than 7 once) Fe = Few (4 – 6 once) R = Rare (1-3 once)

2. Population density of *Thrips tabaci* on onion in different soil at Assiut Governorate:

The quarter-monthly population densities of thrips individuals (larvae and adults) in onion fields and cultivated on three different soil types at Assiut Governorate throughout the two successive onion growing seasons (2016 / 2017 and 2017 / 2018) are graphically illustrated in Figure (1) and Figure (2), respectively.

In clay soils, were varied to *T. tabaci* infestation as shown in Figures (1 and 2) thrips individuals began to occur in relatively small numbers (6.3 and 6.0 / plant in two season, respectively) during the 2nd half of January and gradually increased in

In sandy soils, showed the Figures (1 and 2) relatively small counts of thrips individuals occurred during January (5.4 and 5.6 / plant in two seasons, respectively). Starting from early February, the population density tended to increase gradually but rather rapidly during the 2nd half of the month. Population increase continued to a peak of (32.7 and 31.1 / plant in two seasons, respectively) reached during the second half of March. This peak was followed by a drop in thrips count during the 3rd

number throughout February and March until they reached a high peak of (33.4 and 34.2 / plant in early April in the first season and mid-March in the second season, respectively). Thrips counts tended to decrease until harvest-time.

In silty soils, Figures (1 and 2) showed that, the mean number of *T. tabaci* began to occur in relatively small numbers (7.2 and 6.5 / plant in two season, respectively) during the 2nd half of January and gradually increased in number throughout February and March until they reached a high peak of (41.9 and 32.8 / plant by mid-March in two season, respectively). Thrips counts tended to decrease until harvest-time.

quarter of March then before harvest-time.

Generally, in three soil type population density began to occur in relatively small counts by early January until the start in counts increased throughout late of January and early February and March until a high peak of taking place in mid-March. This peak was followed by a gradual decline in thrips population until all larvae and adults completely disappeared from onion fields in early May.

Figure (1): Mean number of individuals in onion plant for *Thrips tabaci*, in various soil types during 2016 / 2017 season.

Figure (2): Mean number of individuals on onion plant for *Thrips tabaci*, in various soil types during 2017 / 2018 season.

In seasons 2016 / 2017 and 2017 / 2018 and Table (2) shows that the highest mean number of thrips individuals on onion plant occurred in silty soils (23.5 and 19.6 with a general mean of 21.5 in two seasons, respectively) and the lowest mean took place in sandy soils (16.8 and 16.4 with a general mean of 16.6 in two seasons, respectively) while in clay soils this mean was slightly less than in silty soils (19.1 and 17.4 with a general mean of 18.2 in two seasons, respectively).

The above results more or less agree with the findings of a group of investigations conducted in Egypt. Karaman (1970) and Khalil *et al.* (1971) coincided that the various stages of *T. tabaci* are found in onion fields in relatively low numbers during December, then increase rapidly to reach maximum abundance throughout April. Haydar and Sherif (1987) mentioned that the population of *T. tabaci* begins to build up by early February and reaches its maximum during April. El-Gendi (1998) stated that *T. tabaci* is active in onion fields from mid-December to mid-May. Embarak (2006) found that the daily rate of population fluctuation of onion thrips increase was lower in newly reclaimed area than in traditional cultivated land in the first planting date. While, in the second planting date, it

was higher in the newly reclaimed area than in traditional cultivated land and Sabra *et al.*(2007) observed to thrips attack onion in nursery and perennial field and its population peaked in March. Furthermore, El-Serwiy *et al.*(1985) observed that in Iraq the population density of *T. tabaci* varies from one year to another and reaches a peak by early April. In Texas, USA, Edelson *et al.* (1986) found that *T. tabaci* individuals occur in onion fields from February till harvest-time in April or May with a peak of abundance in early April. Lu and Lee (1987) contributed that the population density of *T. tabaci* in Taiwan increases from November to April. Kalafchi *et al.* (2006) added that in Iran the population density of *T. tabaci* is the highest 130-158 days after planting.

3. Effect of different soil type on onion yield:

The results for total yield of the different soil type are shown in the same Table (2) and Figure (3) . Significant variation in the total yield of soil type was observed in the two successive growing seasons of study. The silty soil gave the highest total yield (15.351 and 16.054 with a mean 15.703 ton / fed. in seasons 2016 / 2017 and 2017 / 2018, respectively) and followed by the clay soils (13.242 and 13.801 with a mean 13.521 ton / fed. in

two seasons, respectively). While, the sandy soils gave the lowest total yield (11.932 and 11.256 with a mean 11.595 ton / fed. in two seasons, respectively). These results are in agreement with those obtained by Koriem and Farag (1990) who mentioned that Giza 20 gave the highest total yield under Mallawi conditions when compared with other cultivars. However, Gamie *et al.* (1996) showed that Giza 6 Mohassan cv. gave the highest total yield when sown on Sept. 20. Salman

(2000) indicated that, the differences between onion yield at the different sowing dates were significant in both seasons. Amro *et al.* (2009) who found that significant variation in the total yield of cultivars and strains was observed in the two successive growing seasons of study. El-Azhar noua gave the highest total yield (15.62 ton/fed.) and followed by Giza 20 (14.16 ton/fed.). While Giza 6 Mohassan cv. gave the lowest total yield (13.06 ton/fed.).

Table (2): Impact of different soil types on mean number of *Thrips tabaci* on onion plants and yield during two growing seasons at Assiut Governorate.

Soil type	* Mean number of <i>T. tabaci</i> /plant			**Onion yield (ton / feddan)		
	2016 / 2017	2017 / 2018	General mean	2016 / 2017	2017 / 2018	Mean
Clay soil	19.1a	17.4a	18.2a	13.242a	13.801a	13.521a
Silty soil	23.5a	19.6a	21.5a	15.351b	16.054b	15.703b
Sandy soil	16.8b	16.4a	16.6b	11.932c	11.256c	11.595c
L.S.D. (0.05)	4.96	4.11	4.21	0.94	1.11	0.71

* Mean followed by different letters are not significantly different at 5% level.

** Mean followed by different letters are significantly different at 5% level.

Figure (3): Effect of soil type on the total weight (Tons / feddan) of onion yield during two growing seasons.

4. Impact someone chemical compound on *Thrips tabaci* in three different soil types in relation to the onion yield:

The effect of the someone chemical compound on *T. tabaci* infesting onion plants in three different soil types in relation to the onion yield is presented in Tables (3 and 4). Data revealed that the used compound reduced the population density of *T. tabaci* on onion plants in comparison with the control in three soil types and in both two seasons. Regarding the initial effect (7 days after spraying), the chemical insecticide, Marsal 25 % WP were more effective in controlling thrips resulting in [(81.3 and 85.2) and (86.1 and 82.4) in clay soil], [(71.1 & 87.9) and (81.5 & 83.6) in silty soil] and [(81.1 and 88.5) and (80.1 and 82.7) in sandy soil] reduction in 1st and 2nd application during two seasons, respectively. The same observation was found after 14, 21 and 28 days of spray.

Reduction percentages of *T. tabaci* increased with the time elapsed after treatment. The general reduction percentage of the pest can be arranged in descending order as follows: Sandy

soil (48.5 and 50.1) > clay soil (46.2 and 50.1) > silty soil (41.5 and 45.5) during two seasons, respectively. Although, the reduction percentage of the pest numbers caused by using the compound in the sandy soil was higher than other soils, there was no variation in crop yield. Also, it is of importance to notice that the yield increased by from (5.5 – 7.2 %) in season 2016 / 2017. Also, the same found in 2017 / 2018 season, these results are around from (5.5 – 8.3 %) increase in yield income in treating than untreated onion. In general, the used insecticide in sandy soil gave the highest mean percentage of reduction followed by the same used insecticide in clay soil, while the same used insecticide in silty soil gave the lowest mean percentage of reduction.

Similar results were also obtained by El-Sebae *et al.* (1971), El-Serwi and Razouki (1986), Mourad (1992), Omar and El-Kholy (2001), Saleh (2004), Sebra *et al.* (2005), Amro *et al.* (2009), Ibrahim and Adesiyun (2009), Haider, *et al.* (2014), Neetu and Virendra (2016) and Satinder *et al.* (2019).

Table (3): Effect someone chemical compound on *Thrips tabaci* and yield income of onion in three different soil type during 2016 / 2017 season.

Treat-ment	Application	Mean number of <i>T. tabaci</i> per plant and reduction percentage in infestation										Yield		
		Days after spray										% General reduction	Income (ton/fed)	% increase
		Before spray	7 days		14 days		21 days		28 days					
			Mn/p	R%	Mn/p	R%	Mn/p	R%	Mn/p	R%				
Clay soil														
Marsal	1 st.	12.7	2.3	81.3	6.3	58.6	13.7	21.0	19.7	10.1	42.7	46.2	14.063	5.8
25%WP	2 nd.	19.7	3.1	85.2	10.2	63.2	15.5	45.3	25.8	5.1	49.7			
Control	1 st.	13.1	12.7	--	15.7	--	17.9	--	22.6	--	--	--	13.242	--
	2 nd.	22.6	24.1	--	31.8	--	32.5	--	31.2	--	--			
Silty soil														
Marsal	1 st.	11.5	2.7	71.1	7.5	36.8	18.5	17.4	28.4	11.5	34.2	41.5	16.248	5.5
25%WP	2 nd.	28.4	3.4	87.9	13.4	59.4	21.3	34.4	39.7	13.7	48.8			
Control	1 st.	15.4	12.5	--	15.9	--	21.1	--	34.1	--	--	--	15.351	--
	2 nd.	34.1	33.9	--	39.7	--	39.0	--	41.9	--	--			
Sandy soil														
Marsal	1 st.	10.7	2.1	81.1	5.4	66.9	15.2	13.3	18.9	23.2	46.1	48.5	12.860	7.2
25%WP	2 nd.	18.9	2.5	88.5	7.7	67.5	19.6	29.2	25.7	18.4	50.9			
Control	1 st.	9.7	10.1	--	14.8	--	15.9	--	22.3	--	--	--	11.932	--
	2 nd.	22.3	25.7	--	28.0	--	32.7	--	25.6	--	--			

1 st. Application: 2 February 2017.

2 nd. Application: 2 March 2017

Table (4): Effect someone chemical compound on *Thrips tabaci* and yield income of onion in three different soil types during 2017 / 2018 season.

Treat-ment	Application	Mean number of <i>T. tabaci</i> per plant and reduction percentage in infestation										Yield		
		Before spray	Days after spray								General reduction	Income (ton/fed)	% increase	
			7 days		14 days		21 days		28 days					
			Mn/p	R%	Mn/p	R%	Mn/p	R%	Mn/p	R%				
Clay soil														
Marsal	1 st.	12.1	2.0	86.1	6.0	68.4	13.5	33.3	15.3	33.7	55.4	50.1	14.855	7.1
25%WP	2 nd.	15.3	2.9	82.4	7.7	65.1	17.5	21.3	19.9	11.0	44.9			
Control	1 st.	11.9	14.2	--	18.7	--	19.9	--	22.7	--	--	--	13.801	--
	2 nd.	22.7	24.5	--	32.7	--	33.0	--	26.6	--	--			
Silty soil														
Marsal	1 st.	12.8	2.5	81.5	8.0	58.9	16.6	22.8	23.2	15.8	44.7	45.5	16.986	5.5
25%WP	2 nd.	23.2	3.2	83.6	9.9	60.1	19.8	25.3	31.4	16.4	46.3			
Control	1 st.	13.1	13.8	--	19.9	--	22.0	--	28.2	--	--	--	16.054	--
	2 nd.	28.2	23.7	--	30.2	--	32.2	--	32.8	--	--			
Sandy soil														
Marsal	1 st.	10.9	1.9	80.1	5.0	74.9	11.7	44.5	16.5	32.9	58.1	50.1	12.272	8.3
25%WP	2 nd.	16.5	2.7	82.7	9.5	53.9	15.4	27.8	23.2	4.3	42.2			
Control	1 st.	8.9	7.8	--	16.3	--	17.2	--	20.1	--	--	--	11.256	--
	2 nd.	20.1	19.0	--	25.1	--	26.0	--	27.1	--	--			

1 st. Application: 4 February 2018.

2 nd. Application: 4 March 2018.

References

- Abd-El-Fattah, T. A. (1980):** Factors affecting the insect population during the storage of onion bulbs. M.Sc. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Al-Azher University.
- Abd-El-Wahab, A. S. (2004):** Insects and insect-borne viruses associated with Alliaceae crops in Egypt. Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Cairo University.
- Ahn, S. B.; Lee, S. B. and Cho, W. S. (1991):** Leaf feeding insect pests and their damage on welsh onion and shallot fields in Chonrabukdo and Chonranamdo Districts. Research Reports of the Rural Development Administration Crop Protection, 33 (1): 66-73.
- Amro, M. A.; Abd El-Rahim, G. H. and Abd El-Raheem, A. A. (2009):** Population fluctuation, relative susceptibility and control of *Thrips tabaci* Lind. on some onion and garlic cultivars and strains. Ass. Univ. Bull. Environ. Res., 12(2): 131-141.
- Awadalla, S. S.; El-Naggar, M. E.; Abdel-Baky, N. F. and Omnia, F. H. (2011):** The insect pests attacking onion plants with special references to the onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* lind. at Mansoura region. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 2 (1): 1-12.
- Chernenko, V. L. and Chernenko, K. M. (2004):** Onion pests from the east of forest-steppe of Ukraine. Nowosci-Warzywnicze, 38: 95-100.
- Ciociola-Jr, A. I.; Franca, F. H. and Ciociola, A. I. (2002):** Pests associated with onion crops and their control. Informe-Agropecuario, 23 (218): 68-74.
- Duchovskiene, L. (2003):** Dynamics of pest harmfulness in onion crop depending on growing technique. Sodininkyste ir Darzininkyste, 22 (1): 153-163.
- Edelson, J. V.; Cartwright, B. and Royer, T. A. (1986):** Distribution and impact of *Thrips tabaci* (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) on onion. J. Econ. Entomol., 79(1): 502-505.
- Elaine, J. F.; Jessica, D. P. and Brian, A. N. (2014):** Relationships between insect predator populations and their prey, *Thrips tabaci*, in onion fields grown in large-scale and small-scale cropping systems. Bio Control, 59: 739-748.
- El-Bolok, M. M.; Ismail, I. I. and El-Shabrawy, H. A. (1990):** Survey and relative abundance of insects attacking onion in field and store with the accompanied natural enemies at Giza and Assuit regions. Annals of Agric. Sc., Moshtohor, 28 (3): 1791-1804.
- El-Gendi, S. M. (1998):** Population fluctuation of *Thrips tabaci* Lind. on onion plants under Fayoum environmental conditions. Arab Universities J. Agric. Sci., 6(1): 267-276.
- El-Sebae, A. H.; Khalil, F. M.; Ali, A. M. and Karaman, G. A. (1971):** The efficiency of side treatment of some insecticides on the population density of *Thrips tabaci* in onion fields. Assuit J. Agric. Sci., 2(1): 232-242.
- El-Serwiy, S. A. and Razouki, I.A. (1986):** Comparative efficiency and application number of some insecticides and sulfur against thrips, *Thrips tabaci* (lind.) on onion and their effects on bulb weights. J. Agric. Water reso. Res., 5(2): 177-184.
- El-Serwiy, S. A.; Razoki, I. A. and Ragab, A. S. (1985):**

- Population density of *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman and the predators *Orius albidipennis* Reut. and *Aeolothrips fasciatus* L. on onion. J. Agric. Water Reso. Res., 4(3): 57-67.
- El-Sherif, A. R. A. (1971):** Studies on insects infesting onion and garlic in field and storage. Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Cairo University.
- El-Sherif, S. I. and Mahmoud, H. H. (2008a):** Insect fauna of onion plants in seedbeds, fields and stores in Assiut Governorate. Bull. Fac. Agric. Cairo Univ., 59(4): 318-325.
- El-Sherif, S. I. and Mahmoud, H. H. (2008b):** The population densities of two major insect pests of onion; the onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci* Lindeman) in fields and the onion bulb fly (*Eumerus amoenus* Loew.) in stores. Bull. Fac. Agric. Cairo Univ., 59(4): 326-332.
- Embarak, M. Z. (2006):** Development of onion thrips, *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman, as a function of certain agricultural practices. Assiut J. of Agricultural Science, 37 (4): 219-232.
- Gamie, A.A.; Abd El-Rahim, G.H.; Imam, M.K. and Abdoh, A.E. (1996):** Effect of sowing dates on yield and bulb quality on some onion cultivars grown by direct seeding. Assiut J. Agric. Sci., 27(2):101-110.
- Gebretsadkan, Z. (2017):** Seasonal distribution and abundance of Thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) on onion production in central zone of Tigray, Ethiopia. Int. J. of Life Sciences, 5 (3): 323-331.
- Gupta, R. P.; Srivastava, K. J. and Pandey, U. B. (1991):** Management of onion diseases and insect pests in India. Onion Newsletter for the Tropics, 3: 15-17.
- Haider, K.; Ghulam, A.; Asifa, H.; Ghayour, A. and Amjad, A. (2014):** Losses in onion (*Allium cepa*) due to onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci*) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) and effect of weather factors on population dynamics of thrips. World Applied Sciences Journal, 32 (11): 2250-2258.
- Haydar, M. F. and Sherif, L. S. (1987):** Ecological aspects and developing method of onion pest control. Bull. Soc. Ent. Egypt, Economic Series, 16: 119-126.
- Henderson, C. F. and Tilton, E. W. (1955):** Tests with acaricides against the brown wheat mite. J. Econ. Entomol., 48:157-161.
- Ibrahim, N. D. and Adesiyun, A. A. (2009):** Effect of staggered planting dates on the control of *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman and yield of onion in Nigeria. Afr. J. Agric. Res., 4(1): 33-39.
- Kalafchi, M.; Mobli, M.; Ebadi, R. and Rezaei, A. M. (2006):** A study of population fluctuations of onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci* Lind.) and its effect on bulbing and yield of selected onion cultivars in Isfahan. Iranian J. Agric. Sci., 36(6): 465-477.
- Karaman, G. A. I. (1970):** Studies on certain pests of onion with special reference to their control. M. Sc. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Assiut University .
- Khalil, F. M.; El- Sebae, A. H. and Karaman, G. A. (1971):** Some ecological studies on *Thrips tabaci* Lind. Assiut J. Agric. Sci., 2(1): 197-206.
- Koriem, S. and Farag, I.A. (1990):** Effect of cultivar, age and size of seedling on yield and quality of onion (*Allium cepa* L.) bulb

- crop. Assiut J. Agric. Sci., 21 (3): 195-203.
- Lu, F. M. and Lee, H. S. (1987):**The life history and seasonal occurrence of onion thrips (*Thrips tabaci* Lindeman). J. Agric. Res. of China, 36 (1): 118-124.
- Maher, A. M. and Shafiq, A. M. (2014):** Population Dynamics of Onion Thrips, *Thrips tabaci*, on Onion Cultivars. Journal of Agroecology and Natural Resource Management, 1(3): 141-147.
- Mahmoud, H. H. (2008):** Ecological studies on certain insect pests of onion with special emphasis on the onion bulb fly *Eumerus amoenus* Loew. (Diptera: Syrphidae). Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Cairo University.
- Mesic, A. and Baric, J. I. (2004):** Diptera pests on onion vegetables in Croatia. Entomologia-Croatica, 8 (1/2): 45-56.
- Mourad, E. I. (1992):** Potency and residual activity of insecticides against *Thrips tabaci* Lind. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 70(2): 443-450.
- Neetu, S. and Virendra, K. (2016):** Monitoring the infestation and damage level of onion thrips, *Thrips tabaci* on onion crop in Aligarh (U.P.). Asian Journal of Agriculture and life Sciences, 1(3): 12-19.
- Omar, B. A. and El-Kholly, M. I. (2001):** Comparative bio-efficacy of certain traditional and non-traditional insecticides against thrips infesting onion. J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 26 (4) :2373-2381.
- Sabra, I. M.; El-Nagar, M. A. and Khewa, M. M. I. (2005):** Efficacy of some non-chemical insecticides against *Thrips tabaci* lind. And its associated predators. Egypt. J. Agric. Rec., 83(2): 653-659.
- Sabra, I. M.; El-Nagar, M. A. and Shalaby, M. S. I. (2007):** Further ecological studies on onion pests in Egypt. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 85(4): 1259-1266.
- Saleh, M. Z. E. (2004):** Ecological studies on some onion pests and their control in Assiut Governorate. Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Assiut University .
- Salman, A. M. A. (2000):** Effect of onion sowing dates on onion thrips, *Thrips tabaci* (Lind.) infestation in Upper Egypt. Zagazig J. Agric. Res., 27(3): 723-732.
- Satinder P.; Johnson, W.; Raut, A.M. and Najitha Banu, A. (2019):** Eco-biology and management of onion thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae). J. ent. Res., 43 (3): 371-382.
- Szwejd, J. (2005):** Pests threatening onion in Poland. Nowosci-Warzywnicze, 40: 53-59.
- Szwejd, J. (1998):** Threat of onion plantations with pests, especially Diptera. Biuletyn warzywniczy, 48: 57-64.
- Thiramurthi, S.; Udayasoorian, C. and Balamurugan, P. (1989):** Insects affecting onion flowers. Seeds and Farms, 15 (2): 23-24.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

On a collection of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) of Iran

Majid, Navaeian¹; Hamid, Sakenin²; Angélica, Maria Pentead-Dias³; Najmeh, Samin⁴;
Reijo, Jussila⁵ and Shaaban, Abd-Rabou⁶

¹ Department of Biology, Yadegar- e- Imam Khomeini (RAH) Shahre Rey Branch, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran.

² Department of Plant Protection, Qaemshahr Branch, Islamic Azad University, Mazandaran, Iran.

³ Departamento de Ecologia e Biologia Evolutiva, Universidade Federal de São Carlos – UFSCar, Rodovia Washington Luís, São Carlos, SP, Brasil.

⁴ Department of Plant Protection, Science and Research Branch, Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran.

⁵ Zoological Museum, Section of Biodiversity and Environmental Sciences, Department of Biology, FI-20014 University of Turku, Finland.

⁶ Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 1/4/2021

Accepted: 3/6/2021

Keywords

Ichneumonid wasps,
species diversity,
fauna, new records and
Iran.

Abstract:

This faunistic paper on Iranian Ichneumonidae deals with 69 species in 15 subfamilies Adelognathinae (one species), Anomaloninae (Three species, three genera), Banchinae (11 species, five genera), Campopleginae (19 species, 13 genera), Cryptinae (Four species, four genera), Ctenopelmatinae (Seven species, five genera), Diplazontinae (Two species, two genera), Ichneumoninae (11 species, nine genera), Metopiinae (One species), Ophioninae (One species), Orthocentrinae (One species), Pimplinae Two species, two genera), Poemeniinae (Two species, two genera), Tersilochinae (Three species, three genera), and Tryphoninae (One species) which were collected from different regions of Iran. Eight species are new records for the fauna of Iran: *Barichneumon perversus* (Kriechbaumer, 1893), *Bioblapsis polita* (Vollenhoven, 1878), *Chasmias motatorius* (Fabricius, 1775), *Diadegma contractum* (Brischke, 1880), *Diphyus castanopyga* (Stephens, 1835), *Euporizon exilis* (Holmgren, 1860), *Sympherta montana* (Gravenhorst, 1829), and *Syrphoctonus dimidiatus* (Schrank, 1802).

Introduction

The Hymenoptera are one of the four largest orders of insects, with over 152 677 described species worldwide (Zhang, 2013). The Ichneumonidae is the largest hymenopteran family with 1 601 genera and 25,285 described species (Yu *et al.*, 2016). This

cosmopolitan family usually occurs in all kinds of climates, though humid habitats are more favourable for them (Wahl, 1993 and Broad *et al.*, 2018). The catalogue of Iranian Ichneumonidae has been published by Kolarov and Ghahari (2005), they recorded 144 species belonging to 65

genera and 14 subfamilies. After that Barahoei *et al.* (2012) published the checklist comprises 502 species belonging to 189 genera and 24 subfamilies. Later, other authors (Mohammadi-Khoramabadi *et al.*, 2013; Ghahari and Jussila, 2014a, 2014b, 2015a, 2015b, 2016a, 2016b; Barahoei *et al.*, 2014a, 2014b, 2015; Ghahari, 2015, 2016; Ghahari and Gadallah, 2017; Riedel and Aghadokht, 2017 and Mohammadi- Khoramabadi and Talebi, 2018, etc.) have made contributions to the Iranian fauna. The aim of this paper is the faunistic study on the ichneumonids from some regions of Iran and introducing of eight new country records.

Materials and methods

Most of the specimens of this faunistic paper were obtained from insect collections of some universities (Branches of Islamic Azad University), private collections, and world museums (e.g., HNHM, NMPC, Turku University, and etc.). Additionally, some materials were collected by Malaise traps and sweeping net from different regions of Iran. The specimens are deposited in the collections of authors and also in the mentioned universities and museums. Here we follow Yu *et al.* (2016) for nomenclature, classification and distributional data.

Results and discussion

In total, 69 species of Ichneumonidae within 53 genera and 15 subfamilies are listed in this paper, with eight new country records. The list of species is represented below alphabetically with distributional data.

The results of this research with eight new country records and also the conducted researches in different regions of Iran indicate that the fauna of ichneumonid wasps is very diverse in Iran and also unknown. So, we expect a diverse fauna of Ichneumonidae in most regions of Iran where have not been

sampled systematically. These beneficial insects have been used successfully as biocontrol agents and are huge potential for utilization in managed biological control programs (Wahl, 1993; Godfray, 1994; Ghahari *et al.*, 2006 and Quicke, 2015). Additionally, the hosts of most species of Iranian Ichneumonidae are unknown because of using of Malaise traps and sweeping net for collecting. So, conducting the faunistic surveys upon parasitoids-host relationships will result to determining of ichneumonids' hosts and establishment of biological control programs.

Subfamily Adelognathinae

Genus *Adelognathus* Holmgren, 1855
***Adelognathus nigrifrons* Holmgren, 1857**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Behshahr, 1♀, September 2005.

General distribution: Azerbaijan, Canada, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, Germany, Poland, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Anomaloniinae

Genus *Aphanistes* Förster, 1869
***Aphanistes ruficornis* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Neka, 2♀, September 2002.

General distribution: Belgium, Bulgaria, Former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Barylypa* Förster, 1869
***Barylypa insidiator* (Förster, 1878)**

Material examined: Isfahan province, Shahreza, 2♀, 2♂, April 2004.

General distribution: Afghanistan, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Former former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Korea, Latvia,

Lithuania, Mongolia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Ukraine, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Therion* Curtis, 1829

***Therion giganteum* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Razavi Khorasan province, Torbat Heydarieh, 1♀, April 2004.

General distribution: Algeria, Azerbaijan, China, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Mongolia, Poland, Russia and Sweden.

Subfamily Banchinae

Genus *Alloplasta* Förster, 1869

***Alloplasta plantaria* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Zanjan province, Abhar, 1♀, July 2003.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, China, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Turkey and United Kingdom.

Genus *Banchus* Fabricius, 1798

***Banchus falcatorius* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined: Fars province, Kazeroon, 2♀, August 2000.

General distribution: Eastern Palearctic, Europe and Western Palearctic.

***Banchus zonatus* Rudow, 1883**

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Maraqeh, 1♀, July 2009.

General distribution: Algeria, France, Germany, Israel, Italy, Morocco, Russia and Spain.

Genus *Cryptopimpla* Taschenberg, 1863

***Cryptopimpla caligata* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Markazi province, Ashtiyan, 3♀, May 2010.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Kazakhstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands,

Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Exetastes* Gravenhorst, 1829

***Exetastes femorator* Desvignes, 1856**

Material examined: Chaharmahal & Bakhtiari province, Lordegan, 1♀, July 2013.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, China, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Mongolia, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Turkey and United Kingdom.

***Exetastes gracilicornis* Gravenhorst, 1829**

Material examined: Guilan province, Rasht, 2♀, 1♂, April 2008.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, China, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Lissonota* Gravenhorst, 1829

***Lissonota bivittata* Gravenhorst, 1829**

Material examined: Guilan province, Roodsar, 1♀, 1♂, September 2011.

General distribution: Algeria, Bulgaria, Croatia, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Moldova, Mongolia, Poland, Romania, Spain, Turkey, Turkmenistan and former Yugoslavia.

***Lissonota dubia* Holmgren, 1856**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Ramsar, 1♀, 1♂, June 2007

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

***Lissonota deversor* Gravenhorst, 1829**

Material examined: Khuzestan province, Andimeshk, 1♀, May 2008.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, South Africa, Spain, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

***Lissonota proxima* Fonscolombe, 1854**

Material examined: Khuzestan province, Gotvand, 2♀, April 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

***Lissonota variabilis* Holmgren, 1860**

Material examined: Bushehr province, Borazjan, 1♀, May 2004.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Campopleginae

Genus *Bathyplectes* Förster, 1869

***Bathyplectes quinqueangularis* (Ratzeburg, 1852)**

Material examined: Alborz province, Nazar-Abad, 1♀, June 2013.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Tunisia, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

***Bathyplectes stenostigma* (Thomson, 1887)**

Material examined: Guilan province, Lahijan, 1♀, October 2005.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, Canada, former former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Sweden and USA.

Genus *Callidora* Förster, 1869

***Callidora albovincta* (Holmgren, 1860)**

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Oshnavieh, 1♀, September 2006.

General distribution: Austria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Japan, Latvia, Poland, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Genus *Campoletis* Förster, 1869

***Campoletis chlorideae* Uchida, 1957**

Material examined: Kerman province, Jiroft, 1♀, April 2010.

General distribution: Bangladesh, Barbados, China, India, Japan, Korea, Mauritius, Nepal, Pakistan and Syria.

***Campoletis crassicornis* (Tschek, 1871)**

Material examined: Chaharmahal & Bakhtiari province, Lordegan, 2♀, August 2015.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Genus *Casitaria* Holmgren, 1859

***Casitaria albipalpis* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Alborz province, Taleghan, 1♀, September 2007.

General distribution: Austria, former Czechoslovakia, Egypt, France, Germany, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Poland, Russia, Spain, Tunisia and United Kingdom.

Genus *Diadegma* Förster, 1869

***Diadegma contractum* (Brischke, 1880)**

Material examined: Lorestan province, Azna, 1♀, September 2014.

General distribution: Azerbaijan, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Netherlands, Poland, Romania and Russia.

***Diadegma elishae* (Bridgman, 1884)**

Material examined: Hamadan province, Toyrserkan, 2♀, May 2010.

General distribution: Afghanistan, Austria, France, Germany, Lithuania, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Spain, Tajikistan and United Kingdom.

***Diadegma tenuipes* (Thomson, 1887)**

Material examined: Semnan province, Damghan, 1♀, 1♂, June 2012.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Faeroe Islands, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Tunisia and United Kingdom.

***Diadegma trochanteratum* (Thomson, 1887)**

Material examined: Razavi Khorasan province, Ferdos, 1♀, August 2013.

General distribution: Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Faeroe Islands, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Tunisia, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Echthronomas* Förster, 1869

***Echthronomas quadrinotata* (Thomson, 1887)**

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Mahabad, 1♀, September 2014.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, Egypt, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Poland, Russia and Spain.

Genus *Enytus* Cameron, 1905

***Enytus apostata* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Alborz province, Taleghan, 1♀, 1♂, September 2007.

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greenland, Hungary, India,

Ireland, Isle of Man, Israel, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Slovakia, South Africa, Sri Lanka, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Hyposoter* Förster, 1869

***Hyposoter dolosus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Kuhgiloyeh & Boyerahmad province, Dehdasht, 2♀, August 2011.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Tunisia, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Lathrostizus* Förster, 1869

***Lathrostizus lugens* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Guilan province, Astara, 1♀, July 1998.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Norway, Poland, Romania, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Genus *Lemophagus* Townes, 1965

***Lemophagus pulcher* (Szépligeti, 1916)**

Material examined: Ardabil province, Meshginshahr, 1♀, July 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy and Switzerland.

Genus *Nemeritis* Holmgren, 1860

***Nemeritis fallax* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Guilan province, Lahijan, 1♀, October 2006.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Poland, Russia, Switzerland and Ukraine.

Genus *Olesicampe* Förster, 1869

***Olesicampe fulcrans* (Thomson, 1887)**

Material examined: Hamadan province, Malayer, 1♀, June 2008.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Moldova, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia and United Kingdom.

Olesicampe fulviventris (Gmelin, 1790)

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Savadkooh (Pol-e Sefid), 1♀, August 2002.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Norway, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Genus *Sinophorus* Förster, 1869

Sinophorus xanthostomus (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Kermanshah province, Ravansar, 3♀, 2♂, May 2011.

General distribution: Eastern Palaearctic, Ethiopian, Europe, Oriental and Western Palaearctic.

Subfamily Cryptinae

Genus *Atractodes* Gravenhorst, 1829
Atractodes croceicornis Haliday, 1838

Material examined: Razavi Khorasan province, Sabzevar, 1♀, May 2009.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Isle of Man, Italy, Japan, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Hoplocryptus* Thomson, 1873
Hoplocryptus fugitivus (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Chaharmahal & Bakhtiari province, Sarkhoon, 1♀, September 2012.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Moldova, Norway, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Rhembobius* Förster, 1869

Rhembobius bifrons (Gmelin, 1790)

Material examined: Guilan province, Langrood (Liseh Rud), 1♀, May 2014.

General distribution: Azerbaijan, Bulgaria, Croatia, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Poland, Romania, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Stilpnus* Gravenhorst, 1829

Stilpnus (Polyrhembia) tenebricosus (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Hamadan province, Gol Tappeh, 3♀, 1♂, September 2015.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Faeroe Islands, Finland, France, Germany, Greenland, Hungary, Iceland, Ireland, Latvia, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, USA, Ukraine, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Subfamily Ctenopelmatinae

Genus *Campodorus* Förster, 1869

Campodorus variegatus (Jurine, 1807)

Material examined: Razavi Khorasan province, Chenaran, 2♀, April 2010.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Hadrodactylus* Förster, 1869

Hadrodactylus indefessus (Gravenhorst, 1820)

Material examined: Golestan province, Gorgan, 1♀, June 2006.

General distribution: Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, USA, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Sympherta* Förster, 1869

***Sympherta montana* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Kordestan province, Saqez, 1♀, July 2010.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

***Sympherta ullrichi* (Tschek, 1869)**

Material examined: Kuhgiloyeh & Boyerahmad province, Sisakht, 3♀, August 2011.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey and United Kingdom.

Genus *Syndipnus* Förster, 1869

***Syndipnus lateralis* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Alborz province, Nazar-Abad, 1♀, June 2013.

General distribution: Canada, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Ireland, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, USA and United Kingdom.

Genus *Xenoschesis* Förster, 1869

***Xenoschesis fulvipes* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Guilan province, Lahijan, 1♀, 1♂, September 2005.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

***Xenoschesis (Polycinetis) ustulata* (Desvignes, 1856)**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Savadkooh (Pol-e Sefid), 1♀, 1♂, August 2002.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Estonia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Diplazontinae

Genus *Bioblapsis* Förster, 1869

***Bioblapsis polita* (Vollenhoven, 1878)**

Material examined: Golestan province, Golestan National Park, 1♀, August 2006.

General distribution: Belarus, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Japan, Netherlands, Poland, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Syrphoctonus* Förster, 1869

***Syrphoctonus dimidiatus* (Schrank, 1802)**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Ramsar, 2♀, June 2010.

General distribution: Afghanistan, Azerbaijan, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Iceland, India, Ireland, Italy, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Ichneumoninae

Genus *Barichneumon* Thomson, 1893

***Barichneumon perversus* (Kriechbaumer, 1893)**

Material examined: Alborz province, Taleghan, 1♀, September 2007.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Switzerland and former Yugoslavia.

***Barichneumon sedulus* (Gravenhorst, 1820)**

Material examined: Northern Khorasan province, Jajarm, 3♀, June 2011.

General distribution: Afghanistan, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain and United Kingdom.

Genus *Chasmias* Ashmead, 1900

***Chasmias motatorius* (Fabricius, 1775)**

Material examined: Hamedan province, Asad-Abad, 2♀, May, 2008.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Ireland, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Moldova, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Genus *Crypteffigies* Heinrich, 1961

***Crypteffigies lanius* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Lorestan province, Aleshtar, 2♀, May 2017.

General distribution: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Genus *Diphyus* Kriechbaumer, 1890

***Diphyus bicingulatus* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Salmas, 1♀, September 2014.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden and Switzerland.

***Diphyus castanopyga* (Stephens, 1835)**

Material examined: Golestan province, Golestan National Park, August 2008.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, France, Germany, Hungary, Netherlands,

Norway, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland and United Kingdom.

Genus *Goedartia* Goie, 1841

***Goedartia alboguttata* (Gravenhorst, 1829)**

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Qaemshahr, 1♀, August 2006.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Czech Republic, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Japan, Latvia, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Ichneumon* Linneaus, 1758

***Ichneumon pictus* Gmelin, 1790**

Material examined: Ardabil province, Meshginshahr, 1♀, July 2009.

General distribution: Azerbaijan, Belgium, Bulgaria, France, Germany, Norway, Poland, Romania and United Kingdom.

Genus *Melanichneumon* Thomson, 1893

***Melanichneumon albipictus* (Gravenhorst, 1820)**

Material examined: Fars province, Fasa, 2♀, April 2002.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, China, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Italy, Japan, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Taiwan, Ukraine, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Rhadinodonta* Szépligeti, 1908

***Rhadinodonta flaviger* (Wesmael, 1845)**

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Khoy (Bilehvar), 1♀, May 2012.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, France, Germany, Hungary, Poland, Romania, Switzerland and former Yugoslavia.

Genus *Spilichneumon* Thomson, 1894

Spilichneumon johansonii (Holmgren, 1871)

Material examined: Isfahan province, Najaf-Abad, 2♀, July 2001.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Korea, Luxembourg, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Metopiinae

Genus *Bremiella* Dalla Torre, 1901

Bremiella pulchella (Kriechbaumer, 1890)

Material examined: Kordestan province, Bijar, 1♀, June 2016.

General distribution: Algeria, Bulgaria, Hungary, Israel, Moldova, Russia, Switzerland, Turkey and Ukraine.

Subfamily Ophioninae

Genus *Eremotylus* Förster, 1869

Eremotylus marginatus (Jurine, 1807)

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Sari, 2♀, October 2012.

General distribution: Austria, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, France, Germany, Hungary, Japan, Korea, Moldova, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Switzerland, Turkey, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Orthocentrinae

Genus *Hyperacmus* Holmgren, 1856

Hyperacmus crassicornis (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: East Azarbaijan province, Hashtrood, 3♀, September 2005.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Canada, Czech Republic, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, India, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Mongolia, Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden, Tajikistan, USA, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Subfamily Pimplinae

Genus *Sinarachna* Townes, 1960

Sinarachna nigricornis (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Miandoab (Hesarlu), 2♀, April 2013.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, China, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, Germany, Poland, Romania, Russia, Sweden and United Kingdom.

Genus *Townesia* Ozols, 1962

Townesia tenuiventris (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined: Qazvin province, Takestan, 2♀, 1♂, June 2005.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Canada, former Czechoslovakia, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Japan, Latvia, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, USA, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Subfamily Poemeniinae

Genus *Deuteroxorides* Viereck, 1914

Deuteroxorides elevator (Panzer, 1799)

Material examined: West Azarbaijan province, Salmas, 1♂, August 2015.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Genus *Poemenia* Holmgren, 1859

Poemenia hectica (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Chaharmahal & Bakhtiari province, Shahrekod, 2♀, September 2010.

General distribution: Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Netherlands, Norway,

Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom and former Yugoslavia.

Subfamily Tersilochinae

Genus *Barycnemis* Förster, 1869

Barycnemis gracillima (Thomson, 1889)

Material examined: Semnan province, Shahrood, 2♀, June 2011.

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Estonia, Finland, Georgia, Germany, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Lithuania, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden and Ukraine.

Genus *Diaparsis* Förster, 1869

Diaparsis aperta (Thomson, 1889)

Material examined: Zanjan province, Mahneshan, 2♀, September 2015.

General distribution: Armenia, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belgium, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Georgia, Germany, Kyrgyzstan, Moldova, Poland, Russia, Slovakia, Sweden, Turkey and Ukraine.

Genus *Gelanes* Horstmann, 1981

Gelanes fuscus (Holmgren, 1860)

Material examined: Mazandaran province, Sari (Citrus orchard), 2♀, October 2007.

General distribution: Austria, Belarus, Bulgaria, Finland, Germany, Hungary, Kazakhstan, Norway, Poland, Russia, Sweden and Ukraine.

Subfamily Tryphoninae

Genus *Cycasis* Townes, 1965

Cycasis rubiginosa (Gravenhorst, 1829)

Material examined: Chaharmahal & Bakhtiari province, Koohrang, 2♀, September 2010.

General distribution: Albania, Austria, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Belgium, Bulgaria, former Czechoslovakia, Finland, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Latvia, Moldova, Mongolia, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Romania, Russia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland,

Turkmenistan, Ukraine and United Kingdom.

Acknowledgements

Sincere thanks to M.R. Shaw (UK), E. Diller (Germany), D.R. Kasparian (Russia) and M.G. Fitton (UK) for their scientific cooperation in this project. This research was supported by Islamic Azad University and University of Turku.

References

- Barahoei, H.; Rakhshani, E. and Riedel, M. (2012):** A checklist of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) from Iran. Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics, 8(2): 83-132.
- Barahoei, H.; Rakhshani, E.; Fathabadi, K. and Moradpour, H. (2014a):** A survey on the fauna of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) of Khorasan-e-Razavi province. Iranian Journal of Animal Biosystematics, 10(2): 145-160.
- Barahoei, H.; Nader, E. and Rakhshani, E. (2014b):** Cryptinae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) of Isfahan province, central Iran. Turkish Journal of Zoology, 39: 279-284.
- Barahoei, H.; Nader, E. and Rakhshani, E. (2015):** A survey on Ichneumonidae of Isfahan province, central Iran. Journal of Crop Protection, 4(2): 157-166.
- Broad, G.R.; Shaw, M.R. and Fitton, M.G. (2018):** Ichneumonid wasps (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae): their classification and biology. Royal Entomological Society and Field Studies Council, pp. 418.
- Ghahari, H. (2015):** A faunistic study on Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) from Semnan

- province, Iran. Wuyi Science Journal, 31: 34-42.
- Ghahari, H. (2016):** A study on the fauna of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) in the province of Tehran, Iran. Arquivos Entomoloxicos, 16: 125-132.
- Ghahari, H. and Jussila, R. (2014a):** A faunistic study on the Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) from the west of Iran. Linzer biologische Beiträge, 46(2): 1373-1377.
- Ghahari, H. and Jussila, R. (2014b):** A study on the subfamily Ichneumoninae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) from Khorasan province, Iran. Linzer biologische Beiträge, 46(2): 1367–1371.
- Ghahari, H. and Jussila, R. (2015a):** An additional contribution to the fauna of ichneumonid wasps (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) from Iran. Far Eastern Entomologist, 299: 18-24.
- Ghahari, H. and Jussila, R. (2015b):** Faunistic notes on the ichneumonid wasps (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) in alfalfa fields in some regions of Iran. Entomofauna, 36(12): 185-192.
- Ghahari, H. and Jussila, R. (2016a):** Contribution to the knowledge of the fauna of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) from Iran. Contributions to Entomology (Beiträge zur Entomologie), 66(1): 119-124.
- Ghahari, H. and Jussila, R. (2016b):** The Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) of northern Iran: a faunistic study. Acta Musei Moraviae, Scientiae biologicae (Brno), 101(1): 55-62.
- Ghahari, H.; Yu, D.S. and van Achterberg, C. (2006):** World bibliography of the family Baraconidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) (1964 – 2003). NNM Technical Bulletin 8:pp. 293.
- Ghahari, H. and Gadallah, N.S. (2017):** Species diversity of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonoidea) in Tehran province, Iran. Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control, 27(1): 1-5.
- Godfray, H.C.J. (1994):** Parasitoids, behavioral and evolutionary ecology. Princeton University Press, pp. 473.
- Kolarov, J. and Ghahari, H. (2005):** A catalogue of Ichneumonidae (Hymenoptera) from Iran. Linzer biologische Beiträge, 37: 503–532.
- Mohammadi-Khoramabadi, A.; Talebi, A.A. and Zwakhalas, K. (2013):** A study of the subfamily Pimplinae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) in the north of Iran, with eleven new species records. Entomofauna, 34: 29-56.
- Mohammadi-Khoramabadi, A. and Talebi, A.A. (2018):** Study of three genera of the *Orthocentrus* genus-group (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae, Orthocentrinae) in northern Iran. Journal of Entomological Society of Iran, 37(4): 441-460.
- Quicke, D.L.J. (2015):** The braconid and ichneumonid parasitic wasps: Biology, systematics, evolution and ecology. Wiley Blackwell, Chichester, pp. 688.
- Riedel, M. and Aghadokht, P. (2017):** Contribution to the Ichneumoninae (Hymenoptera: Ichneumonidae) of Iran, with descriptions of three new species. Zoology in the Middle East, 63(4): 1-8.
- Wahl, D.B. (1993):** Family Ichneumonidae. In: Goulet, H.

and Huber, J.T. (eds.),
Hymenoptera of the world: An
identification guide to families.
Canada Communications
Group, Ottawa, pp. 668 .

**Yu, D.S.; van Achterberg, K. and
Horstmann, K. (2016):** World
Ichneumonoidea 2011.
Taxonomy, Biology,
Morphology and Distribution.
Taxapad.com. Canada.

Zhang, Z.Q. (2013): Animal
biodiversity: An outline of
higher level classification and
survey of taxonomic richness.
Zootaxa, 3703(1): 1-82.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Influence of mobile phone radiation on brood area, pollen gathering and inoculation virgin queen in honeybees *Apis mellifera* (Hymenoptera: Apidae) colonies

Atif, M. El-Hady and Amany, S.M. Abou-Lila

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 5/4/2021

Accepted: 10/6/2021

Keywords

Apis mellifera, cell phone mobiles, brood area, gathering pollen and virgin queen.

Abstract:

The present study was done at a private apiary at Ayash village in Gharbia Governorate during October –November, 2020. Twelve colonies were used, nine colonies equipped with cell phone mobiles in working conditions for 3, 6 and 10 minutes, three colonies for each and the remained three colonies acts as a control without a cell phone. This experiment was taken 39 days. In general, significant differences were found between all the measured parameters. The maximum brood area was found the control colonies (354.33 inch²), while the lowest was detected with 10 min * of mobile phone radiation (214.00 inch²). The highest average of gathering pollen was found in the control colonies (125.33 g) and the lowest was found in colonies exposed to 10 min * of radiation (37.33 g). Cell phone mobile affected significantly in the inoculation of virgin queen, since no inoculation was done with 10 min exposure. The remarkable decline in brood area, gathering pollen and inoculation of queen virgin was observed in the course of study due to exposure to cell phone mobile radiation.

Introduction

Honeybees are one of the most important industry in the world. Bees are liable to attack by viruses, bacteria, and pesticides and recently cellular equipment which blame the unprecedented honey bee decline. New experiments suggest a strong correlation between population decline and cellular equipment. The massive amount of radiation produced by towers and mobile phones is frying the navigational skills of the honey bees and preventing them from returning back to their hives (Sahib, 2011). The thriving hives suddenly left with only queens, eggs and hive bound immature worker bees.

The behavioral pattern of bees alters when they are in close proximity

to mobile phones and towers. The vanished bees are never found but thought to die singly far from home. Bee keepers were told that several hives have been abruptly abandoned. If towers and mobile phones increase the honey bees might be wiped out in ten years. In North America, the National Agricultural Statistics reported in February 2008 stated that hives honeybees decreased from 5.9 million in 1947 to 4.5 million in 1980 then 2.44 million in 2008 (Gerber, 2007). In South Lebanon losses reached 30 – 35 % where 100 of 450 hives were lost (Taylor, 2011). The present work aims to study the effect of cell phone radiation on brood-rearing activity, quantity of gathering pollen and inoculated virgin queen.

Materials and methods

The effect of cell phone radiation on the behavior of bees (*Apis mellifera*) was studied in a private apiary at Gharbia Governorate from October- November,2020 (Figure 1). Twelve colonies having the bee strength of 8-9 frames were selected for this study. Nine colonies were used as test colonies for radiation and the remained three colonies acted as control. The tested colonies were provided with mobile phones in working conditions for 3, 6 and 10 minutes , three colonies for each.

The experimental observation

hive had one mobile phone placed in the hive. The experimental observation hive had one mobile phone placed in the hive. The control colonies were not provided with mobile phones.

Observations on brood-rearing activity in inch² were measured before exposure, and after exposure, two weeks intervals in all the colonies, observation on collecting pollen loads was recorded weekly from 1st October to 10th November,2020, while inoculated mating of queen was measured at the end of the exposure.

Figure (1): Honeybee colonies with cell phone of 900 MHZ frequency.

Results and discussion

1. Brood-rearing area:

Data in (Table 1) showed that after 39 days the brood-rearing activity significantly decreased after exposure (Table 1). In general, the control treatment was found to be maximum (354.33 inch²). Ten minutes of exposure significantly was found to be the minimum (214.00 inch²). No significant differences were found between 3 min (284.66 inch²) and 6 minutes of exposure (269.66 inch²).

Mall and Kumar (2014) found that maximum brood area in the colonies kept near towers measured by (537.85cm²), followed by the brood area in the colonies equipped with cell phone (534.82 cm²), compared to the brood area in the control colonies (560.36 cm²). Sharma and Kumar (2010) found a significant decline in colony strength and in the egg laying rate of the queen due to EMRs. On the contrary, Mall and Kumar (2014) reported no apparent effect of EMR on brooding

behavior of *A. mellifera*, colonies.

2. Gathering pollen:

Data in Table (1) the amount of pollen gathering, showed a significant decline at all the periods of exposure compared to the control colonies. The control colonies found the maximum rate of pollen gathering (125.33g). However, the 10 minutes of cell phone exposure were found the minimum rate

Table (1): Effect of bee colonies to cell phone on brood-rearing activity, collected pollen and inoculated mating virgin queen at different periods mobile radiation.

Treatment	Brood-rearing activity inch ²		Collected pollen / gm.	Inoculated mating queen %
	Before Treat.	After treat.		
3 minutes	112.66	284.66 b	87.33 b	0.33 ab
6 minutes	158.33	269.66 b	56.00 c	0.33 ab
10 minutes	141.66	214.00 c	37.33 d	0.00 b
Control Untreated	150.66	354.33 a	125.33 a	1.00 a
L.S.D. at 0.05%		21.38	16.11	0.69

3. Inoculation of mating queen:

No significant differences were found between 3 minutes (0.33), 6 minutes (0.33) of cell phone exposure comparative as the control colonies (1.00) concerning with the inoculated virgin queens.

The massive amount of radiation produced by mobile phones is actually frying the navigational skills of the honey bees and preventing them from returning back to their hives resulting in decline in brood area and pollen gathering (Warnke, 1975 and 1976). Solutions to the problem will not be as simple as eliminating the towers or cell mobile phone. Communities need to be given the opportunity to reject cell towers and national Governments need to consider ways of growing their cellular networks without constantly exposing people to radiation. More research is essential on how to protect the bee hives from the electromagnetic exposure, but perhaps more to study the impacts on humans.

References

Gerber, R. (2007): Target Health Inc. webpage on Environment

Sharma and Kumar (2010) reported that there was neither honey nor pollen, brood and bees sustained in the colonies resulting in complete loss of the colony. The massive amount of radiation produced by towers and mobile phones is actually frying the navigational skills of the honey bees and preventing them from returning back to their hives (Sahib, 2011).

Matters. [Online]. Available: <http://blog.targethealth.com/?p=58>.

Mall, P. and Kumar, Y. (2014): Effect of electromagnetic radiations on brooding, honey production and foraging behavior of European honeybees (*Apis mellifera* L.). African Journal of Agricultural Research, 9 (13): 1078 -1085.

Sahib, S. S. (2011): Impact of mobile phones on the density of honeybees. Journal of Public Administration and Policy Research, 3(4) : 131-117.

Sharma, V.P and Kumar, N.R. (2010): Changes in honey bee behavior and biology under the influence of cell phone radiation. Current Sci., 98(10):1376 -1378.

Taylor, A . (2011): Lebanese“ beekeepers feel the sting as hives collapse.”The Daily Star, Lebanon, 2011. [Online] Available: <http://www.dailystar.com.lb/Culture/Lifestyle/2011/Sep-5/1478862011-lebanese->

beekeepers-feel-the-sting-as-hives-collapse.ashx.

Warnke, U. (1975): Bienen unter Hochspannung (Bees under high voltage). Umschau, 13:

416-417.

Warnke, U. (1976): Effect of electrical charges on honey bees. Bee World, 57(2): 50-56.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Effect of propolis extracts and *Bacillus thuringiensis* on leafminer fly *Liriomyza sativae* (Diptera: Agromyzidae)

Amal, E. Marouf; Ghada, E. Abd-Allah and Marwa, M. Shalaby

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 12 / 4 / 2021

Accepted: 27 / 5 / 2021

Keywords

Liriomyza sativae,
tomato crop, propolis,
Bacillus thuringiensis
and control.

Abstract:

This study aimed to evaluate the effect of water, ethanol extracts of propolis, and *Bacillus thuringiensis* on larvae of tomato leafminer *Liriomyza sativae* Blanchard (Diptera: Agromyzidae). This pest is considered one of the most serious pests all over the world because it has a wide host range and may promote pathogen transmission followed by loss of crop quality and yield. Due to the problems of chemical pesticides to all organisms and the environment, natural control replaced pesticides. Microbial control with *B. thuringiensis* is one of the effective methods used in pest control. Also, propolis extracts are one of the natural control methods which is used recently in pest control. In this study, a water propolis extract achieved a high mortality rate against *L. sativae* with LC₅₀ of 4628.002 ppm followed by BT with LC₅₀ of 7110.849 ppm, then propolis ethanolic extract was less effective material with LC₅₀ of 9288.848 ppm.

Introduction

Tomato (*Lycopersicon* spp.) is economically one of the most important vegetables (Polston and Anderson, 1999). Leafminer flies (Diptera: Agromyzidae) are phytophagous insects distributed worldwide, with approximately 2500 species being described (Spencer, 1990 and Winkler *et al.*, 2009). These leafminers are characterized by the development of eggs and larvae inside the leaves, leading to the formation of mines in the leaf parenchyma that reduce photosynthesis, increase premature leaf drop and promote pathogen transmission, subsequently compromising crop quality and yield (Johnson *et al.*, 1983; Parrella, 1987 and Matteoni and Broadbent, 1988). International trade of ornamental and vegetable crops facilitates their

dispersion because the eggs and larval mines are not always visible in the host. *Liriomyza sativae* Blanchard (Diptera: Agromyzidae) is polyphagous and cosmopolitan, with an increased distribution and agricultural importance. Pesticides produced from natural products have been recently attracting the attention of many scientists to avoid the problems caused by synthetic compounds. They are deeply interested in their chemical constituents and biological properties (Abou-Yousef *et al.*, 2010).

Propolis is generally known as the “bee glue”, which is a generic name that refers to the resinous substance accumulated by the bees from different types of plants. The word “propolis” is derived from Greek to mean defense for “pro” and city or community for “polis”, or in other words the beehive

(Castaldo and Capasso , 2002). Propolis functions in sealing holes and cracks and for the reconstruction of the beehive. It is also used for smoothing the inner surface of the beehive, retaining the hive's internal temperature (35 °C), preventing weathering, and invaded by predators. Furthermore, propolis harden the cell wall and contributes to an aseptic internal environment. Propolis generally becomes soft and sticky upon heating (Shehu *et al.* , 2016). It also possesses a pleasant smell. Propolis and its extracts have numerous applications in treating various diseases due to its antiseptic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antibacterial, antimycotic, antifungal, antiulcer, anticancer, and immunomodulatory properties.

Bacillus thuringiensis (BT) is an aerobic gram-positive endospore-forming bacterium which is a part of the family Bacillaceae and it is widely used in agriculture as a biological pesticide (Aronson *et al.*, 1986; Höfte and Whiteley, 1989 and Feitelson *et al.*, 1992).

The hypothesis of the present study was to evaluate the influence of natural and microbial control methods with propolis extracts and *B. thuringiensis*, respectively, as control agents against leafminer which considered one of the most serious pests all over the world because it has a wide host range, followed by loss of crop quality and yield. As well as reducing the use of chemical pesticides that cause a lot of hazards to all organisms and the environment.

Materials and methods

1. Insect rearing:

Tomato leaves carrying larvae of *L. sativae* were collected from the unsprayed farm of Agricultural College, Mansoura University, Dakahlia, Egypt. The leaves were kept in jars at 27 ± 2 °C and $65 \pm 5\%$ RH. The colony was maintained for two

generations before the beginning of the tests. Then, the leaves with the newly hatched larvae of *L. sativae* were placed in plastic Petri dishes (10 cm diam). Each dish was covered with muslin for aeration and tomato leaves were put on the bottom of the dish (Madahi and Sahragard, 2012). Whenever the leaves appeared discoloured, they were replaced with fresh ones.

2. Bacterial strain used, source and applications:

Bacillus thuringiensis (4QSTR1) was obtained from the Center of *Bacillus* Genetics Stock, Biochemistry Department, Ohio University, Columbus, U.S.A. *Bacillus thuringiensis* was preserved on Luria-Bertani (LB) medium, containing: 0.5% NaCl, 0.5% yeast extract, and 1% tryptone and pH 7.0 (Sambrook *et al.*, 1989). *B. thuringiensis* was grown in Petri dishes. The spores were collected from L.B agar plates, then washed three times with ice-cold distilled water. Pellets (spores and crystals) were resuspended in small volumes of distilled water. The bacterial crystals and endospores were prepared according to the method described by Karamanlidou *et al.* (1991).

3. Preparation of propolis extracts:

Propolis, which used in this work was collected. then kept in the dark until processing. The procedure was described by Alencar *et al.* (2007) with some modifications. Twenty g of finely ground propolis was added to different solvents (Water and 95% ethanol) to a final volume of 100 ml. The mixtures were protected from light, with moderate shaking during 24 h, at room temperature, and left to rest overnight. These mixtures were filtered through Whatman filter paper No.1. The mixtures were an ethanolic extract of propolis (EEP) and water extract of propolis (WEP) (Sabrien *et al.*, 2016).

4.HPLC separation of flavonoids and phenolic compounds:

HPLC analysis was conducted in the laboratories of Food Science and Technology Institute, Giza, Egypt. An Agilent 1100 HPLC system (Agilent Technologies, Palo Alto, CA, USA) was used to identify and quantify the flavonoids and phenols of propolis (Shuai *et al.*, 2014).

5. Spray application:

Tomato leaves which containing larvae of *L. sativae* were used for the application. Four concentrations were used as well as four replicates for each concentration. Ten larvae for each replicate were used to estimate the mortality line. Different concentrations were sprayed directly on the larvae. The concentrations used were 5000, 10 000, 15 000, and 20 000 ppm. The percentage mortality was recorded after one, three, five, and seven days and the data were corrected relative to control mortality (Abbott, 1925). LC₅₀ values were determined using the probit analysis statistical method of Finney (1971). The equation of Sun (1950) was used to determine LC₅₀ index

Toxicity index for LC₅₀ =

$$\frac{LC_{50} \text{ of the most effective compound}}{LC_{50} \text{ of the least effective compound}} \times 100$$

6. Field experiment:

LC₉₀ for each material was used for this experiment. A field experiment was conducted on tomato plants at Aga, Dakahlia Governorate, Egypt. All cultural practices for tomato plants were followed according to the instruction laid down by the Egyptian Ministry of Agriculture.

A complete randomized block design with three replicates was adopted in this experiment and the treatments are as follows :

1. Control treatment (Tap water)
2. LC₉₀ BT.
3. LC₉₀ propolis water extract .
4. LC₉₀ Propolis ethanolic extract

Regular samples of larvae were collected and examined to record the percent of reduction in larval infestation, according to Hendrson and Tilton formula (1955) after 3, 5 and 10 days of spraying by assigning treatments according to the formula:

$$\text{Reduction (\%mortality)} = [1 - \left(\frac{C_b}{C_a} \times \frac{T_a}{T_b} \right)] \times 100$$

Where:

C_b= number of alive pest individuals in control before treatment.

C_a= number of alive pest individuals in control after treatment.

T_a= number of alive pest individuals after treatment.

T_b= number of alive pest individuals before treatment.

Results and discussion

1. Effect of *Bacillus thuringiensis* and propolis extracts on the mortality rate of *Liriomyza sativae* larvae:

In Table (1), results indicated that the water extract of propolis was the most effective material than the other materials, the ethanolic extract of propolis and BT, against larvae of leafminer *L. sativae* with different concentrations. At the higher concentration, 2000 ppm, the mortality rates were 76.67, 73.33, and 70 ppm for water extract of propolis, ethanolic extract of propolis, and BT, respectively.

2. Efficiency and toxicity index of the tested materials (Water propolis extract, ethanolic propolis extract, and *Bacillus thuringiensis*) against larvae of *Liriomyza sativae*:

However, Table (2) and Figure (1) showed that propolis water extract was the most effective material with LC₅₀ 4628.002 ppm and LC₉₀ 78279.872 ppm. Then BT was effective with LC₅₀ 7110.849 ppm and LC₉₀ 98172.253 ppm. The propolis ethanolic extract was less effective material than the other tested materials with LC₅₀ 9288.848 ppm and LC₉₀ 51399.335 ppm.

Data in Tables (3 and 4) demonstrated reduction in *L. sativae* after 3, 5 and 10 days that treated with propolis water extract, propolis

ethanolis extract and BT. comparing with control.

Table (1): Corrected mortality % of larvae of *Liriomyza sativae* treated with *Bacillus thuringiensis* and propolis extracts under laboratory conditions at 27 ± 2 °C and 65 ± 5 % RH.

Treatments	Conc. (ppm)	Mortality after treatments %				Total Mortality %
		One day	Three days	Five days	Seven days	
Propolis water Extract	5000	3.33	26.67	10	13.33	53.33
	10000	3.33	33.33	20	3.33	60
	15000	6.67	30	16.67	16.67	70
	20000	16.67	43.33	13.33	3.33	76.67
Propolis ethanolic extract	5000	3.33	10	13.33	6.67	33.33
	10000	3.33	13.33	20	3.33	40
	15000	3.33	43.33	10	6.67	63.33
	20000	10	40	20	3.33	73.33
BT	5000	3.33	10	3.33	10	26.67
	10000	10	16.67	3.33	16.67	46.67
	15000	10	20	23.33	10	63.33
	20000	3.33	50	10	6.67	70

Table (2) : Efficiency of propolis extract and *Bacillus thuringiensis* against *Liriomyza sativae*.

Treatments	Conc.	Corrected mortality%	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	Slope± S.D.	Toxicity index LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀ /LC ₅₀
Propolis water extract	5000	53.33	4628.002	78279.872	1.043	100	16.91
	10000	60					
	15000	70					
	20000	76.67					
Propolis ethanolic extract	5000	33.33	9288.848	51399.335	1.725	49.823	5.53
	10000	40					
	15000	63.33					
	20000	73.33					
BT	5000	26.67	7110.849	98172.253	1.124	65.084	13.81
	10000	46.67					
	15000	63.33					
	20000	70					

Figure (1): LC-P line for propolis extracts and *Bacillus thuringiensis* of *Liriomyza sativae*.

Table (3): Effect of assigned treatments on infestation reduction percentage of *Liriomyza sativae* after 3, 5 and 10 days of treatments

Treat.	1 st replicate			2 nd replicate			3 rd replicate			4 th replicate			Treatment efficiency		
	Pest number		Red. %	Pest number		Total Red. %									
	Before	After		Before	After		Before	After		Before	After		Before	After	
After 3 days															
Propolis water extract	11	0	100	11	4	80	11	4	80	11	4	80	11	3	85
Propolis ethanolic extract	11	4	80	11	4	80	11	4	80	11	4	80	11	4	80
BT	4	3	58.75	4	3	58.75	4	3	58.75	4	3	58.75	4	3	58.75
Control	11	20	-----	11	20	-----	11	20	-----	11	20	-----	11	20	-----
After 5 days															
Propolis water extract	6	0	100	6	2	84.7	6	0	100	6	2	84.7	6	0	92.35
Propolis ethanolic extract	11	6	75	11	6	75	11	6	75	11	6	75	11	6	75
BT	4	0	100	4	0	100	4	0	100	4	0	100	4	0	100
Control	11	24	-----	11	24	-----	11	24	-----	11	24	-----	11	24	-----
After 10 days															
Propolis water extract	6	1	93.45	6	1	93.45	6	1	93.45	6	1	93.45	6	1	93.45
Propolis ethanolic extract	11	2	92.86	11	2	92.86	11	2	92.86	11	2	92.86	11	2	92.86
BT	4	2	80.36	4	2	80.36	4	2	80.36	4	2	80.36	4	2	80.36
Control	11	28	-----	11	28	-----	11	28	-----	11	28	-----	11	28	-----

Table (4): Mean of total reduction percentage of *Liriomyza sativae* infestation.

Treatments	Mean reduction of 1 st scan	Mean reduction of 2 nd scan	Mean reduction of 3 rd scan	Mean of total reduction
Propolis water extract	85	92.35	93.45	90.3
Propolis ethanolic extract	80	75	92.86	82.6
BT	58.75	100	80.36	79.7

As described in Sabrien *et al.* (2016), the spores appeared as a dark-staining body. *Bacillus thuringiensis* (4QSTR1) produced cry proteins that appeared as stained crystals. There is a relationship between the insecticide activity and the crystal morphology of *B. thuringiensis* (Maeda *et al.*, 2000). The results indicated that the water extract of propolis was the most effective material than the other materials, ethanolic extract of propolis

and BT, against larvae of leafminer, *L. sativae* with different concentrations. In the higher concentration, 2000 ppm, These results were in agreement with Zewdu and Legessa (2016) Evaluate the insecticidal effect of propolis against larvae of lesser wax moth *Achroia grisell* concluded that the extract of propolis at higher concentrations is a powerful contact toxicant against young wax moth larvae. High-performance liquid chromatography equipped with a

diode array detector was used to separate flavonoids and phenolic compounds from samples with varied matrixes. It was used to identify and quantify the flavonoids and phenolic compounds in propolis. These results were in agreement with Sabrien *et al.* (2016) who proved that The resultant appeared that chlorogenic was the most identified phenolic compound (120.62 µg/100 g dry weight) and the acacetin was the major identified flavonoid component in propolis (647.53 µg/100 g dry weights) (Shuai *et al.*, 2014). These results can state that propolis has general biological activities as insecticides activity These results were in agreement with Sabrien *et al.* (2016) who proved that water extract of propolis was the most effective material against *Tetranychus urticae*. Also, Talha *et al.* (2019) proved that microbial control using BT was effective and safe in controlling most pests. Sabrien *et al.*, 2016 , also, proved effectiveness of water propolis extract against pests.

In the present investigation, bioinsecticidal effect of *B. thuringiensis* cry toxin, propolis extracts against larvae of *L. sativae* were studied. The results revealed that they would be suitable for developing a biological process and can be used successfully in IPM program to control leafminer *L. sativae* .

References

- Abbott, W.S. (1925):** A method of computing the effectiveness of an insecticide. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 18 : 265-267.
- Abou-Yousef, H. M.; Farghaly, F.S. and Torkey, H.M. (2010):** Insecticidal activity of some plant extracts against some sap-sucking insects under laboratory conditions. *World Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 6(4): 434- 439.
- Alencar, S.M.; Oldoni, T.L.C.; Castro, M.L.; Cabral, I.S.R.; Costa-Neto, C.M.; Cury, J.A.; Rosalen, P.L. and Ikegaki, M. (2007):** Chemical composition and biological activity of a new type of Brazilian propolis: red propolis. *J Ethnopharmacol*, 113:278–283.
- Aronson, A.I.; Beckman, W. and Dunn, P. (1986):** *Bacillus thuringiensis* and related insect pathogens. *Microbiological Reviews*, 50: 1–24.
- Castaldo S. and Capasso, F. (2002):** Propolis, an old remedy used in modern medicine. *Fitoterapia*, 73(1): 367-373.
- Feitelson, J.S.; Payne, J. and Kim, L. (2002):** *Bacillus thuringiensis*: insects and beyond. *Biotechnology*, 10: 271–275.
- Finney, D.J. (1971):** *Probit Analysis*. Cambridge University Press, London, U.K., pp. 333.
- Henderson C.F. and Tilton, E.W. (1955).** Tests with acaricides against the brown wheat mite. *J.Econ. Ent.*,38:157.
- Höfte, H. and Whiteley, H.R. (1989):** Insecticidal crystal proteins of *Bacillus thuringiensis*. *Microbiological Reviews*, 53: 242–255.
- Johnson M.W.; Welter, S.C.; Toscano, N.C.; Ting, I.P. and Trumble, J.T. (1983):** Reduction of tomato leaflet photosynthesis rates by mining activity of *Liriomyza sativae* (Diptera: Agromyzidae). *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 76: 1061– 1063.
- Karamanlidou, G.; Lambropoulos, A.F. ; Koliais, S.I. ; Manousis, T. and Ellar, D. (1991):** Toxicity of *Bacillus*

- thuringensis* to laboratory populations of the olive fruit fly (*Dacus oleae*). Applied and Environmental Microbiology, 57: 2277-2282.
- Maeda, M.; Mizuki, E.; Nakamura, Y.; Hatano, T. and Ohba, M. (2000):** Recovery of *Bacillus thuringiensis* from marine sediments of Japan. Current Microbiology, 40: 413-422.
- Madahi, K. and Sahragard, A. (2012):** Comparative life table of *Aphis pomi* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) on two host plants *Malus pumila* L. and *Chaenomeles japonica* under laboratory conditions. Journal of Crop Protection, 1(4): 321-330.
- Matteoni, J.A. and Broadbent, A.B. (1988):** Wounds caused by *Liriomyza trifolii* (Diptera: Agromyzidae) as sites for infection of chrysanthemum by *Pseudomonas cichorii*. Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology, 10: 47– 52.
- Sabrien, O. A. ; Elsayed, I. A.; Marouf, E. A. and Dawood, D. H. (2016):** Effects of *Bacillus thuringiensis* cry toxin, propolis extracts and silver nanoparticles synthesized by soil fungus (*Fusarium oxysporum*) against two species of *Tetranychus* spp. (Acari:Tetranychidae). Journal of Agricultural Chemistry and Biotechnology Mans. Univ., 7(12): 283- 289.
- Parrella, M.P. (1987):** Biology of *Liriomyza*. Annual Review of Entomology, 32:201– 224.
- Polston J. E. and Anderson, P. K. (1999):** Surgimiento y distribución de Gemini virus transmitido spormoscablanca en tomate en el Hemisferio Occidental. Manejo Integrado de Plagas, 53:24-42.
- Sambrook, J.; Fritsch, E.F. and Maniatis, T. (1989):** Molecular cloning: a laboratory manual, vol. 3. Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory Press, Cold Spring Harbor, N.Y.
- Shehu, A.; Ismail, S.; Rohin, M. A. K. ; Harun, A. ; Aziz, A. A. and Haque, M. (2016):** Antifungal properties of Malaysian Tualang honey and stingless bee propolis against *Candida albicans* and *Cryptococcus neoformans*. Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Science, 6(2): 44–50.
- Shuai, H.; Cui-Ping, Z.; Kai, W.; George, Q. L. and Fu-Liang, H. (2014):** Recent Advances in the Chemical Composition of Propolis. Molecules, 19:19610-19632.
- Spencer K.A. (1990):** Host Specialization in the World *Agromyzidae* (Diptera). Kluwer Academic Publishers, Dordrecht, The Netherlands.
- Sun, Y. P. (1950):** Toxicity index - An Improved method of comparing the relative toxicity of insecticides. Journal of Economic Entomology, 43 (1): 45-53.
- Talha, N.; Sehroon, K. and Dewen, Q. (2019):** Biological control of insect pest. Pests Control and Acarology, 10: 57- 67.
- Winkler, I.S.; Scheffer, S. J. and Mitter, C. (2009):** Molecular phylogeny and systematics of leaf-mining flies (Diptera: Agromyzidae): delimitation of *Phytomyza* Fallén sensu lato and included species groups, with new insights on morphological and host-use evolution. Systematic Entomology, 34:260– 292.

Zewdu, A. and Gemechis, L. (20 16):
Insecticidal action of honeybees
propolis extract against larvae
of lesser wax moth. Agriculture

and Biology Journal of North
Amrica, 7 : 302-306.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Influence of mixing ammonium acetate and di-ammonium phosphate on their attraction to the peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* (Diptera: Tephritidae) under field conditions

Nabil, M. Ghanim; Reda, A. El-Sharkawy and Wafaa, M.M. El-Baradeey

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 15 /4/2021

Accepted: 20/6 /2021

Keywords

Fruit fly, *Bactrocera zonata*, mixtures, ammonium compound and mandarin orchard.

Abstract:

Peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae) is one of the most destructive key pests infesting fruit orchards. Ammonium acetate and di-ammonium phosphate were evaluated as attractants for the peach fruit fly *B. zonata* in a mandarin orchard (Using concentrations of 1, 2 and 3% of each ammonium compound lonely or mixed between them interchangeably). The highest attractive treatments to *B. zonata* were ammonium acetate 3% mixed with di-ammonium phosphate 3 or 1%, while; the lowest attractive treatments to this pest were ammonium acetate 3% and di-ammonium phosphate 1% (With no mixing). On the other hand, all of the tested treatments attracted females of *B. zonata* obviously more than males. The concentration of ammonium acetate showed a positive effect on the attraction of *B. zonata*. Females and males of *B. zonata* exhibited positive responses to the increase of the pH-level of the tested treatments. As conclusion, the present results may be useful in applying integrated pest management control programs by using mixtures of ammonium acetate and di-ammonium phosphate (Ammonium acetate 3% mixed with di- ammonium phosphate 3 or 1%) because of its good attraction for *B. zonata* adults.

Introduction

Peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae) is one of the most dominant and destructive key pests in of fruit orchards in different agro-ecosystem in Egypt (Ghanim, 2009 and Dras *et al.*, 2016). It is a polyphagous species attacking a wide range of fruits that differ in their ripening time stage all over the year (White and Elson-Harris, 1992 and Ghanim, 2013). According to Kaspi *et al.* (2000), Yuval *et al.* (2007), Hemeida *et al.* (2017), El-Metwally (2017) and Ghanim and El-Metwally (2019) a strong influence on the physiology and behavior of tephritid

flies are correlated with food sources which are rich in nitrogen. Epsky *et al.* (2014) and Pinero *et al.* (2015) mentioned that the effectiveness of protein bait is behaviorally relying on the fact that immature females need a protein meal to reach sexual maturity and for the development of eggs to maturity. So, food sources which are rich in nitrogen act as food attractants. Ghanim *et al.* (2014), Bayoumy and El-Metwally (2017), Hemeida *et al.* (2017) and Ghanim and El-Metwally (2019) added that ammonia is associated with protein-rich foods and has long been known to attract fruit flies.

Ammonium compounds are considered to be from the most important fruit fly attractants. However, Moore (1969), Moustafa and Ghanim (2008), Abd El-Kareim *et al.* (2008), Ghanim *et al.* (2014) and El-Abbassi *et al.* (2017) used various formulations of synthetic ammonium compounds as baits for fruit flies. These compounds, including ammonium acetate di-ammonium phosphate, tri-ammonium phosphate, ammonium carbonate and ammonium chloride. Mazor *et al.* (1987) used dilutions of a pure ammonia solution to obtain a direct correlation between the capture of *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) females and concentration of ammonia. Also, the relationship between ammonia release rate and captured *C. capitata* and *Anastrepha suspensa* (Loew) females were reported by Heath *et al.* (1994) and Epsky *et al.* (1993).

According to Abd El-Kareim *et al.* (2008), Ghanim *et al.* (2014), Ghanim (2018) and El-Metwally (2017); attractants of fruit flies are used for two objectives: the first one to detect and monitor populations of fruit flies; while, the second one is for control of fruit flies. So, the present study aimed to mix the solutions of ammonium acetate and di-ammonium phosphate for detecting a new treatment which may be more attractive to *B. zonata* under field conditions.

Materials and methods

The commercial products of ammonium acetate (Aa) and di-ammonium phosphate (Da) were obtained from El-Naser for Drugs and Chemicals Company. These two ammonium compounds were evaluated as olfactory attractants for the peach fruit fly, *B. zonata* under field conditions. The concentrations of 1, 2 and 3% (As w: v of ammonium compound: water) of each ammonium compound were investigated lonely and mixed with the concentrations of the

other ammonium compound (As interchangeably mixing the concentrations of ammonium acetate and di-ammonium phosphate).

An experiment was carried out in a mandarin orchard on the Experimental Farm of the Faculty of Agriculture, Mansoura University at Mansoura district, Dakahlia Governorate. The total area of the selected orchard was about six feddans (One feddan equal 4200 m²). The experiment was carried out during the period from the 9th of till the 25th of September 2020.

By using the modified Nadel traps (Described by Hanafy *et al.*, 2001), 300 ml of each treatment was put in a trap. Each treatment was replicated four times. All prepared traps were distributed in a completely randomized design in the orchard. The distance between every two successive hanged traps was not less than 20 meters to avoid interference among traps loaded with different treatments. The traps were hanged at about 1.5 meters in a shady site of the trees.

Along the period of study, the traps were inspected every 4 days (as interval period) with no renewal of solutions. Captured females and males of *B. zonata* were counted and recorded as FTD (Number of flies per trap per day). Also, relative attraction (RA) was calculated as a contribution percentage of each treatment from the total attracted flies.

Data were analyzed by using one-way ANOVA followed by least significant difference (LSD) at probability level of 0.05. Regression analysis was also performed. All analyses were performed using CoHort Software (2004).

Results and discussion

Data in Table (1) showed that peach fruit fly, *B. zonata* adults exhibited variance preferences to the tested ammonium compounds.

However, the highest attractive treatment to *B. zonata* after 4 days was that of ammonium acetate 3% mixed with di-ammonium phosphate 2% (FTD= 0.81). After 8 days, ammonium acetate 3% mixed with di-ammonium phosphate 3% was the most effective treatment in attracting *B. zonata*. The mixture of ammonium acetate and di-ammonium phosphate as 3% of each

exhibited the highest attraction to this pest after 12 days. While, ammonium acetate 3% mixed with di-ammonium phosphate 2% was the highest attractant to *B. zonata* after 16 days. On the other hand, all of the tested treatments attracted females of *B. zonata* obviously more than males.

Table (1): Attracted *Bactrocera zonata* adults to different preparations of ammonium acetate (Aa) and di-ammonium phosphate (Da) under field conditions.

Treatment	FTD after											
	4 days			8 days			12 days			16 days		
	♀	♂	♀+♂	♀	♂	♀+♂	♀	♂	♀+♂	♀	♂	♀+♂
Aa1	0.19	0.00	0.19	0.69	0.00	0.69	0.44	0.00	0.44	0.44	0.00	0.44
Aa2	0.25	0.00	0.25	0.44	0.00	0.44	0.25	0.06	0.31	0.88	0.06	0.94
Aa3	0.19	0.00	0.19	0.19	0.00	0.19	0.06	0.00	0.06	0.44	0.00	0.44
Da1	0.125	0.00	0.125	0.44	0.00	0.44	0.19	0.00	0.19	0.31	0.00	0.31
Da2	0.31	0.00	0.31	0.50	0.00	0.50	0.56	0.00	0.56	0.44	0.125	0.56
Da3	0.25	0.00	0.25	0.31	0.00	0.31	0.38	0.00	0.38	0.44	0.06	0.50
Aa1+Da1	0.25	0.00	0.25	0.44	0.00	0.44	0.69	0.00	0.69	0.69	0.06	0.75
Aa1+Da2	0.25	0.00	0.25	0.31	0.00	0.31	0.44	0.19	0.63	0.56	0.00	0.56
Aa3+Da3	0.19	0.00	0.19	0.125	0.00	0.125	0.56	0.00	0.56	0.56	0.19	0.75
Aa2+Da1	0.25	0.00	0.25	0.50	0.00	0.50	0.44	0.00	0.44	1.25	0.25	1.50
Aa2+Da2	0.56	0.00	0.56	0.56	0.00	0.56	0.88	0.00	0.88	0.69	0.31	1.00
Aa2+Da3	0.125	0.00	0.125	0.44	0.06	0.50	0.44	0.00	0.44	0.50	0.00	0.44
Aa3+Da1	0.75	0.00	0.75	0.50	0.00	0.50	0.50	0.00	0.50	1.31	0.38	1.69
Aa3+Da2	0.81	0.00	0.81	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.44	0.06	0.50	0.50	0.06	0.56
Aa3+Da3	0.63	0.00	0.63	0.94	0.00	0.94	1.38	0.00	1.38	1.00	0.19	1.19
LSD	0.333	0.00	0.333	0.351	0.045	0.348	0.355	0.005	0.356	0.328	0.207	0.304

Note: 1,2,3 in all treatments mean concentrations of 1%, 2%, 3% respectively

Data illustrated in Figure (1) showed that the concentration of 2% was the most attractive treatment of ammonium acetate alone to *B. zonata* (Mean FTD was 0.61). While, the concentration of 2% was the highest of di-ammonium phosphate alone (Mean FTD was 0.44). When the concentrations of ammonium acetate

and di-ammonium phosphate were mixed interchangeably, ammonium acetate 3% mixed with di-ammonium phosphate 3% exhibited the highest attractive treatment to *B. zonata* (Mean FTD was 1.03) followed by the mixture of ammonium acetate 3% and di-ammonium phosphate 1% (Mean FTD was 0.86).

Figure (1): Mean numbers of attracted *Bactrocera zonata* (As females + males) to different concentrations of ammonium acetate (Aa) and di-ammonium phosphate (Da) all over 16 days under field conditions (Note: 1,2,3 in all treatments mean concentrations of 1%, 2%, 3% respectively).

To evaluate the effect of concentration of ammonium compounds on the attractiveness of the tested compounds (As lures for *B. zonata* adults), regression analysis has been done between the relative attraction and concentrations of each ammonium compound (Figures 2 and 3).

As shown as in Figure (2), the concentrations of ammonium acetate showed positive effects on attracting *B. zonata* when it was alone or mixed with di-ammonium phosphate 1, 2 or 3%. However, each increase of ammonium acetate concentration by 1%; the

attracted *B. zonata* (As relative attraction) increased by 0.003, 0.015, 0.017 and 0.038% all over 16 days when ammonium acetate was alone or mixed with di-ammonium phosphate 1, 2 and 3% respectively. On another hand, the highest effect of ammonium acetate concentration was recorded when it was mixed with di-ammonium phosphate 1%; where, the calculated R²-value was 0.922. On the contrary, the lowest effect of ammonium acetate concentration was recorded when it was not mixed; where calculated R²-value was 0.030 (Figure 2).

Figure (2): The relationship between concentration (C) of ammonium acetate (Alone or mixed with di-ammonium phosphate) and its relative attraction (RA) to *Bactrocera zonata* under field conditions (Note: 1,2,3 in all treatments mean concentrations of 1%, 2%, 3% respectively).

Data illustrated in Figure (3) showed that the concentration of di-ammonium phosphate showed positive effects on attracting *B. zonata* when it was alone or mixed with ammonium acetate 3%. However, each increased of di-ammonium phosphate concentration by 1%; the relative attraction increased by 0.005 and 0.010%, respectively all over the 16 days. In contrary, di-ammonium phosphate showed a

negative effect when it mixed with ammonium acetate 1 and 2% (b-regression = -0.012 and -0.017). As it was previously recorded in the case of ammonium acetate, the highest effect of di-ammonium phosphate concentration was recorded when it was mixed with ammonium acetate 1% ($R^2 = 0.862$); while, the lowest was recorded when it was not mixed ($R^2 = 0.298$) (Figure 3).

Figure (3): The relationship between concentration (C) of di-ammonium phosphate (Aone or mixed with ammonium acetate) and its relative attraction (RA) to *Bactrocera zonata* under field conditions (Note: 1,2,3 in all treatments mean concentrations of 1%, 2%, 3% respectively).

As shown in Table (2), the elapsed time (T) showed its highest effect on the mixture of ammonium acetate 3% + di-ammonium phosphate 2%; where, the calculated R^2 -value was 0.952 ($RA = 0.199 - 0.010 T$) followed by the mixture of ammonium acetate 3% + di-ammonium phosphate 1% ($R^2 = 0.773$ and $RA = 0.157 - 0.008 T$), di-ammonium phosphate 2% alone ($R^2 = 0.680$ and $RA = 0.069 - 0.001 T$) and

the mixture of ammonium acetate 2% + di-ammonium phosphate 1% ($R^2 = 0.667$ and $RA = 0.017 + 0.006 T$). In contrast, the elapsed time exhibited its lowest effect on the mixture of ammonium acetate 3% + di-ammonium phosphate 3%, ammonium acetate alone 3 and 1%; where, the calculated R^2 - values were 0.002, 0.015, 0.024 , respectively (Table 2).

Table (2): Effect of passed time (T) on the relative attraction (RA) of ammonium acetate, di-ammonium phosphate and the mixtures between them towards *Bactrocera zonata* under field conditions.

Treatment	Relationship	R ²
Aa1%	$RA = 0.062 + 0.000 T$	0.024
Aa2%	$RA = 0.039 + 0.001 T$	0.299
Aa3%	$RA = 0.030 - 0.0003 T$	0.015
Da1%	$RA = 0.039 + 0.000 T$	0.041
Da2%	$RA = 0.069 - 0.001 T$	0.680
Da3%	$RA = 0.048 - 0.0002 T$	0.083
Aa1% + Da1%	$RA = 0.065 + 0.001 T$	0.052
Aa2% + Da1%	$RA = 0.017 + 0.006 T$	0.667
Aa3% + Da1%	$RA = 0.157 - 0.008 T$	0.773
Aa1% + Da2%	$RA = 0.045 + 0.001 T$	0.080
Aa2% + Da2%	$RA = 0.103 - 0.0008 T$	0.043
Aa3% + Da2%	$RA = 0.199 - 0.010 T$	0.952
Aa1% + Da3%	$RA = 0.012 + 0.004 T$	0.486
Aa2% + Da3%	$RA = 0.035 + 0.001 T$	0.124
Aa3% + Da3%	$RA = 0.135 - 0.0003 T$	0.002

Note: 1,2,3 in all treatments mean concentrations of 1%, 2%, 3% respectively

Data represented in Figure (4) showed that females and males of *B. zonata* exhibited positive responses to the increase of the pH- level of the tested treatments. However, the relative

attraction (RA) of females, males and total of them increased by 0.017, 0.030 and 0.030%, respectively by increasing one degree of pH- level.

Figure (4): Effect of pH-level of the tested compounds on the attracted *Bactrocera zonata* (Females, males and total adults) under field conditions (Note: 1,2,3 in all treatments mean concentrations of 1%, 2%, 3%, respectively).

Peach fruit fly *B. zonata* is one of the most destructive key pests infesting fruit orchards in different agro-ecosystems. Like other tephritid flies, it is physiologically and behaviorally influenced by food sources which are rich in nitrogen. Ammonia is associated with protein-rich foods and has long been known to attract fruit flies. According to the obtained data, *B. zonata* adults exhibited different preferability to the tested ammonium compounds. Where, the highest attractive treatment to *B. zonata* all over 16 days was that of ammonium acetate 3% mixed with di- ammonium phosphate 3%, followed by ammonium acetate 3% mixed with di- ammonium phosphate 1%. On another hand, the lowest attractive treatments to this pest were ammonium acetate 3% and di- ammonium phosphate 1% (which were not mixed with other treatments). The present results are in agreement with that of El-Abbassi *et al.* (2017); they mentioned that mixing of ammonium acetate and di-ammonium phosphate was more attractive to the tephritid, *C.*

capitata adults than the use of each compound lonely. Also, Abd El-Kareim *et al.* (2008), Moustafa and Ghanim (2008), Ghanim *et al.* (2014), Hemeida *et al.* (2017) and Ghanim *et al.* (2018) stated that ammonium compounds could be used in monitoring populations of fruit flies or in mass trapping as a part of integrated control of fruit flies.

The present study explained that the mixture of ammonium acetate and di- ammonium phosphate as 3% of each exhibited the highest attraction to this pest after 12 days; while, most of the rest tested treatments exhibited its highest attraction to *B. zonata* after 16 days. Approximately the same results were obtained by Moustafa and Ghanim (2008), Abd El-Kareim *et al.* (2008) and Ghanim *et al.* (2014) recorded that the highest attraction of ammonium acetate was recorded after 12-15 days; while, the highest attraction of di- ammonium phosphate was recorded after 3–6 days of hanging traps. According to El-Abbassi *et al.* (2017), mixtures of ammonium acetate and di-

ammonium phosphate exhibited its attraction to *C. capitata* until 8 weeks; while, when these compounds were used lonely, the highest attraction was recorded during the first 4 weeks. The differences between the present study and others may be attributed to the variation of the tested form of treatments, fruit fly species, weather factors and/ or host plants.

On the other hand, the present results showed that the efficiency of all treatments containing ammonium acetate 1% increased in attracting *B. zonata* adults by the elapsed time. With respect to the other treatments, it showed differences in their attractiveness toward *B. zonata* with the elapsed time. Also, the results of Abd El-Kareim *et al.* (2008) and Moustafa and Ghanim (2008) came in the line of the present one. However, they reported that the efficiency of ammonium acetate 1% in attracting *B. zonata* and *C. capitata* increased by the elapsed time. In contrary, Ghanim *et al.* (2014) reported that the efficiency of all concentration of ammonium acetate as lures for the tephritid, *Carpomya incompleta* in Saudi Arabia decreased by the elapsed time. The variation between these results and the present may be attributed to the variation of fruit fly species and/or climatic factors.

Concentrations of ammonium acetate and di-ammonium phosphate (lonely or mixed together) significantly attracted females more than males of *B. zonata*. Similar results were obtained by Delrio and Orto (1989), Hanafy *et al.* (2001), Saafan (2005), Abd El-Kareim *et al.* (2008), Moustafa and Ghanim (2008) and Hemeida *et al.* (2017); they mentioned that ammonium compounds attracted females of *B. zonata* and *C. capitata* than males. Also, Ghanim *et al.* (2014) found that ammonium compounds significantly attracted more females of *Carpomya incompleta* (Beeker) than males. Because of the

great need for protein by females for egg development; it would be reflected in increased numbers of antennal receptor neurons sensitive to volatile by products of protein degradation, and consequently, in an increased physiological response to ammonia (Arn *et al.*, 1975; Mayer *et al.*, 1987 and Landolt and Davis-Hernandez, 1993).

The concentration of ammonium acetate showed a positive effect on the attraction of *B. zonata* when it was used alone or mixed with di-ammonium phosphate 1, 2 and 3%. These findings are in agreement with the studies of Abd El-Kareim *et al.* (2008), Moustafa and Ghanim (2008), Ghanim *et al.* (2014) and Ghanim and El-Metwally (2019). They reported that attraction of fruit flies showed positive response to the increase of ammonium acetate concentration when it was used lonely or mixed with other attractants. Also, the present results revealed that concentration of di-ammonium phosphate (alone or mixed with ammonium acetate 3%) showed a positive effect on the attraction of *B. zonata*; on contrary, di-ammonium phosphate mixed with ammonium acetate 1 or 2% exhibited adverse effect on the attraction of this pest. These findings are in the same trend of Moustafa and Ghanim (2008) and El-Abbassi *et al.* (2017); they reported that *C. capitata* adults exhibited a negative response to the increase of di-ammonium phosphate concentration.

The obtained data revealed that there was a positive response of attracting *B. zonata* flies (Females and males) to the increase of the pH-level. However, the highest number of attracted flies was recorded pH-level of 8.14. These results came in the same line with those of El-Metwally (2017), Ghanim (2018) and Ghanim and El-Metwally (2019); they reported that attraction of *B. zonata* and *C. capitata* adults is positively correlated with pH-

level of the attraction solutions. The same authors added that the highest attraction of *B. zonata* and *C. capitata* were occurring between 6.32 and 8.29 of pH- level.

From the previously mentioned of view, it could be concluded that the present results may be useful in applying integrated pest management control programs by using mixtures of ammonium acetate and di- ammonium phosphate (Ammonium acetate 3% mixed with di- ammonium phosphate 3 or 1%) because of its good attraction for *B. zonata* adults.

References

- Abd El-Kareim, A.I.; Shanab, L.M. ; El-Naggar, M.E. and Ghanim, N.M. (2008):** Response of peach fruit fly, *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae) to some ammonium compounds as olfactory stimulants. J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 33 (12): 8965-8973.
- Arn, H.; Stadler, E. and Raischer, S. (1975):** The electroantennographic detector- a selective and sensitive tool in the gas chromatographic analysis of insect pheromones. Z. Naturforsch., 30: 722-725.
- Bayoumy, M. H. and El-Metwally, M. M. (2017):** Daily flight activity rhythms of the peach and Mediterranean fruit flies using sexual and olfactory attractants. Acta Phytopathol. et Entomol. Hung., 52:227–244.
- CoHort Software (2004):** CoStat. www.cohort.com Monterey, California, USA.
- Delrio, G. and Orto, S. (1989):** Attraction of *Ceratitidis capitata* (Wied.) to sex pheromones, trimedlure, ammonium and protein bait traps. J. App. Ent., 77 (12): 69-73.
- Dras, K.A.; Tabikha, R.M.; El-Aw, M.A.; El-Gendy, I.R. and Darwish, H.F. (2016):** Population activity of peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Diptera: Tephritidae) at fruits orchards in Kafer El-Shikh Governorate, Egypt. Arthropods, 5(1): 28-43.
- El-Abbassi, T.S.; Makkar, A.W. ; El-Metwally, M.M. and Ghanim, N.M. (2017):** Field evaluation of some ammonium compounds when used at different combination ratios on attracting med fly adults, *Ceratitidis capitata* (Wied.) in citrus orchards. Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt, 43: 131-145.
- El-Metwally, M.M. (2017):** Enhancing the attraction efficiency of GF-120 for the Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitidis capitata* (Wied.) by adding some ammonium compounds. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 8 (11): 541 –547.
- Epsky, N. D.; Kendra, P. E. and Schnell, E. Q. (2014):** History and development of food-based attractants. In: T. Shelly, N. Epsky, E. B.
- Epsky, N.D.; Heath, R.R. ; Sivinski, J.M. ; Calkins, C.O. ; Baranowski, R.M. and Fritz, A.H. (1993):** Evaluation of protein bait formulations for the Caribbean fruit fly (Diptera: Tephritidae). Fla. Entomol., 76: 627-635.
- Ghanim, N.M. (2009):** Studies on the peach fruit fly, *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) (Tephritidae : Diptera). Ph. D. Theses, Fac. Agric., Mansoura University.
- Ghanim, N.M. (2013):** Influence of methyl eugenol diluted with paraffin oil on male annihilation technique of peach fruit fly, *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders)

- (Diptera: Tephritidae). Entomol. Ornithol. Herpetol., 2:3 : doi.org/10.4172/2161-0983.1000114.
- Ghanim, N.M. (2018):** Improving the efficiency of GF-120 baits in attracting *Bactrocera zonata* by adding ammonium compounds with particular emphasis on pH level. International Journal of entomology, 1(1): 1-16.
- Ghanim, N.M. and El-Metwally, M.M. (2019):** Relationship between hydrogenionic potential (pH) of protein-based baits and attraction of the Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitidis capitata* (Wiedemann). Acta Phytopathol. Entomol. Hungarica, 54 (1): 99–112.
- Ghanim, N.M.; Abdel-Baky, N.F.; Al-Doghairi, M.A. and Fouly, A.H. (2014):** Evaluation of some ammonium compounds as olfactory stimulants for zizyphus fruit fly *Carpomya incomplete* (Diptera: Tephritidae) in christ's thorn orchards at Qassim, Saudi Arabia. J. Plant Prot. and Path., Mansoura Univ., 5 (4): 367 - 377.
- Ghanim, N.M.; Fathy, D.M. and Ramadan, M.M. (2018):** Occurrence of Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitidis capitata*, (Tephritidae, Diptera) in mango orchard and its response to certain ecological factors and different attractants. Middle East J. Appl. Sci., 8(3): 913-921.
- Hanafy, A.H.; Awad, A.I. and Abo-Sheasha, M. (2001):** Field evaluation of different compounds for attracting adults of peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) and Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitidis capitata* (Wied.) in guava orchards. J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 26 (7):4537-4546.
- Heath, R.R.; Epsky, N.D.; Bloem, S.; Bloem, K. ; Acajabon, F. ; Guzman, A. and Chambers, D. (1994):** pH effect on the attractiveness of a corn hydrolysate to the Mediterranean fruit fly and several *Anastrepha* species (Diptera: Tephritidae). J. Econ. Entomol., 87: 1008-1013.
- Hemeida, I.A.; Ghanim, N.M.; Mosallam, A.M.Z. ; EL-Shabrawy, H.A. and Metwaa, B.M. (2017):** Enhancement of some protein-based baits for attracting *Bactrocera zonata* (Diptera: Tephritidae) by adding ammonium compounds. Egypt. Acad. J. Biol. Sci., 10(6): 153–166.
- Kaspi, R.; Taylor, P. W. and Yuval, B. (2000):** Diet and size influence sexual advertisement and copulatory success of males in Mediterranean fruit fly leks. Ecol. Entomol., 25: 279–284.
- Landolt, P.J. and Davis-Hernandez, K. M. (1993):** Temporal patterns of feeding by Caribbean fruit flies (Diptera: Tephritidae) on sucrose and hydrolyzed yeast. Ann. Entomol. Soc. Am., 86: 749-755.
- Mayer, M.S.; Mankin, R.W. and Grant, A.J. (1987):** Quantitative comparison of behavioral and neurophysiological responses of insects to odorants: inferences about central nervous system processes. J. Chem. Ecol., 13: 509-531.
- Mazor, M.; Gothilf, S. and Galun, R. (1987):** The role of ammonia in the attraction of females of the Mediterranean fruit fly to

- protein hydrolyzate baits. Entomol. Exp. Appl., 43: 25-29.
- Moore, R.C. (1969):** Attractiveness of baited and unbaited lures to apple maggot and beneficial flies. J. Econ. Entomol., 62: 1076-1078.
- Moustafa, S.A. and Ghanim, N.M. (2008):** Some ammonium compounds as olfactory stimulants for Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitis capitata* Wiedemann (Diptera: Tephritidae). J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 33 (12): 8909-8918.
- Pinero, J. C.; Souder, S. K.; Smith, T. R.; Fox, A. J. and Vargas, R. I. (2015):** Ammonium acetate enhances the attractiveness of a variety of protein-based baits to female *Ceratitis capitata* (Diptera: Tephritidae). J. Econ. Entomol., 108: 694–700.
- Saafan, M. H. (2005):** Field evaluation of some attractants for attracting the adults of Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitis capitata* (Wiedemann) and peach fruit fly, *Bactrocera zonata* (Saunders) in citrus orchards. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 83 (3): 1141-1156.
- White, I.M. and Elson-Harris, M.M. (1992):** Fruit Flies of Economic Significance: Their Identification and Bionomics. CAB International, London, UK.
- Yuval, B.; Maor, M.; Levy, K.; Kaspi, R.; Taylor, P. W. and Shelly, T. E. (2007):** Breakfast of champions or kiss of death? Survival and sexual performance of protein fed, sterile Mediterranean fruit flies. Fl. Entomol., 90: 115–122.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Antifeedant effects of two plant extracts of (*Bidens pilosa* and *Rumex dentatus*) and neem oil on certain stored grains insects

Samy, S. El-badawy¹; Sahar, Y. Abdel-Aziz²; Ahmed, A. Elhefny¹ ; Ahmed, Abdel-Monem Taha³ and Elham, A. Khalifa²

¹Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Centre, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

²Department of Economic Entomology and Pesticides, Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt.

³Central Laboratory of Organic Agriculture, Agricultural Research Centre, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 19 /4/2021

Accepted: 24/ 6 /2021

Keywords

Antifeedant activity, plant extracts, *Bidens pilosa* , *Rumex dentatus* and stored grain pests.

Abstract:

The present study was carried out to evaluate the antifeedant activities of methanolic extracts of two weedy plants leaves (*Bidens pilosa* L. and *Rumex dentatus* L.) at three different concentrations 3, 5 and 7% against three stored grain pests, saw-toothed grain beetle *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* (L.) (Coleoptera:Silvanidae), rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) and bean weevil *Acanthoscelides obtectus* (Say) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) compared to neem oil as a commercial product under the laboratory conditions. The obtained results revealed that all of the tested botanicals had antifeedant effects against the three tested stored grain pests. Comparison between of the two plant extracts and neem oil effects on the three tested pests showed that *B. pilosa* extract causing the highest feeding deterrence indices (FDI) against *A. obtectus* at the three tested concentrations. While, the highest antifeedant effect was recorded with *R. dentatus* followed by neem oil, then *B. pilosa* extract against *O. surinamensis* at the same concentrations, but in case of both *S. oryzae* extracts and neem oil have the same antifeedant activity. The three botanical tested showed high antifeedant action and was directly proportional to the tested concentrations. Additionally, the methanol extract of *R. dentatus* showed strong inhibition on adult emergence of the three tested pests at the tested concentrations. In conclusion, the methanol extract of *R. dentatus* was the strongest antifeedant against *O. surinamensis* while, *B. pilosa* the most effective against *A. obtectus*. Finally, these results indicated that methanol extracts of *B. pilosa* and *R. dentatus* achieved significantly antifeedant activities against the three tested pests and can be incorporated used in IPM programs as grain protectants in the future.

Introduction

The groups of insect species associated with postharvest products are commonly called stored product pests. These insects can cause losses of

9-10 % in developing countries, while, the losses can be more than 50 % in undeveloping countries (Pimentel, 1991). Among these pests, three important store product pests, rice

weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) which is one of the most insect pests which cause heavy losses of cereal grains both quantitatively and qualitatively throughout the world (Saljoqi *et al.*, 2006), the saw-toothed grain beetle, *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* (L.) (Coleoptera:Silvanidae), is an important and widespread pest of stored grain and cereal products and it is usually found as a secondary pest on grain damaged by other insects (Hashem *et al.*, 2012) and the bean weevil, *Acanthoscelides obtectus* (Say) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae) is a bruchid species that attacks seeds of various leguminous crops (Naroz *et al.*, 2019). Although, using of chemical pesticides and fumigants against stored product pests are effective, but repeated use led to many problems, including insect resistance, disrupted natural biological control systems, toxic residues in food grains, undesirable effects on no target organisms and environmental pollution. For this reason, effective, safe and eco-friendly alternatives to protect stored grain products and minimizing chemical pesticide use are necessary. In recent years, there is a growing interest in the use of plant extracts as alternatives to chemical pesticides in Integrated Pest Management (IPM) (Golob *et al.*, 1999) and in this regard, recently, the use of plant-derived insect feeding inhibitors (Antifeedants) for crop protection has received increased emphasis (Khani *et al.*, 2013; Brari and Kumar, 2019 and Karakas, 2020). The term antifeedant is defined by Isman (2002) as “a peripherally mediated behavior-modifying substance that deters through a direct action on taste organs in insects and resulting in feeding deterrence”. Pesticides based on plant extracts have demonstrated antifeedant properties against a range of stored product pests, such as *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst)

(Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) (Suthisut *et al.*, 2011), *Callosobruchus maculatus* (F.) (Coleoptera: Bruchidae) (Hussain *et al.*, 2008), *Sitophilus zeamais* Motschulsky (Coleoptera: Curculionidae) (Suthisut *et al.*, 2011 and Liu *et al.*, 2012) *S. oryzae* (Rani *et al.*, 2011 and Brari and Kumar, 2019), *Sitophilus granarius* Linnaeus (Coleoptera Curculionidae) (Ignatowicz and Wesolowska, 1994), *Rhyzopertha dominica* Fabricius (Coleoptera. : Bostrichidae) (Kłys', 2004) and *Tribolium confusum* Jacquelin du Val (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae) (Cis *et al.*, 2006).

The *Bidens pilosa* (Linn.) is a cosmopolitan weed, belonging to the family Asteraceae, originating from South America and common in all tropical and subtropical areas of the world climates (Alvarez *et al.*, 1999). *B. pilosa* plant is reported as a noxious weed to crops in Egypt and over 40 countries because because it causes high reducing in the crop yields (Boulos, 2002). The second plant *Rumex dentatus* is a plant of Polygonaceae family is a weedy plant widely distributed in many countries including Egypt. Although, feeding inhibition in insect pests is the most important in the search for new and safer methods for pest control in stored grains, however, previous works investigating the antifeedant activities of the two weedy plants against stored product pests are scanty, so, the present study was carried out to investigate the antifeedant effects of the two plant weeds extracts of *B. pilosa* and *R. dentatus* against the three stored product insect pests, *A. obtectus* (Say) and *S. oryzae* as a models for primary insect pests on legume seeds and cereal grain, respectively and *O. surinamensis* as a model for secondary insect pests on cereal product compared with neem oil (Commercial product).

Materials and methods

1. Plants materials collection:

Naturally growing populations of *B. pilosa* and *R. dentatus* plants were identified and individually collected after the growing season from the different arable zones of fields located in Giza Research Station (GRS) that affiliated with Agricultural Research Center (ARC), Giza, Egypt.

2. Preparation of botanical extracts:

The two collected plant species root region were thoroughly cleaned by tapping, running water, then washed with distilled water and placed for a while on paper for semi-drying and finally, hung vertically upside down for complete air drying for 4 weeks in shade at room temperature 25°C. The dried plant materials were then pulverized into a coarse powder and sieved by 40 meshes to give equal particle size. The powdered leaves were successively extracted with methanol (98%) at room temperature for 48 hrs. The extracts were concentrated under low pressure using a rotary evaporator. The crude extracts were weighed and stored in refrigerator. Three concentrations (3, 5 and 7%) of the two plant species and neem oil were prepared in methanol.

3. Insects culture:

The culture of three tested species was obtained from a stock maintained in the Stored Grain and Product Insect Laboratory, Economic Entomology Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University. Adults of *A. obtectus* were reared on dry beans and maintained in glass jars (1kg capacity). Newly laid eggs were transferred onto fresh kidney beans to develop in subsequent stages until they reach the adult stage. Adults of *S. oryzae* reared on whole wheat in continuous darkness, while, *O. surinamensis* reared on sterilized oat seeds. The adults were then put into jars containing black cloths. All test insects

were kept in a darkened incubator maintained at 27±2°C and 65±5% relative humidity (r.h.).

4. Antifeedant activity:

Antifeedant activity of the two extracts (*B. pilosa* and *R. dentatus*) and neem oil was carried out as described by Brari and Kumar (2019) with some modifications. Different concentration levels of 3,5,7% of the two extracts and neem oil were prepared in methanol. For each treatment and control, five grams of clean and infestation-free, wheat grains, dry beans and oat seeds were separately placed in appropriate glass jars and treated with 1 ml of each concentration and shaken manually for 2 min to achieve complete distribution of extracts throughout the grains. After the complete evaporation of the solvent, ten adults of the three tested stored grain pests (*S. oryzae*, *A. obtectus* and *O. surinamensis*) were transferred to each pre-weighed food media (Wheat, kidney and oat bean, respectively) in the glass jars. Four replicates for each concentration of treatments and control were prepared, then all jars were placed in the incubator at same previously mentioned insect rearing conditions. After feeding for 45 days of feeding, food media was collected and re-weighed. The weight loss % determined and calculated by the "count-and-weight" method described by Harris and Lindblad (1978) and at apply applying the following equation:

$$\% \text{ Weight loss} = \frac{(W_u \times N_d) - (W_d \times N_u)}{W_u \times (N_d + N_u)} \times 100$$

Where

Number of undamaged grains (Nu)

Weight of undamaged grains (Wu)

Number of damaged grains (Nd)

Weight of damaged grains (Wd).

Feeding Deterrence was calculated by

using the feeding deterrent index

following Isman *et al.* (1990).

$$\text{FDI} (\%) = \frac{C - T}{C} \times 100$$

where, C = Weight loss in the control diet and T = Weight loss in the treated diet.

5. Evaluation adult emergence reduction:

The number of emerging adults of *S. oryzae* , *A. obtectus* and *O. surinamensis* was counted after 45 days of treatment. The reduction percentage in adult emergence of the three tested pests calculated by the following equation as described by El-Lakwah *et al.* (1992).

$$\% \text{ Reduction} = \frac{\text{MNEC} - \text{MNET}}{\text{MNEC}} \times 100$$

MNEC = Mean no. of emerged adults in the control.

MNET = Mean no. of emerged adults in the treatment.

6. Statistical analysis:

All the data concerning mortality were corrected by using Abbott's formula (Abbott, 1925). Tests for insecticidal activity were performed in triplicate and data presented are mean \pm SE. The mean values were compared by one-way ANOVA and Tukey's multiple comparison tests using software SPSS, version 11.5.

Results and discussion

Table (1): Antifeedant activity of three plant extracts against *Acanthoscelides obtectus* .

Plant Extracts	Concentrations (%)	Weight loss (%) (Means \pm SE)	FDI (%) (Means \pm SE)
<i>Rumex dentatus</i>	3	51.10 \pm 5.80 ^{ab}	14.20 \pm 9.70 ^d
	5	46.90 \pm 4.60 ^b	21.20 \pm 7.70 ^d
	7	13.30 \pm 5.10 ^{de}	77.60 \pm 8.50 ^{ab}
<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	3	10.90 \pm 0.40 ^{de}	81.7 \pm 0.70 ^{ab}
	5	8.70 \pm 1.10 ^{de}	85.30 \pm 1.60 ^{ab}
	7	4.45 \pm 1.20 ^c	92.52 \pm 1.90 ^a
<i>Neem oil</i>	3	48.5 \pm 0.90 ^{ab}	18.60 \pm 1.60 ^d
	5	26.10 \pm 1.20 ^c	56.10 \pm 2.10 ^c
	7	20.50 \pm 6.50 ^{cd}	65.60 \pm 10.90 ^{bc}
Control	0.0	59.50 \pm 3.30 ^a	
F value		30.160	24.107
P value		0.000	0.000

Values followed by different letters within a column are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ (Duncan's Multiple Range Tests).

1. Evaluation of antifeedant efficacy of botanical extracts:

Feeding deterrence indices (FDI) showed that, methanol extracts of *B. pilosa* , *R. dentatus* and neem oil had antifeedant action against the three tested insects the three tested concentrations of 3,5 and 7% (Tables 1-3).

2. Antifeedant activity of botanical extracts against *Acanthoscelides obtectus* :

Data in (Table 1) showed that, *B. pilosa* extract at its the highest the highest concentration 7% showed 92.52 \pm 1.90% Feeding deterrence index (FDI) with 4.45 \pm 1.20% minimum weight loss followed by *R. dentatus* resulted in obtaining 77.60 \pm 8.50% feeding deterrence with 13.30 \pm 5.10% weight loss, then neem oil that caused FDI 65.60 \pm 10.90% and weight loss 20.50 \pm 6.50% as compared to control 59.51 \pm weight loss. Weight loss caused by *A. obtectus* was significantly reduced with the application of the botanical extracts.

3. Antifeedant activity of botanical extracts against *Sitophilus oryzae* :

Maximum feeding deterrence (100.00%) with 0.00±0.00% weight loss was exhibited by the three botanical extracts (*B. pilosa*, *R. dentatus* and neem oil) when applied with 7% concentration as compared to control 61.04±6.00 weight loss. There was low significant weight loss of food feedings by the three treatments (*B. pilosa*, *R. dentatus* and neem oil)

against *S. oryzae*. *R. dentatus* was recorded as most effective (FDI 67.50±1.90, 96.20±4.60 and 100.00±0.00%) feeding deterrent at the three different concentrations (3,5,7%) against *S. oryzae* followed by *B. pilosa* (FDI 53.90±2.70, 95.30±1.10 and 100.00±0.00%) then neem oil (FDI 63.90±8.20, 79.30±10.40 and 100.00±0.00%), respectively at the same concentrations (Table 2).

Table (2): Antifeedant activity of three plant extracts against *Sitophilus oryzae* .

Plant Extracts	Concentrations (%)	Weight loss (%) (Means± SE)	FDI (%) (Means± SE)
<i>Rumex dentatus</i>	3	19.80±1.20 ^{bc}	67.50±1.90 ^{bc}
	5	2.30±2.80 ^d	96.20±4.60 ^a
	7	0.00±0.00 ^d	100.00±0.00 ^a
<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	3	28.10±1.70 ^b	53.90±2.70 ^c
	5	2.80±0.60 ^d	95.30±1.10 ^a
	7	0.00±0.00 ^d	100.00±0.00 ^a
Neem oil	3	21.90±5.00 ^b	63.90±8.20 ^c
	5	12.60±6.30 ^c	79.30±10.40 ^b
	7	0.00±0.00 ^d	100.00±0.00 ^a
Control	0.0	61.04±6.00 ^a	
F value		47.266	14.161
P value		0.000	0.000

Values followed by different letters within a column are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ (Duncan's Multiple Range Tests).

4. Antifeedant activity of botanical extracts against *Oryzaephilus surinamensis*:

R. dentatus and neem oil at 7% showed high FDI of 100.00±0.00 and 97.40 ±1.10% with 0.00 ± 0.00 and 1.10±0.50% weight loss, while, *B. pilosa* recorded FDI of 86.80±17.50% with weight loss 4.70±6.90% as

compared to 41.20±4.70% weight loss in control (Table 3). The effect of applying of 7% concentration of the two extracts and the neem oil on weight loss (%) caused by *O. surinamensis* can be arranged as: *B. pilosa* >Neem oil > *R. dentatus*.

Table (3): Antifeedant activity of three plant extracts against *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* .

Plant Extracts	Concentrations (%)	Weight loss (%) (Means± SE)	FDI (%) (Means± SE)
<i>Rumex dentatus</i>	3	14.40±4.30 ^{bc}	65.00±10.50 ^a
	5	2.60±4.40 ^{bc}	93.50±10.70 ^a
	7	0.00±0.00 ^c	100.00±0.00 ^a
<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	3	23.20±17.70 ^{ab}	45.80±41.50 ^a
	5	20.90±1.60 ^{abc}	48.70±3.70 ^a
	7	4.70±6.90 ^{bc}	86.80±17.50 ^a
Neem oil	3	20.30±0.90 ^{abc}	50.50±2.10 ^a
	5	2.10±0.90 ^{bc}	94.90±2.40 ^a
	7	1.10±0.50 ^c	97.40±1.10 ^a
Control	0.0	41.20±4.70 ^a	
F value		4.202	2.087
P value		0.004	0.093

Values followed by different letters within a column are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ (Duncan's Multiple Range Tests).

Approximately at all concentrations of botanical extracts, *A. obtectus* caused the highest weight loss as compared to *S. oryzae* and *O. surinamensis* except with *B. pilosa* extract. Methanol extract of *R. dentatus* was the strongest antifeedant against *O. surinamensis* while, *B. pilosa* the most effective against *A. obtectus*. Both extracts have the same antifeedant activity with *S. oryzae*. In general, the two extracts *B. pilosa* and *R. dentatus* were found efficacious against *A. obtectus*, *S. oryzae* and *O. surinamensis* as antifeeding agent. As shown in Figures (1, 2 and 3), feeding inhibition was significantly increased with an increase in the concentration of plant extracts applied, resulting in reduction of the weight loss caused by the three tested pests *A. obtectus*, *S. oryzae* and *O. surinamensis*.

5. Effect of botanical extracts on adult emergence rate:

The effect of different extracts on emergence adults of *A. obtectus*, *S. oryzae* and *O. surinamensis* are shown in Tables (4-6). Treatments of *A. obtectus*, *S. oryzae* and *O. surinamensis* with different concentrations of *B. pilosa*, *R. dentatus* and neem oil caused significant strongly reduced adult emergence of the three insect species after 45 days of treatment when compared to control. All the treatments of methanol extract from *R. dentatus*

strongly reduced adult emerged of *A. obtectus*, *S. oryzae* and *O. surinamensis* at the lowest concentrations 3%. The recorded adult's emergence reduction of *R. dentatus* and *B. pilosa* at the moderate concentration (5%) were (93.10±0.80, 90.90±1.10 and 95.80±0.70%) and (72.60± 0.50, 83.30±2.30 and 90.90±1.20%), while, adult's emergence reduction of neem oil were (88.90±0.70, 84.10±2.30 and 95.60±1.90%) against the same pests, respectively. Approximately the highest methanolic concentration (7%) of *R. dentatus* achieved complete adult's emergence reduction of *A. obtectus*, *S. oryzae* and *O. surinamensis* (98.00±0.10, 100.00±0.00 and 100.00±0.00 %, respectively), while the recorded adult's emergence reduction of *B. pilosa* were 85.10±0.30, 95.20±1.49 and 100.00±0.00 compared to adult's emergence reduction caused by neem oil (97.00±0.50, 100.00±0.00 and 96.10 %), against the same three pests, respectively at the same concentration. The number of the adults emerging by the three tested pests was significantly decreased in all treatments with increasing concentration of the tested plant extracts (*R. dentatus*, *B. pilosa* extracts and neem oil) compared to the control (Figures, 4, 5 and 6).

Table (4): Adult emergence and progeny reduction of *Acanthoscelides obtectus* exposed to different concentrations of of three plant extracts after 45 days of treatment.

Plant Extracts	Concentrations (%)	Adult emergence	Progeny reduction (%)
<i>Rumex dentatus</i>	3	51.70±4.60 ^c	58.30±3.70 ^g
	5	8.50±1.00 ^{fg}	93.10±0.80 ^{cd}
	7	2.40±0.06 ^h	98.00±0.10 ^a
<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	3	102.00±1.73 ^b	17.70±1.30 ^h
	5	34.00±0.57 ^d	72.60±0.50 ^f
	7	18.40±0.34 ^e	85.10±0.30 ^e
Neem oil	3	18.00±1.15 ^e	85.50±0.90 ^e
	5	13.70±0.88 ^{ef}	88.90±0.70 ^{de}
	7	3.70±0.66 ^{gh}	97.00±0.50 ^{bc}
Control	0.0	124.00±4.00 ^a	
F value		538.70	320.00
P value		0.000	0.000

Values followed by different letters within a column are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ (Duncan's Multiple Range Tests).

Table (5): Adult emergence and progeny reduction of *Sitophilus oryzae* exposed to different concentrations of of three plant extracts after 45 days of treatment.

Plant Extracts	Concentrations (%)	Adult emergence	Progeny reduction (%)
<i>Rumex dentatus</i>	3	12.60±0.30 ^{bc}	56.80±1.10 ^c
	5	2.60±0.30 ^{ef}	90.90±1.10 ^b
	7	0.00±0.00 ^f	100.00±0.00 ^a
<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	3	14.60±0.80 ^b	49.90±3.00 ^f
	5	4.90±0.60 ^c	83.30±2.30 ^c
	7	1.40±0.40 ^{ef}	95.20±1.49 ^{ab}
<i>Neem oil</i>	3	9.60±0.60 ^d	67.10±2.30 ^d
	5	4.60±0.60 ^c	84.10±2.30 ^c
	7	0.00±0.00 ^f	100.00±0.00 ^a
Control	0.0	29.30±3.40 ^a	
F value		56.499	105.985
P value		0.000	0.000

Values followed by different letters within a column are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ (Duncan's Multiple Range Tests).

Table (6): Adult emergence and progeny reduction of *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* exposed to different concentrations of of three plant extracts after 45 days of treatment.

Plant Extracts	Concentrations (%)	Adult emergence	Progeny reduction (%)
<i>Rumex dentatus</i>	3	19.30±2.00 ^d	87.40±2.30 ^d
	5	6.40±0.70 ^e	95.80±0.70 ^b
	7	0.00±0.00 ^f	100.00±0.00 ^a
<i>Bidens pilosa</i>	3	42.00±3.20 ^b	72.70±3.60 ^d
	5	14.00±1.10 ^d	90.90±1.20 ^c
	7	0.00±0.00 ^f	100.00±0.00 ^a
<i>Neem oil</i>	3	30.00±1.70 ^c	80.50±1.90 ^e
	5	6.70±1.70 ^e	95.60±1.90 ^b
	7	6.00±1.10 ^e	96.10±1.20 ^b
Control	0.0	154.00±3.50 ^a	
F value		604.687	78.28
P value		0.000	0.000

Values followed by different letters within a column are significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$ (Duncan's Multiple Range Tests).

Figure (1): Weight loss % caused by *Acanthoscelides obtectus* at different concentrations of *Rumex dentatus*, *Bidens pilosa* and neem oil.

Figure (2): Weight loss % caused by *Sitophilus oryzae* at different concentrations of *Rumex dentatus*, *Bidens pilosa* and neem oil.

Figure (3): Weight loss % caused by *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* at different concentrations of *Rumex dentatus*, *Bidens pilosa* and neem oil.

Figure (4): *Acanthoscelides obtectus* adult emergence from dry beans treated with methanol extracts of *Rumex dentatus*, *Bidens pilosa* and neem oil at different concentrations.

Figure (5): *Sitophilus oryzae* adult emergence from whole wheat treated with methanol extracts of *Rumex dentatus*, *Bidens pilosa* and neem oil at different concentrations.

Figure (6): *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* adult emergence from oat seeds treated with methanol extracts of *Rumex dentatus*, *Bidens pilosa* and neem oil at different concentrations.

Means followed by the same letters are not significantly different at $p \leq 0.05$

SEM: Standard error of the mean

Our findings coincide with Goudoum *et al.* (2016) who observed that, essential oil of *B. pilosa* reduced weight loss of Bambara groundnut *C. maculatus* and Feeding deterrence index (FDI) increase with increasing of concentration essential oil of *B. pilosa*. The LC₅₀, LC₈₀ and LC₉₉ of *B. pilosa*, reduced respectively 62.33, 85.00 and 98.00% of damages of *C. maculatus*. These observations were supported by (Feng *et al.*, 2012) who revealed that, significant antifeedant activity was induced by extract of *B. pilosa* when applied against *Spodoptera exigua*. As for antifeedant activity of *R. dentatus* extract, Shoukry *et al.* (2003) showed that, *R. dentatus* oil effects on the biochemical activities of *Plodia interpunctella* larvae and leading to disturbances in carbohydrate, lipid and protein levels in the haemolymph, this disturbance may cause antifeedant activities (Kalavathi *et al.*, 1991). In other study, the aqueous extracts (5%) of eight plant species including *Rumex nepaiensis* Spreng reflected varying degree of antifeedant effect against major insect pests infesting cabbage viz., diamondback moth, *Plutella xylostella* (L.), cabbage white butterfly, *Pieris brassicae* (L.) and cabbage aphid, *Brevicoryne brassicae* (L.) (Mehta *et al.* , 2005). In a related study, Mehta *et al.* (2002) concluded that among five plant species evaluated against cabbage butterfly, *P. brassicae* (L.), *Artemisia brevifolia* Wall. extract resulted in significantly high antifeedant activity followed by *R. nepalensis* and *Melia azedarach* (L.) at 1.25, 2.5 and 5.0% concentrations. Also, Sharma (2016) studied efficacy of antifeedant activities of different extracts including *R. nepalensis* at 1.25, 2.5 and 5.0% concentrations against the same pest. Plant extracts applied at 5.0% concentration resulted in significantly high antifeedant effect against the third instar caterpillar of *P. brassicae* as compared to the 2.5 and 1.25% concentration. Our results of

adults emergence reduction are in conformity with Renuka *et al.* (2014) who reported that, methanol and acetone extracts of *B. pilosa* has proved effective and resulted a significant reduction in F1 progenies of *A. obtectus* and *Zabrotes subfasciatus*. The methanolic concentration (8%) of *B. pilosa* caused high reduction in F1 adult's emergence of *A. obtectus* and *Zabrotes subfasciatus*, while the other concentrations 2,4 and 6% of methanol and acetone extracts of *B. pilosa* significantly reduced the emergence of F1 adults of *A. obtectus*. There was a significant reduction in F1 progenies with increase in treatment dosage. In this regard, Jovanovic *et al.* (2007) showed that, *Utrica dioica* and *Taraxacum officinale* extracts efficiently killed 100% of adults of *A. obtectus* and significant level of reduction in F1 progeny was also achieved. On the other hand, the effect of plant extracts on the reduction of progeny of adults of *O. surinamensis*, revealed that *Conyza discorides* was the highest (92.93%) followed by *Cymbopogon nardus* spreng (88.68%), then *Moringa oliefera* (70.80%) (Omran *et al.*, 2020). In another study Shafaie *et al.* (2019) showed that, essential oils, extracts and powders of *Cupressus arizonica* Greene, *Juniperus communis* L. and *Mentha longifolia* L recorded a high level of reduction in F1-Progeny against the three stored product pests *Callosobruchus maculatus* Fabricus, *S. granarius* L. and *O. surinamensis* L. The Inhibition of progeny emergence resulted from activities of plant extracts against grain stored pests has been reported by many studies; *Sitophilus oryzae* (Khani *et al.*, 2011 and 2017); *A. obtectus* (Karakas, 2020); *Trogoderma granarium* (Derbalah, 2012); *Callosobruchus maculatus* F. (Hussain *et al.*, 2008 and Vanmathi *et al.*, 2010) and *Corcyra cephalonica* (Khani *et al.*, 2013).

The observed antifeedant effect of the two botanical extracts (*R. dentatus* and *B.*

pilosa) indicates presence of toxic bioactive components. The present findings suggest that the leaves of these plants possess certain bioactive components which require further investigation to determine the exact mode of action of these active components and their effect on non-target organisms. The present study, therefore, revealed that both *R. dentatus* and *B. pilosa* possess antifeedant effects against *A. obtectus*, *S. oryzae* and *O. surinamensis*. Weight loss caused by the three tested pests was considerably decreased with the application of these two botanical extracts. Based on the results of the present study, it is possible to claim that the effects of the two botanical extracts achieved a high adult emergence reduction when applied against *A. obtectus*, *S. oryzae* and *O. surinamensis*. Finally, *R. dentatus* extract was concluded as the most effective feeding deterrent among tested botanical extracts and as this plant is available and easy to be found among the Egyptian flora, therefore, it could be used as a potential botanical insecticide and a wonderful substitute of synthetic chemicals for the management of stored grain pests.

References

- Abbott, W. (1925):** A method of computing the effectiveness of an insecticide. J. Econ. Entomol., 18(2):265-267.
- Alvarez, A.; Pomar, F., Sevilla, M.A. and Montero, M.J. (1999):** Gastric antisecretory and antiulcer activities of an ethanolic extract of *Bidens pilosa* L. var. radiata Schult.Bip. J. Ethnopharmacol., 67: 333-340.
- Boulos, L. (2002):** Flora of Egypt, Vol. 3 (Verbinaceae – Compositae), 373 pp., Al Hadara Publ, Cairo, Egypt.
- Brari , J. and Kumar, V. (2019):** Antifeedant activity of four plant essential oils against major stored product insect pests International Journal of Pure and Applied Zoology, 7(3) : 41-45.
- Cis, J.; Nowak, G. and Kisiel, W. (2006):** Antifeedant properties and chemotaxonomic implications of sesquiterpene lactones and syringin from *Rhaponticum pulchrum*. Bioch Syst. Ecol., 34:862–867.
- Derbalah, A. S. (2012):** Efficacy of Some Botanical Extracts against *Trogoderma granarium* in Wheat Grains with Toxicity Evaluation, The Scientific World, Article, ID 639854,pp. 9.
- El-Lakwah, F. A.; Darwish, A. A. and Khaled, O. M. (1992):** Effectiveness of Dill seed powder on stored products insects. Annals of Agricultural Science, Moshtohor, 34: 2031–2037.
- Feng, X.; Jiang, H. ; Zhang, Y.; He, W. and L. Zhang (2012):** Insecticidal activities of ethanol extracts from thirty Chinese medicinal plants against *Spodoptera exigua* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Journal of Medicinal Plants Research, 6(7): 1263-1267.
- Golob, P.; Dales, M.; Fidgen, A.; Evans, J. and Gudrups, I. (1999):** The use of spices and medicinal as bioactive protectants for grains. FAO Bulletin. FAO, Rome.
- Goudoum, A.; Ngamo Tinkeu, L. S.; Ngassoum, M. B. and Mbofung, C. M. (2016):** Insecticidal and antifungal properties of essential oil of *Bidens Pilosa* Linn. Var. Radita (Asteraceae) towards stored bambara groundnut insect and fungi pests. Asian Journal of Agriculture and Food Sciences , 4 (2): 66-72.
- Harris, K.L. and lindblad, C.J. (1978):** Post-harvest Grain Loss Assessment Methods, American Association of Cereal Chemists, St. Paul, Minnesota, pp. 193.

- Hashem, M. Y. ; Ahmed, S. S.; El-Mohandes, M. A. and Gharib, M. A. (2012):** Susceptibility of different life stages of saw-toothed grain beetle *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* (L.) (Coleoptera: Silvanidae) to modified atmospheres enriched with carbon dioxide. *Journal of Stored Products Research*, 48 :46-51.
- Ignatowicz, S. and Wesolowska, B. (1994):** Potential of common herbs as grain protectant: repellent effect of herb extracts on granary weevil, *Sitophilus granarius*. In: Highley EJ, Wright EJ, Banks JJ, Champ, BR (eds) *Proceedings of the sixth international working conference on stored product protection*, Vol. 2. Canberra
- Isman, M. B.; Koul, O.; Luczynski, A. and Kaminskis, J. (1990):** Insecticidal and antifeedant bioactivities of neem oils and their relationship to azadirachtin content. *Journal of Agriculture and Food Chemistry*, 38: 1406-1411.
- Isman, M. (2002):** Insect antifeedants. *Pesticide Outlook*, 13(4):152-157.
- Jovanovic, Z; Kostic, M. and Popovic, Z. (2007):** Grain protective properties of herbal extract against the bean weevil *Acanthoscelides obtectus* Say. *Ind. Crop Prod.*, 26: 100-104.
- Kalavathi, P.; David, B.V. and Peter, C. (1991):** Evaluation of *Vitex negundo* (Verbenaceae) for the control of certain insect pests of crops. *Pesticides Research Journal*, 3 (1): 79-85.
- Karakas, M. (2020):** Antifeedant and repellent effects of root extracts of some aromatic plants against bean weevil *Acanthoscelides obtectus* Say (Coleoptera: Bruchidae) *International Journal of Entomology Research*, 5(2): 33-37.
- Khani, M.; Awang, R.M. ; Omar, D.; Rahmani, M. and Rezazadeh, S. (2011):** Tropical medicinal plant extracts against rice weevil, *Sitophilus oryzae* L. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 5(2):259-265.
- Khani, M.; Awang, R.M. ; Omar, D. and Rahmani, M. (2013):** Toxicity, antifeedant, egg hatchability and adult emergence effect of *Piper nigrum* L. and *Jatropha curcas* L. extracts against rice moth, *Corcyra cephalonica* (Stainton) . *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 7(18): 1255-1262.
- Khani, M.; Marouf, A.; Amini, S.; Yazdani, D.; Farashiani, M.E.; Ahvazi, M.; Khalighi-Sigaroodi, F. and Hosseini-Gharalari, A. (2017):** Efficacy of three herbal essential oils against rice weevil, *Sitophilus oryzae* (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *J. Essent. Oil Bear. Plants*, 20: 937–950.
- Klys', M. (2004):** Feeding inhibitors in pest control: effect of herb addition to food on the population dynamics of the lesser grain borer *Rhyzopertha dominica* F. (Coleoptera: Bostrychidae). *Pol. J. Ecol.*, 52:575–581
- Liu, Z.L.; Chu, S.S.; Jiang, G.H. and Liu, S.L. (2012):** Antifeedants from Chinese medicinal herb, *Erythrina variegata* var. *orientalis*, against maize weevil *Sitophilus zeamais*. *Nat Prod Commun.*, 7:171–172.
- Hussain, S.; Mahdi, A. and Rahman, M.K. (2008):** Insecticidal effect of some spices on *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius) in black gram seeds. *J. Zool. Rajshahi Univ.* 27: 47–50.
- Mehta, P.K.; Sood, A.K.; Parmar, S. and Kashyap, N.P. (2002):** Antifeedant activity of some plants of North-Western Himalayas against

- cabbage caterpillar, *Pieris brassicae* (L.) Journal of Entomological Research, 26 (1): 51-54.
- Mehta, P.K.; Sood, A.K.; Patial, A. and Ramesh, L. (2005):** Evaluation of Toxic and Antifeedant Properties of Some Plant Extracts against Major Insect-Pests of Cabbage Pesticide Research Journal , 17 (2): 30-33.
- Naroz, M. H.; Ahmed, S. S.; Abdel-Aziz, S.Y. and Abdel-Shafy, S. (2019):** First Record of *Acanthoscelides obtectus* (Say) (Coleoptera: Chrysomelidae: Bruchinae) in Egypt: Development and Host Preference on Five Species of Legume Seeds. The Coleopterists Bulletin, 73(3) : 727-734.
- Omran, I. M.; Kadhim, S. H. and Almansour, N. (2020):** Effect of some plants powder and insecticides admiral and runner against saw-toothed grain beetle *Oryzaephilus surinamensis* L. (Silvanidae: Coleoptera). International Journal of Entomology Research, 5(2); 33-37.
- Pimentel, D. (1991):** World resources and food losses to pest. In: Gorham JR (ed) Ecology and management of food industry pests. FDA Technical Bulletin 4, Association of Official Analytical Chemists, Arlington, Arlington, VA.
- Rani, P.U.; Venkateshwarama, T. and Devenand, P. (2011):** Bioactivities of *Cocos nucifera* L. (Arecales: Arecaceae) and *Terminalia catappa* L. (Myrtales: Combretaceae) leaf extracts as postharvest grain protectants against four major stored product pests. J .Pest .Sci., 84:235–247.
- Renuka, D. R.; Thakur, R. and Sharma, K. (2014):** Bioefficacy of *Bidens pilosa* L. against *Acanthoscelides obtectus* (Say) and *Zabrotes subfasciatus* (Boheman), stored pests of kidney beans, world wide. Intl. J. Agri. Crop. Sci., 7 (15): 1470-1477.
- Saljoqi , A.U.R. ; Afridi, M. K. ; Khan, S. A. and Rehman, S. (2006):** Effects of six plant extracts on rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* in the stored wheat grains. J. Agric. Biol. Sci., 1:1–5.
- Shafaie, F.; Aramideh, Sh. ; Valizadegan, O. and Safaralizadeh, M.H. (2019):** Bioactivity of Essential Oils, Extracts and Powders of *Cupressus arizonica* Greene, *Juniperus communis* L. and *Mentha longifolia* L. on three stored product pests. Thai Journal of Agricultural Science, 52 (4): 205-219.
- Sharma, S. (2016):** Evaluation of some plant derivatives for management of cabbage butterfly (*Pieris brassicae*). International Journal of Science, Environment and Technology, 5 (2): 395 – 400.
- Shoukry, I.F.; Khalaf, A.A.; Hussein, K.T. and Khater, K.S. (2003):** Toxicological evaluation of some botanical oils on biochemical aspects in the Indian meal moth *Plodia interpunctella* HB. (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) Egyptian Journal of Biology, 5: 155-163.
- Suthisut, D.; Fields, P.G. and Chandrapatya, A. (2011):** Contact toxicity, feeding reduction, and repellency of essential oils from three plants from the ginger family (Zingiberaceae) and their major components against *Sitophilus zeamais* and *Tribolium castaneum*. J . Econ. Entomol., 104:1445–1454.
- Vanmathi, J.S.; Padmalatha, C.; Singh, A.J..AR. and Isaac, S.S. (2010):** Efficacy of selected plant extracts on the oviposition deterrent and adult emergence activity of *Callosobruchus maculatus* F. (Bruchidae: Coleoptera). Global J. Sci. Frontier Res., 8: 2-7.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejprii.eg.net

Performance of *Schistocerca gregaria* haemocytes in response to entomopathogenic
fungi *Metarhizium acridum* and *Beauveria bassiana* single and mixed infections

El-Maghraby, M. M. A. ¹ and Abdelatef, G. M. ²

¹ Plant Protection Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Zagazig University, Egypt.

² Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 20/4/2021

Accepted: 17/ 6 /2021

Keywords

Immune response,
haemocytes,
Metarhizium acridum,
Beauveria bassiana,
combined infection
and desert locust.

Abstract:

Desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria* (Forskål) (Orthoptera: Acrididae) was infected with two entomopathogenic fungi *Metarhizium acridum* (Driver and Milner) (Ma), *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill (Bb). The haemocytes defense response was investigated using light microscope. Five types of blood haemocytes were recognized which were: prohaemocyte, plasmatocyte, spindle-shaped haemocytes, spherulocyte and granulocyte. The first response was noted after 48 hrs. post infection as haemocytes aggregated in the haemolymph of infected nymphs, by the 3rd day the aggregation of haemocytes increased to form nodules specially in case of Bb infection. By the 4th day the aggregation and nodules were increased in the Bb and were less in Ma and Ma + Bb joint infection also the hyphal bodies were present for the first time in the haemolymph of Ma + Bb joint infection. The hyphal bodies increased during the 5th to 8th day post infection in the haemolymph of all infected nymphs accompanied with significant haemocytes destruction.

Introduction

Desert locust *Schistocerca gregaria* (Forskål) (Orthoptera: Acrididae) one of the most dangerous pests threaten planted crop in wide areas in Africa and Asia, its attacks cause huge destruction and required large amount of pesticides to control such attacks (Zhang *et al.*, 2019).

Entomopathogenic fungi, e.g. *Metarhizium acridum* (Driver and Milner) (Ma), *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill (Bb) confirmed as a good alternative to chemical

insecticides in desert locust and grasshopper control in Egypt (El-Maghraby *et al.*, 2009).

Fungal infection starts via successful penetration of the insect's cuticle using extracellular cuticle-degrading enzymes (Pedrini *et al.*, 2007). Once the fungus enters the haemolymph, it stimulates the immune response of haemocytes (Strand, 2008 and Hillyer, 2016). Haemocytes defense response include Phagocytosis, encapsulation and coagulation (Strand, 2008).

The present work investigates the behavior of desert locust haemocytes in

response of *M. acridum* and *B. bassiana* infection.

Materials and methods

Desert locust *S. gregaria* 5th nymphal instars were obtained from the stock culture maintained for several generations at Locust and Grasshopper Research Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Egypt. Spores of Ma and Bb were mass produced according to El-Maghraby *et al.* (2009). Three treatments were applied topically to 5th nymphal instar 1 day old after the fourth molting as a topical application according to Abdelatef *et al.* (2009), these treatments were: 1- (Ma) at a dose 1×10^3 spores/nymph, 2- (Bb) at a dose 1×10^3 spores/nymph and 3- combination of Ma and Bb at a dose 1×10^3 spores/nymph of both fungi. Samples of haemolymph were taken daily after treatment till the 8th day, the nymphs were allowed to feed for 2 hrs., then were chilled on ice for 10 minutes, the arthroal membrane of the hind leg of each nymph was pierced with sterile needle, the haemolymph was collected using 10 μ l capillary pipette, small haemolymph droplet was placed on clear glass slide, then the drop was quickly smeared to a thin film on the slide by using an edge of another slide, the smear was then air dried, then fixed in 2-3 drops of methanol 95%. The smears were stained with diluted Gemsa stain for 15 minutes, then washed with distilled water. The haemocytes were examined and photographed using a light microscope under the oil immersion lens, the haemocytes were identified according to Gupta (1979).

Results and discussion

In the present work 5 types of haemocyte were recognized, these types were: Prohaemocyte, plasmatocyte, spindle-shaped haemocytes, spherulocyte and granulocyte as shown in Figure (1). The obtained results showed clearly that the treatment of 5th nymphal instar of *S. gregaria* with Ma and Bb caused several

morphological and behavioral changes in the haemocyte.

Such changes began after 48 hrs. post infection as aggregation of haemocyte, as shown in Figure 2 (A, B, C), a multiplication in cells was noticed as in Figure 2 (A) a prohaemocyte was divided into 2 new cells. While at the 3rd day post infection the haemocytes began to form nodules, in treating insects, Figure 2 (D, E, F) shows more haemocytes aggregation at the 3rd day post infection with Ma and Bb mixture, Ma and Bb it could be noticed that more cells participate in aggregation specially in case of Bb infection.

There were no aggregations noticed in the non-infected nymph's haemolymph (Not shown). By the 4th day post infection, there were more aggregation forming nodules in case of Bb infection (Figure 3 A, B, C), while in case of Ma (Figure 3 D and E) and Ma and Bb mixture (Figure 3F) infection, there were less aggregation, also in Figure 3 (F) the first appear on the hyphal bodies in the haemolymph of infected insects with Ma and Bb mixture was noticed.

In Ma and Bb mixed infection, at the 5th, 6th and 7th day post treatment (Figure 4), there was a slight increase in the hyphal bodies (Figure 4 A) as well as distortion of the prohaemocytes, granulocytes and spherulocytes at the 5th, while at the 6th day (Figure 4 B) more hyphal bodies occurred, some of the granulocytes lost part of its membrane, also pyconosis appeared obviously in the nuclei of spherulocyte, by the 7th day (Figure 4 C) the haemolymph was full of hyphal bodies with lysed granulocytes and there was spherulocyte with obvious pyconosis in the nuclei. At the 8th day there was no haemocytes only hyphal bodies occurred in the haemolymph.

While in case of Ma infection at the 5th, 6th, and 7th day (Figure 5), at the 5th day post infection hyphal bodies were present for the first time (Figure 5 A) also there was

abnormalities in the granulocytes and spherulocytes, moreover, there were a lot of vacuoles in the cytoplasm of the granulocytes and pycnosis in the nuclei of the spherulocyte, on the 6th day more hyphal bodies occurred surround the haemocytes, also some lysed spherulocytes were present (Figure 5 B), by the 7th day post infection (Figure 5 c) few haemocyte were found surrounded with more hyphal bodies, there were also lysed granulocytes and plasmatocytes, the cytoplasm of the plasmatocytes was full of vacuoles. While at the 8th day post infection there were no sign of haemocytes and the haemolymph was full of hyphal bodies. Figure (6) shows the effect of Bb infection on the 5th and 6th day post infection. At the 5th day (Figure 6 A) post infection there were many plasmatocytes with large vacuoles, distorted granulocytes showing vacuolization in the cytoplasm, and abnormal spherulocytes, also aggregation of few cells, although on the 6th day (Figure 6 B) post infection there were abnormal spherulocytes, granulocytes and prohaemocytes with lysed cytoplasm, the hyphal bodies were first occurred. Figure (7) illustrates the effect of Bb infection on the 7th and 8th day, there were abnormal granulocytes and spherulocytes with obvious pycnosis in the nuclei, plasmatocytes with large vacuoles and abnormal prohaemocytes, also more hyphal bodies occurred on the 7th day (Figure 7 A). On the 8th day (Figure 7 B) there were distorted in the granulocytes with obvious pycnosis in the nuclei, abnormal plasmatocytes, spherulocytes and

prohaemocytes, more hyphal bodies occurred.

Lackie *et al.* (1985) observed a greater number of plasmatocytes in control desert locust, which in harmony with the present work. During the infection, there was an increase in the proportion of spherulocytes and granulocytes, this may be due to their role in production of humoral defense reaction. The insect immune system is subdivided into humoral and cellular defense responses. Humoral defenses include the production of antimicrobial peptides and the complex enzymatic cascades that regulate coagulation or melanization of hemolymph. In contrast, cellular defense refers to hemocyte-mediated immune responses like phagocytosis, nodulation and encapsulation (Lavine and Strand 2001). The failure of the immune system of mycosed desert locust *S. gregaria* nymphs may be due to the secretion of mycotoxins by the entomopathogenic fungi, Vey *et al.* (2002) suggested that the destruxin may intervene during the disease by true immune-inhibitory effect occurring at doses which do not cause paralysis or any general sign of toxicity. It's clear that combined infection of both used fungi caused a greater reduction to the 5th nymphal instar of *S. gregaria* immune system followed by *M. acridum* then *B. bassiana* infection, such effect may explain the superior effect of the combined infection and *M. acridum* treatments as previously reported in work of (Abdelatef *et al.*, 2009 and El-Maghraby *et al.*, 2009).

Figure (1): Haemocytes types of *Schistocerca gregaria*. (A) Prohaemocyte (B) Plasmatocyte (C) Spindleshaped cell (D) Spheriouloucytes (E) Granulocyte, Bar= 8µ.

Figure (2): Haemocytes of *Schistocerca gregaria* at 48 hr. (A,B,C) and 3 days (D, E, F) post infection. *M. acridum* (B, E), *B. bassiana* (C, F) *M. acridum* and *B. bassiana* mixture (A, D) infection. (Pr=prohaemocyte Pl= plasmatocyte Sp= spindle shaped cell Gr= granulocyte Sph= spherulocyte) Bar= 8µ.

Figure (3): Haemocytes of *Schistocerca gregaria* at 4th day post infection with *B. bassiana*, (A,B,C) *M. acridum* (D, E), and *M. acridum* and *B. bassiana* mixture (F) (Hy= hypha) Bar= 8µ

Figure (4): Haemocytes of *Schistocerca gregaria* at 5th (A) , 6th (B) and 7th (C) day post infection with *M. acridum* and *B. bassiana* mixture. (Pr=prohemocyte Pl= plasmatocyte Gr= granulocyte Sph= spherulocyte Hy= hypha) Bar= 8µ.

Figure (5): Haemocytes of *Schistocerca gregaria* at 5th (A) , 6th (B) and 7th (C) day post infection with *M. acridum* (Pr=proheamocyte PL= plasmatocyte cell Gr= granulocyte Sph= spherulocyte Hy= hypha) Bar= 8μ

Figure (6): Haemocytes of *Schistocerca gregaria* at 5th (A) and 6th (B) day post infection with *B. bassiana*. (Pr=proheamocyte Pl= plasmatocyte Sp= spindle shaped cell Gr= granulocyte Sph= spherulocyte) Bar= 8μ

Figure (7) Haemocytes of *Schistocerca gregaria* at 7th (A) and 8th (B) day post infection with *B. bassiana*. (Pr=prohaemocyte, Pl= plasmatocyte, Gr= granulocyte, Sph= spherulocyte Hy= hypha) Bar= 8µ

References

- Abdelatef, G. M.; El-Maghraby, M. M. A. ; Gomaa, E. A. and Metaweh, H. H. (2009): Haemolymph picture and its chemical components in *Schistocerca gregaria* (Forskål) as affected by two entomopathogenic fungi. *Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control*, 19 (2): 119-128.
- El-Maghraby, M. M. A; Gomaa, E. A. ; Metaweh, H. H. and Abdelatef, G. M. (2009): Susceptibility of *Schistocerca gregaria* (Forskål) and *Euprepocnemis plorans* (Charpentier). to *Metarhizium anisopliae* var. *acidum* (Metchnikoff) Soroken, *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill. and *Nosema locustae* Canning. *Egyptian Journal of Biological Pest Control*, 19 (1): 55-61.
- Gupta A.P. (1979): Haemocyte types: their structures, synonymies, interrelationships, and taxonomic significance. In Gupta A.P. (eds.) 1979. *Insects haemocytes*. Cambridge University Press, 85-127.
- Hillyer, J. F. (2016): Insect immunology and hematopoiesis. *Developmental and Comparative Immunology*, 58: 102-118.
- Lackie A.M.; Takle, G. and Tetley, L. (1985): Haemocytic encapsulation in the locust *Schistocerca gregaria* (Orthoptera) and in the cockroach *Priplaneta Americana* (Dictyoptera). *Cell Tissue Res.*, 240:343-351.
- Lavine, M. and Strand, M. R. (2001): Surface features mediating cellular encapsulation in noctuid moths. *J. Insect Physiol.*, 47: 965-974.
- Pedrini, N.; Crespo, R. and Juarez, M.P. (2007): Biochemistry of insect epicuticle degradation by entomopathogenic fungi. *Comp. Biochem. Physiol. C Toxicol. Pharmacol.*, 146: 124e137.
- Strand, M. R. (2008): The insect cellular immune response. *Insect Science*, 15: 1-14.
- Vey, A.; Matha, V. and Dumas, C. (2002): Effect of the peptide mycotoxin destruxin E on insect haemocytes and on dynamics and efficiency of the

multicellular immune reaction. J.
Invert. Pathol., 80: 177-187.

**Zhang, L.; Lecoq, M. ; Latchininsky, A.
and Hunter, D. (2019):** Locust and

grasshopper management. Annual
Review of Entomology, 64: 15-34.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

**Impact of certain insecticides with different mode of action on the California red scale
Aonidiella aurantii (Hemiptera-Diaspididae) on orange under local conditions in Egypt**

Rezk, M.¹ ; Ahmed, S. Abdel-Aty² and Rasha, S. Abdel-Fattah¹

¹Plant Protection Research Institute, Sabahia Plant Protection Station, Agricultural Research Center, Alexandria, Egypt.

² Department of Pesticide Chemistry and Technology, Faculty of Agriculture, Alexandria University, 21545-El-Shatby, Alexandria, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 20/4/2021

Accepted: 31 /5 /2021

Keywords

California red scale, pyriproxyphen (Admiral), imidacloprid (Best), spirotetramat (Movento), sulfoxaflor (Isoclast), Kz oil and population reduction.

Abstract:

The California red scale (CRS) (*Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell). (Hemiptera-Diaspididae) is one of the most important pests infested citrus trees, which come second to grapes of fruit trees worldwide. In Egypt, It is threatening the citrus trees that are important either in exporting or national consumption. The California red scale is able to develop resistance, so five insecticides with different modes of action were tested in this study. These insecticides are: Pyriproxyphen (Admiral), 10% EC; imidacloprid (Best), 25% WP; spirotetramat (Movento), 10% SC; sulfoxaflor (Isoclast), 50% WG and a mineral oil (Kz oil) 95% EC. The used insecticides were applied using 20 Liter Sprinkler using randomized complete blocks design (RCBD) design on fruit full navel orange trees. The tested insecticides reduced the treated insect stages population in a function of the treated stage, the insecticide mode of action and the time after treatment. Among the tested insecticides, Kz oil was the most effective, reducing the treated population in systemic arrangement through suffocation effect. Pyriproxyphen (Admiral) appeared too low effective to cause 50% adult population reduction with multiplied effect against the other stages to as maximum as 97.9% because of its IGR mode of action. Sulfoxaflor (Isoclast) and spirotetramat (Movento) exceeded the imidacloprid (Best) in their lethal effects against all stages of almost the checked time after treatment in both 2018 and 2019 seasons. Different effects of the tested insecticides are explained. These insecticides are known as integrated pest management compatible with little to no effect against CRS natural enemies, low toxicity to mammals and man. They are also classified as non-carcinogenic, non-mutagenic and non-reprotoxic under the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) classification.

Introduction

Citrus fruits come second to grapes of fruit trees worldwide (Grafton-Cardwell, 2010). According to 2020 statistics of the Egyptian Ministry of Agriculture, Egypt is the 1st citrus exporting country exporting 1.8 million ton to 111 countries all over the world. Scale insects are one of the problematic phenomena threatens the citrus trees that are important in Egypt either in exporting or national consumption. Imidacloprid, clothianidin and sulfoxaflor strongly caused significant repellency, reduction in feeding and adults body weight of *Schizaphis graminum* (Rondani) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and *Coccinella septempunctata* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) at sub-lethal doses (Bilal *et al.*, 2020). Imidacloprid is used to control sucking insects, some chewing insects, including termites, soil insects, and fleas on pets. In addition to its topical use on pets, imidacloprid may be applied to crops, soil, and as a seed treatment (Tomlin, 2006).

The California red scale (CRS) (*Aonidiella aurantii* Maskell, Family, Diaspididae) is one of the most important pest infested citrus trees in different parts of the world (Sorribas *et al.*, 2010). This pest causes leaf drop (Defoliation), fruit, dry out and fall off and trunk heavy infestation (Bedford, 1998). It decreases the tree viability and the fruits cosmetic damage, resulting in its downgrading. In severe infestations, leaf yellowing and dieback of branches occur, reducing the tree productivity and health to death (Flint *et al.*, 1991). Biological control is not always sufficient to keep it below an economic threshold (Forster *et al.*, 1995). Fresh market fruit, results in a pest management challenge that often requires insecticides. California red scale has developed resistance to the used insecticides. CRS was controlled in late in the 18 century with hydrogen cyanide (HCN), but its resistance was detected (Quayle, 1938).

In the 1940s, citrus growers next relied on organophosphate and later carbamate insecticides (Carman, 1977), which the CRS developed their resistance in 1970s in South Africa (Nel *et al.*, 1979), Australia (Abdelrahman, 1973) and in the 1990s in California (Grafton-Cardwell and Vehrs, 1995). Several generic 350 SC imidacloprid formulations are used in drip or micro sprinkler irrigation systems, but CRS control was inconsistent depending on the quality of the irrigation system. Insect growth regulators (IGRs) were used to interfere with insect metamorphosis, growth or reproduction. However, some are non-selective and may detrimentally affect natural enemies. Buprofezin and pyriproxyfen IGRs were registered for CRS control in California in the late 1990s.

Pyriproxyfen was used for 90% of the IGR applications in the San Joaquin Valley in 2005-2010 because of its low cost and great efficacy [California Department of Pesticide Regulation (CDPR)] (2000-2010) (Grafton-Cardwell *et al.*, 2006). Pyriproxyfen and buprofezin are low toxic on the primary parasitoid of CRS, *Aphytis melinus* DeBach (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae) (Rill *et al.*, 2008), increasing the scale control. Although pyriproxyfen was the primary CRS treatment for more than a decade, its resistance monitoring has not revealed significant levels (Ouyang and Grafton-Cardwell, 2010). Because of the ability of California red scale to develop resistance, it is important to introduce insecticides with alternative modes of action into the treatment regime. So, in this study, some insecticides with different modes of action were tested against the CRS different stages on navel orange trees on October 2018 and October 2019 as *A. aurantii* has two peaks in April and October.

This study aimed to differentiate among the used toxicants (Pyriproxyphen (Admiral), 10% EC; imidacloprid (best), 25% WP; spirotetramat (Movento), 10% SC;

sulfoxaflor (Isoclast), 50% WG and a mineral oil (Kz oil) 95% EC), regarding their reduction of each CRS stage as well as its total population.

Material and methods

1. Treated Insect:

The California Red Scale (CRS), *A. aurantii* as the most spreader, the highest census and the most effective in the treatment region. The all treated insect stages were treated *in situ* on the fruit full navel orange trees in Rashid City, Behira Governorate, Egypt.

2. Tested insecticides:

Five commercial insecticides belong to different chemical groups were tested for their lethality against the treated insect (CRS) different stages. These insecticides were applied at the recommended rates. The tested insecticides common and trade names, formulations, application rates, chemical classes and chemical structures as well as their basic manufacturers are arranged in the following Table (1).

3. Experimental procedure:

Treating the CRS insect stages was carried out on navel fruit full orange host plant trees using the foliar application. The host plant trees were not chemically treated two years before this study. The treatment experiment was designed in randomized complete block design (RCBD). Four host plant trees were taken for each replicate and four replicates were used for each treatment. The navel orange host plant trees were sprayed once with the tested compounds at the application rates (Table 1) using the 20 liter sprinkler machine. Fifty (50) leaves of each replicate were randomly taken directly before spraying (Pre-spraying). The treated

insect (CRS) stages were counted and the infestation limit was determined. This step (Taking 50 leaves of each replicate) was repeated again four times in 2, 4, 6 and 8 weeks after treatment in both treatment and control. These leaves were transferred in paper bags to the laboratory and each stage of the treated insect was individually counted at each time interval. The total studied stage number was calculated. This count and discrimination of each stage alive number were carried out using the stereomicroscope. Counting was repeated four times in each replicate and its mean \pm SD number was considered. The four mean \pm SD numbers of the four replicates were averaged for each treatment. Control was concurrently conducted. The reduction percentage in each studied stage population and the total population number was calculated according to (Henderson and Tilton, 1955) formula.

$$\text{Reduction \%} = 100 [1 - (T_2 / T_1 * C_1 / C_2)]$$

T₂ Population in Treatment after spray

T₁ Population in Treatment before spray

C₁ Population in control before spray

C₂ Population in control after spray

4. Statistical analysis:

The split-plot system in randomized complete block design (RCBD) with five treatments and control, four replicates in each treatment were designed according to Steel and Torrie (1981). The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed, Costat Software version 6.311 (Cohort Soft Ware, 2005) at 0.05 probability level. Effective time that reduces 50% of the treated stage (ET₅₀) value was calculated according to probit analysis (Finney, 1971).

Table (1): The tested insecticides used against the *Aonidiella aurantii* (CRS) insect stages.

Common name (Trade name)	Chemical class	Basic manufacturer	Application rate	Chemical structure
Pyriproxyphen (Admiral) 10% EC	Phenoxyphenylpyridyloxy propyl ether	Sumitomo Chemical Australia Pty Ltd A.B.N. 21 081 096 255	50 ml/ 100 L	
Imidacloprid (Best) 25% WP	Neonicotinoids	El-Helb Pesticides and Chemicals Industries, Egypt	100 gm/ 100 L	
Spirotetramat (Movento) 10% SC	Tetramic acid derivative (Ketoenol)	Bayer Crop Science LP, Research Triangle Park, NC	40 ml/ 100 L	
Sulfoxaflor (Isoclast) 50% WG	Sulfoximines	Dow AgroSciences, LLC, Indianapolis, IN	125 gm/ 100 L	
Mineral oil (Kz oil) 95% EC		Kz Company for Pesticides and Chemical Industries, Kafr-Elzayat, Egypt	1.5 L/ 100 L	

Results and discussion

The tested insecticides killed the treated insect stages differently in a function of the treated insect stage, the insecticide mode of action and the time after treatment. These effects are shown in Tables (2, 3 and 4), from which it could be said that the untreated adult population increased systematically with the time after spraying until 8 weeks in both 2018 and 2019 treatments. The other untreated stages population density was fluctuated through the test period; however, the average total population count was increased from 1193 to 1591 and from 936.5 to 1207 in 2018 and 2019 studies, respectively (Table 2).

Among the tested insecticides, the used mineral oil (Kz oil) was the most effective with lethal effect against the CRS stages increased with increasing the time in

systemic arrangement. It harshly reduced the treated populations from 234.5 to 10.8, from 408.8 to 12.0, from 235.5 to 7.3 and from 394 to 12.3 in case of adult, crawler, 1st instar nymph and the 2nd instar nymph stages, respectively in the 2018 season, comparing with the reduction from 188.3 to 0.75, from 294.8 to 4.0, from 186.8 to 0.8 and from 273.5 to 4.0 in the same arrangement in 2019 experiment.

The average total stages population number was reduced with its treatment from 1272.8 to 42.3 and from 243.3 to 9.5 (Table 2) in the two seasons, respectively. It caused reduction percent increased along the experiment time ranged from 89.0 to 97.1, from 80.4 to 97.3, from 93.3 to 98.1, from 64.4 to 97.1, from 83.5 to 97.5 in case of adult, crawler, 1st instar nymph, 2nd instar

nymph and the total stages population in 2018 test, respectively (Table 3).

In 2019 experiment, it achieved reduction ranges from 91.2 to 99.8, from 80.6 to 98.7, from 94.1 to 99.7, from 68.6 to 98.4 and from 84.9 to 99.2 in the same order in the 2019 experiment (Table 3). Our obtained results agreed with Helmy *et al.* (1991) who proved the sensitivity of *A. aurantii* to Kz oil and the more susceptibility of the nymphal stage than adult females and with Khalil *et al.* (1996) who reported the satisfactory results of Kz oil against different *A. aurantii* (CRS) stages at 2, 4 and 6 weeks after summer spray on balady orange trees. From the obtained results, Kz oil was the most effective emphasizing that the use of oils in crop protection is a good alternative to conventional synthetic insecticides. Oils have good control of some pests and plant pathogens at low doses (1–2%), no resistance in target pathogens, low cost, excellent spreading on leaf surface and low environmental impact. Its relatively identical results in 2018 and 2019 seasons emphasize its similar strong effect.

Imidacloprid (Best) reduced the treated insect stages populations nearly similar in both 2018 and 2019 treatments. Its reduction percent ranges were 77.6 – 87.7, 64.7 – 82.8, 74.8 – 80.9 and 54.0 – 80.1 against adult, crawler, 1st instar and 2nd instar, respectively in 2018 treatment, comparing with 79.9 – 84.4, 72.1 – 87.7, 75.8 – 83.9 and 53.0 – 84.4 in the same arrangement in 2019 treatment emphasizing its toxicity precision. Low fluctuation in its effect with the time after spraying can be referred to the fluctuation in control population or to its weak residual effect. It decreased the total treated insect stages population with 70.7, 82.7, 85.4 and 78.5 in 2018, comparing with 74.9, 85.9, 85.9 and 79.4 in 2019, respectively at 2, 4, 6 and 8 weeks after treatment (Table 3).

These results agreed with Tomlin (2006) as he reported that imidacloprid is designed to be effective by contact or ingestion controlling sucking insects, some chewing insects, including termites, soil insects, and fleas on pets as a systemic insecticide that rapidly translocate through plant tissues following application and it can be applied to crops, soil, and as a seed treatment (Tomlin, 2006). Spirotetramat (Movento) affected the treated insect stages in a function of both treated stage and time after treatment. It killed the treated population exhibiting 82.3 – 92.5, 75.9 – 90.6, 85.5 – 93.4, 57.1 – 86.6 and 78.8 – 92.8 reduction ranges in population of adult, crawler, 1st instar and 2nd instar as well as total population, respectively in 2018 treatment. These values were 87.0 – 94.6, 78.0 – 93.5, 90.7 – 94.8, 59.1 – 89.2 and 80.5 – 94.1, respectively in the same order in 2019 treatment insuring the insecticide effect precision (Table 3). These results agreed with several researchers who proved spirotetramat, a foliar systemic tetracyclic acid insecticide activity against sucking insects as white mites, psyllids, and aphids was registered in California citrus in 2008 (Frank and Lebude, 2011; Jamieson *et al.*, 2010 and Page-Weir *et al.*, 2011). Its unique two-way systemic action (Moving via the phloem and xylem) potentially allows its application at lower water volumes comparing with other foliar insecticides (Bruck *et al.*, 2009). 1st and 2nd instars male and female *A. aurantii* were more susceptible to spirotetramat than early and late 3rd instar females because of reduction in feeding (Forster *et al.*, 1995) as it has limited contact toxicity and its main effect is achieved through ingestion (Bruck *et al.*, 2009). Spirotetramat also reduced the fecundity of California red scale but did not eliminate it (Cruz *et al.*, 2013). Sulfoxaflor (Isoclast) appeared more effective than imidacloprid achieving 83.6 – 92.8, 77.3 – 92.2, 87.3 – 93.7, 59.4 – 88.6 and 80.5 – 93.4

population reduction percent ranges in 2018 treatment, comparing with 88.8 – 96.5, 78.0 – 94.5, 92.4 – 96.4, 64.3 – 90.7 and 82.3 – 95.9 in 2019 treatment in adult, crawler, 1st instar, 2nd instar and total stages population, respectively (Table 3). Pyriproxyphen (Admiral) behaved different from the other tested insecticides as its reduction in the treated adult population was as high as 41.6% at 4 weeks after treatment and decreased after that time. Its effect was multiplied to 97.9, 96.1 and 75.1% against crawler, 1st instar and 2nd instar stages, respectively in 2018 treatment, comparing with 89.7, 97.6 and 76.4 in the same order in 2019 treatment at 8 weeks after treatment. Its low reduction in average total population might be due to its low adult stage population reduction in agreement with Mohamed (2002) who proved the toxicity of admiral pyriproxyfen (Admiral) on CRS (*A. aurantii*). Sulfoxaflor (Isoclast) and spirotetramat (Movento) exceeded the imidacloprid (Best) in its lethal effect against all treated insect stages at all the checked time after treatment in both 2018 and 2019 seasons. Pyriproxyphen (Admiral) behaved different from the other tested insecticides as its mortal effect appeared too low to reach 50% of the treated adult population (As high as 41.6%) at 4 weeks after treatment and decreased after that time. Its lethality was multiplied on the other stages to as maximum as 97.9, 96.1 and 75.1% against crawler, 1st instar and 2nd instar stages, respectively in 2018 treatment, comparing with 89.7, 97.6 and 76.4 in the same order in 2019 treatment at 8 weeks after treatment. Its low reduction effect on total population might be due to the low reduction against the adult stage population. Mohamed (2002) proved the toxicity of Kz oil and admiral (Pyriproxyfen) on *A. aurantii* and proved that Admiral was more effective in summer than spring. The difference among the used insecticides activities against the treated California red scale (CRS), *A.*

aurantii may be due to their different mode of action. KZ oil controls the California red scale (CRS), *A. aurantii* through blocking effect on the respiratory system openings resulting in suffocation effect (Cook *et al.*, 2004 and Martín *et al.*, 2004). In general, oils suffocate the full range of scale developmental stages on leaves or wood more than on fruits because the mature scale seals down their scale cover more securely on the comparatively smooth, uniform fruit surface than leaves or wood. However, imidacloprid (best) acts as a nicotinic acetyl choline receptors (nAChRs) agonist (Kayser *et al.*, 2016). It acts on several types of post-synaptic nicotinic acetylcholine receptors in the nervous system (CNS) (Matsuda and Sattelle, 2005), which are located only within the CNS in insects. Its binding to the nicotinic receptor causes nerve impulses spontaneously discharging at first, followed by the neuron failure to propagate any signal (Sheets, 2001). This binding process is irreversible (Ware and Whitacre, 2004). Sulfoxaflor (Isoclast) has a novel mode of action as a new nAChRs modulating insecticide (Cutler *et al.*, 2013). Bacci *et al.* (2018) added that it binds to nAChR in place of acetylcholine and acts as an allosteric activator of nAChR. Its binding to receptors caused uncontrolled nerve impulses followed by muscle tremors, paralysis and finally death. Sulfoxaflor binds differently from neonicotinoids and so, it causes a high efficacy degree against a wide range of insects including resistant to neo-nicotinoids exhibiting structure activity relationship that are different from other nAChRs agonists such as imidacloprid (Sparks *et al.*, 2013). Sulfoxaflor passes cross-resistance of many pest species because of some monooxygenase as Cytochrome P450 and CYP6G1 are able to degrade some neonicotinoids as imidacloprid, but are incapable of metabolizing sulfoxaflor (Zhu *et al.*, 2011).

Table (2): Effect of the tested insecticides on *Aonidiella aurantii*; shown as mean \pm SD.

Tested Compounds	Season	Treated Stage	Number of the treated insect stages after different times				
			Pre-Spraying	2 weeks	4 weeks	6 weeks	8 weeks
Control	2018	Adult	223.5 \pm 6.61	272.3 \pm 9.74	303.5 \pm 4.8	336.3 \pm 14.8	351.8 \pm 8.58
		Crawler	384.3 \pm 14.80	402.8 \pm 8.77	412.0 \pm 4.99	416.3 \pm 6.02	412.0 \pm 7.40
		1 st instar	226.8 \pm 5.19	429.0 \pm 10.2	367.3 \pm 8.66	383.5 \pm 4.8	375.3 \pm 5.1
		2 nd instar	358.5 \pm 14.6	230.5 \pm 8.10	289.5 \pm 6.40	100.0 \pm 2.9	379.0 \pm 2.50
		Total	1193.0\pm32.03	1334.5\pm21.76	1372.0\pm18.57	1498.0\pm7.04	1591.0\pm11.64
	2019	Adult	184.0 \pm 4.69	233.5 \pm 5.56	253.3 \pm 5.12	278.3 \pm 12.87	300.0 \pm 11.52
		Crawler	292.5 \pm 5.80	308.3 \pm 1.26	318.0 \pm 2.16	304.5 \pm 4.80	299.8 \pm 10.24
		1 st instar	175.5 \pm 3.87	319.5 \pm 3.87	252.3 \pm 5.44	250.5 \pm 2.65	246.0 \pm 5.60
		2 nd instar	284.5 \pm 6.35	195.3 \pm 5.44	247.8 \pm 3.95	82.5 \pm 2.65	254.3 \pm 4.50
		Total	936.5\pm13.92	1061.8\pm9.00	1071.0\pm10.70	1196.0\pm10.6	1207.0\pm20.90
Pyriproxyfen (Admiral)	2018	Adult	225.8 \pm 5.38	194.5 \pm 4.93	189.5 \pm 5.0	211.5 \pm 5.8	222.3 \pm 6.19
		Crawler	384.3 \pm 12.04	119.5 \pm 9.04	41.5 \pm 2.08	9.75 \pm 2.22	8.75 \pm 2.21
		1 st instar	224.5 \pm 4.94	113 \pm 4.43	49.3 \pm 2.75	10.5 \pm 1.73	14.8 \pm 1.71
		2 nd instar	368.0 \pm 9.4	191.8 \pm 9.7	124.3 \pm 3.60	77.5 \pm 3.40	92.3 \pm 2.99
		Total	1202.5\pm19.64	618.3\pm11.64	404.5\pm7.42	309.3\pm9.29	338.0\pm7.12
	2019	Adult	172.5 \pm 4.66	164.0 \pm 6.37	150.5 \pm 1.92	162.0 \pm 2.94	178.5 \pm 4.44
		Crawler	294.8 \pm 5.68	86.0 \pm 4.55	26.0 \pm 2.83	4.8 \pm 2.50	4.0 \pm 1.63
		1 st instar	190.3 \pm 2.99	99.8 \pm 2.99	28.0 \pm 4.83	4.5 \pm 1.29	6.0 \pm 1.63
		2 nd instar	284.0 \pm 4.97	137.8 \pm 4.03	89.0 \pm 1.83	52.0 \pm 3.56	60.0 \pm 2.58
		Total	941.5\pm7.60	487.5\pm14.25	293.5\pm7.60	223.3\pm6.40	248.5\pm7.00
Imidacloprid (Best)	2018	Adult	224.5 \pm 5.69	61.3 \pm 6.1	49.5 \pm 2.65	41.5 \pm 2.1	73.0 \pm 3.65
		Crawler	390.3 \pm 10.87	144.0 \pm 5.16	57.3 \pm 3.30	72.5 \pm 5.80	91.8 \pm 8.34
		1 st instar	225.0 \pm 4.97	81.3 \pm 5.74	75.0 \pm 7.39	77.2 \pm 1.9	94.0 \pm 3.56
		2 nd instar	374.5 \pm 10.5	110.8 \pm 5.9	60.3 \pm 3.59	21.3 \pm 1.7	89.3 \pm 8.30
		Total	1214.3\pm16.58	397.3\pm13.94	242.0\pm11.28	222.0\pm4.24	348.0\pm16.75
	2019	Adult	179.5 \pm 3.70	36.3 \pm 3.30	26.3 \pm 0.96	38.8 \pm 4.35	58.8 \pm 5.91
		Crawler	294.8 \pm 12.12	86.8 \pm 2.75	39.5 \pm 1.29	57.8 \pm 2.87	63.0 \pm 3.65
		1 st instar	178.8 \pm 3.50	52.3 \pm 3.30	46.5 \pm 1.91	52.0 \pm 3.16	60.8 \pm 3.78
		2 nd instar	278.5 \pm 6.81	89.8 \pm 2.22	37.8 \pm 1.71	18.8 \pm 1.71	64.8 \pm 4.99
		Total	931.5\pm21.00	265.0\pm4.90	150.1\pm0.82	167.3\pm6.90	247.3\pm12.60
Spirotetramat (Movento)	2018	Adult	229.8 \pm 5.32	49.5 \pm 3.42	32.0 \pm 2.58	26.0 \pm 3.74	56.0 \pm 2.16
		Crawler	389 \pm 9.89	98.5 \pm 5.57	48.25 \pm 2.5	39.5 \pm 1.29	69.5 \pm 3.7
		1 st instar	230.0 \pm 2.16	39.3 \pm 4.50	32.3 \pm 2.22	25.8 \pm 4.86	55.25 \pm 4.79
		2 nd instar	377.8 \pm 8.99	104.3 \pm 8.6	40.8 \pm 1.50	19.3 \pm 1.7	68.8 \pm 7.80
		Total	1226.5\pm16.90	291.5\pm9.40	153.3\pm5.62	110.5\pm9.26	249.5\pm14.80
	2019	Adult	177.0 \pm 2.58	29.8 \pm 0.96	21.3 \pm 1.71	14.5 \pm 1.29	28.0 \pm 0.82
		Crawler	303.8 \pm 5.62	70.5 \pm 1.29	30.3 \pm 0.96	20.5 \pm 1.29	40.3 \pm 3.78
		1 st instar	180.0 \pm 3.74	29.5 \pm 1.29	17.8 \pm 0.96	13.5 \pm 1.29	23.5 \pm 0.58
		2 nd instar	277.3 \pm 4.92	77.8 \pm 2.75	26.0 \pm 1.41	22.0 \pm 1.83	41.0 \pm 1.41
		Total	938.0\pm14.20	207.5\pm2.60	95.3\pm3.60	70.5\pm2.60	138.8\pm4.50
Sulfoxaflor (Isoclast)	2018	Adult	230.0 \pm 2.94	39.3 \pm 4.86	30.3 \pm 1.98	25.0 \pm 1.83	59.3 \pm 1.71
		Crawler	395.0 \pm 5.72	93.8 \pm 5.44	39.0 \pm 1.83	33.3 \pm 1.71	70.8 \pm 1.71
		1 st instar	228.5 \pm 1.30	37.0 \pm 3.20	28.8 \pm 2.60	24.3 \pm 0.96	48.0 \pm 4.20
		2 nd instar	380.3 \pm 5.30	99.3 \pm 3.10	35.0 \pm 2.90	20.5 \pm 1.30	56.5 \pm 8.7
		Total	1233.8\pm11.33	269.3\pm5.19	133.0\pm7.57	103.0\pm1.41	234.5\pm14.20
	2019	Adult	180.5 \pm 3.0	26.3 \pm 1.71	15.3 \pm 0.96	10.5 \pm 1.29	22.0 \pm 1.41
		Crawler	298.0 \pm 7.62	69.0 \pm 3.16	25.5 \pm 2.38	17.0 \pm 1.41	35.8 \pm 2.22
		1 st instar	183.0 \pm 5.48	25.3 \pm 1.50	13.0 \pm 0.82	9.5 \pm 1.29	16.8 \pm 1.71
		2 nd instar	280.5 \pm 5.80	68.8 \pm 2.22	22.8 \pm 3.30	12.8 \pm 1.26	29.3 \pm 1.71
		Total	942.0\pm17.80	189.3\pm4.90	76.5\pm3.50	49.8\pm1.90	96.0\pm13.6
Mineral oil (Kz oil)	2018	Adult	234.5 \pm 8.74	31.5 \pm 1.91	15.3 \pm 1.26	14.0 \pm 1.83	10.8 \pm 1.71
		Crawler	408.8 \pm 2.63	83.8 \pm 7.14	16.0 \pm 0.82	15.0 \pm 2.16	12.0 \pm 1.41
		1 st instar	235.5 \pm 4.80	29.8 \pm 4.20	21.3 \pm 2.50	11.0 \pm 0.82	7.3 \pm 0.96
		2 nd instar	394.0 \pm 5.60	90.3 \pm 4.60	21.3 \pm 1.70	18.3 \pm 1.50	12.3 \pm 0.96
		Total	1272.8\pm10.81	235.3\pm7.14	73.8\pm6.13	58.3\pm2.99	42.3\pm2.75
	2019	Adult	188.3 \pm 2.75	21.5 \pm 2.08	7.3 \pm 0.96	4.5 \pm 1.29	0.75 \pm 0.96
		Crawler	294.8 \pm 9.91	60.3 \pm 2.99	12.3 \pm 1.71	6.0 \pm 1.83	4.0 \pm 1.83
		1 st instar	186.8 \pm 5.74	20.0 \pm 1.41	5.5 \pm 1.29	3.5 \pm 1.29	0.8 \pm 0.96
		2 nd instar	273.5 \pm 3.11	59.0 \pm 2.94	10.3 \pm 1.50	6.0 \pm 1.41	4.0 \pm 0.82
		Total	943.3\pm12.70	160.8\pm4.10	35.3\pm1.50	20.0\pm3.90	9.5\pm3.00

Table (3): Effect of the tested insecticides on *Aonidiella aurantii* (CRS) different stages; shown as reduction % in population.

Tested insecticide	Season	Treated Stage	Reduction % in different CRS insect stages after different times			
			2 weeks	4 weeks	6 weeks	8 weeks
Pyriproxyfen (Admiral)	2018	Adult	29.2±3.53	37.5±2.41	37.0±4.23	36.1±1.54
		Crawler	70.3±3.10	89.9±0.51	97.7±0.56	97.9±0.57
		1 st instar	73.5±0.43	86.6±0.90	97.3±0.42	96.1±0.48
		2 nd instar	19.0±3.50	57.1±0.57	22.5±1.90	75.7±0.73
		Total	54.0±1.40	70.5±0.73	79.4±0.65	78.8±0.59
	2019	Adult	26.7±2.85	40.6±1.43	41.7±3.49	40.4±3.75
		Crawler	72.0±1.51	91.8±0.91	98.4±0.84	98.7±0.55
		1 st instar	71.2±0.52	88.9±2.04	98.2±0.52	97.6±0.66
		2 nd instar	29.3±2.75	64.1±1.14	36.9±4.55	76.4±1.21
		Total	54.3±0.80	72.6±0.90	81.3±0.70	79.4±0.90
Imidacloprid (Best)	2018	Adult	77.6±2.94	83.8±1.09	87.7±0.96	79.3±0.83
		Crawler	64.7±2.91	86.3±1.24	82.8±2.65	78.1±1.91
		1 st instar	80.9±1.40	79.4±2.30	77.2±1.90	74.8±0.54
		2 nd instar	54.0±1.80	80.1±1.60	79.7±0.79	77.5±0.74
		Total	70.7±1.58	82.7±1.20	85.4±0.86	78.5±0.61
	2019	Adult	84.4±1.71	89.4±0.48	85.7±1.92	79.9±2.37
		Crawler	72.1±1.33	87.7±0.29	81.2±1.39	79.1±1.90
		1 st instar	83.9±1.23	81.9±1.24	79.6±1.78	75.8±1.47
		2 nd instar	53.0±1.00	84.4±0.73	76.7±2.56	74.0±2.34
		Total	74.9±0.70	85.9±0.20	85.9±0.80	79.4±1.30
Spirotetramat (Movento)	2018	Adult	82.3±1.38	89.7±1.06	92.5±1.14	84.5±0.83
		Crawler	75.9±1.31	88.4±0.79	90.6±0.68	83.3±0.77
		1 st instar	91.0±0.90	91.3±0.80	93.4±1.40	85.5±1.60
		2 nd instar	57.1±3.50	86.6±0.69	81.7±1.87	82.9±1.30
		Total	78.8±0.35	89.1±0.49	92.8±0.60	84.8±0.51
	2019	Adult	87.0±1.10	91.3±0.71	94.6±0.50	90.3±0.32
		Crawler	78.0±0.75	90.8±0.30	93.5±0.59	87.0±1.49
		1 st instar	91.0±0.44	93.1±0.63	94.8±0.39	90.7±0.29
		2 nd instar	59.1±0.64	89.2±0.28	72.6±2.87	83.5±0.54
		Total	80.5±0.60	91.1±0.10	94.1±0.20	89.0±0.40
Sulfoxaflor (Isoclast)	2018	Adult	86.0±1.98	90.3±0.67	92.8±0.82	83.6±0.64
		Crawler	77.3±1.73	90.8±0.79	92.2±0.91	83.3±1.53
		1 st instar	91.4±0.85	92.2±0.67	93.7±0.37	87.3±1.40
		2 nd instar	59.4±1.98	88.6±1.01	80.7±0.94	85.9±2.50
		Total	80.5±0.62	90.6±0.60	93.4±0.17	85.7±1.25
	2019	Adult	88.8±1.07	93.9±0.27	96.2±0.45	92.5±0.65
		Crawler	78.0±0.42	92.1±0.57	94.5±0.44	88.3±0.93
		1 st instar	92.4±0.45	95.1±0.40	96.4±0.36	93.5±0.85
		2 nd instar	64.3±1.77	90.7±1.47	84.3±1.67	88.3±0.95
		Total	82.3±0.40	92.9±0.10	95.9±0.20	92.1±1.10
Mineral oil (Kz oil)	2018	Adult	89.0±0.56	95.2±0.25	96.0±0.44	97.1±0.46
		Crawler	80.4±2.0	96.4±0.26	96.6±0.51	97.3±0.34
		1 st instar	93.3±0.97	94.4±0.45	97.2±0.31	98.1±0.30
		2 nd instar	64.4±2.0	93.3±0.76	83.4±1.99	97.1±0.24
		Total	83.5±0.66	95.0±0.43	96.4±0.27	97.5±0.22
	2019	Adult	91.2±1.01	97.2±0.43	98.4±0.45	99.8±0.31
		Crawler	80.6±0.54	96.2±0.45	98.0±0.66	98.7±0.60
		1 st instar	94.1±0.75	97.9±0.62	98.7±0.54	99.7±0.37
		2 nd instar	68.6±1.06	95.7±0.64	92.4±1.76	98.4±0.36
		Total	84.9±0.40	96.7±0.20	98.3±0.40	99.2±0.30

Data are averages of four replicates means± SD Data are comparing with zero% reduction in control

Table (4): Statistical analysis of the tested insecticides effects on *Aonidiella aurantii* (CRS) stages.

Tested insecticide	Season	Treated Stage	ET ₅₀ (Days)	95% Conf. Limit	Slope ±SE	γ ²
Pyriproxyfen (Admiral)	2018	Adult	> 8			
		Crawler	1.27	0.90 – 1.74	2.68 ± 0.18	0.73
		1 st instar	1.04	0.62 - 1.64	2.11 ± 0.15	2.40
		2 nd instar	5.25	4.69 – 5.89	2.72 ± 0.11	15.13
		Total	1.58	0.92 – 2.59	1.26 ± 0.09	0.09
	2019	Adult	> 8			
		Crawler	1.27	0.91 – 1.72	2.90 ± 0.21	0.55
		1 st instar	1.24	0.86 – 1.72	2.60 ± 0.17	1.7
		2 nd instar	4.23	3.68 – 4.86	2.13 ± 0.09	7.12
		Total	1.54	0.90 – 2.50	1.31 ± 0.09	1.61
Imidacloprid (Best)	2018	Adult	0.16	0.006 -2.44	0.81 ± 0.12	0.77
		Crawler	0.43	0.05 – 2.56	0.77 ± 0.094	8.25
		1 st instar	0.06	0.0002 – 5.23	0.70 ± 0.14	0.19
		2 nd instar	1.39	0.80 – 2.31	1.37 ± 0.091	7.89
		Total	0.15	0.014 – 6.01	0.56 ± 0.10	4.02
	2019	Adult	0.05	0.0001 – 6.52	0.69 ± 0.14	0.38
		Crawler	0.43	0.06 – 2.24	0.84 ± 0.10	0.64
		1 st instar	0.003		0.46 ± 0.16	0.37
		2 nd instar	1.70	1.11 – 2.53	1.48 ± 0.09	0.89
		Total	0.25	0.014 – 2.75	0.73 ± 0.10	0.39
Spirotetramat (Movento)	2018	Adult	0.16	0.006 - 2.45	0.81 ± 0.12	0.77
		Crawler	0.42	0.08 -1.77	1.02 ± 0.11	6.94
		1 st instar	5.96	0.0003 – 5.24	0.70 ± 0.14	0.19
		2 nd instar	1.39	0.85 -2.18	1.56 ± 0.10	2.22
		Total	0.35	0.06 – 1.7	1.03 ± 0.12	0.33
	2019	Adult	0.05	0.0007 -6.50	0.69 ± 0.14	0.38
		Crawler	0.46	0.11 – 1.56	1.21 ± 0.12	0.02
		1 st instar	0.002	..	0.43 ± 0.16	0.30
		2 nd instar	1.52	0.99 – 2.27	1.63 ± 0.10	0.62
		Total	0.34	0.05 – 1.58	1.12 ± 0.13	0.12
Sulfoxaflor (Isoclast)	2018	Adult	0.12	0.002 - 2.99	0.76 ± 0.13	0.51
		Crawler	0.47	0.11 – 1.63	1.14 ± 0.12	0.61
		1 st instar	0.02	0.0001 - 27.5	0.58 ± 0.15	0.20
		2 nd instar	1.37	0.85 – 2.10	1.66 ± 0.10	0.67
		Total	0.31	0.04 – 1.69	1.03 ± 0.12	0.35
	2019	Adult	0.07	0.0005 – 3.83	0.84 ± 0.17	0.18
		Crawler	0.54	0.17 – 1.50	1.36 ± 0.13	0.006
		1 st instar	0.006		0.56 ± 0.19	0.18
		2 nd instar	1.13	0.65 – 1.88	1.65 ± 0.11	0.76
		Total	0.36	0.07 – 1.44	1.28 ± 0.15	0.44
Mineral oil (Kz oil)	2018	Adult	0.15	0.007 – 1.78	1.12 ± 0.20	0.18
		Crawler	0.69	0.31 – 1.39	1.99 ± 0.19	2.14
		1 st instar	0.49	0.0001 – 5.33	1.00 ± 0.23	0.59
		2 nd instar	1.45	1.05 – 1.95	2.41 ± 0.13	0.63
		Total	0.52	0.17 – 1.34	1.72 ± 0.19	0.47
	2019	Adult	0.38	0.08 – 1.35	1.85 ± 0.33	0.75
		Crawler	0.87	0.49 – 1.46	2.48 ± 0.24	0.61
		1 st instar	0.22	0.02 – 1.68	1.63 ± 0.41	0.23
		2 nd instar	1.31	0.94 – 1.77	2.74 ± 0.18	0.52
		Total	0.72	0.34 – 1.38	2.36 ± 0.29	0.17

ET₅₀ (Days) is effective time in days for 50% reduction in each stage.

Sparks *et al.* (2013) added that its effect as nAChRs agonist is in a manner distinct from other insecticides acting at nAChRs. Spirotetramat insecticide affects the treated CRS different stages as a phloem-mobile systemic insecticide targeting acetyl-CoA carboxylase interrupting the lipid biosynthesis that reduces the fecundity of sucking insects upon foliar applications (Ke *et al.*, 2010). So it affects all of the treated insect stages nearly similar as a lipid biosynthesis inhibitor. Pyriproxyphen (admiral) was completely different against adult than the other nymphal and crawler stages because of its mode of action as an insect growth regulator (IGR), which is highly active against California red scale (CRS), and is currently the product of choice for abatement efforts. It sterilizes the adults and causes nymphal mortality. It is fairly selective with 12 hours restricted entry interval. It disrupts the molting process through chitin synthesis inhibition. Since this material affects molting, treatment should be made during peak crawler (1st instar) emergence (Cruz *et al.*, 2013). So, this fact explains why its effect was so low against the adult stage comparing with the other treated crawler and nymphal stages.

From the obtained results, Kz oil achieved its effect in systemic arrangement with the time after treatment and its highest effect was continued to 8 weeks after treatment. However, the highest effect was achieved at 6 weeks after treatment in case of the other tested insecticides in both 2018 and 2019 treatments. So the tested insecticides can be arranged according to their effect against the total stages population reduction as Kz oil, sulfoxaflor (Isoclast), spirotetramat (Movento), imidacloprid ((Best) and pyriproxyphen (Admiral), respectively in both treatment seasons. Spirotetramat is an important rotational insecticide with pyriproxyfen for *A. aurantii* control and is an integrated pest management compatible

insecticide, effective in reducing *A. aurantii* stages (Cruz *et al.*, 2013). However, some of IGR have been shown to be non-selective and are not considered to be IPM friendly but may nevertheless be useful when red scale populations are high and out of biological control.

Worth mentioning, the used insecticides had little or no effect against *A. melinus*, the natural enemy of CRS as spirotetramat at 75 ppm had no negative effect on its egg stage. Residues of spirotetramat; pyriproxyfen and imidacloprid on leaves and twigs collected from a treated citrus orchard allowed 61%, 83% and 95%; 20%, 78% and 95% and 30%, 45% and 94% survival of *A. melinus*, during 1, 2 and 3 weeks after treatment, respectively. Sulfoxaflor also shows a trans-laminar activity and is able to protect plant canopy and undersides leaves (Casida, 2018).

Sulfoxaflor binds to insects nAChRs more strongly than to mammals' ones, so it is much less toxic for mammals and man with a low environmental impact and less aggressive against non-target species (Bacci *et al.*, 2018). Sulfoxaflor is classified as non-carcinogenic, non-mutagenic and non-reprotoxic under the European Chemicals Agency (ECHA) classification with no hepatocellular proliferation induction in humans and therefore would not be a human liver carcinogen (LeBaron *et al.*, 2013). It is non-volatile, rapidly absorbed in crop leaves, degradable in a few days in soil, not persistent in water and not transferable to groundwater. Its rapid dissipation with absence of residual toxicity makes isoclast a good partner in IPM programs. However, the binding affinity of imidacloprid at the nicotinic receptors in mammals and other vertebrate groups including birds is much less than in insect nicotinic receptors, which cause its less toxicity against human (Tomizawa and Casida, 2005). The blood-brain barrier in vertebrates blocks access of

imidacloprid to the central nervous system, reducing its toxicity (Sheets, 2001), which improve its ecosystem communication.

In conclusion from this study, it could be summarized that the used insecticide succeeded in population reduction of the California red scale treated stages (adult, crawler, 1st instar nymphs and 2nd instar nymphs as well as against the total population number in different manners according to their different mode of actions. The tested insecticides were found less toxic on mammals, predators and other non-target biota encouraging us to stress on their entrance the insecticides clique against the examined insect.

References

- Abdelrahman, I. (1973):** Toxicity of malathion to California red scale, *Aonidiella aurantii* (Mask.) (Hemiptera: Diaspididae). Australian Journal of Agricultural Research, 24: 111-118.
- Bacci, L.; Convertini, S. and Rossaro, B. (2018):** A review of sulfoxaflor, a derivative of biological acting substances as a class of insecticides with a broad range of action against many insect pests. Journal of Entomological and Acarological Research, 50: 7836.
- Bedford, E.C.G. (1998):** Red scale *Aonidiella aurantii* (Maskell). In: E.C.G. Bedford, M.A. Van den Berg and E.A. De Villiers (eds.), Citrus pests in the Republic of South Africa. Dynamic Ad., Nelspruit, South Africa, 132-134.
- Bilal, A.; Rizwan, M.; Sabir, A. M.; Gogi, M. D.; Farooq, M.A. and Jamal, A. (2020):** Lethal and sublethal effects of clothianidin, imidacloprid and sulfoxaflor on the wheat aphid, *Schizaphis graminum* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and its coccinellid predator, *Coccinella septempunctata*. International Journal of Tropical Insect Science <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42690-020-00212-w>
- Bruck, E.; Elbert, A.; Fischer, R.; Krueger, S.; Kuhnhold, J.; Klueken, A. M.; Nauen, R.; Niebes, J.-F.; Reckmann, U. and Schnorbach, H.-J., et al. (2009):** Movento, an innovative ambimobile insecticide for sucking insect pest control in agriculture: biological profile and field performance. Crop Protection, 28: 838 - 844.
- Carman, G. E. (1977):** Chemical control of scale insects on California citrus. Proc. Int. Soc. Citriculture, 2: 468 - 474.
- Casida, J. E. (2018):** Neonicotinoids and other insect nicotinic receptor competitive modulators: Progress and prospects. Annual Review Entomology, 63: 125 – 144.
- Cohort Soft Ware Inc. (2005):** Costat user's manual, version 6.311. Berkeley, California, USA.
- Cook, J.; Mercurio, P.; Burns, K.A. and Negri, A. (2004):** Testing the ecotoxicology of vegetable versus mineral based lubricating oils: 1. Degradation rates using tropical marine microbes. Environmental Pollution, 129 (2): 165 – 173.
- Cruz, G.; Ouyang, Y. ; Scott, S.; Molto E. and Grafton-Cardwell, E. (2013):** Effects of spirotetramat on *Aonidiella aurantii* (Homoptera: Diaspididae) and Its Parasitoid, *Aphytis melinus* (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae). Journal of Economic Entomology, 106 (5): 2126 - 2134.
- Cutler, P.; Slater, S.; Edmunds, A. J.; Maienfisch, P.; Hall, R. G.; Early, F. G.; Pitterna, T.; Pal, S.; Paul, V. L.; Goodchild, J.; Blacker, M.; Hagmann, L., and Crossthwalte, A.**

- J. (2013):** Investigating the mode of action of sulfoxaflor, a fourth generation neonicotinoids. *Pest Management Science*, 69 (5):607 – 619.
- Finney, D. J. (1971):** Probit Analysis. 3rd edition Cambridge University Press, London; Page: 138.
- Flint, M. L.; Kobbe, B.; Clark, J. K.; Dreistadt, S. H.; Pehrson, J. E.; Flaherty, D. L.; O’Connell, N. V.; Phillips, P. A. and Morse, J. G. (1991):** Integrated pest management for citrus, 2nd ed. University of California, Statewide Integrated Pest Management Project, Division of Agriculture and Natural Resources Publication 3303, Oakland, CA.
- Forster, L. D.; Luck, R. F. and Grafton–Cardwell, E. E. (1995):** Life stages of California red Scale and its parasitoids. University of California, Division of Agriculture and Natural Resources Publication 21529, Oakland, CA.
- Frank, S. D. and Lebude, A. (2011):** Season-long insecticide efficacy for hemlock woolly adelgid, *Adelges tsugae* (Hemiptera: Adelgidae), management in nurseries. *Fla. Entomolog*, 94: 290 - 295.
- Grafton-Cardwell, E. E. (2010):** Current status of citrus IPM in the San Joaquin Valley of California, pp. 1231-1235. *In* Proceedings, International Society of Citriculture, 11th International Citrus Congress, 26-28 October 2008, Wuhan, China.
- Grafton–Cardwell, E. E. and Vehrs, S.L.C. (1995):** Monitoring for organophosphate- and carbamate-resistant armored scale in San Joaquin Valley citrus. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 88: 495 - 504.
- Grafton–Cardwell, E. E.; Lee, J. E.; Stewart, J. R. and Olsen, K. D. (2006):** Role of two insect growth regulators in integrated pest management of citrus scales. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 99: 733 - 744.
- Helmy, E. I.; Zidan, Z. H.; El-Hamaky, M. A.; El-Emry, S. M. and El-Deep, W. (1991):** Efficacy of certain scalicides against *Parlatoria oleae* (Clovee), other scale insects and their parasites on navel orange trees in summer. 4th Arab Cong of Plant Protection, Cairo, 1–5 Dec., 49 – 57.
- Henderson, C. F. and Tilton, E. W. (1955):** Tests with acaricides against the brown wheat mite. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 48: 157-161.
- Jamieson, L. E.; Page–Weir, N. E. M.; Chhagan, A. and Curtis, C. (2010):** The efficacy of insecticides against Australian citrus white fly (*Orchamoplatus citri*). *N. Z. Plant Protection*, 63: 254 - 261.
- Kayser, H.; Lehmann, K.; Gomes, M.; Schleicher, W.; Dotzauer, K.; Morona, M. and Maienfisch, P. (2016):** Binding of imidacloprid thiamethoxam and N-desmethyl-thiamethoxam to nicotinic receptors of *Myzus persicae*: Pharmacological profiling using neo-nicotinoids, natural agonists and antagonists. *Pest Management Science*, 72 (11): 2166 – 2175.
- Ke, S.; Sun, T.; Zhang, Z.; Zhang, Y-N.; Liang, Y.; Wang, K. and Yang, Z. (2010):** Spirodiclofen analogues as potential lipid-biosynthesis inhibitors: a convenient synthesis, biological evaluation and structure activity relationship. *Bulletin of the Korean Chemical Society*, 31 (8): 2315 – 2321.
- Khalil, E. A. O. (1996):** Survey and population studies of some scale insects attacking citrus trees and its

- control in qualyobia and beni-suef governorates. MSc. Thesis, Fac. of Agric., Cairo University.
- LeBaron, M. J.; Geterd, R.; Rasoulpourr, R. J.; Gollappudi, B. B.; Thomas, J.; Murray, J.; Kan, H. L.; Wood, A. J.; Elcombe, C.; Vardy, A. ; Mcewan, J.; Terry, C. and Billington, R.A.F. (2013):** An integrated approach for prospectively invest-igating a mode of action for rodent liver effects. *Toxicology Applied Pharmacology*, 270: 164-173.
- Martín, B.; Varela, J. and Cabaleiro, C. (2004):** Effects of various oils on survival of *Myzus persicae* Sulzer and its transmission of cucumber mosaic virus on pepper. *Journal Horticultural Science Biotechnology*, 79 (6): 855–858.
- Matsuda, K. and Sattelle, D. B. (2005):** Mechanism of selective actions of neonicotin-oids on insect acetylcholine receptors. *New Discoveries in Agrochemicals: American Chemical Society Symposium Series*; Clark, J. M.; Ohkawa, H., III, Eds.; Oxford University Press: Oxford, UK, 172-183.
- Mohamed, A. A. (2002):** Integrated control of scale insects on certain fruit trees. Ph.D Thesis, Fac. of Agric., Al-Azhar University.
- Nel, J. J. C.; Lange, L. de and Ark, H. van (1979):** Resistance of citrus red scale, *Aonidiella aurantii* (Mask.), to insecticides. *J. Entomol. Society South Africa*, 42: 275 - 281.
- Ouyang, Y. and Grafton–Cardwell, E. E. (2010):** Insecticide resistance management of California red scale and citricola scale populations in the San Joaquin Valley of California, pp. 1226-1230. *In* Proceedings International Society of the Citriculture:11th International Citrus Congress, 26-28 October 2008, Wuhan, China.
- Page–Weir, N.E.M.; Jamieson, L. E.; Chhagan, A.; Connolly, P. G. and Curtis, C. (2011):** Efficacy of insecticides against the tomato/potato psyllid (*Bactericera cockerelli*). *N. Z. Plant Protection*, 64: 276-281.
- Quayle, H. J. (1938):** The development of resistance to hydrocyanic acid in certain scale insects. *Hilgardia*, 11: 183 - 210.
- Rill, S. M.; Grafton–Cardwell, E. E. and Morse, J. G. (2008):** Effects of two insect growth regulators and a neonicotinoid on various life stages of *Aphytis melinus* (Hymenoptera: Aphelinidae). *Bio Control*, 53: 579 - 587.
- Sheets, L. P. (2001):** Imidacloprid: A neonicotinid insecticide. *Handbook of Pesticide Toxicology*, 2nd ed.; Krieger, R. I., Ed.; Academic Press: San Diego, CA, 2, Chapter 54, 1123-1130.
- Sorribas, J.; Rodriguez, R. and Garcia-Mari, F. (2010):** Parasitoid competitive displacement and coexistence in citrus agroecosystems: Linking species distribution with climate. *Ecological Applications*, 20: 1101 - 1113.
- Sparks, T. C.; Watson, G. B.; Loso, M. R.; Geng, C.; Babcock, J. M. and Thomas J. D. (2013):** Sulfoxaflor and sulfoximine insecticides: Chemistry, mode of action and basis for efficacy on resistant insects. *Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology*, 107 (1): 1 – 7.
- Steel, R. G. and Torrie, D. (1981):** Principles and procedures of statistics, A biometric approach. 2nd

- ed., Mc Graw Hill International Book Co., Singapore City.
- Tomizawa, M. and Casida, J. E. (2005):** Neonicotinoid insecticide toxicology: mechanisms of selective action. Annual Review Pharmacology Toxicology, 45: 247-268.
- Tomlin, C. D. S. (2006):** The Pesticide Manual, A World Compendium, 14th ed.; British Crop Protection Council: Surry, England, 598 - 599.
- Ware, G. W. and Whitacre, D. M. (2004):** The Pesticide Book; Meister Pro Information Resources: Willoughby, OH, 70-71.
- Zhu, Y. M.; Loso, M. R.; Watson, G. B.; Spark, T.C.; Rogers, R. B.; Huang, J. X.; Gerwick, B. C.; Babcock, J. M.; Kelley, D.; Hegde, V.B.; Nugent, B.M.; Renga, J. M.; Denholm, I.; Gormank, K.; Deboer, G. J.; Hasler, J.; Meade, T. and Thomas, J. D. (2011):** Discovery and characterization of sulfoxaflor, a novel insecticide targeting sap-feeding pests. J. Agriculture Food Chemistry, 59: 2950 - 2957.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Seasonal abundance of true spiders inhabiting perennial shrubs and evergreen herbs

Manal, S. Ismail; Nadia, H. Habashy; Aida, K.F. Iskandar; Marguerite, A. Rizk and Mona, M.A. Ghallab

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received:21 /4 /2021

Accepted:28 / 6 /2021

Keywords

Araneae, diversity indices, foraging guild, habitat structure, herbs, Orman garden, similarity, shrubs and Sørensen Quotient.

Abstract:

The present study was directed towards the habitat of various true spider species inhabiting different ornamental plants. A one-year study was conducted in the Orman garden; two groups of plants were selected, three evergreen herbs and three perennial shrubs. The results revealed that the evergreen herbs received a total of 261 individuals belonged to 21 genera, 25 species of 10 families, while the perennial shrubs received a total of 255 individuals belonged to 20 genera, 23 species of 10 families. Guild structure analysis revealed eight feeding guilds, the active hunting guild (Ambushers) comprised the largest portion (50.2 and 58.2%) followed by the stalkers guild (22.7 and 16.1%) then space weavers (14.5 and 17.2%) of perennial shrubs and evergreen herbs, respectively. Moreover, a survey over different ornamental plants revealed a total of 178 spiders grouped in 13 families belonging to 28 genera and 35 species collected from thirty ornamental plants. Five families contained 93.1% of the total collected spiders; they are Philodromidae, Salticidae, Theridiidae, Thomisidae and Cheiracanthiidae. The results indicated that the interaction of different communities of spider abundance and species richness depends on the type of plant dense vegetation, shade, and humidity; so, a slight difference was observed between the two categories located in the same location.

Introduction

The landscape of the Orman garden is often characterized by a wide range of diverse flowering plants comprising native and exotic plants. The spider diversity is affected by the different vegetation structure of plants; habitat structure is an important factor that influences the diversity, abundance and distribution of spider species (Evans, 1997 and Whitmore *et al.*, 2002).

As the spiders were broadly distributed in high numbers, associated with the food web, they are used as virtuous predictor organisms (Wise, 1995; Willett, 2001 and Foelix, 2011). The abundance and/or composition of spider species were investigated in different agro-ecosystems (Carroll and Hoyt, 1984 and Wisniewska and Prokopy, 1997). In Egypt, the abundance and occurrence of spiders in different vegetation types and habitats were studied in different

Governorates (Ghallab, 2012 and Obuid-Allah *et al.*, 2015). In addition, Hassan *et al.* (2016) assessed the effect of different vegetation in public parks on the seasonal spider populations. Zaki *et al.* (2020) also studied the biodiversity of spiders concerning different vegetation structures. Few studies have compared the spider distribution in different categories of plants such as evergreen herbs, perennial shrubs, succulents, vines, hedges, palms and trees.

The present study aims to focus on the variation in spider's community inhabiting three evergreen herbs and three perennial shrubs of different ecological values. Concerning the relative abundance, species richness, guild composition, Shannon-Wiener index (H'), Simpson index (S), and evenness (e) to quantify the community structures of spiders among three categories of different vegetation types.

Materials and methods

1. Description of the study area and sampling:

The Orman garden consists of highly fertile cultivated land covered with numerous ornamental plants. Two categories of ornamental plants were selected. The first group consists of three evergreen herbs namely, *Ruscus aculeatus* L., *Pelargonium zonal* (Hértier) and *Ocimum basilicum* L., and the second group of three perennial shrubs namely, *Plumbago auriculata* Lam., *Acalypha hoffmannii* Müll and *Dodonaea viscosa* Jacq. Moreover, a survey of the spider community composition and diversity associated with different vegetation foliage was carried out.

The arboreal spiders live on foliage were collected by shaking plants on a sweeping net with a mesh bag. Samples were collected periodically every two weeks from the different host plants for a one-year study extended from January 2020 till the end of December 2020. Collected spiders were kept in glass vials containing 70% ethyl alcohol

and some droplets of glycerine and examined under a stereo-zoom microscope in the laboratory.

2. Identification of spiders:

The adult spiders were identified, as possible, to species. The scientific names of spiders and their classification follow different specialized description keys.

3. Data analysis:

3.1. Spider community: The Shannon-Wiener Index "H'" is one of the most common ecological indexes; it may indicate of community stability under the balance of nature. A higher number of H' indicates a higher number of species, so, it means an increase in diversity. While Simpson Index "S" is a measure of dominance (Nestle *et al.*, 1993).

The two indices were calculated as described by Ludwig and Reynolds (1988):

$$H' = -\sum (n_i / n) \ln (n_i / n) \text{ and } S = \sum (n_i / n)^2$$

Where n_i is the number of individuals belonging to the i^{th} of "S" taxa in the sample and "n" is the total number of individuals in the sample."

3.2. Sørensen quotient of similarity:

To compare the guild composition between microhabitats of the two categories of the ornamental plants (evergreen herbs & perennial shrubs), Sørensen's quotient of similarity (QS) (Sørensen, 1948) was applied to the number of species and individuals of the two group plants. It was used to determine the similarities of spider species composition among the communities. Sørensen's original formula was intended to be applied to presence/absence data, and it is:

$$QS = 2 C / A + B.$$

Where A and B are the number of species in samples A and B, respectively, and C is the number of species shared by the two samples; QS is the quotient of similarity and ranges from 0-1.

3.3. Guild composition: The spiders collected were separate into eight guilds

according to spider's web-building and prey-catching behaviour as described by Uetz *et al.* (1999).

Results and discussion

In the present investigation, the total number of spiders collected was 694 individuals forming at least 42 species belonging to 33 genera that fall into 15 families.

1. Survey of spiders inhabiting three perennial shrubs:

Table (1) showed the abundance numbers and percentage of spiders inhabiting three ornamental shrubs, *P. auriculate*, *Acalypha wilkesiana hoffmannii* Müll (Twisting green acalypha) and *D. viscosa* (Green dodonaea) shrubs. A list of identified collected spiders was presented, a total of 255 spiders were collected; they belonged to 10 families, 20 genera and 23 species. Among the collected spiders, the most abundant families were Philodromidae represented 39.3 and 65.6% in *Plumbago* and *Dodonaea* shrubs, respectively, followed by Salticidae 34.8 and 22.8% in *Acalypha* and *Plumbago*, respectively, then Cheiracanthiidae 30.4% and Theridiidae 19.6 % collected from *Acalypha*. The abundance of adults was the highest in *Plumbago* (38 ♂: 27 ♀) and the lowest recorded in *Dodonaea* (4 ♂: 6 ♀), while juvenile stages were more abundant in *Plumbago* than *Acalypha* and *Dodonaea* recorded 80, 30 and 54 juvenile, respectively.

Of the most abundant species, 5 ranked in the top, *Pulchellodromus glaucinus* (Simon) (89 individuals), *Cheiracanthium isiacum* O.P. (25 individuals), *Thomisus spinifer* (Sundevall) (24 individuals), *Theridion melanostictum* O. P. (24 individuals), *Thyene imperialis* (Rossi). (22 individuals).

2. Survey of spiders inhabiting three evergreen herbs:

Table (2) listed the identified collected spiders inhabiting three herbs, *R. aculeatus*, *P. zonal* and *O. basilicum* and

showed their abundance numbers and percentage. A total of 261 spiders was collected, they could be classified into 10 families, 21 genera and 25 species. Among the collected spiders, the most abundant families were Philodromidae represented 66.2, 35.9 and 31.2% in *Ruscus*, *Pelargonium* and *Ocimum* herbs, respectively, followed by Theridiidae 28.2% collected from *Pelargonium* then Salticidae 22.1% from *Ocimum* then Thomisidae 20.8% and Theridiidae 18.2% collected from *Ocimum*. The abundance of adults was the highest in *Ruscus* (19 ♂: 17 ♀) followed by *Ocimum* (13 ♂: 22 ♀) and the lowest recorded in *Pelargonium* (8 ♂: 5 ♀), while juvenile stages were abundant in *Ruscus* recorded 109 and those collected from *Pelargonium* and *Ocimum* herbs recorded 26 and 42 juvenile, respectively.

The most dominant species were *P. glaucinus* (115 individuals), *Kochiura aulica* (Koch) (19 individuals) *T. melanostictum* (15 individuals), *T. imperialis* (14 individuals), *Plexippus paykulli* (Audouin) (13 individuals), then *T. spinifer* (13 individuals).

Table (1): Spiders inhabiting three different perennial shrubs during a one-year study in Orman garden.

Family names & species	<i>Plumbago</i>			Σ	%	<i>Twisted Acalypha</i>			Σ	%	<i>Dodonaea</i>			Σ	%	Total	%						
	♂	♀	J			♂	♀	J			♂	♀	J										
Philodromidae																							
<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i> (Simon)	1+4s♂	7+2s♀	35	57	39.3		1	2	3	6.5		1	36	42	65.6	89	40						
<i>Philodromus blankei</i>	1s♂	1	4															4	10				
<i>Thanatus</i> sp.		1	1															1	3				
Salticidae (spiderling)			3	33	22.8				16	34.8			8	12.5		3	22.3						
<i>Thyene imperialis</i> Rossi	3+1s♂	2	5					1			2							1s♂	1	6		22	
<i>Thyene</i> sp.		1																				1	
<i>Plexippus paykulli</i> Audouin	1		5					1s♂			1	11										19	
<i>Bianor</i> sp.	1+1s♂	3	2																			7	
<i>Heliophanus</i> sp.	2s♂	1	1																			4	
<i>Hasarius adansoni</i> Audouin	1																					1	
Cheiracunthiidae				7	4.8				14	30.4			4	4	6.3		9.8						
<i>Cheiracunthium isiacum</i> O.P.			7					1s♂			1	12								4	25		
Theridiidae				21	14.5				9	19.6			6	9.4			14.1						
<i>Theridion melanostictum</i> O.P.	3	4	8					2+1s♂			2							1	1+1s♀	1		24	
<i>Theridion</i> sp. ??																		1s♂				1	
<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	2s♂	2						2s♂			2								1			9	
<i>Euryopis episinoides</i> Walckenaer	1s♂		1												2								
Araneidae				2	1.4				1	2.2			1	1	1.6		1.6						
<i>Neoscona</i> sp.			1								1												2
<i>Araneus</i> sp.			1																				1
<i>Larinia</i> sp.													1		1								
Thomisidae				24	16.5				1	2.2			1	1	1.6		10.2						
<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> O.P.	15	3	4					1											1s♂				24
<i>Thomisus onustus</i> Walckenaer			2												2								
Dictynidae, Dictyna sp.	1s♂			1	0.7											1	0.4						
Uloboridae, Uloborus sp.								1	1	2.2			1	1	1.6	2	0.8						
Lycosidae, Trocosa sp.									1	2.2						1	0.4						
Oonopidae, Orchestina sp.													1	1	1.6	1	0.4						
Total of alive individuals	25+13s♂	25+2s♀	80	145		3+5s♂	8	30	46		1+3s♂	5+1s♀	54	64		255							

Table (2): Spiders inhabiting three different evergreen herbs during a one-year study in Orman garden.

Family names & species	<i>Ruscus</i>			Σ	%	<i>Pelargonium</i>			Σ	%	<i>Ocimum</i>			Σ	%	Total	%						
	♂	♀	J			♂	♀	J			♂	♀	J										
Philodromidae																							
<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i> Simon	1+6s♂		78	96	66.2		1	9	14	35.9		2s♀	18	44	31.2	115	51.3						
<i>Philodromus blankei</i>	2s♂		7																				13
<i>Thanatus sp.</i>			2					1s♂				3											
Salticidae (spiderling)																							
<i>Thyene imperialis</i> Rossi		2	4	18	12.4			2	7	17.9	1+1s♂	3	1	17	22.1	4	16.1						
<i>Thyene sp.</i>		1																	1				14
<i>Plexippus paykulli</i> Audouin	1	1	5								1s♀	3							2				2
<i>Bianor sp.</i>		1																		1			13
<i>Heliophanus sp.</i>																		1s♂	2	1			1
<i>Hasarius adansoni</i> Audouin												1											1
<i>Afraflacilla spiniger</i>		1																					1
<i>Salticus scenicus</i>		2														2							
Cheiracanthiidae																							
<i>Cheiracanthium isiacum</i> O.P.	1		3	4	2.6			2	2	5.1			3	3	3.9	9	3.4						
Theridiidae (spiderling)																							
<i>Theridion melanostictum</i> O.P.	1	4	5	18	12.4	1	1		11	28.2		3	1	14	18.2	1	16.5						
<i>Theridion sp. ??</i>	1	1	1								1												4
<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	2							4+1s♂			1	2						3	3+1s♀	2			19
<i>Euryopsis episinooides</i> Walckenaer	3																	1					4
Araneidae, Araneus sp.			1	5	3.4				1	2.6				1	1.3		2.9						
<i>Neoscona sp.</i>	1	1	2								1								1				6
Thomisidae, Thomisus sp. ??																							
<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> O.P.							1	1	2	5.1	4+2s♂	3	2	16	20.8	13	6.9						
<i>Thomisus onustus</i> Walckenaer												2	2			4							
Dictynidae, Dictyna sp.													2	2	2.6	2	0.8						
Gnaphosidae, G ??			1	1	0.7			2	2	5.1						3	1.2						
Oecobiidae, Oecobius navus		1		1	0.7											1	1.2						
Linyphidae																							
<i>Gnathonarium dentatum</i> Wider		2		2	1.4											20.8							
Total of alive individuals	11+8s♂	17♀	109	145		6+2s♂	4+1s♀	26	39		9+4s♂	18+4s♀	42	77		261							

3. Survey of spider of different ornamental plants in Orman Garden:

The survey study revealed the occurrence of spiders inhabiting thirty ornamental plants as shown in Table (3). A total of 178 spiders was collected belonged to 13 families, 28 genera and at least 35 species.

Table (4) summarized the spiders collected from the different ornamental plants; and showed their abundance numbers and percentage. Among the collected spiders, the most abundant families were Thomisidae 24.2%, Salticidae 23% and Theridiidae 23% then Philodromidae 10.7%. The collected males and females totalled 59.6%, (31.5% ♂: 28.1% ♀), while juvenile stages 40.5%. The sex ratio was 1 female: 1.12 male. The most dominant species were *T.spinifer* (35 individuals) followed by *K. aulica* (27 individuals), *P. paykulli* (15 individuals) and *P. glaucinus* (10 individuals).

4. Family richness and generic diversity:

Fifteen families were collected in the present study; the family Salticidae was the dominant family with maximum generic diversity composed of (8 genera 9species), followed by Theridiidae (4g. 7sp.), then

Thomisidae (2g. 4sp.), Araneidae (3g. 3sp.), Philodromidae (3g. 3sp.), Lycosidae (2g. 2sp.), Uloboridae (1g. 2sp.), Linyphiidae (2g. 2sp.) and Dictynidae (2g. 2sp.). The six remaining families Cheiracanthiidae, Gnaphosidae, Oecobiidae, Oxyopidae, Pholcidae and Oonopidae were represented by only a single genus.

5. Rank abundance of spider families:

The abundance of collecting spiders was summarized by families in Table (5). Five families contained 93.1% of the total collected spiders; they are Philodromidae (36.7%), Salticidae (20.2%), Theridiidae (17.3%), Thomisidae (12.5%) and Cheiracanthiidae (6.5%). The greatest number of individuals was found in the family Philodromidae (255 individuals), then family Salticidae which ranked the second (140 individuals), family Theridiidae was the third (120 individuals), followed by family Thomisidae was the fourth (87 individuals) and family Cheiracanthiidae was the fifth (44 individuals). Three species were represented by only one individual, *Orchestina* sp. (Oonopidae), *Oecobius navus* Blackwall (Oecobiidae) and *Pholcus* sp. (Pholcidae).

Table (3): Survey of spiders on the different ornamental plants in Orman garden.

Scientific name of the host plant	Spider family	Scientific name of Spider	Stage			Total	Months by number
			♂	♀	J		
<i>Acalypha macrophylla</i> Müll (Red copperleaf acalypha)	Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium isiacum</i>	1		1	2	6
	Salticidae	<i>Bianor</i> sp.		1	2	3	6
	Salticidae	<i>Thyene imperialis</i> (Rossi)	1			1	1
	Theridiidae	<i>Theridion melanostictum</i>		2		2	7, 9
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch		1		1	1
	Lycosidae	<i>Trochosa</i> sp.			1	1	12
	Uloboridae	<i>Uloborus</i> sp.			1	1	10
<i>Acalypha marginata</i> Müll (Green single acalypha)	Salticidae	<i>Thyene imperialis</i> (Rossi)			1	1	8
	Salticidae	<i>Plexippus</i> sp.			1	1	8
	Salticidae	<i>Heliphanus</i> sp.			1	1	9
<i>Ageratum mexicanum</i> Müll	Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium</i> sp.			1	1	6
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	1			1	3
	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	6	1		7	3 to 7

Table (3): Continue

Scientific name of the host plant	Spider family	Scientific name of Spider	Stage			Total	Months by number
			♂	♀	J		
<i>Alocasia macrorrhiza</i> (L.)	Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.			1	1	6
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	1s♂		1	2	6
<i>Alyssum maritimum</i> (L.)	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	1s♂			1	6
<i>Bougainvillea glabra</i> Chois.	Theridiidae	<i>Steatoda paykulliana</i> Walck.		1		1	6
<i>Canna indica</i> L.	Salticidae	<i>Afraflacilla spiniger</i> (Pick.)		1		1	10
	Salticidae	<i>Plexippus</i> sp.			1	1	10
	Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.			1	1	11
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	1s♂		1	2	12
<i>Catharanthus rosens</i> (L.) (= <i>Vinca rosea</i>)	Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.			1	1	8
	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)		1		1	5
<i>Casuarina</i> sp.	Salticidae	<i>Heliphanus</i> sp.			1	1	11
	Salticidae	<i>Salticus scenicus</i> (Clerck)			1	1	11
	Philodromidae	<i>Thanatus</i> sp.			1	1	12
<i>Chamomile nobile</i> (L.)	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus</i> sp.	1s♂	2s♀		3	4
<i>Chrysanthemum cornaria</i> (L.)	Dictynidae	<i>Nigma</i> sp.	1	1		2	12
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	1s♂	1	1	3	12
	Philodromidae	<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i>	1			1	12
	Philodromidae	<i>Thanatus</i> sp.			1	1	12
	Salticidae	<i>Plexippus</i> sp.			2	2	12
	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	2			2	12
<i>Clerodendron splendens</i>	Pholcidae	<i>Pholcus</i> sp.		1		1	10
	Theridiidae	<i>Euryopsis episinoides</i>	1			1	10
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch		1		1	7
	Philodromidae	<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i>	2s♂		3	5	7,12
	Gnaphosidae	G ?			2	2	12
<i>Cordyline terminalis</i> Kunth	Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium</i> sp.			2	2	9
	Philodromidae	<i>Thanatus</i> sp.			1	1	9
	Salticidae	<i>Plexippus</i> sp.			1	1	8
	Salticidae	<i>Thyene imperialis</i> (Rossi)		1	1	2	10
	Theridiidae	<i>Theridion</i> sp.			1	1	10
	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	3	1		4	8,9,11,12
<i>Crinum asiaticum</i> L.	Salticidae	<i>Heliphanus</i> sp.		1		1	10
	Salticidae	<i>Plexippus</i> sp.			2	2	8,9
	Salticidae	<i>Hasarius adansoni</i> (Aud.)		1	1	2	8
	Philodromidae	<i>Philodromus</i> sp.			2	2	10
	Salticidae	<i>Thyene imperialis</i> (Rossi)			1	1	10
	Lycosidae	<i>Pardosa</i> sp.			1	1	8
	Uloboridae	<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas			1	1	10
<i>Cycas revolute</i> Thunb.	Salticidae	<i>Heliphanus</i> sp.		1		1	6
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch		1s♀		1	7
<i>Dimorphotheca ecklonis</i>	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	1			1	8
	Uloboridae	<i>Uloborus walckenaerius</i> Lat.		1		1	4
	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	1			1	4
	Philodromidae	<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i>			1	1	5
	Oxyopidae	<i>Oxyopies bilineatus</i> O.P.			1	1	5

Table (3): Continue

Scientific name of the host plant	Spider family	Scientific name of Spider	Stage			Total	Months by number
			♂	♀	J		
<i>Dombeya burgessiae</i>	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	2			2	5
	Salticidae	<i>Plexippus paykulli</i> Audouin		1	2	3	7
	Salticidae	<i>Bianor</i> sp.	1			1	1
	Theridiidae	<i>Steatoda erigoniformis</i> Sund	1			1	9
<i>Gerbera jamesonii</i> Bolus	Lycosidae	<i>Pardosa inopina</i> (Pickard)	1			1	3
	Aranaeidae	G ?			1	1	12
	Salticidae	<i>Thyene</i> sp.			1	1	12
	Theridiidae	<i>Theridion</i> sp.			1	1	12
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	1			1	4
	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	1		1	2	4
	Thomisidae	<i>Runcinia grammica</i> (Koch)	1			1	3
<i>Helichrysum bracteatum</i>	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	2+1s♂			3	4, 5
	Philodromidae	<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i>		1		1	4
<i>Jasminum multiflorum</i>	Aranaeidae	<i>Araneus</i> sp.		1		1	5
	Dictynidae	<i>Nigma</i> sp.		1		1	6
	Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium</i> sp.			2	2	11
	Gnaphosidae	G ?			1	1	10
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	1			1	5
	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	1			1	10
	Oxyopidae	<i>Oxyopides bilineatus</i> O.P.			1	1	11
<i>Jasminum sambac</i> (L)	Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiracanthium</i> sp.			3	3	10, 11
	Salticidae	<i>Hasarius adansoni</i> (Aud.)		1	1	2	8
	Salticidae	<i>Ballus</i> sp.			1	1	11
	Salticidae	<i>Plexippus</i> sp.			2	2	8, 9
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	1	1		2	8
<i>Matricaria chamomilla</i> L.	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	1	2		3	4
<i>Petunia axillaris</i> (Lam.)	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	1			1	6
	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	1	2		3	4
	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus</i> sp.	1s♂	1s♀	1	3	6
<i>Pinus halepensis</i>	Philodromidae	<i>Thanatus albini</i> (Audouin)			1	1	11
	Salticidae	<i>Plexippus paykulli</i> (Audouin)	1s♂			1	11
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch		1		1	11
<i>PLumbago</i>	Philodromidae	<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i>	1	1		2	2
	Salticidae	<i>Heliphanus</i> sp.	1			1	2
	Aranaeidae	<i>Araneus</i> sp.			1	1	1
<i>Salvia splendens</i> Sell.	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)	1			1	5
	Dictynidae	<i>Nigma</i> sp.		1		1	5
	Linyphiidae	<i>Sengletus extricates</i>		1		1	5
<i>Severina monophylla</i> (L)	Theridiidae	<i>Theridion spinitrise</i>	1			1	8
	Theridiidae	<i>Theridion melanostictum</i>	1			1	7
	Aranaeidae	<i>Neoscona</i> sp.		1		1	7
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i>		1		1	8
	Uloboridae	<i>Uloborus walckenaerius</i>		1	1	2	11
<i>Tagetes crecta</i> L.	Theridiidae	<i>Theridion melanostictum</i>	1			1	9
	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i>		1	1	2	5
<i>Thuja orientalis</i>	Theridiidae	<i>Theridion</i> sp.		1	3	4	11, 12
	Salticidae	<i>Plexippus</i> sp.			2	2	11, 12
	Salticidae	<i>Thyene</i> sp.			2	2	11, 12
	Salticidae	<i>Hasarius adansoni</i>	1			1	11
	Theridiidae	<i>Kochiura aulica</i>	4	5	1	10	12
	Lycosidae	<i>Pardosa</i> sp.			1	1	12
<i>Viola tricolor</i> L.	Thomisidae	<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> (Sund.)		1		1	3
Total			56	50	72	178	

Table (4): Spiders collected randomly from the different ornamental plants.

Family names & species	Spider stages			Σ	Total	%
	♂	♀	J			
Philodromidae , <i>Thanatus</i> sp.			4	4		
<i>Pulchellodromus glaucinus</i> (Sim.)	4	3	3	10	19	10.7
<i>Philodromus</i> sp.			5	5		
Salticidae						
<i>Thyene imperialis</i> Rossi	1	1	3	5		
<i>Thyene</i> sp.			3	3		
<i>Plexippus paykulli</i> Audouin	1	1	13	15		
<i>Ballus</i> sp.	1		1	2	41	23
<i>Bianor</i> sp.	1	1	2	4		
<i>Heliophanus</i> sp.	1	2	2	5		
<i>Hasarius adansoni</i> Audouin	1	2	2	5		
<i>Afraflacilla spiniger</i>		1		1		
<i>Salticus scenicus</i>			1	1		
Cheiracanthiidae						
<i>Cheiracanthium isiacum</i> O.P.	1		1	2	10	5.6
<i>Cheiracanthium</i> sp.			8	8		
Theridiidae (spiderling)			2	2		
<i>Theridion melanostictum</i> O.P.	2	2		4		
<i>Theridion spinitrax</i>	1			1		
<i>Theridion</i> sp. ??		1	3	4	41	23
<i>Kochiura aulica</i> Koch	11	12	4	27		
<i>Euryopis episinoides</i> (Walckenaer)	1			1		
<i>Steatoda paykulliana</i>		1		1		
<i>Steatoda erigoniformis</i>	1			1		
Araneidae			1	1		
<i>Neoscona</i> sp.		1		1	4	2.2
<i>Araneus</i> sp.		1	1	2		
Thomisidae						
<i>Thomisus spinifer</i> O.P.	24	9	2	35		
<i>Thomisus onustus</i> (Walckenaer)		1		1	43	24.2
<i>Thomisus</i> sp. ??	2	3	1	6		
<i>Runcinia grammica</i> (Koch)	1			1		
Dictynidae						
<i>Nigma</i> sp.	1	3		4	4	2.2
Gnaphosidae , G ??			3	3	3	1.7
Lycosidae , <i>Trocosa</i> sp.			1	1		
<i>Pardosa inopina</i>	1			1	4	2.2
<i>Pardosa</i> sp.			2	2		
Uloboridae , <i>Uloborus</i> sp.			1	1		
<i>Uloborus walckenaerius</i> Latreille		2	1	3	5	2.8
<i>Uloborus plumipes</i> Lucas			1	1		
Linyphidae , <i>Sengletus extricates</i>		1		1	1	0.6
Oxyopidae						
<i>Oxyopis bilineatus</i> O.P.		1	1	2	2	1.1
Pholcidae , <i>Pholcus</i> sp.		1	0	1	1	0.6
Total of alive individuals	56	50	72	178	178	

Table (5): Rank abundance of spider families associated with the different vegetation structure.

Family names	Spiders of perennial shrubs	Spiders of evergreen herbs	Spiders of different vegetation	Total	%
Philodromidae	102	134	19	255	36.7
Salticidae	57	42	41	140	20.2
Cheiracanthiidae	25	9	10	44	6.5
Theridiidae	36	43	41	120	17.3
Araneidae	4	7	4	15	2.2
Thomisidae	26	18	43	87	12.5
Dictynidae	1	2	4	7	1.01
Uloboridae	2	-	5	7	1.01
Lycosidae	1	-	4	5	0.7
Oonopidae	1	-	-	1	0.14
Gnaphosidae	-	3	3	6	0.9
Linyphidae	-	2	1	3	0.4
Oecobiidae	-	1	-	1	0.14
Oxyopidae	-	-	2	2	0.3
Pholcidae	-	-	1	1	0.14
Total	255	261	178	694	

6. Species richness:

Among the 41 species of spiders collected during the study, 23 species of 10 families were recorded on perennial shrubs and 25 species of 10 families on evergreen herbs; while the spiders of different vegetation (survey) were at least 35 species of 13 families. Most of the families were presented on the three selected categories of vegetation except Oonopidae were unique in shrubs, Oecobiidae in herbs while Oxyopidae and Pholcidae were unique in the spider survey. A total of 25 species had a common occurrence in the three categories mentioned before. The dominant species were *P. glaucinus* represented by 89, 115 and 19 individuals in shrubs, herbs and survey, respectively. Followed by *T. spinifer* of 35, 24 and 13 individuals in survey, shrubs and herbs, respectively. Then *T. melanostictum* of 24, 15 and 4 in shrubs, herbs and survey, respectively. Then *K. aulica* of 27, 19 and 9 individuals in survey, herbs and shrubs, finally, *C. isiacum* recorded 25, 9 and 10 in shrubs, herbs and survey, respectively.

7. Spider guild composition:

The Ambusher spider guild was the dominant on the three categories representing

50.2, 58.2 and 34.8% in shrubs, herbs and different vegetation, respectively, and had the highest species richness, followed by the space weavers and stalkers 25.3 and 24.2% in different vegetation, then stalkers in shrubs of 22.7% and the space weavers of 17.2% in herbs as shown in Table (6). A total of 25 species were common, the most of them was 8 species of family Salticidae, and 4 species of family Theridiidae; while the unique species were two species *Orchestina* sp. (Oonopidae) and *Larinia* sp. (Araneidae) collected from the perennial shrubs and two species, *Gnathonarium dentatum* Wider (Linyphidae) and *O. navus* (Oecobiidae) collected from the evergreen herbs and twelve species collected from different vegetation three of them off family Theridiidae.

8. Faunal similarity of spiders:

In Table (6), the species richness of spiders collected from shrubs was (255 individuals) and that of herbs was (261 individuals). While, the number of spider species of shrubs was (23 species) and that of herbs was (25 species). Among the 29 genera obtained (In shrubs and herbs), only 4 were distributed in shrubs and 6 in herbs, whereas

the common genera were 19. To allow a comparison between the habitats of the two categories, the QS was calculated. It is concluded that community of shrubs and that of herbs have a high overlap as they recorded 80% of similarity. By comparing the community of shrubs and that of different vegetation, among the 31 genera obtained; only 5 were distributed in shrubs and 17 in the different vegetation, whereas the common genera were 18 species. By calculating the QS, the two communities were semi-similar as they recorded 60% of similarity. By comparing the two communities of the herbs and the different vegetation, 31 genera were obtained; 4 species were distributed in the herbs only and 14 in the different vegetation, while the common genera were 21 species. By calculating the QS, the community of vegetation and herbs have a high similarity as they recorded 70%.

9. Spider's diversity:

Table (7) showed the comparison of the biodiversity of spider species in the different communities. The biodiversity index calculation indicated that the different vegetation of survey is the most diverse recorded the value (1.9), the bigger number is more diverse, and its species richness of spiders in different families were higher and evenness recorded (0.73); followed by spiders diversity in perennial shrubs (1.5) and species evenness (0.65). According to Simpson Index, it was found that diversity of spiders in evergreen herbs included the highest number of dominant species (0.33).

About 204 genera, 41 families reported from Egypt, so far (El-Hennawy, 2017), in this study, 41 species, 33 genera of 15 families were recorded from the Orman Garden. These 15 families represent 36.6% of the total families recorded in Egypt. The high species diversity of spiders collected from the survey of different ornamental plants (28 g. and 35 sp.) can be attributed to

the high diversity of plants (30 host plants). The presence of diverse habitats like grassland, shrubs, herbs, trees, and palms in this ecosystem are further evidence of this. Diversity generally increases when a greater variety of habitat types are present (Ried and Miller 1989; Sudhikumar *et al.*, 2005; Habashy *et al.*, 2005 and Ghallab, 2012).

In the perennial shrub category, the most frequent families were Philodromidae (40%), followed by Salticidae (22.3%), Theridiidae (14.1%), then Thomisidae and Cheiracanthidae (10.2 and 9.8%), respectively; the least frequent were Dytinidae, Uloboridae and Lycosidae (0.4% each); Araneidae was absent. In the evergreen category, Philodromidae was also the dominant (51.3%) followed by Theridiidae (16.5%), Salticidae (16.1%) then Thomisidae (6.9%); Dytinidae and Linyphiidae were the lowest (0.8% each). In the spider survey collected from different vegetation, family Thomisidae was the most abundant (24.2%) followed by Salticidae and Theridiidae (23% each) then Philodromidae (10.7%); the least frequent were Linyphiidae, Oxyopidae, Gnaphosidae (0.6, 1.1 and 1.7%), respectively.

When spiders divided according to their functional groups there was a great effect of habitat on the diversity of these groups. Simberloff and Dayan (1991) cited that guilds are useful in the comparative study of different communities which enable to concentrate on specific groups with specific functional relationships. Guild structure varied considerably concerning the structural quality of vegetation. The hunting spiders or the ambushers were the prepotent feeding guilds; this was in accordance with Masson *et al.* (1997) who found that family Philodromidae was the most abundant spiders in the foliage of Western and Midwestern coniferous trees. It comprised 7 species of spiders of two families Philodromidae (3sp.) and Thomisidae (4sp.),

followed by the stalkers guild comprised 11 species of spiders belonging to three families Salticidae (9sp.), Oxyopidae (1sp.) and Oonopidae (1sp.). This group of spiders of considerable interest to pest manager of high polyphagous has a functional response to certain numerous preys (Nyffeler *et al.*, 1994). Then families of the web building group (space weavers) comprised 9 species of spiders of two families Theridiidae (7sp.) and Dictynidae (2sp.).

Also, the evergreen herbs appeared to be suitable sites for ambusher spiders; this observation is in conformity with that of (Evans, 1977; Nentwig, 1993; De Souza and Martins, 2004 and Souza and Módena, 2004) where they found that crab spiders preferred the plant species with minor leaves and that the ambushers were anticipated in high frequency in flowering branches as spiders of the Thomisidae family were characteristic of inflorescences. This result showed the responses of spider abundances to different structural vegetation.

Foliage runners showed that only one species found in the study area (*Cheiracanthium isiacum*) of activity density 9.8% on perennial shrubs compared to evergreen herbs 3.4% and spiders of survey 5.6%. De Souza and Martins (2005) found that the foliage-runners constituted the dominant guild on the plant which have few branches as well as density of leaves per

branch be strongly related to number of spiders. This data was in accordance with Hassan *et al.* (2016) who showed that *C. isiacum* was dominant in most plants in the Orman garden. Similarly, Sallam *et al.* (2010) demonstrated that the most frequent spider species associated with a field of cotton and maize plants were *C. isiacum* and *T. imperialis* of relatively frequent occurrence 20.45 and 12.5%, respectively.

Numerous workers have detailed the strong relationship between vegetation structure and the composition of spider communities (Wise, 1995 and Habashy *et al.* 2005). Consequently, it was expected that the diversity of spiders and the species composition of the dominant spiders in shrubs and herbs could reflect the different communities' ecological value when that value is defined by an index of quality integrating the vegetation architecture. The structure of vegetation and microclimatic conditions are important factors determining the composition and distribution of spiders (Uetz, 1999 and Ziesche and Roth, 2008).

The results indicated that the interaction of different communities of spider abundance, population fluctuation of spiders showed a slight difference between the two categories located in the same location.

Table (6): The functional groups of spiders to obtain their preys.

Foraging guild	Spiders of perennial shrubs			%	Spiders of evergreen herbs			%	Spiders of different vegetation			%	Common species	Total
	Sp. richness	No. of Sp.	Unique sp.		Sp. richness	No. of Sp.	Unique sp.		Sp. richness	No. of Sp.	Unique sp.			
Ambushers														
Philodromidae	102	3	-	50.2	134	3	-	58.2	19	3	-	34.8	3	3
Thomisidae	26	2	-		18	3	-		43	4	1		3	4
Foliage runners														
Cheiracanthiidae	25	1	-	9.8	9	1	-	3.4	10	1	-	5.6	1	1
Ground runners														
Lycosidae	1	1	-	0.4	-	-	-		4	2	1	3.9	1	2
Gnaphosidae	-	-	-		3	1	-	1.2	3	1	-		1	1
Stalkers														
Salticidae	57	6	-		42	8	-		41	9	1		8	9
Oxyopidae	-	-	-	22.7	-	-	-	16.1	2	1	1	24.2	-	1
Oonopidae	1	1	1		-	-	-		-	-	-		-	1
Orb weavers														
Araneidae	4	3	1	2.4	7	2	-	2.7	4	2	-	5.1	2	3
Uloboridae	2	1	-		-	-	-		5	2	2		1	3
Space weavers														
Theridiidae	36	4	-	14.5	43	4	-	17.2	41	7	3	25.3	4	7
Dictynidae	1	1	-		2	1	-		4	1	1		1	2
Sheet-web- builders														
Linyphiidae	-	-	-	--	2	1	1	1.2	1	1	1	0.6	-	2
Oecobiidae	-	-	-		1	1	1		-	-	-		-	1
Scattered-line-weavers														
Pholcidae	-	-	-	--	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	0.6	-	1
Total	255	23	2		261	25	2		178	35	12		25	41

Table (7): Comparison of the biodiversity of spider species in the different communities.

Type of Index	Spiders diversity in perennial shrubs	Spiders diversity in evergreen herbs	Spiders diversity in different vegetation
Shannon–Wiener (H')	1.5	1.4	1.9
Species evenness	0.65	0.61	0.73
Simpson Index (S)	0.26	0.33	0.28

Acknowledgement

The authors express their sincere gratitude to Mr. Hisham K. EL-Hennawy, Specialist (Spiders and scorpions) for revising the identification of spiders.

References

- Carroll, D.P. and Hoyt, S.C. (1984):** Natural enemies and their effects on apple aphid *Aphis pomi* Degeer (Homoptera: Aphididae), colonies on young apple trees in central Washington. *Environmental Entomology*, 13:469-481.
- De Souza, A.L.T. and Martins, R.P. (2004):** Distribution of plant-dwelling spiders: Inflorescences versus vegetative branches. *Austral Ecology*, 29 (6): 342-349.
- De Souza, A.L.T. and Martins, R.P. (2005):** Foliage density of branches and distribution of plant-dwelling spiders. *Biotropica: The Journal of Biology and Conservation*, 37(3):416-420.
- El-Hennawy, H.K. (2017):** A list of Egyptian spiders (Revised in 2017). *Serket*, 15(4): 167-183.
- Evans, T.A. (1997):** Distribution of social crab spiders in eucalypt forests. *Australian Journal of Ecology*, 22(1):107–111.
- Foelix, R. (2011):** Biology of spiders. Oxford University Press, New York.
- Ghallab, M.M.A. (2012):** Preliminary study of the spiders inhabiting ornamental plants in Orman Garden Egypt (Arachnida: Araneae). *Serket*, 13(1/2):169-181.
- Habashy, N.H.; Ghallab, M.M.A. and Rizk, M. A. (2005):** Spider populations associated with different types of cultivation and different crops in Fayoum Governorate, Egypt. *Serket*, 9 (3):101-107.
- Hassan, M.F.; El-Bishlawy, S.M.O.; Sallam, G.M. and Sawers, M.A. (2016):** Incidence of spiders in Parks at Cairo and Giza Governorates, Egypt. *Acarines*, 10:81-87.
- Ludwig, J.A. and Reynolds, J.F. (1988):** *Statistical Ecology: A primer on methods in computing*. New-York, John Wiley and Sons, pp. 337.
- Masson, R.R.; Jennings, D.T.; Paul, H.G. and Wickman, B.E. (1997):** Patterns of spider (Araneae) abundance during an outbreak of Western spruce budworm (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae). *Environmental Entomology*, 26 (3): 507-518.
- Nentwig, W. (1993):** Spiders of Panama: Biogeography, investigation, phenology, check list, key and bibliography of a tropical spider fauna. (Fauna and Flora Handbook, no. 12. Gainesville, USA: Sandhill Crane Press. pp. 247).
- Nestle, D.; Dickschen, F. and Altieri, M.A. (1993):** Diversity patterns of soil macro-Coleoptera in Mexican shaded and unshaded coffee agro-ecosystems: an indication of habitat

- perturbation. Biodiversity and conservation, 2(1): 70-78.
- Nyffeler, M.; Dean, D.A. and Sterling, W.L. (1994):** How spiders make a living environment. Entomology, 23:1357-1367.
- Obuid-Allah, A.H.; Mahmoud, A. A. and Hussien E.H. (2015):** A Key for identification of spiders at Qena Governorate, Upper Egypt. American Journal of Life Sciences, 3(6-1): 13-23.
- Ried, W.V. and Miller, K.R. (1989):** Keeping options alive: A scientific basis for conserving biodiversity. Washington D.C. World Resources Institute.
- Sallam, M.E.G.; Abdel Azeim, N. and El-Kawas, H.M.G. (2010):** Biodiversity of spiders associated with cotton and maize in Sharkia governorate with a special reference to spider *kochiura aulica* Koch. Acarines, 4(1):67-71.
- Simberloff, D. and Dayan, T. (1991):** The guild concept and the structure of ecological communities. Annual Review of Ecology and Systematics, 22:115-143.
- Sørensen, T. (1948):** A method of establishing groups of equal amplitude in plant sociology based on similarity of species and its application to analyses of the vegetation on Danish commons. Biologiske Skrifter/Kongelige Danske Videnskabernes Selskab, 5:1-34.
- Souza, A.L.T. and Módena, É S. (2004):** Distribution of spiders on different types of inflorescences in the Brazilian Pantanal. The Journal of Arachnology, 32 (2):345-348.
- Sudhikumar, A.V.; Mathew, M.J.; Sunish, E.; Murugesan, S. and Sebastian, P.A. (2005):** Preliminary studies on the spider fauna in Mannavan shola forest, Kerala, India (Araneae). European Arachnology Supplement, 1:319-327.
- Uetz, G.W.; Halaj, J. and Cady, A.B. (1999):** Guild structure of spiders in major crops. Journal of Arachnology, 27(1):270-280.
- Whitmore, C.; Slotow, R.; Crouch, T.E. and Dippenaar-Schoeman, A.S. (2002):** Diversity of spiders (Araneae) in a savanna reserve, Northern Province, South Africa. Journal of Arachnology, 30:344-356.
- Willett, T. R. (2001):** Spiders and other arthropods as indicators in old growth versus logged redwood stands. Restoration Ecology, 9:410-420.
- Wise, D. H. (1995):** Spiders in Ecological Webs. Cambridge University Press.
- Wisniewska, J. and Prokopy, R.J. (1997):** Pesticide effect on faunal composition, abundance, and body length of spiders (Araneae) in apple orchards. Environmental Entomology, 26(4):763-776.
- Zaki, A.Y.; Ghallab, M.M.A.; Iskandar, A. K.F. and Rizk, M. A. (2020):** Spider biodiversity in connection with the vegetation structure and its surrounding soil. Egyptian Journal of Plant Protection Research Institute, 3(4):1169-1182.
- Ziesche, T.M. and Roth. M. (2008):** Influence of environmental parameters on the small-scale distribution of soil-dwelling spiders in forests: What makes the difference, tree species or microhabitat?. Forest Ecology Management, 255(3-4):738-752.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejprii.eg.net

Dissipation of chlorpyrifos-methyl and lufenuron in and on tomato fruits infested with the cotton leafworm *Spodoptera littoralis* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) under the field conditions

Hanim, M. Soliman¹ and Yasmin, A. Fergani²

¹*Pesticide Residues and Environmental Pollution Department, Agriculture Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.*

²*Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.*

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 23 /4/2021

Accepted: 3/ 6 /2021

Keywords

Tomato, chlorpyrifos-methyl, lufenuron, dissipation, QuEChERS and *Spodoptera littoralis*.

Abstract:

Organophosphates and IGR have captured the popular choice among other groups of insecticides being used against the Egyptian cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), in Egypt. This study was designed to estimate the residue levels of two insecticides belonging to two different groups with different modes of action, chlorpyrifos-methyl and lufenuron in/on tomato fruits infested with *S. littoralis* in the field. The experiment was designed in randomized block design. Samples of tomatoes were randomly collected from treated and un-treated plants after a time interval of zero time, 1, 3, 7, 10, and 15 days for both insecticides. The technique was validated for chlorpyrifos-methyl and lufenuron at different fortification levels (0.01, 0.5, and 0.1 µg/kg) in/on tomato fruits. The mean recoveries were from 90% to 111%. The insecticide residues extracted by an optimized QuEChERS coupled with the gas chromatographic analysis technique (GC) in the case of chlorpyrifos-methyl, and the high-performance liquid chromatographic (HPLC) analysis combined with diode array detection for lufenuron. HPLC and GC analytical systems were characterized by high accuracy and acceptable sensitivity to meet the requirements for monitoring insecticides in/on local tomato cultivation. Under the optimized condition, the residues in/on tomato fruits were below the codex maximum residue limit (MRL) (1 and 0.4 mg/kg) after pre-harvest intervals (PHI) were 3 and 8 for chlorpyrifos-methyl and lufenuron, respectively. The limit of quantitation and detection for chlorpyrifos-methyl were 0.1 and 0.02 while for lufenuron were 0.01 and 0.003 mg/kg, respectively. The results suggest that the chlorpyrifos-methyl and lufenuron dissipation curves followed the first-order kinetics and its half-life values were 1.03 and 1.50 days, respectively.

Introduction

Nowadays, the cultivation of tomato fruits is widespread around the world and cultivated over a large area in Egypt. Tomato production is one of the most economic industries due to their nutritional content, either used as a fresh product or canned for later use (El-Nabarawy and Abou-Dania, 1992). Tomato cultivation was obstructed by many pests. The Egyptian cotton leafworm, *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) proved to be the most important pest destructing Tomato fruit fields in Egypt. The use of chemical pesticides such as organophosphorus (Ops) and insect growth regulators insecticides in/on tomato fruits agriculture is still progressive because of the efficacy of Ops and IGR in reducing insect infestation (Prabhaker *et al.*, 1985).

The Successive use of these synthetic insecticides might cause serious problems such as resistance development, environmental pollution, and detrimental hazards to non-target organisms (Hamama and Fergani, 2019). One of these problems is a remaining residue in fresh consumed edible crops as vegetables and fruits that hazards to human health (Zidan *et al.*, 1996). Over 20 pesticide residues and their degradation metabolites have been determined in different food products by Abdel-Gawad and Shams El-Deen (1989). Inadequate use and failure to comply with pre-harvest intervals can cause the occurrence of residues above MRL. Therefore, different countries and international organizations have included several laws to regulate pesticide residues in food sources that are required to protect the health of consumers (Wang *et al.* 2015). Field evaluations should control the unwise use of insecticides in/on tomato crops that may cause accumulation of pesticide residues more than the permitted levels.

Accurate measurements of dissipation or degradation rates of various insecticides under field conditions to ensure

that the established pre-harvest interval (PHI) residues level were below the maximum residue limit (Malhat *et al.*, 2011). In recent decades, the QuEChERS “Quick, Easy Cheap, Effective, Rugged and Safe” method is one of the most distinctive AOAC (AOAC, 2000) official protocols for quantitation of pesticide residues in food matrices (Lehotay, 2007). Also, choosing the appropriate methodology for sample preparation methods greatly influences the reliability and accuracy of food analysis (Seddik *et al.*, 2012).

The main objectives of this study were to estimate the residue levels of Chlorpyrifos-methyl and Lufenuron and in tomato fruits cultivation infested with *S. littoralis* in the field using PHL and $t_{1/2}$ parameters which suggested as one of the most important registration requirement using the QuEChERS method coupled with (HPLC) connected with photodiode array detector (DAD) and (GC) analysis technique.

Materials and methods

1. Chemicals:

Two different groups were purchased locally and used for a field experiment in this work at the recommended dose:

1.1. Chlorpyrifos-methyl (insecticide, acaricide), organophosphate IUPAC name *O*, *O*-dimethyl *O*-3, 5, 6-trichloro-2-pyridyl phosphorothioate, *O*, *O*-dimethyl *O*-(3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinyl) phosphorothioate, 50 % EC, at rate 1000 cm³/ 100 liters.

1.2. Lufenuron (insecticide, acaricide) benzoylurea, *RS*-1-[2,5-dichloro-4-(1,1,2,3,3,3-hexafluoropropoxy)phenyl]-3-(2,6-difluorobenzoyl)urea 5% EC. at 1000 cm³/ 100 liters.

2. Field trials:

The experiments were carried out at Etai El-Barood Agricultural Research Station, El-Beheira, March 2020 Egypt. Tomato seedling [*Solanum Lycopersicum* Mill.) cv. Malika]. The experiments were designed in the following ways: plot size, 7 x 6 m; plot to plot distance, 1.5 m; plant to plant distance, 0.4 m for a row to row distance 1 m. Treatment plots were arranged in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Cultural practices were made according to the recommended crop schedule. To ensure the reliability of the experimental results, the field trials were previously investigated to be free of the pesticide. A hand-operated knapsack sprayer (20 liters) was used to apply the tested insecticides to the tomato plants. The recommended formulation used by sprayer volume of 1L/feddan (1feddan=4.200 m²) for Chlorpyrifos-methyl 50% EC (Burodan) and 50cm³/100Lwater for lufenuron (Granda). The spray was done in June 2020.

3. Reagent and chemicals:

Analytical standards of Chlorpyrifos-methyl and Lufenuron (≥99.9% purity) were obtained from Dr. Ehrestorfer Augusburg, Germany. All organic solvents used in this study were of HPLC grade and purchased from Scharlau (Barcelona, Spain). The suitability of solvents was ensured by running a reagent blank along with actual analysis. Sodium chloride of analytical grade was purchased from El Naser Pharmaceutical Chemicals Co. (Cairo, Egypt). Anhydrous magnesium sulfate of analytical grade, purchased from Merck (Germany), was activated by heating at 400°C for 4 hours in a

muffle furnace, then cooled and kept in a desiccator before use. Primary secondary amine (PSA, 40 µm Bondesil) was obtained from Supelco (Bellefonte, PA).

4. Preparation of standard solutions:

The stock solution containing 100 µg/ml of the analyte was prepared using acetonitrile as a solvent and kept in a refrigerator at 4°C. The working standard solutions (0.001, 0.01, 0.05, and 0.1 µg/ml) were prepared through a series of dilutions of a standard stock solution in acetonitrile. Meanwhile, a matrix-matched standard solution was similarly produced with blank tomato extract added to each diluted solution using the same calibration graph. The standard calibration curves of used insecticides were constructed by plotting analyte concentrations versus peak area.

5. Residue analysis:

5.1. Sampling and extraction:

After a spray of the tested insecticides, samples of treated and untreated tomato fruits were collected randomly from each replicate at intervals of zero time (2h after application), 1, 3, 7, 10, 15 days for all treatments. Samples were transferred to the laboratory and stored at -20 °C until using for analysis. One kilo of each sample was chopped into small cubes and homogenized for 5 min at high speed in a laboratory homogenizer and extracted according to the procedure described and modified by Lehotay *et al.* (2010). Ten grams of each homogenized sample was weighed into a 50 ml Teflon-Tube, extraction, and cleaned-up were done extracted by an optimized QuEChERS method (Anastassiades *et al.*, 2003) by blending with 10 ml of 1.0% acidified acetonitrile with acetic acid and shake vigorously for 1 min, the whole extract decanted through a glass wool plug in a glass funnel containing 4 g of anhydrous magnesium sulfate and 1 g of sodium chloride then shake vigorously for 1 min. one gram sodium citrate dehydrate, and 0.5 g

disodium hydrogen citrate sesquihydrate were added. The filtrate then vigorously shaken for 1 min using a vortex mixer at maximum speed. Afterward, 4 g of anhydrous MgSO₄, 1 g of NaCl, 1 g sodium citrate dehydrate, and 0.5 g disodium hydrogen citrate sesquihydrate were added, then extract by shaking vigorously on vortex for 2 min and centrifuged for 10 min at 5,000 rpm. An aliquot of 3 ml was transferred from the supernatant to a new clean 5-ml centrifuge tube and cleaned by dispersive solid-phase extraction with 75 mg of PSA and 500 mg of magnesium sulfate. Afterward, centrifugation was carried out at 6,000 rpm for 5 min. An aliquot (2 ml) from the supernatant was filtered through a 0.2- μ m PTFE filter (Millipore, USA) and then analyzed by Agilent 1100 HPLC-DAD.

5.2. Determination:

5.2.1. Chlorpyrifos-methyl:

Determination of Chlorpyrifos-methyl residues was performed using the Gas chromatographic (GC) analytical system. After extraction 0.5 mL of the cleaned supernatant was transferred into a screw cap vial and 1.0 μ L of the solution was injected into (G.C) Agilent-GC analysis. Chlorpyrifos-methyl (Hewlett Packard GC Model 6890) equipped with Ni⁶³ electron capture detector (ECD). The gas chromatography conditions HP-5MS capillary column (30m length x 0.32 mm internal diameter (i.d) x 0.25 μ m film thickness). Operating temperatures were: column temperature was programmed: initial oven temperature, 40 °C to 220°C at 30°C /min then to 240°C at 5 °C /min and detector temperature 320 °C with nitrogen carrier gas flow at 1.0 ml/min. all compounds were identified by their retention times compared to known standards.

5.2.2. Lufenuron:

Lufenuron residues were determined by the HPLC system. The chromatographic conditions were as follows: an Agilent 1100

series equipped with an analytical column (150 mm×4.6 mm id, × 5 μ m ODS) attached to a photodiode array detector. The flow rate of mobile phase methanol 80 % + water 20 %) was 0.8ml/min and the injection volume were 20 μ l. the detection wavelength was set at 255nm. Residues were estimated by comparison of peak area of standards with that of the unknown or spiked samples run under identical conditions

6. Recovery studies:

According to SANCO/1257/2013 (SANCO, 2013) within laboratory method validation was performed to provide evidence that the method is fit for the extraction and quantitative determination of Chlorpyrifos-methyl and Lufenuron in/on tomato fruits. The method was validated following a conventional validation procedure that included the following parameters: (Linearity) multilevel calibration of Chlorpyrifos-methyl and Lufenuron was diluted either with pure solvent in series at (5, 2.5, 1, 0.5, 0.2, and 0.01) μ g/ml, (Matrix effect) comparing the response produced from the Chlorpyrifos-methyl and Lufenuron in a pure solvent solution with the samples were first extracted and then spiked with Chlorpyrifos-methyl and Lufenuron in the same solvent at the same concentration level, (Selectivity and Sensitivity). Determining limit of quantification (LOQ), the limit of detection (LOD), Trueness (bias) five replicates were used to check the recovery at the levels (1, 0.5, and 0.01) mg/ and Repeatability Precision (RSD).

7. Half-life Calculation:

Half-life times ($t_{1/2}$) of recovery of chlorpyrifos-methyl and Lufenuron residues were calculated mathematically according to Moye *et al.* (1987). The dissipation kinetics of both insecticide residues were determined by plotting residue concentration against elapsed time after application and the equation of best curve fit with maximum coefficients of determination (R^2) was

determined. For dissipation of targeted insecticide in tomato, an exponential relationship was found to be applied corresponding to the general first-order kinetics equation:

$$C_t = C_0 e^{-kt}$$

Where C_t represents the concentration of the pesticide residue at the time of t , C_0 represents the initial deposits after application, and k is the constant rate of pesticide disappearance per day. From this equation, the dissipation half-life periods ($t_{1/2} = \ln(2)/k$) of the studied insecticide.

8. Statistical analysis:

Data were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by the least significant difference (CoStat Statistical Software, 1998-2005) The Dissipation and Persistence values were calculated according to the following formula:

Dissipation% = [(initial residue residues found at different time) / initial residue] x 100

Persistence = 100 - Dissipation%

Results and Discussion

To confirm the safe treatment of tomato fruits in fields with the tested insecticides, low residues of insecticides should be detected, and their pre-harvest intervals (PHI), i.e. the time (in days) required for dissipation of the initial residue levels to below their corresponding maximum residue limits (MRL) (Codex Alimentarius Commission for Pesticides residues, 2013) with highly selective, sensitive, and accurate analytical methods.

1. Residual behavior of chlorpyrifos-methyl:

The method for the determination of chlorpyrifos-methyl was based on the use of reverse-phase (HPLC) analysis. The obtained data in (Table 2 and Figure 1) showed that the residue levels in/on tomato fruits treated with chlorpyrifos-methyl significantly decrease with time elapsing. The maximum amount of detected residues levels of chlorpyrifos-methyl was after two hours (Zero time) after

treatment where it reached 1.13 mg kg⁻¹. One day post-treatments significant dissipation was recorded as the level of residues decreased to 0.83 mg kg⁻¹ corresponding to 26.54% dissipation. The lowest number of residues was detected after one week (0.04 mg kg⁻¹) with a significantly maximum dissipation rate was recorded as 96.46%. After ten days, no residues were detected in all samples. The same pattern for dissipation was recorded for organophosphate insecticides (Abdalla *et al.*, 1993 and Al-Eed, 2006). The dissipation rate of tomato fruit exhibited first order kinetics. The half-life of chlorpyrifos- methyl calculated in/on tomato fruit treated at recommended dose was 1.03 days. The pre-harvest interval (PHI), during which the residue level was below the maximum permitted residues level (MRL) (EU, 2009) was three.

2. Residual Behavior of lufenuron:

The data in (Table 2 and Figure 1) showed that the concentration of lufenuron residues detected two hours after treatment was significantly at the maximum level of 4.31 mg/kg. However, rapid dissipation levels were recorded after one-day post-treatment (58.19) where the residue level significantly decreased to 1.8 mg/kg. The residual level of lufenuron dissipated by 91.39 % on the seventh day with an average deposit of 0.37 mg kg⁻¹. The residues of lufenuron were dissipated in/on the tomato to undetectable limits ten days after treatments. The calculated half-life time of lufenuron was 1.5days. The pre-harvest interval (PHI) of lufenuron was 8 days. The residue levels of lufenuron tended significantly to decrease with time (Fig1) and these results were in line with (Malhat *et al.*, 2012).

The limit of quantification was 0.1 mg/kg and 0.01 mg/kg, far below the MRLs established for chlorpyrifos-methyl and lufenuron, respectively. The acceptable recovery range ranged between 70 and 120% while the RSD was ≤20% according to EU

method validation guide lines (SANTE/11813/2017, 2017). Mean recoveries between 90 and 111% were obtained during method development. A relative standard deviation of $\leq 20\%$ is also feasible with this method (Table 2). The recovery results fully comply with the EU method validation guidelines (Table 1). Different dissipation rates of both

insecticides might due to the difference between their chemical structure and physiochemical characters under the field conditions that almost affect their persistence in the field with different climatic parameters and through the different processing procedures of tomato products.

Table (1): Recoveries and relative standard deviations for chlorpyrifos-methyl and lufenuron in/on tomato fruits at various fortification levels.

Spike level (mg/kg) (n*=3)	Chlorpyrifos-methyl			Lufenuron		
	Recovery \pm SD	Average% \pm SD	RSD%	Recovery \pm SD	Average% \pm SD	RSD%
0.10	90 \pm 5.16	97.3 \pm 6.66	5.10	99 \pm 4.24	105 \pm 6.00	4.21
0.50	99 \pm 1.2		1.1	105 \pm 7.03		6.99
0.01	103 \pm 4.3		3.99	111 \pm 4.24		4.1

* Number of replicates

Table (2): Determination of chlorpyrifos-methyl and lufenuron in/on tomato fruits at different time intervals from the application.

Days after treatment	Chlorpyrifos-methyl			Lufenuron		
	Residues (mg/kg)	Dissipation %	Persistence %	Residues (mg/kg)	Dissipation %	Persistence %
Z	1.13 ^a \pm 0.14	0.00 ^d \pm 0.00	100.00 ^a \pm 0.00	4.31 ^a \pm 0.58	0.00 ^d \pm 0.00	100.00 ^a \pm 0.00
1	0.83 ^b \pm 0.26	26.54 ^c \pm 3.58	73.46 ^b \pm 5.78	1.8 ^b \pm 0.12	58.19 ^c \pm 3.28	41.81 ^b \pm 4.83
3	0.25 ^c \pm 0.17	77.87 ^b \pm 6.51	22.13 ^c \pm 3.43	0.93 ^c \pm 0.21	78.37 ^b \pm 5.04	21.63 ^c \pm 2.99
7	0.04 ^d \pm 0.02	96.46 ^a \pm 10.89	3.54 ^d \pm 0.82	0.37 ^d \pm 0.09	91.39 ^a \pm 12.16	8.61 ^d \pm 3.14
10	ND			ND		
15	ND			ND		
MRL(ppm)	1			0.4		
t _{1/2} (day)	1.03			1.50		
PHI	3			8		

Z: two hours after the insecticide application (zero time). MRL: acceptable maximum residue limit

Rec: Mean recovery t_{1/2}: Half-time PHI: Pre-harvest interval ND: Not detected. LOQ limit of quantification

Values within the same row having the same letters are non-significant, p>0.05.

Figure (1): Decline rate of chlorpyrifos-methyl and lufenuron in/on tomato fruits after different time intervals of application.

Tomato fruits are considered one of the economic vegetables in the world. It is one of the main sources of national agricultural income, which occupies an important position in export to attract foreign exchange to the Egyptian economy. Tomato contains multi-nutrients such as vitamin A, vitamin C, potassium, phosphorus, magnesium, and calcium (USDA, 2009). *S. littoralis* is one of the most known pests infesting tomato cultivation all over the year. The integrated pest management strategies aimed mainly to reach good agricultural practices including reduction of pesticide usage to reduce the most environmentally dangerous pesticides. Monitoring of pesticide residues is one of the main targets of integrated pest management to predict adequate concentrations and the pre-harvest interval should be estimated. To certify the quality of both Chlorpyrifos-methyl and Lufenuron residue results should align with standard limits. The limits of quantification (LOQ) in both insecticides were lower than MRLs established by Codex Committee and Switzerland (EU, 2008). The QuEChERS method showed good recoveries, and the analytical method allowed good separation of the tested insecticides. Based on these results of this study that residue levels will be acceptable when applied to tomatoes in

Egypt due to their relatively low cost and their lack of bioaccumulation in the ecosystems, these results were in agreement with Prabhaker *et al.* (1985). Also, their lower toxicity to non-target species, very short half-life time in the tomato plant. The obtained results suggest that if tomatoes are destined to be sold as a fresh product, it may be advisable to lower the dose of the treatments with lufenuron. Also, because washing the fruit does not seem to guarantee a significant decrease of residues that were in line with (Gambacorta *et al.*, 2005).

Several concerns should be taken when using pesticides in the tomato fruits cultivations under field conditions because tomato production is intended exclusively for fresh consumption. Monitoring of pesticides is very important for defining pesticide residues. The proposed method has been validated with good recoveries and low LOQs. The MRLs of chlorpyrifos-methyl and lufenuron were lower than MRLs, fulfilling the Codex Committee and (EU) criteria. The results obtained in this study confirm that the proposed methods are easy and reliable for the determination of the analyzed Chlorpyrifos-methyl and Lufenuron insecticide residues in/on tomato fruits.

References

- Abdalla, E. F.; Sammour, E. A.; Abdallah, S. A. and EL-Sayed, E. I. (1993):** Persistence of some organophosphate insecticides residues in/on tomato and bean. *Bull. Fac. Agric. Univ. Cairo*, 44:465-476.
- Abdel-Gawad, A. A. and Shams El-Deen, A. (1989):** Insecticides residues in total diet samples. *J. Egypt. Soc. Toxicol.*, 4:79-84.
- Al-Eed, M. A. (2006):** Determination of Primiphos-Methyl and Chloropyrifos-Ethyl residues on Tomato and pepper fruits grown in green house. *J. Appl. Sci.*, 6(4): 979-982.
- Anastassiades, M.; Lehotay, S. J.; Stajnbaher, D. and Schenck, F. J. (2003):** Fast and easy multiresidue method employing acetonitrile extraction/partitioning and "dispersive solid-phase extraction" for the determination of pesticide residues in produce. *J. AOAC Int.*, 86(2):412-431.
- AOAC (2000):** Official methods of analysis (2000) 17th edn. AOAC International, Gaithersburg.
- Codex Alimentarius Commission for Pesticides residues (2013):** List of maximum residue limits for pesticides in food and animal feeds, Part-1. Joint FAO/WHO food standards program.
- CoStat (1998-2005).** 6.4. Cohort software 798 light house Ave. PMB320, Monterey, CA93940, and USA.
- El-Nabarawy, I. and Abou-Dania, M. (1992):** Determination of profenofos and malathion residues in fresh tomatoes and paste. *Egypt. J. Appl. Sci.*, 7:106-111.
- EU (2008):** MRL sorted by pesticide (available at <http://Ra Kim, Mi Young Yun, Dae Myung Lee and Gae-Ho www.ec.europa.eu/food/plant/protect> ion/pesticides Lee, 2008. A multi-residue metho for the /index_en.htm).
- EU (2009):** Maximum residue levels impact and benefits for Authorizations and Trade.
- Gambacorta, G.; Faccia, M.; Lamacchia, C.; Di Luccia, A. and La Notte, E. (2005):** Pesticide residues in tomato grown in open field. *Food Control*, 16: 629-632.
- Hamama, H.M. and Fergani, Y.A. (2019):** Toxicity and Oxidative Stress Induced in *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisduval) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) Treated with Some Insecticides. *African Entomology*, 27(2): 523-531.
- Lehotay, S. J. (2007):** Determination of pesticide residues in foods by acetonitrile extraction and partitioning with magnesium sulfate: collaborative study. *J. AOAC Int.*, 90(2):485-520.
- Lehotay, S. J; Son, K. A.; Kwon, H.; Koesukwiwat, U.; Fu, W., Mastovska, K.; Hoh, E. and Leepipatpiboon, N. (2010):** Comparison of QuEChERS sample preparation methods for the analysis of pesticide residues in fruits and vegetables. *J. Chromatogr A*, 1217, (16):2548-2560.
- Malhat, F; Abdallah, H. and Hegazy, I. (2011):** Dissipation of chlorantraniliprole in tomato fruits and soil. *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 88: 349-351.
- Malhat, F; Almaz, M; Arief, M; El-Din, K and Fathy, M. (2012):** Residue and Dissipation Dynamics of Lufenuron in Tomato Fruit Using QuEChERS Methodology. *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol.*, 89:1037-1039.
- Moye, H. A.; Malagodi, M. H.; Yoh, J.; Leibee, G. L.; Ku, C. C. and Wislocki, P. G. (1987):** Residues of

- avermectin B1a in rotational crops and soils following soil treatment with [14C] avermectin B1a. J. Agric. Food. Chem., 35 (6): 859-864.
- Prabhaker, N.; Coudriet, D. L. and Meyerdirk, D. E. (1985):** Insecticide resistance in the sweetpotato whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae). J. Econ. Entomol., 78: 748-752.
- SANCO/12571/2013 (2013):** Guidance document on analytical quality control and method validation procedures for pesticides residues analysis in food and feed.
- SANTE/11813/2017 Document (2017):** Guidance document on analytical quality control and method validation procedures for pesticides residues and analysis in food and feed.
- Seddik, H.; Marstani, Z. and ALazzam, T. (2012):** Trace level determination of insecticide using gas chromatography, and the application for residual monitoring in local Syrian vegetables. Arab. J. Chem., 10: S212–S218.
- USDA (United State Department of Agriculture) (2009):** Tomatos (red, ripe, row, year-round average) - Nutrient values and weights for edible portion (NDB NO: 11529). USDA National Nutrient Database for Standard Reference. Release, 22.
- Wang, H. Z.; Peng, L.; Luo, Y.; Wang, M. and Liu, X. M. (2015):** Multi-residue analysis of over 200 pesticides in cereals using a QuEChERS and gas chromatography– tandem mass spectrometry-based method. Food Chem., 169:372–80.
- Zidan, Z. H.; Selim, A. A.; Afifi, F. A.; Abdel-Daim, Y. A. and Mohamed, K. A. (1996):** Decontamination of insecticide residues from vegetables through laboratory processing. Annals. Agric. Sci. Ain Shams Uni. Cairo., 41:1051-10641.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejprii.eg.net

**Impact of the thrips-borne tomato spotted wilt virus infestation on some
cucurbitaceous plant yield, Egypt**

Khalifa, E. A.; Salah, S. and Risha, E. M.

Department of Economic Entomology and Pesticides, Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 25/ 4/2021

Accepted: 29 / 6 /2021

Keywords

Tomato spotted wilt virus (TSWV), thrips, yield loss, cucumber, squash and Egypt.

Abstract:

In Egypt, two cultivated cucurbitaceous vegetable crops, (Cucumber, *Cucumis sativa* L. (Cultivar: Beta Alfa) and squash, *Cucumis pepo* L. (Cultivar: Eskandarani)) were used to define the thrips-borne tomato spotted wilt virus (TSWV) species attack them, during two successive seasons, 2010 and 2011, for summer and nili plantation in Giza Governorate. These species were, onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman, palm thrips *Thrips palmi* Karny, western flower thrips *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande), and grass thrips *Chirothrips texanus* (Andre). With note, the data of *C. texanus* recorded for the first time in Egypt. The occurrence and seasonal abundance of each thrips species of both plants were determined and thrips species numbers were direct counted and recorded. Either in cucumber or squash fields, the population of each thrips species expressed a higher total number in the nili plantation than the summer plantation with significant difference in both plantation in the same growing season, but not between the growing seasons based on the mean of collected thrips numbers. The correlation between climatic factors and thrips population was also performed and found that, thrips population was affected by both temperature and relative humidity. Otherwise, pathological symptoms of TSWV infection on the two plant crops were categorized according to the visual syndromes, and the highest rate of infection was observed. The effect of the natural infection of thrips on reduction of leaves number, loss of fruit weight, and the percentage of yield loss due to thrips-borne TSWV infection, in relation to the average yield of the healthy plant was determined and observed significant differences among the nili and the summer plantations in the same growing season, but not between the growing seasons, either in cucumber or squash plants.

Introduction

Cucurbitaceous (Cucurbit) plants, especially squash and cucumber, are

important vegetable crops in Egypt, they are ranked fourth after potato, tomato and onion (Mohamed *et al.*, 2003). In Egypt,

cucurbitaceous crops are attacked by many insect pests and viral diseases. Piercing sap sucking insect pests such as whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae), onion thrips *Thrips tabaci* (Linderman) (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) , cotton aphid *Aphis gossypii* Glover (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and leafhoppers *Empoasca decipiens* Paoli (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae) causing serious damage to the host plants either directly by feeding on plant sap or indirectly through transmitting the causative agents of various diseases especially those belong to viral diseases (Abd El-Salam *et al.*, 2008 and Ghallab *et al.* , 2011). The common diseases on cucurbit crops are varying causes approximately 16% decrease in yield crop. Several viral diseases infect cucurbits as tomato spotted wilt virus (TSWV) and zucchini yellow mosaic virus (ZYMV), previously known as a muskmelon yellow stunt virus in melon, squash, watermelon, field cucumber, greenhouse cucumber, zucchini and some wild cucurbit hosts is considered important viral diseases.

Worldwide, fourteen thrips species have shown to be vectors of plant viruses among 5500 described thrips species (Hassani-Mehraban *et al.*, 2010 and Nakahara and Footitt, 2012). Until now, only eight thrips species are known as vectors of tospoviruses and they are members of the genera *Thrips* Linnaeus and *Frankliniella* Karny (Thysanoptera) within the family Thripidae (Nagata and Peters, 2001). Biological insect transmission test indicated that four different thrips species were tested as vectors of tospovirus (Salah, 2016).

The present study aimed to study the impact of the thrips-borne tomato spotted wilt virus infestation on some cucurbitaceous plant yield, Giza, Egypt.

Materials and methods

1. Location of field study:

Two cultivated cucurbitaceous vegetable crops, (Cucumber, *Cucumis sativa*

L. (Cultivar: Beta Alfa) and squash, *Cucumis pepo* L. (Cultivar: Eskandarani)) were used in the present study to define the thrips species attack them by direct plant inspection. During two successive seasons, 2010 and 2011, the field study was conducted at the Experimental Station, Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt. The field area was approximately 1/3 feddan (1400 m²), prepared and cultivated 700 m² per each crop, and seeds were sown directly in the field during April for summer plantation and during July for nili plantation in each season. All the agricultural practices were done, and no insecticides were used in pest control and squash.

2. Seasonal abundance and inspected of thrips species:

Two successive growing seasons of 2010 and 2011 to define the thrips species attack cucumber and squash fields by direct plant inspection. Four thrips-borne TSWV species were inspected in the present study are belonging to order Thysanoptera and family Thripidae. These species were, onion thrips *T. tabaci*, palm thrips *Thrips palmi* Karny, western flower thrips *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande), and grass thrips *Chirothrips texanus* (Andre). Monitoring and direct count of thrips species on the host plants, sampling was started as soon as the plants appeared above the ground. Samples were taken at each of the four cardinal directions of the field. Also, samples were collected weekly; 15 leaves (3 leaves/plant) from each plant species and dusted on a white paper sheet and collected thrips species numbers were counted and recorded.

3. Field monitoring of tomato spotted wilt virus (TSWV) viral syndromes:

Pathological symptoms of TSWV infection on cucumber and squash plants were diagnosed through signs of yellowing, stunning, crinkled, vein banding, mottling and local lesions on leaves. During the survey of thrips species on the plants in the

field, parallel observations were made to detect the appearance of any viral symptoms. Natural infection of cucumber and squash plants shown viral symptoms were labelled, weekly observed and categorized into groups according to the visual syndromes.

4. Assessment of crop yield:

Both the infected plants and the healthy plants were labelled. The weight of the fruit yield of each group was recorded at the end of the season by using the digital balance (Brother, Capacity 40Kg, China). The percentage of yield loss due to thrips-borne TSWV infection was determined, in relation to the average yield of the healthy plant, according to the following formula described by Dereje (1993).

$$\text{Yield loss, YL (\%)} = \frac{\text{YH-YD}}{\text{YH}} \times 100$$

Where, YL= Yield loss. YH= Yield of the healthy plant. YD= Yield of the diseased plant.

5. Statistical analysis:

Analysis of variance test was conducted for the different seasons, plantations, thrips species and the effect of the virus infection on the different plant parameters by using SPSS program (Levesque, 2013). L.S.D was conducted using Fisher's test in SPSS program. The correlation between temperature, relative humidity and thrips population was performed.

Results and discussion

1. Population density of different thrips species on cucumber plants:

The occurrence and seasonal abundance of each thrips species of the cucumber plants was determined and thrips species numbers were counted and recorded (Figure 1).

1.1. *Thrips tabaci* :

Population in cucumber fields expressed a higher total number in the nili plantation during the two growing seasons (58.53 and 53.20 individuals per leaf), respectively, than the population in the summer plantation (53.27 and 45.40 individuals/leaf), respectively. This result agrees with that found by Abd El Kaream *et al.* (1984) and El-Dabi (1999).

1.2. *Thrips palmi* :

Population expressed a relatively lower total number in case of the nili plantations than the first season with an average of (37.47 and 38.67 individuals/leaf), respectively. The total thrips number per leaf was more than the summer ones (36.33 and 33.00 individuals/leaf) in each season, respectively. These results agree with that found by Kawai (1983).

1.3. *Chirothrips texanus* :

The data of *Chirothrips texanus* Andre population showed that the total number in the nili plantation (4.80 and 3.67 individuals/ leaf) respectively, were more than in the summer ones (5.07 and 4.00 individuals/ leaf) respectively. These data were recorded for the first time in Egypt based on the published literatures by Zur Strassen (1960) and Nagata and Peters, (2001).

1.4. *Frankliniella occidentalis*:

Population occurred the total number in both nili plantations (45.80 and 44.87 individuals/ leaf) respectively, which were more (Higher) than in the summer ones (41.80 and 37.73 individuals/leaf) respectively, which agree with what recorded by EPPO/CABI (1996).

Figure (1): Mean numbers of thrips species in cucumber fields recorded weekly during the (a,c) summer plantation, (b,d) nili plantation at Giza region, 2010/2011, respectively.

2. Population density of different thrips species on squash plants:

The occurrence and seasonal abundance of each thrips species of the squash plants was determined and thrips species numbers were counted and recorded (Figure 2).

2.1. *Thrips tabaci* :

In the summer plantation of the growing seasons 2010 and 2011, *T. tabaci* occurred on squash plants in the field from mid April to early November. The average number of thrips increased gradually with the growing of the seedling and reached the maximum in late May (6.73 and 6.73 individuals/leaf), in each season, respectively.

This result on contrast with what found by El-Dabi (1999) in Egypt and agree with Abd El Kaream *et al.* (1984). In the case of the nili plantation, the average number of thrips increased gradually with the seedling age and reached its maximum in mid October (7.53 and 7.67 individuals/leaf), in each season respectively.

This result agrees with Abd El Kaream *et al.* (1984) and El-Dabi (1999). The thrips population in a squash field expressed as the total number in both nili plantation in each season (63.80 and 55.67 individuals/leaf) respectively, which were higher than in the summer ones (42.40 and 51.67 individuals/ plant), respectively.

2.2. *Thrips palmi* :

T. palmi occurred also from mid April to early November in each season 2010 and 2011. In the summer plantation, the average number of thrips increased gradually with seedlings growing and reached its maximum in late May (6.20 and 6.20 individuals/leaf) in each season respectively. This result is recorded for the first time in Egypt. The nili plantation, the number of thrips increased gradually and reached its maximum in early September (6.07 and 6.20 individuals/leaf) at early October in each season, respectively.

This result agrees with that found by Kawai (1983). The thrips population expressed as the total number in both nili plantations (34.80 and 35.67 individuals/leaf) respectively, which were higher than the summer ones (34.73 individuals/leaf), in each season, respectively.

2.3. *Chirothrips texanus* :

Ch. texanus occurred on squash seedlings grown in the field also from mid April to early November in both season 2010 and 2011. In the summer plantation of the first growing season 2010 the average number increased gradually with seedlings and reached its maximum in early June (0.80 individuals/leaf).

However, during the second growing season 2011, *Ch. texanus* occurred their maximum in early May (0.87 individuals/leaf). This result is recorded for the first time in Egypt based on the published literatures by Zur Strassen (1960) and Nagata and Peters (2001). The nili plantation of the first growing season 2010, the number of thrips increased gradually with seedlings and reached its maximum in late September (0.87 individuals/leaf). While their maximum reached on at late August (0.67 individuals/leaf) during the second growing season 2011.

The thrips population expressed as the total number in both nili plantations (5.73 and 4.73 individuals/ leaf), in each season respectively, which were higher than in the summer ones (4.53 and 4.87 individuals/ leaf) respectively.

2.4. *Frankliniella occidentalis*:

F. occidentalis occurred on squash seedlings grown in the field also from mid April to early November during 2010 and 2011. In the summer plantation, the average number of thrips increased gradually and reached its maximum in early May (9.07 and 8.93 individuals/leaf) in each season respectively.

In the nili plantation, the average number of thrips increased gradually with the seedling age and reached its maximum in early September (5.53 individuals/leaf). But *F. occidentalis* occurred their maximum in mid September (9.07 individuals/ leaf), which agree with what recorded by EPPO/CABI (1996). The thrips population in the squash field expressed as the total number in both nili plantation (45.87 and 44.67 individuals/leaf), which were higher than in the summer ones (38.80 and 38.67 individuals/ leaf) in each season, respectively.

With both plants, statistical analysis showed a significant difference among the nili and the summer plantations in the same growing season, but not between the growing seasons. Also, there was a significant difference between the thrips species population in both plantations based on the mean of collecting thrips numbers.

Figure (2): Mean numbers of thrips species on squash fields recorded weekly during the (a,c) summer plantation, (b,d) nili plantation at Giza region, 2010/2011, respectively.

3. Correlation values between population of thrips species and the climatic factors:

Based on the meteorological data regarding the mean daily temperature and relative humidity obtained by recording them daily, thrips population was affected by both temperature and relative humidity. In cucumber fields, there was a significant positive correlation between the temperature and the average numbers of thrips and a negative correlation between the relative humidity and the average number of thrips, referring that with the gradual increasing with the temperature degrees. This result is applicable to both plantations in each season. In squash fields, in the summer plantation in each season, the correlation values showed a significant positive correlation between the temperature and the average numbers of thrips, while, a negative correlation was found between the relative humidity and the

average number of thrips. But, in the nili plantation, in each season a significant negative correlation was found between the temperature and the average numbers of thrips, while, a positive correlation between the relative humidity and the average number of thrips was found.

4. Determination of reduction in cucumber leaves number and loss of fruit weight:

The obtained data indicated the effect of the natural infection on the yield of cucumber. In the first growing season 2010, a remarkable reduction in all tested parameters was recorded compared with the healthy plants. The infection resulted in (12.1%) reduction in the cucumber leaves and (29.7%) reduction in the fruit weight compared to the healthy plants yield (Figure 3). The estimated average number of leaves/ healthy plant (19.96 leaves) was reduced to

(17.56) leaves/infected plant (Table 1) as showed in Figure (5). However, the estimated average weight of 10 fruits/healthy plant was 866 gm reduced to 608.72 gm in case of unhealthy plants (Table 2). In case of nili plantation, the natural infection on the yield of the nili plantation 2010, on a cucumber field in the first growing season 2010, caused a remarkable reduction in leave numbers and fruit weight compared with the healthy plants. The infection resulted in a 14.6% reduction in the cucumber leaves and 30.3% reduction in the fruit weight in comparison with the healthy plant, (Figure 3). The estimated average number of leaves/healthy plant was 19.72 leaves reduced to 16.84 leaves/infected plant (Table 1). However, the estimated average weight of 10 fruits in case of the healthy plant was 876.8 gm reduced to 611.52 gm in case of infected plants (Table 2).

In the second cucumber growing season (2011), the data indicated also a remarkable reduction in both leave the numbers and fruit weight during the summer plantation 2011, compared with the healthy plants. The infection resulted in a 11.9 % reduction in the cucumber leaves and 23 % reduction in fruit weight compared with the healthy plant (Figure 3). The counted average number of leaves of the healthy plants (20.08 leaves) was reduced to (17.68 leaves) in case of the infected plant (Table 1). Also, the estimated average weight of 10 fruits for healthy plant was (890.8 gm) reduced to (686 gm) in case of infected plants (Table 2). The obtained results in Figure (3) indicated that, the natural infection on the yield of the nili plantation in the second growing season 2011, with TSWV caused a remarkable reduction in all tested parameters compared with the healthy plants, the infection resulted in (12.4 %) reduction in the cucumber leaves and (27.9 %) reduction in the fruits weight in comparison with the healthy plant. The estimated average number of leaves/healthy

plant (20 leaves) was reduced to (17.52 leaves) in case of the infected plant (Table 1). However, the estimated average weight of 10 fruits for healthy plant was (900.4 gm) reduced to (649.2 gm) in case of infected plants (Table 2).

Although the statistical analysis presented in Table (1) showed significant differences in the cucumber leaves numbers among the nili and the summer plantations in the same growing season, but not between the growing seasons. Also, the results in Table (2) showed a significant difference in the cucumber fruit weight among the nili and the summer plantations in the same growing season, but not between the growing seasons. These results partially agree with that found by Abd El-Salam *et al.* (2008), Farrag and Fatouh (2010) and Ghallab *et al.* (2011) .

5. Determination of reduction in squash leaves number and loss of fruit weight :

Two parameters were estimated to study the effect of thrips population on the squash yield. The obtained data in Figure (4) indicated a remarkable reduction in all tested parameters compared with the healthy squash plants cultivated in the summer plantation 2010. The infestation resulted in 11.7 % reduction in the squash leaves and 28 % reduction in the fruits weight in comparison with the healthy plant. The estimated average number of leaves/ healthy plant was 20.96 leaves reduced to 18.52 leaves in case of infected plants, (Table 3) as showed in (Figure 5) . However, the estimated average weight of 10 fruits for healthy plant was 894.4 gm reduced to 643.96 gm in case of infested plants (Table 4). The obtained data presented in Figure (4) showed the effect of the natural infection on squash yield of nili plantation 2010, in the first growing season 2010. The TSWV caused a remarkable reduction in all tested parameters compared with the healthy plants. The infection resulted in (22.1 %) reduction in the squash leaves and (30 %) reduction in the fruits weight in

comparison with the healthy plant, The estimated average number of leaves/healthy plant (20.96 leaves) was reduced to (16.32 leaves) in the case of infected plant (Table 3). However, the estimated average weight of 10 fruits for healthy plant (912 gm) was reduced to (637.96 gm) in the case of infected plants, (Table 4).

The presented data in Figure (4) showed the effect of the natural infection on squash yield of the summer plantation in the second growing season 2011, The TSWV caused a remarkable reduction in all tested parameters compared with the healthy plants. The infection resulted in (10 %) reduction in the squash leaves and (25 %) reduction in the fruits weight in comparison with the healthy plant. The estimated average number of leaves for the healthy plant (21.16 leaves) was reduced to (19.04 leaves) for the infected plant (Table 3). However, the estimated average weight of 10 fruits of the healthy plant (900.4 gm) was reduced to (675.96 gm) in case of the infected plants (Table 4). The obtained data illustrated in Figure (4) showed the effect of the natural infestation of thrips on squash yield of the nili plantation in the second growing season 2011, Thrips species transmit TSWV caused a remarkable reduction in all tested parameters compared

with the healthy plants, The thrips infestation resulted in 9 % reduction in squash leaves and 27.8 % reduction in the fruits weight compared to the healthy plant. The estimated average number of leaves for healthy plant was 21.32 leaves reduced to 19.36 leaves for the infested plant (Table 3). However, the estimated average weight of 10 squash fruits of the healthy plant was 898 gm reduced to 647.6 gm in case of infested plants (Table 4).

The statistical analysis presented in Table (3) showed significant differences in the squash leaves numbers between the nili and the summer plantations in the same growing season, but not between the growing seasons. In Table (4) a significant difference in the squash fruits weight among the nili and the summer plantations in the same growing season was recorded, but not between the growing seasons. These results partially agree with that found by Abd El-Salam *et al.* (2008) , Hassani-Mehraban *et al.* (2010) and Ciuffo *et al.* (2010) .

The infected cucumber and squash fruits were showed obviously infection symptoms compared with the healthy ones as shown in Figures (5 and 6).

Table (1): Effect of natural infection with TSWV on number of cucumber leaves during 2010/ 2011 seasons.

	The first season (2010)		The second season (2011)	
	Summer plantation	Nili plantation	Summer plantation	Nili plantation
Healthy	19.96	19.72	20.08	20.0
Infected	17.56	16.84	17.68	17.52
LSD 0.05	2.33	2.53	2.24	2.03
Seasons	NS	Seasons * plantation		NS
Plantation	Sig.	Seasons * infection		NS
Infection effect	Sig.	Plantation * infection		Sig.
		Seasons * plantation* infection		NS

Table (2): Effect of natural infection with TSWV on fruit weight of cucumber during 2010/ 2011 seasons.

	The first season (2010)		The second season (2011)	
	Summer plantation	Nili plantation	Summer plantation	Nili plantation
Healthy	866.0	876.80	890.80	900.40
Infected	608.72	611.52	686.0	649.20
LSD 0.05	69.13	70.31	79.43	79.22
Seasons	NS	Seasons * plantation		NS
Plantation	Sig.	Seasons * infection		NS
Infection effect	Sig.	Plantation * infection		Sig.
		Seasons * plantation* infection		NS

Table (3): Effect of natural infection with TSWV on number of squash leaves during 2010/ 2011 seasons.

	The first season (2010)		The second season (2011)	
	Summer plantation	Nili plantation	Summer plantation	Nili plantation
Healthy	20.96	20.96	21.16	21.32
Infected	18.52	16.32	19.04	19.36
LSD 0.05	1.89	1.72	1.63	1.98
Seasons	NS	Seasons * plantation		NS
Plantation	Sig.	Seasons * infection		NS
Infection	Sig.	Plantation * infection		Sig.
		Seasons * plantation* infection		NS

Table (4): Effect of natural infection with TSWV on fruit weight of squash during 2010/ 2011 seasons.

	The first season (2010)		The second season (2011)	
	Summer plantation	Nili plantation	Summer plantation	Nili plantation
Healthy	894.40	912.0	900.40	898.0
Infected	643.96	637.96	675.96	647.60
LSD 0.05	72.54	69.67	72.59	78.68
Seasons	NS	Seasons * plantation		NS
Plantation	Sig.	Seasons * infection		NS
Infection	Sig.	Plantation * infection		Sig.
		Seasons * plantation* infection		NS

Figure (3): Reduction percentage in leaves number and fruit weight of cucumber plant due to natural infection with TSWV during a,c) the summer plantation and b,d) nili plantation, Giza region, 2010/2011, respectively.

Figure (4): Reduction percentage in leaves number and fruit weight of squash plant due to natural infection with TSWV during a,c) the summer plantation and b,d) nili plantation, Giza region, 2010/2011, respectively.

Figure (5): Visible symptoms of TSWV, a) On cucumber plant, b) On squash plant

Figure (6): Symptoms appeared on a) Cucumber fruits b) Squash fruits due to natural infection with TSWV. (H) Healthy fruit, (I) Infected fruits.

References

Abd El Kaream, A.I.: Shanab, L.M. and Abou El Naga, A.M. (1984): The fluctuation in the activity of *Thrips*

tabaci Lind. On squash throughout the hours of the day (Egypt). J. of Agri. Sci. Mansoura. Egypt, 4:88-95.

- Abd El-Salam, A.M.; Assemand, M.A. and Ragab, F.Y. (2008):** Chemical control of some squash pests in Egypt. *Ang. Entomo.*, 70: 169- 174.
- Ciuffo, M.; Mautino, G. C.; Bosco, L.; Turina, M. and Tavella, L. (2010):** Identification of *Dictyothrips betae* as the vector of Polygonum ring spot virus. *Annals of Applied Biology* 157: 299–307.
- Dereje, G. (1993):** Yield loss of faba bean caused by foot rot *Fusarium avenaceum*. *FABIS Newsletter*, 33: 24-27.
- El-Dabi, R.M.A. (1999):** Population and control studies on three sap sucking insects on different plantations of squash and cucumber in Giza governorate. M.Sc. Thesis, Fac. Agri., Cairo University.
- EPPO/CABI (1996):** *Frankliniella occidentalis* (Pergande) in quarantine pests for Europe. 2nd edition (Ed. By Smith, I.M.; McNamara, D.G.; Scott, P.R.; Holderness, M.). CAB INTERNATIONAL., Wallingford, UK.
- Farrag, E.S.H. and Fatouh, Y.O. (2010):** Solarization as a method for producing fungal-free container soil and controlling wilt and root-rot diseases on cucumber plants under greenhouse conditions. *Arch. Phytopathol. and Plant Prot.*, 43(6):519-526.
- Ghallab, M.M.; Habashi, N.H.; Iskandarand, A.K. F. and Rizk, M.A. (2011):** Sensitivity of four cucumber cultivars to some piercing sap sucking pests infestation and their impact on yield. *Egypt. J. Agric. Res.*, 89 (4):1363-1373.
- Hassani-Mehraban, A.; Botermans, M.; Verhoeven, J.T.J.; Meekes, E.; Saaijer, J.; Peters, D.; Goldbach, R. and Kormelink, R. (2010):** A distinct Tospovirus causing necrotic streak on *Alstroemeriasp* in Colombia. *Archives of Virology* 155: 423–428.
- Kawai, A. (1983):** Studies on population ecology of *Thrips pulmi* Karny. I. Population growth and distribution pattern on cucumber in greenhouse. *Jpn. J. Appl. Entomol. Zool.*, 27:261-264.
- Levesque, R. (2013):** SPSS Programming and Data Management: A Guide for SPSS and SAS Users (4th ed.). Chicago, Illinois: SPSS Inc. ISBN, 1-56827-390-8.
- Mohamed, M.F.; Refaeiand, E.F.S.; Shalaby, G.I. (2003):** Growth and yield of inbred zucchini squash (*Cucurbitapepo* L.) lines developed under adverse climatic conditions. *Ass. Univ. Bull. Environ. Res.*, 6 (1):1-13.
- Nagata, T. and Peters, D. (2001):** An anatomical perspective of Tospovirus transmission. In: Harris KF, Smith OP, Duffus JE (eds) *Virus–insect–plant interactions*, Academic Press, New York, 51–67.
- Nakahara, S. and Footitt, R.G. (2012):** Review of *Chirothrips* and related genera (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) of the Americas, with descriptions of one new genus and four new species. *Zootaxa*, 3251:1-29.
- Salah, S. (2016):** Studies on thrips species (Order: Thysanoptera: Family: Thripidae) and their relation in tospovirus transmission to some cucurbitaceous crops in Giza, Egypt. M.Sc. Thesis, Fac. Agri., Cairo University.
- Zur Strassen, R. (1960):** Key to and catalogue of the known species of *Chirothrips Haliday*, 1836 (Thysanoptera:Thripidae). *Journal of the Entomological Society of South Africa*, 23(1): 144-176.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejprii.eg.net

Evaluation of three different spraying volumes produced from two variables technique against tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and cotton aphid *Aphis gossypii* (Hemiptera: Aphididae) infesting marrows plants

Ammar, A. E. and Salloum, W.

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 26 /4/2021

Accepted: 23/ 6 /2021

Keywords

Spraying volumes , evaluation, *Bemisia tabaci* , *Aphis gossypii* and marrows.

Abstract:

Current experiment was carried out at the New Salheia, El-Sharkyia Governorate, during agricultural seasons 2017/2018. The work aims to evaluate the effect of technique type (Air atomization and hydraulic atomization) on four insecticides (Buprofezin, imidacloprid, mineral oil and MTI-446) efficiency against tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and cotton aphid *Aphis gossypii* (Glover) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) on marrows plants. Besides, evaluate the loss of land. Three equipment were tested; Knapsack motor sprayer (Oleo Mac) with spray volume 42.7L., Electric battery sprayer fitted with hollow cone nozzle Tx-6 with spray volume 55.13L. and Conventional sprayer with spray volume 200L. The result obtained showed that inverse fit between spray with high volume and the efficiency of spraying. So, the conventional sprayer recorded a low reduction of pests while, the Knapsack motor gave a high reduction compared with conventional sprayer, but Electric battery with Tx-6 nozzle give the highly reduction.

Introduction

Marrows are one of the most important vegetables cultivated under all conditions in Egypt. Fruits are consumed as vegetables or dessert (pie) and seeds as nuts and to a lesser extent as cooking oil (Lazos, 1986 and 1992). Because of their resistance to drought and the high protein (23-35%) and oil (25-55%) contents of their seeds. Marrows have attracted the attention of many growers and plant breeders within the past 50 years (Curtis, 1946; Bemis *et al.*, 1978 and Scheerens *et al.*, 1991). According to FAO (2012), the Egyptian production for marrows

was 658.234 metric tons. The cultivated area with this crop increased during the last two decades, especially in new reclaimed regions in both open and protected plantation. Throughout the growing season, cucurbit plants are suffering from a severe infestation with different phytophagous insect pests such as cotton aphid *Aphis gossypii* (Glover) (Hemiptera: Aphididae) and the tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius) (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) which considered the most common and dangerous insect pests of cucurbit plants. In case of heavy infestation, these pests cause serious damage

to plants, leading to greater reduction in the final yield (Hanafy, 2004).

In Egypt, pest control through chemical spraying is highly needed to reduce the annual losses in crops caused particularly by pests. Four types of insecticides have been recommended to control piercing-sucking insects, aphids and whiteflies. Insecticides efficiency depends on the spray spectrum (Number and size of droplets) (Palti and Ausher, 1986), which in turn depends on suitable techniques used. So, this study compared the efficiency of three equipment, air atomization technique (Knapsack motor sprayer (Oleo Mac) with 42.7L/fed., pressure or pneumatic atomization, Electric battery sprayer fitted with flat fan nozzle Tx-6) with 55.13 L/fed. and pressure or hydraulic atomization and (Conventional sprayer) with 200L/fed).

Therefore, this study aimed to evaluate the above mentioned application techniques on spraying efficiency, volume median diameter, number of droplets/cm² and loss of land.

Materials and methods

Marrows hybrids, variety new iskandarani (H1) was used in this study for

manual planting were planted in ridges the distance between each ridge was 80cm. and row spacing between the plants was 50cm., this variety is recommended in Egypt. The experiment was carried out in a rectangular shape area about 52 kerates. Marrows area is planted by hand in ridges. The experiment area divided into thirteen plots area of plot 700m². (58.3x12m.) and left 6m.between each plot (Treatment) and the other for measure the drift spray. Twelve plots for treatment and one for control, 4 kerates for each treatment. Four recommended insecticides were tested. Buprofezin (Applaud 25% SC with recommended rate 600cm/fed.), imidacloprid (Avenue 70%WG with recommended rate 120gm./fed.), mineral oil (Chemisol with recommended rate 1.5 liter/100liter water) and MTI-446 20% W.P. with recommended rate 100gm/100-liter water.

1. Equipment spraying machinery:

Equipment spraying machinery used (Table 1) in this investigation and specification of equipment as follow:

Table (1): Technical data of three spraying equipment's.

Items	Knapsack motor sprayer (Oleo mac), Tip 3	Electric battery sprayer fitted with hollow cone nozzle (Tx-6)	Conventional Sprayer
Type of sprayer	Pneumatic	Hydraulic	Hydraulic
Spray tank (L).	14	20	20
Flow rate, (l/min.)	2.033	0.525	1.905
Rate of application,(L/fed.)	42.7	55.13	200
Spray height, (m)	0.50	0.50	0.50
Swath width, (m)	5	1.0	1.0
Working speed, (Km/h.)	3	2.4	2.4
Type of spray used	Target	Target	Target
Productivity, (fed/h.)	2.86	0.57	0.57
Rate of performance (fed/day.)	11.44	2.28	2.28

$$\text{Productivity, (fed/h.)} = \frac{60 * \text{speed} * \text{swath width}}{4200}$$

$$\text{Rate of performance/day} = \text{Productivity, (fed/h.)} * (6) * \left(\frac{2}{3}\right).$$

1.1. Knapsack Motor Sprayer (Oleo Mac):

This equipment has a 14 liter tank capacity, with spray volume 42.7, the air outlet velocity about 120 m/s, with cool air. While, the rate of air discharge is about 16 m³/min., the flow rate is 2.033 liters /min. and the swath width are 5 m.

1.2. Electric battery sprayer fitted with hollow cone nozzle (Tx-6): It has a 20 liter liquid tank capacity, and diaphragm pump motor operated without air chamber. The power consumption for 4.5 hrs continuous operation is batter 12 volts, the spray volume is 55.13 L., flow rate is 0.525 L./min. and swath width is 0.75m.

1.3. Conventional Sprayer: Fitted with one hydraulic nozzle of conical spray pattern. It has a 20 liter liquid tank capacity, the spray volume is 200 L., flow rate is 1.905 L./min. and swath width is 1m.

2. Description of sampling line: Six plots were sprayed, and one was left for control. The sampling line consisted of 5 wires holders fix at one (m.). In diagonal line inside each treatment to collected sprayer chemicals. Sensitive paper cards double with the wire holder were fixed in "L" shape on the top of wire holders to measure the distribution ratio on the upper and lower surface of the sensitive paper. Three sensitive paper cards double were distribution on some

plants (Right, middle, and left) at distance of one meter to measure the distributed on the upper and lower surface at five plants. In addition to one sensitive paper card was placed under each plant to measure loss of land. All cards were numbered, collected and transferred carefully to the laboratory for measurement the volume and number of deposited droplets per cm² by the above mentioned Strubin lens. Therefore, calculate the VMD of droplets.

Results were recorded, in ten successive classes with a range of 50microns. Volume median diameter (VMD) value was calculated according to the following equation Gabir (1978).

$$V.M.D = \left[\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n xi^3}{\sum_{i=1}^n xi} \right]^{\frac{1}{3}}$$

Where:

Xi= droplet diameter for a given size class (1)

$$\sum_{i=1}^n i$$

= total number of droplet, in all droplets categories

3. Laboratory coverage for used equipment (Table 2) :

Table (2): Spray coverage on artificial targets as produced by electric battery sprayer and knapsack motor sprayer Oleo Mac (AM 180).

Equipment			Electricbattery sprayer			Knapsack motor Sprayer (Oleo mac)			
Nozzle			Hollow cone Tx-6			Tip3			
Spray Volume (L/fed)			55.13			42.7			
Droplets spectrum Spray parameter			VMD µm	N/cm ²	%N	VMD µm	N/cm ²	%N	
Working speed (2.4 km/h)	Spray height	(0.30m.)	Upper	150	104	67%	146	91	75.2%
			Lower	101	51	33%	107	30	24.8%
		(0.50m.)	Upper	115	102	63.8%	153	92	68.7%
			Lower	101	58	36.2%	99	42	31.3%
Working speed (3km/h)	Spray height	(0.30m.)	Upper	138	76	69.7%	155	93	72%
			Lower	79	33	30.3%	116	36	28%
		(0.50m.)	Upper	12	72	72%	148	85	72%
			Lower	87	28	28%	106	33	28%

The air temperature in the field at 3.6.2017 and 10.5.2018 were 31°C and 34°C respectively, while relative humidity was 68% and 73%. Measurements used described by Barry (1978). A simple anemometer has a pith ball which moves up at vertical tube according to the strength of the wind “Dwyer’s anemometer”. The wind velocity: Face the wind hold meter in front of you in vertical position and with scale side toward. Do not block bottom holes. Height of ball indicates wind velocity for high scale, cover hole at extreme top with finger.

4. Determination of spray deposit:

Number and size spots (Droplets) on Ciba-Geigy sensitive cards will be measured with a special scaled monocular lens (Struben) with a magnification of X 15. This is a hand lens which gives a direct measurement because it magnifies both the spot and scale at the same rate, scales 6 mm in 60 parts, and diameter 7 mm. The area of its field = 0.432 cm². Obtained data was corrected (By knowledge of the spread factor) and is calculated to obtain the Volumemedian diameter of droplets (VMD) and the number of these droplets in one square centimeter (N/cm²), according to Gabir (1995).

5. Bioassay of whitefly and aphids:

Samples of 25 plants were chosen randomly from each replicate before treatment and at 1, 3, 7 and 15 days after pesticides application. The number of target insects was counted. Percentage of the insect population was calculated according to Henderson and Tilton (1955). Comparing differences mean, the main effect and independent factors interaction were

analyzed throughout Spss, program version 19.

Results and discussions

Data in Table (2) showed that the best coverage of each equipment at laboratory, electric battery sprayer with hollow cone Tx-6 nozzles gave the best coverage at working speed 2.4km/h and spray height 0.5m. while, Knapsack motor sprayer (Oleo Mac) tip 3 gave the best coverage at working speed 3km/h and spray height 0.5m. So, these parameters were used at field work.

1. Qualitative assessment of techniques:

The evaluation of techniques was based on volume median diameter (VMD) (µm) and number of droplets (N/cm²), and the effect of them on reduction percentage. This will be on both a horizontal card on leaves for the plant right, middle and left, it was calculated as follows upper and lower of surfaces the card while, on the land loss was calculated on upper surface the card.

1.1. Knapsack motor sprayer (Oleo Mac), (Air atomization technique):

Data of effect of different equipment used on spray spectrum (Volume and size) at spray volumes of equipment, with pesticides used. Volume median diameter and number of droplets with four different pesticides and loss of land are given in Table (3). The obtained results showed that the volume median diameter and number of droplets decreased on lower surface and increased on upper surface for plants while, increases the volume median diameter and decreased the number of droplets on the land loss with two types of pesticides.

Table (3): The effect of equipment used on volume median diameter and number of droplets with the pesticides used.

Pesticides	Spray spectrum	Knapsack motor sprayer (Oleo Mac) (42.7L.)			Electric battery sprayer, with Tx-6 (55.13L.)			Conventional sprayer (200 L.)		
		Plant level		Loss of land	Plant level		Loss of land	Plant level		Loss of land
		Upper	Lower		Upper	Lower		Upper	Lower	
Buprofezin	VMD μm	118	84	149	103.7	87.7	142	482	168.7	519
	N/cm ²	63	35	27	75	38	36	24	21	18
	% N	50.4%	28%	21.6%	50.3%	25.5%	24.2%	38.1%	33.3%	28.6%
Imidacloprid	VMD μm	108	89	158	133	84.7	133	467.3	146.3	518
	N/cm ²	62	36	20	68	39	38	27	19	19
	% N	52.5%	30.5%	17%	46.9%	26.9%	26.2%	41.5%	29.2%	29.3%
Mineral oil	VMD μm	139	105	102	150	130	126	630	0	602
	N/cm ²	135	36	18	64	22	8	8	0	4
	% N	71.4%	19%	9.6%	68.1%	23.4%	8.5%	66.7%	0%	33.3%
MTI-446	VMD μm	163	126	130	172	140	136	615	0	610
	N/cm ²	170	37	22	67	29	11	11	0	6
	% N	74.2%	16.2%	9.6%	62.6%	27.1%	10.3%	64.7%	0%	35.3%

VMD: volume median diameter, N/cm²: number of droplets / cm²,

N%: percentage number of droplets

Effect of Knapsack motor sprayer (Oleo Mac) at 42.7 L/fed on volume median diameter and number of droplets:

The results which obtained in Table (3) obvious that Applaud 25% SC (Buprofezin), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (118 and 84 μm), (63and 35N/cm²), respectively. Meanwhile, the droplet loosed of land was 149 μm , 27N/cm². With Avenue 70% WG (Imidacloprid), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (108 and 89 μm), (62and 36N/cm²), respectively. Meanwhile, the droplet loosed of land was 158 μm , 20N/cm². With Chemisol (mineral oil), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (139 and 105 μm), (135and 36N/cm²), respectively. Meanwhile, the droplet loosed of land was 102 μm , 18N/cm². With (MTI-446), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (163 and 126 μm), (170and 37N/cm²),

respectively. Meanwhile, the droplets loosed of land was 130 μm , 22N/cm².

1.2. Electric battery sprayer fitted with hollow cone nozzle (Tx-6) (Hydraulic atomization technique) at 55.13 L/fed:

Also, in Table (3) Applaud 25% SC (Buprofezin), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (103.7 and 87.7 μm), (75and 38N/cm²), respectively. Meanwhile, the droplet loosed of land was 142 μm , 36N/cm². With Avenue 70% WG (Imidacloprid), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (133 and 84.7 μm), (68and 39N/cm²), respectively. Meanwhile, the droplet loosed of land was 133 μm , 38N/cm². With Chemisol (mineral oil), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (150 and 130 μm), (64and 22N/cm²), respectively. Meanwhile, the droplet loosed of land was 126 μm , 8N/cm². With (MTI-446), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (172

and 140 μ m), (67 and 29N/cm²), respectively. Meanwhile, the droplet loosed of land was 136 μ m, 11N/cm².

1.3. Conventional Sprayer (Hydraulic atomization technique) at spray rate 200L/fed:

Also, in Table (3) Applaud 25% SC (Buprofezin), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (482 and 168.7 μ m), (24 and 21N/cm²), respectively. Meanwhile, the droplets loosed of land was 519 μ m, 18N/cm². With Avenue 70% WG (Imidacloprid), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (467.3 and 146.3 μ m), (27 and 19N/cm²), respectively. Meanwhile, the droplet loosed of land was 518 μ m, 19N/cm². With Chemisol (mineral oil), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (630 and 0 μ m), (8 and 0N/cm²), respectively. Meanwhile, the droplet loosed of land was 602 μ m, 4N/cm². With (MTI-446), the volume median diameter and number of droplets on upper and lower surface of plant leaves was (615 and 0 μ m), (11 and 0N/cm²), respectively. Meanwhile, the droplet loosed of land was 610 μ m, 6N/cm².

From these results it could be stated that inverse fit between spray with high volume and the efficiency of spraying. So, the conventional sprayer recorded low reduction of pests while, the Knapsack motor gave high reduction compared with conventional sprayer, but Electric battery with Tx-6 nozzle give the highly reduction.

These results are closely related with those obtained by Ammar *et al.* (2018) they used two equipment for control wheat aphid, *Rhopalosiphum padi*, the first equipment, knapsack sprayer (3WDB) with battery charge and fitted with flat fan nozzle. The second equipment, Knapsack motor sprayer (IE34F) with hydraulic pump and spray gun, to determine the effect of application methods on initial and late biological efficacy of Imidacloprid and Dinotefuran against wheat aphid. Results indicated that, Knapsack motor sprayer showed less initial efficacy compared with knapsack sprayer. Although the Imidacloprid pesticide gives high efficacy compared with Dinotefuran pesticide. The author noticed that the main obtained differences were Imidacloprid with knapsack sprayer gave the highest efficacy with a significant difference compared with Dinotefuran with Knapsack motor sprayer.

2. Biological assessment of techniques:

Efficiency of the applied insecticides against aphids and whitefly infesting marrows plants: Data in Tables (4 and 5) and graphically illustrated in Figures (1 and 2) showed the initial effect (after 24 hrs.) and average % reduction (7, 15 and 30 days after application). Buprofezin showed slight increase in reduction percent compared to Imidacloprid. While, the greatest effect was obtained after 7 days of application, followed by 15 day and 30 day, respectively. Similar trend was observed with *B. tabaci* the tested insecticides showed similar reduction percent profile. With the least reduction percent initial and greatest reduction percent after 7 days.

Table (4): Effect of pesticides used against cotton aphid *Aphis gossypii* infesting marrows plants with various ground application techniques during seasons (2017/ 2018)

Pesticide	Date	Knapsack motor sprayer (Oleo Mac)	Electric Battery sprayer fitted with hollow cone nozzle (Tx-6)	Conventional sprayer
(Buprofezin) Applaud 25% SC	Pre-count	34.15	26.00	60.50
	Initial effect	66.07 d	81.84 b	96.24 a
	Mean residual effect	75.91 b	88.89 ab	80.83 a
	Average % reduction	73.94 b	87.41 a	83.92 a
(Imidacloprid) Avenue 70% WG	Pre-count	55.50	38.30	34.60
	Initial effect	72.81 c	80.59 b	69.54 d
	Mean residual effect	71.60 ac	87.55 bc	80.68 b
	Average % reduction	71.68 bc	86.16 d	78.45 c
(Mineral oil) Chemisol	Pre-count	34.00	39.40	35.70
	Initial effect	48.72 c	80.26 b	71.02 d
	Mean residual effect	74.52 b	86.62 cd	80.33 b
	Average % reduction	69.36 c	84.86 c	78.47 c
MTI-446 (20%) WP	Pre-count	45.00	38.20	26.20
	Initial effect	75.72 b	87.84 a	79.34 c
	Mean residual effect	78.49 a	90.51 a	80.31 b
	Average % reduction	77.93 a	89.97 c	80.12 b

N.B: Initial effect: after application with 24 hours. Mean residual effect: after application with (1, 3, 7 and 15 days).

Figure (1): Effect of four different insecticides against *Aphis gossypii* infesting marrows plants with various ground application techniques during season 2017/2018.

Figure (2): Effect of four different insecticides against *Bemisia tabaci* infesting marrows plants with various ground application techniques during season 2017/2018.

Table (5): Effect of pesticides used against tomato whitefly *Bemisia tabaci* infesting marrows plants with various ground application techniques during seasons (2017/ 2018).

Pesticide	Date	Knapsack motor sprayer (Oleo Mac)	Electric Battery sprayer fitted with hollow cone nozzle (Tx-6)	Conventional sprayer
(Buprofezin) Applaud 25% SC	Pre-count	10.80	14.40	9.00
	Initial effect	83.48 a	88.40 a	87.45 b
	Mean residual effect	73.08 a	67.78 b	72.30 cd
	Average % reduction	75.16 a	87.9 b	75.33 b
(Imidacloprid) Avenue 70% WG	Pre-count	9.20	13.50	11.20
	Initial effect	75.29 b	89.4 a	91.59 a
	Mean residual effect	64.62 c	82.64 c	75.77 b
	Average % reduction	66.75 c	83.99 a	78.93 a
(Mineral oil) Chemisol	Pre-count	8.40	13.20	10.20
	Initial effect	68.29 c	78.37 c	72.30 d
	Mean residual effect	69.41 bc	87.86 b	75.18 bc
	Average % reduction	66.78 c	85.96 b	74.6 b
MTI-446 (20%)WP	Pre-count	8.50	13.90	12.20
	Initial effect	69.34 c	88.35 a	82.11 c
	Mean residual effect	68.78 b	91.76 a	80.92 a
	Average % reduction	68.89 bc	91.07 a	81.15 a

N.B: Initial effect: after application with 24 hours. Mean residual effect: after application with (1, 3, 7 and 15 days).

Results as shown in Table (4), and graphically illustrated in Figure (1), all tested pesticides reduced the population of the aphids with varies percentage according to the spraying application techniques used. Based on the obtained results in general mean of percentage reduction, Imidacloprid and

Buprofezin were the most effect pesticides which caused 89.97 and 87.41% of reduction, respectively. Followed by MTI-446 and Chemisol, with percentage of reduction 86.16 and 84.86% respectively in case of Electric Battery Sprayer, with Tx-6 technique. While Knapsack sprayer technique exhibited the

lowest effect which caused 77.93, 73.94, 71.68 and 69.36% of reduction in aphids population with Imidacloprid, Buprofezin, MTI-446 and Chemisol, respectively.

As well as data in Table (5) and graphically illustrated in Figure (2), revealed that, the efficacy of the tested pesticides in this study could be arranged according to the general mean of reduction percentages of whitefly population in a descending order as follows: Imidacloprid, MTI-446, Chemisol, and Buprofezin they were 91.07, 87.9, 85.96 and 83.99 % of reduction, respectively.

From the above results in Tables (4 and 5), Electric battery sprayer, with Tx-6 technique exhibited the highest effects with all pesticides used followed by Knapsack motor sprayer (Oleo Mac) and Knapsack sprayer technique, respectively.

From the afore mentioned results, it could be stated that, all pesticides used in this study reached the highest efficacy after 7 days of application, followed by 15 day,

References

Ammar, A. E. (1997): studies on certain aerial and ground techniques for controlling the common sucking insects on cotton. M. Sc. Thesis Zagazig University.

Ammar, A.E.; Mokbel,E.M.S. and Salloum,W. (2018): Effect of Application methods of twoNeonicotinoid pesticides on spray coverage spectrum and reduction percent of wheat aphid, *Rhopalosiphum padi* at Sharqia Governorate. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 96(2): 493-501.

Barry, J. W. (1978): Meteorological condition and measurement Tech. U. S. A., 1596: 34 – 37.

Bemis, W. P.; Curtis, L. D.; Weber, C. W. and Berry, J. M. (1978): The feral buffalo gourd, *Cucurbitafoetidissima*. Econ. Bot., 32:87-95.

respectively against aphids and whitefly population with similar trend as shown in Tables (4 and 5). These results in harmony with those carried out on different equipment technique by many authors. Ramadan and Laila (1995) found that they tested the efficacies of seven insecticides sprayed with knapsack sprayer at the spray volume 200 l/fed. against aphids on potato plants. Data showed that Profenofos, Methomyl and Etofenprox showed the highest efficacy insecticides against the aphids while Prothiophos was the least one. Ammar (1997) evaluated four spraying techniques on cotton plantation against aphids by means of various doses. Deltanet and Prempet insecticides. The tested machines were Tapa, Semco, CP-3 and Conventional sprayer. Generally using the recommended dose of Prempet insecticide gave higher reduction piercing sucking insects (85%) than Deltanet insecticide (75%).

Curtis, L. C. (1946): The possibilities of using species of perennial cucurbits as a source of vegetable fats and protein. Chemung. Dig., 13: 221-224.

FAO (2012): Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nations, Pumpkins, Marrows and gourds.

Gabir, I. (1978): The parameters of agricultural sprayer nozzles. Roczniki Nauk Rolniczych, 73(4): 25-47.

Gabir, I. (1995): Spraying application of pesticide – with especial reference to the role of electrostatics (In Arabic) Lecturers and Notes, Fac. Agric., Ain Shams Univ., Egypt, p. 217.

Hanafy, A. R. I. (2004): Studies on the most important cucumber pests in the open field and suitable control programs. Ph.D. thesis, Fac. of. Agric. Moshtohor, Benha Branch- Zagazig University .

- Henderson, C.F. and Tilton, E.W. (1955):** Test with Acaricides Against the Brown Wheat Mite. J. Econ. Ent., 48: 157-161.
- Lazos, E. S. (1992):** Certain functional properties of defatted pumpkin seed flour. Plant Foods Hum. Nutr., 43: 257-273.
- Lazos, E. S.(1986):** Certain functional properties of defatted pumpkin seed flour. Plant Foods Hum. Nutr., 51: 1382-1383.
- Palti, J. and Ausher, R. (1986):** Advisory work in crop pest and disease management". Spring-Verlage Berlin Heidelberg, 132-160.
- Ramadan, M.F. and Laila, M. A. (1995):** Field evaluation of chemical insecticide for the control of three insect pests on potato plants. 6th. Nat Conf. of pest & Dis if vegetables & fruits in Egypt, 147-158.
- Scheerens, J. C.; Ralowcz, A. E.; McGriff, T. L.; Bee, K. A.; Nelson, J. M. and Gathman, A. C. (1991):** Phenotypic variation of agronomic traits among coyote gourd accessions and their progeny. Econ. Bot., 45: 365-378.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejppri.eg.net

Molluscicidal effect of ammonium nitrate and some biopesticides on the brown garden snail *Eobania vermiculata* (Gastropoda: Helicidae)

Mohamed, Hassan A. Soliman and Hend, Sh. Ghareeb

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 27/4/2021

Accepted: 16 / 6 / 2021

Keywords

Bacillus thuringiensis,
Metarhizium anisopliae, microbial control, ultraviolet exposure, ammonium nitrate, pre and post treatment.

Abstract:

The molluscicidal activity of biopesticide formulations *Bacillus thuringiensis* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* at the under recommended, recommended and up to recommended concentrations was evaluated against adults of *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) snail. Concentrations of both biopesticides were submitted to the ultraviolet radiation in different times of exposure and then assessed also against the same snail species. On the other hand, the molluscicidal effect of ammonium nitrate fertilizer individually and as post treatment against snails that pre treated with each of irradiated and non-irradiated biopesticides was investigated. The impact of all these treatments on the biological behavior and enzyme activity of snails were also studied. Ammonium nitrate caused the highest mortality 73.33% of snails at the highest concentration 2% after only 7 days of the experiment. On the other hand, the post treatment of snails with ammonium nitrate at the highest concentration 2% after treating them with each of the non-irradiated and irradiated up to recommended concentration 16×10^3 spores/ml of *B. thuringiensis* irradiated for 90 min., recorded the same highest mortality of snails, 70% after 7 and 14 days of the experiment, respectively. All of the tested treatments in this study completely prevented the egg laying of snails. In addition, *M. anisopliae* at 16×10^3 spores/ml irradiated for 60 min. achieved the highest reduction in the activity of alkaline phosphatase enzyme and decrease also the activity of the acid phosphatase enzyme compared with the control. On the contrary, the same treatment caused the highest increase in the activity of protease enzyme. The highest reduction in the level of amylase and lipase enzyme activity was recorded by *B. thuringiensis* at 4×10^3 spores/ml exposed to UV radiation for 60 min.

Introduction

Land snails are considered one of the most serious and destructive pest cause immense damage to a wide range of plants in Egypt (Gabr *et al.*, 2006). *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) represent one of the most harmful and abundant snails in different districts (Eshra, 2013). Due to the direct and latent hazards of the chemical pesticides and their toxic effect on the ecosystem, it is always advised to use safe biopesticides for controlling pests. In addition, the recent strategies of Integrated Pest Management (IPM) have mainly concentrated on the use of safe control method (El-Metwally *et al.*, 2010 and Kares *et al.*, 2012) for reaching to a minimum residue of pesticides in food (Vu *et al.*, 2007).

Microbial agents (containing pathogenic microorganisms) represented one important component of biological control techniques (Moussa *et al.*, 2014). It has low toxicity to the environment and ecosystem, low probability of target pests building up resistance, low cost of multiplication and registration, etc. (Rodrigues *et al.*, 2016). Fungal biopesticides can be used as an alternative method to control the terrestrial gastropods (Hendawy *et al.*, 2015). Entomopathogenic fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae* has pathogenic action against various agricultural pests (Marques *et al.*, 2000 and Zappellini *et al.*, 2010). Moreover, it can also produce some effective antimicrobial agents for control plant diseases (Butt *et al.*, 2001). Bacteria considered also another microbial biocontrol method of land snails that received greater attention in the few years ago (Genena and Mostafa, 2010). *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) is a gram negative bacterium which produces chemicals has a toxic effect against pests. The toxic activity of this bacterium against some land snails in Egypt has been investigated in several studies (Azzam and Belal, 2003 ;

Genena *et al.*, 2008 and Kramarz *et al.*, 2007). Related to these aspects, fertilizer is a new molluscicide with different mode of action and improved effectiveness safety when applied at low rates. It is a successful molluscicide and at the same time improves plant growth and yield when added to the soil. Ammonium nitrate has a high toxicity against *E. vermiculata* snail at low concentrations (Hend, 2013).

Toxic effect of nitrate against pests may be related to *in vivo* reduction of nitrate to nitrites and a conversion of hemoglobin to methemoglobin (Scott and Crunkilton, 2000). Biopesticide formulations (Particles) contain the microorganisms encapsulated in some materials such as starch, cellulose and gelatin, etc. Each particle can contain hundreds of conidia and after the drying process, it is ready for agricultural use and can be applied directly on the target pest and even on soil and plants without the need for dispersion in an aqueous medium, facilitating the application (Burgess, 1998). In the last few years, more attention has been paid to direct ultraviolet radiation effects on fungi and bacteria (Martyn *et al.*, 2003). Ultraviolet radiation can reduce the viability of microorganisms conidia (Rangel *et al.*, 2008). But it doesn't have the same negative effect against the microorganisms when used as encapsulated formulated products. These products provide great benefits such as protecting conidia from radiation, increasing the shelf life, facilitating storage and transport (Batista *et al.*, 1998).

In addition, when the biopesticides that exposed to radiation used to control pests it doesn't affect negatively on the ecosystem. Several studies confirmed that doses of ionizing radiation do not damage most fresh fruits and vegetables (Hallman, 2011). On the other hand, fungal species such as *Trichoderma viride*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Coriolus versicolor* and *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* strongly

affected on the fertility of snails there were reduces the egg laying capacity of *B. alexandrina* snail (Ragab and Ismail, 2001). Radiation also reduced the reproduction capacity of terrestrial snails. It was decreased the number of eggs laid and prevent the hatching of those laid by the irradiated adults of the land snail, *Cornu aspersum* (Hallman, 2016). Biopesticides also negatively affected on the biochemical parameters of snails. It is decreased the level of total proteins and free amino acids of snails (El-Halim *et al.*, 1990).

This study aimed to evaluate the effect of irradiated and non-irradiated biopesticides *B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae* against the adults of *E. vermiculata* snail. The study also extends to assess the molluscicidal activity of ammonium nitrate alone and as post treatment to snails which pretreated with tested irradiated and non-irradiated biopesticides. The effect of all previous treatments on the biological and biochemical parameters of snails was also investigated.

Materials and methods

1. Collection and maintenance of *Eobania vermiculata* snails:

Adults of *E. vermiculata* were collected from infested navel orange field in Banadf village, Meniet El-Kamh district, Sharkia Governorate, Egypt. The snails were transferred in muslin bags to the laboratory and kept in a glass container ($30 \times 30 \times 50$ cm³) containing moist clay soil and covered with muslin cloth for preventing snails escaping. Snails were supplied daily with fresh cabbage leaves for two weeks before any tests for acclimatization (Abd El-Aal, 2001).

2. Tested biopesticide formulations:

The two biopesticide formulations *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Berliner) and *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Bioranza) which used in this study were obtained from the Central Agricultural Pesticides Laboratory, Dokki, Egypt. Weights of 0.025, 0.05 and 0.1

gram of each biopesticide were diluted separately in 100 ml sterilized distilled water to obtain the under recommended, recommended and up to recommended concentrations of each biopesticide represents as 4×10^3 , 8×10^3 and 16×10^3 spores/ml, consecutively.

3. Exposure of tested biopesticides to UV radiation:

Each biopesticide concentration was exposed to UV light; 254 nm (Philips, 20 W/4C) and at a distance of 50 cm for three times 30, 60 and 90 min. exposure.

4. Preparation of ammonium nitrate solution:

Pure ammonium nitrate (33% N) produced in pills form was purchased from El- Gomhouria Company, Egypt. Three concentrations 0.5, 1 and 2% of this fertilizer were prepared by dissolving the required amount in distilled water to obtain the appropriate concentration (Mahmoud, 1994).

5. Pathogenic activity of the biopesticide formulations exposed and not exposed to the UV radiation against *Eobania vermiculata* snails:

The pathogenic effect of *Bacillus thuringiensis* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* biopesticides at the under recommended, recommended and up to recommended concentration of each one represents as 4×10^3 , 8×10^3 and 16×10^3 spores/ml was assessed separately against adults of *E. vermiculata* snails. Each tested concentration of each biocide was exposed to UV radiation at three exposure times (30 min., 60 min. and 90 min.).

Plastic boxes (3/4 kg capacity) were used, each containing 1/2 kg sterilized clay soil and ten adults of *E. vermiculata* snail. Water holding capacity of the soil was adjusted and ten discs of cabbage leaves were introduced in each box. Each irradiated concentration of both biocides was sprayed separately on the soil and cabbage discs (Foster *et al.*, 1991). Three replicates were

prepared for each concentration. Other adults of the same snail species were treated with the same tested biocides as explained previously exactly, but without exposing their concentrations to radiation. Control boxes were prepared by the same manner without any treatment with three repetitions. All treated and control boxes were tightly covered with muslin cloth and secured with a rubber band for prevent snails escaping. Mortality percentages were recorded for all boxes at intervals of three days for one month and corrected by Abbott's formula (1925). At every time the results are recorded, cabbage discs were changed with other fresh discs.

6. Molluscicidal effect of ammonium nitrate against *Eobania vermiculata* snails:

Ammonium nitrate was tested against the adults of *E. vermiculata* snail at the concentrations 0.5, 1 and 2%. Plastic boxes were used in this experiment, each box contained 1/2 kg moistened clay soil. Ten adults and ten discs of cabbage leaves were placed on the soil surface of each box. The tested concentrations were directly sprayed on the soil and cabbage discs. Three replicates were prepared for each concentration and other three replicates were prepared by the same manner without any treatment as control. All boxes were examined daily, and mortality percentages were recorded for one month.

7. Toxic effect of ammonium nitrate against *Eobania vermiculata* snails pre-treated with non-irradiated and irradiated biopesticides:

Adults of *E. vermiculata* were treated with each of *B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae* at the tested concentrations 4×10^3 , 8×10^3 and 16×10^3 spores/ml for each biocide, respectively. Other adults of the same snail species were treated with the same tested concentrations exposed to UV radiation at the exposure times referred to previously (30 min., 60 min. and 90 min.).

Three replicates were prepared for each irradiated and non-irradiated concentration, each replicate containing ten adult snails. The treatments were carried out by using spray technique as mentioned before in the previous experiments according to Foster *et al.* (1991). After 10 days of the experiment, snails which treated with irradiated and non-irradiated biocides at the tested concentrations were sprayed individually with ammonium nitrate at 0.5, 1 and 2% concentrations, respectively. Mortality percentages were recorded daily for one month.

8. Impact of the tested biopesticides and ammonium nitrate on the biological behavior of *Eobania vermiculata* snail:

During following up the molluscicidal effect of the biopesticides *B. thuringiensis*, *M. anisopliae* (Irradiated and non-irradiated) and ammonium nitrate individually against *E. vermiculata* snails and the treatment of snails with ammonium nitrate after treated with the irradiated and non-irradiated biopesticides in the previous experiments, the egg laying and biological behavior of the snails were also observed. At all of these treatments, treated and control boxes checked every two days for the presence of egg clutches (Hend, 2007). Examination of boxes continued for this purpose for a year, started from the beginning of the study experiments at 15 November 2019 until 20 November 2020.

9. Effect of some tested irradiated biopesticides on the biochemical parameters of *Eobania vermiculata* snail:

Due to the observed effect of tested biopesticides on the biological behavior of *E. vermiculata* snail, the effect of some selected irradiated biopesticide treatments on certain enzymes which related to the reproduction of snails was studied. These treatments were *B. thuringiensis* at under recommended concentration (4×10^3 spores/ml) exposed to UV for 60 min., *M. anisopliae* at up to

recommended concentration (16×10^3 spores/ml) exposed to UV radiation for 60 min. and *M. anisopliae* at recommended concentration (8×10^3 spores/ml) exposed to UV radiation for 90 min. The effect of each of these treatments on the enzymes alkaline and acid phosphatase, amylase, protease and Lipase which strongly related to the reproduction process in snails as mentioned by Clelland *et al.* (2001) and Ademolu *et al.* (2013) was estimated.

Ten snail individuals at 1 g weight were randomly taken from replicates of each of these treatments after 96 hrs. of the treatment. The snails were dissected according to the method of Segun (1975). Tissues of snails were homogenized and centrifuged at 4000 r.p.m. for 30 min. The sediment was discarded while the supernatants were kept in a deep freezer till it's using to determine the levels of alkaline and acid phosphatase, amylase, protease and lipase in tissues of tested and control snails.

The activity of alkaline and acid phosphatase (ALP and ACP) was determined according to the method of Kind and King (1954). While, amylase (AMY), protease (PRO) and lipase (LIP) activities were determined by the methods described by Adedire *et al.* (1999) and Ademolu *et al.* (2009).

10. Statistical analysis

All data from the above experiments were analyzed and the difference between means was tested by Costat (2005) statically program analysis, computer program software. The least significant difference (L.S.D.) at 0.05 level was also calculated.

Results and discussion

1. Pathogenic effect of irradiated and non-irradiated biopesticides against *Eobania vermiculata* snail:

In the treatment of *E. vermiculata* snails with each of *B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae* with and without exposing to the UV radiation, there is no mortality was found

in all boxes till the end of experiment which continued for 21 days. This result was strongly supported by Genena *et al.* (2008) reported that in the treatment of *E. vermiculata* and *Monacha cantiana* snails with eight strains of *B. thuringiensis*, the all strains did not show any adverse effect or mortality against both snail species.

The same results were also confirmed by Kramarz *et al.* (2007) indicated that *B. thuringiensis* had no negative effect against *Helix aspersa* snail under the laboratory conditions. This bacterium also not have observed effect against *Oncomelania hupensis* snail, it was recorded only 1.1% mortality of snails (Gao *et al.*, 2008). While, Zedan (2004) revealed that *M. anisopliae* at the concentrations 0.5×10^8 , 1×10^8 , 2×10^8 and 4×10^8 spores/ml exhibited 28.75, 50, 67.86 and 85.71% mortality of *E. vermiculata* snails after 7 days of treatment, respectively.

The other biopesticide, Biovar (*Beauveria bassiana*) caused 40, 60 and 80% mortality of *Monacha obstructa* snails at the concentrations of 2×10^5 , 4×10^5 and 8×10^5 spores/ml after 6 days of experiment, respectively (Bahy El-Din *et al.*, 2016). At the same trend, Khidr (2015) showed that the double dose from the recommended dose of spinetoram 12% SC, Emamectin benzoate 0.5% EC and Emamectin benzoate 1.92% EC biopesticides recorded high mortality of *E. vermiculata* and *M. obstructa* snails than the using of recommended doses. *M. obstructa* was more sensitive and affected by these bioagents than *E. vermiculata* snails.

On the other hand, Khorramvatan *et al.* (2014) demonstrated that exposing of *B. thuringiensis* to UV radiation not increase its ability to control pests, this may be a return to the destroying effect of radiation against the bacterial conidia which reduce its potency against pests. The same effect was also recorded against the conidia of fungi, leads to decrease its pathogenic activity (Rodrigues *et*

al., 2016). On the other direction, Cortesao *et al.* (2019) showed that UV radiation cause mutation to *Bacillus subtilis* bacterium. The mutagenesis of this bacterium was strongly depending on the function of the structural components, coat layers and the dipicolinic acid as key protectants against the DNA damage. The mutation of bacteria by radiation can makes a severe form of it. This new form had strong pathogenic activity against host (Kong *et al.*, 2010). α / β - type SASP group in the bacterial spores saturate DNA and protect it from damage by the UV radiation (Hathout *et al.*, 2003).

2. Molluscicidal effect of ammonium nitrate against *Eobania vermiculata* snails:

The toxic effect of ammonium nitrate against *E. vermiculata* snails was investigated. As shown in Table (1), snails mortality increased with increasing the ammonium nitrate concentrations and exposure times. After one day of treatment,

Table (1): Molluscicidal effect of ammonium nitrate against *Eobania vermiculata* snails.

Concentrations (%)	Mean of mortality % after indicated days					General mean
	1	3	7	14	21	
0.5	10.00 ^b	10.00 ^b	16.66 ^b	40.00 ^b	43.33 ^b	24.00 ^b
1.0	13.33 ^b	13.33 ^b	20.00 ^b	43.33 ^b	50.00 ^b	28.00 ^b
2.0	56.66 ^a	56.66 ^a	73.33 ^a	73.33 ^a	73.33 ^a	66.66 ^a
Control	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^b	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c
P	.0000 ^{***}	.0000 ^{***}	.0000 ^{***}	.0000 ^{***}	.0000 ^{***}	.0000 ^{***}
L.S.D. 0.05	1.80	1.80	0.76	2.24	1.53	13.08

The same letter in the same column means not significant at $P < 0.05$.

These results were confirmed by Hend (2013) reported that mortality of *E. vermiculata* snails increases with increasing concentrations of ammonium nitrate and the time elapsed. This fertilizer recorded 56.66% mortality of snails at the highest concentration 2% after one day of

ammonium nitrate recorded its highest effect at the highest concentration 2.0% by record 56.66% mortality of snails. It was followed by the concentrations 1 and 0.5% which achieved 13.33 and 10% mortality, respectively. The mortality percentage reached to its maximum value 73.33% at the highest concentration 2% after 7 days of the experiment and then it still stable until the end of experiment. While, the other concentrations 1.0 and 0.5% recorded their highest molluscicidal effect at the end of experiment with 50 and 43.33% mortality after 21 days of the experiment, respectively. No death of snails was found in the control replicates. The obtained results also showed a high significant difference in the mortality of snails treated with the different concentrations in comparing with the control.

experiment. While, the lowest tested concentration 0.5% showed only 20% mortality after the same period of treatment. At the same trend, urea caused 67 and 86% mortality of *E. vermiculata* and *Theba pisana* snails at the concentration 800×10^2 ppm after two days of treatment, respectively. The

same concentration showed 80 and 100% mortality of each snail species after three days of treatment, respectively (Eshra, 2014). El-Wakil (2009) had earlier observed that copper sulfate has a high toxic effect against *T. pisana* snail. While, potassium sulfate recorded a slight effect against the same snail species. Additionally, the using of ammonium bicarbonate has an advantage for being molluscicidal. But, the using of it has declined with the advent of urea and diammonium phosphate. These fertilizers causes agriolimacides and arionides to emit large amounts of mucus, which strongly leads to the dehydration and death of gastropod (Barker, 2002). Consequently, fertilizers considered a newer successful alternative molluscicide instead of pesticides. Moreover, it is safer than pesticides for use around pest and vertebrate wild life (Speiser and Kistler, 2002).

3. Molluscicidal effect of ammonium nitrate against *Eobania vermiculata* snails pre-treated with non irradiated and irradiated biopesticides:

The molluscicidal impact of ammonium nitrate at the concentrations 0.5, 1.0 and 2% against *E. vermiculata* snails which pre treated with the under recommended, recommended and up to recommended concentrations (4×10^3 , 8×10^3 and 16×10^3 spores/ml) of each biocide separately was evaluated, respectively.

As cleared in Table (2), by increasing the concentrations of biopesticides and ammonium nitrate, the mortality percentages of snails increases. Snails which pre treated with *B. thuringiensis* at 4×10^3 spores/ml and then treated with the lowest concentration of ammonium nitrate 0.5% not affected at all until the 7th day of experiment. Low effect of this treatment was appeared at the 14th day of experiment with 13.33% mortality which remained constant until the end of experiment. *M. anisopliae* also recorded its lowest effect at the lowest tested concentration 4×10^3 spores/ml and post treatment with 0.5% of ammonium nitrate, caused only 10% mortality at the first day of experiment. This percentage remained as it is until the 14th day of experiment and then increased to 20% after 21 days. *B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae* gave the same final mortality 43.33% at the recommended concentration 8×10^3 spores/ml and post treatment with ammonium nitrate at the concentration 1%. Moreover, both biopesticides recorded their highest impact at the up to recommended concentration 16×10^3 spores/ml and post treatment with ammonium nitrate at the highest concentration 2% by record 40 and 56.66% mortality after one day of experiment, respectively.

Table (2): Molluscicidal effect of ammonium nitrate against *Eobania vermiculata* snails pre-treated with non irradiated biopesticides.

Pre-treatment with biopesticides Conc. (spores/ml)	Post-treatment with ammonium nitrate Conc. (%)	Mean of mortality % after indicated days					General mean
		1	3	7	14	21	
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>							
4×10^3	0.5	0.00 ^e	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^c	13.33 ^c	13.33 ^d	5.33 ^d
8×10^3	1.0	26.66 ^{bc}	26.66 ^b	26.66 ^b	43.33 ^b	43.33 ^{bc}	33.32 ^b
16×10^3	2.0	40.00 ^b	60.00 ^a	70.00 ^a	70.00 ^a	70.00 ^a	62.00 ^a
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i>							
4×10^3	0.5	10.00 ^{de}	10.00 ^{cd}	10.00 ^{bc}	10.00 ^c	20.00 ^{cd}	12.00 ^{cd}
8×10^3	1.0	20.00 ^{cd}	20.00 ^{bc}	20.00 ^b	20.00 ^c	43.33 ^{bc}	24.66 ^{bc}
16×10^3	2.0	56.66 ^a	56.66 ^a	56.66 ^a	56.66 ^{ab}	56.66 ^{ab}	56.66 ^a
Control		0.00 ^e	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^c	0.00 ^d	0.00 ^d
P		.0000 ^{***}	.0000 ^{***}	.0000 ^{***}	.0000 ^{***}	.0000 ^{***}	.0000 ^{***}
L.S.D. 0.05		1.42	1.42	1.70	2.19	2.41	16.01

The same letter in the same column means not significant at $P < 0.05$.

The mortality 56.66% which recorded by *M. anisopliae* as pre treatment and post treatment with 2% of ammonium nitrate remained constant until the end of experiment. While, the mortality of snails which pre treated with *B. thuringiensis* at the up to recommended concentration 16×10^3

spores/ml and post treated with 2% of ammonium nitrate increased to 70% at the 7th day of experiment and then stabilized till the end of experiment. All tested treatments had significantly higher than the control.

Table (3) showed the effect of ammonium nitrate at the concentrations 0.5,

1 and 2% against *E. vermiculata* snails that pre treated with each of 4×10^3 , 8×10^3 and 16×10^3 spores/ml of *B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae* separately, respectively. Each

concentration of both biopesticides was initially exposed to the UV radiation for 30, 60 and 90 min. before the treatment of snails.

Table (3): Molluscicidal effect of ammonium nitrate against *Eobania vermiculata* snails pre-treated with irradiated biopesticides.

Pre-treatment with biopesticides Conc. (Spores/ml)	Exposure times to UV radiation (min.)	Post-treatment with ammonium nitrate Conc. (%)	Mean of mortality % after indicated days					General mean	
			1	3	7	14	21		
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> 4×10^3	30	0.5	0.00 ^e	0.00 ^e	13.33 ^{fg}	16.66 ^{ef}	16.66 ^{fg}	9.33 ^{fg}	
	60		13.33 ^{de}	13.33 ^{de}	13.33 ^{fg}	20.00 ^e	20.00 ^f	16.00 ^{efg}	
	90		16.66 ^{cde}	16.66 ^{cde}	23.33 ^{def}	23.33 ^{de}	23.33 ^{ef}	20.66 ^{def}	
	8×10^3	30	1.0	0.00 ^e	13.33 ^{de}	13.33 ^{fg}	20.00 ^e	20.00 ^f	13.33 ^{fg}
		60		16.66 ^{cde}	16.66 ^{cde}	20.00 ^{ef}	33.33 ^{cde}	33.33 ^{def}	24.00 ^{def}
		90		20.00 ^{cd}	23.33 ^{cd}	46.66 ^{abc}	46.66 ^{bc}	46.66 ^{bcd}	36.66 ^{bcd}
	16×10^3	30	2.0	46.66 ^{ab}	46.66 ^{ab}	50.00 ^{abc}	50.00 ^{bc}	53.33 ^{abc}	49.33 ^{abc}
		60		50.00 ^{ab}	50.00 ^{ab}	50.00 ^{abc}	56.66 ^{ab}	60.00 ^{ab}	53.33 ^{ab}
		90		56.66 ^a	56.66 ^a	63.33 ^a	70.00 ^a	70.00 ^a	63.33 ^a
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i> 4×10^3	30	0.5	0.00 ^e	10.00 ^{de}	16.66 ^{efg}	20.00 ^e	20.00 ^f	13.33 ^{fg}	
	60		16.66 ^{cde}	16.66 ^{cde}	20.00 ^{ef}	26.66 ^{de}	26.66 ^{ef}	21.32 ^{def}	
	90		16.66 ^{cde}	20.00 ^{cd}	20.00 ^{ef}	26.66 ^{de}	30.00 ^{def}	22.66 ^{def}	
	8×10^3	30	1.0	16.66 ^{cde}	23.33 ^{cd}	23.33 ^{def}	23.33 ^{de}	23.33 ^{ef}	22.00 ^{def}
		60		20.00 ^{cd}	20.00 ^{cd}	20.00 ^{ef}	20.00 ^e	30.00 ^{def}	22.00 ^{def}
		90		23.33 ^{cd}	23.33 ^{cd}	40.00 ^{bcd}	40.00 ^{bcd}	40.00 ^{cde}	33.33 ^{cde}
	16×10^3	30	2.0	20.00 ^{cd}	23.33 ^{cd}	23.33 ^{def}	23.33 ^{de}	30.00 ^{def}	24.00 ^{def}
		60		33.33 ^{bc}	33.33 ^{bc}	33.33 ^{cde}	33.33 ^{cde}	33.33 ^{def}	33.33 ^{cde}
		90		50.00 ^{ab}	50.00 ^{ab}	56.66 ^{ab}	56.66 ^{ab}	56.66 ^{abc}	54.00 ^{ab}
Control			0.00 ^e	0.00 ^e	0.00 ^e	0.00 ^f	0.00 ^g	0.00 ^e	
P			.0000 ***	.0000 ***	.0000 ***	.0000 ***	.0000 ***	.0000 ***	
L.S.D. _{0.05}			1.90	1.89	1.80	1.80	1.73	17.52	

The same letter in the same column means not significant at $P < 0.05$.

It seems clear from the obtains results that by increasing the concentration of ammonium nitrate and biopesticides and the exposure times to UV; the mortality of snails increases. After one day of the experiment, the pre treatment with highest concentration 16×10^3 spores/ml of *B. thuringiensis* that irradiated for 90 min. by UV and post treatment with ammonium nitrate at the highest concentration 2% recorded the highest mortality of snails 56.66%. Over the same period of experiment, *B. thuringiensis* at the other concentrations 8×10^3 and 4×10^3 spores/ml and the same exposure time to UV 90 min. and post treatment with 1 and 0.5% of ammonium nitrate, the mortality of snails were 20 and 16.66%, respectively. The mortality of snails increased gradually by increasing the experiment period, it reached to its maximum value 70% at 16×10^3 spores/ml of the same biopesticide that irradiated with UV for 90 min. and post treatment with 2% of ammonium nitrate after 14 days of experiment. The other two concentrations 8×10^3 and 4×10^3 spores/ml gave their highest activity after 7 days of experiment with record 46.66 and 23.33% mortality at the same exposure time 90 min. and post treatment with 1 and 0.5% of ammonium nitrate, respectively. This activity of these treatments remained stable until the end of the experiment. On the other hand, the pre treatment of snails with *M. anisopliae* at the highest concentration 16×10^3 spores/ml which irradiated by UV for 90 min. and post treatment with 2% of ammonium nitrate record 50% mortality after one day of the experiment. While, the pre treatment of snails with the other concentrations 8×10^3 and 4×10^3 spores/ml that irradiated with UV for the same exposure time 90 min. and post treatment with ammonium nitrate at 1 and 0.5% achieved 23.33 and 16.66% mortality after the same period of experiment, respectively. These treatments gave their maximum effect against snails with record 40

and 30% mortality after 7 and 21 days of the experiment, respectively. While, the highest concentration 16×10^3 spores/ml that exposed to UV for 90 min. and post treatment with 2% of ammonium nitrate showed the highest mortality 56.66% after only 7 days of experiment. This mortality remained constant until the end of the experiment. It is also worth to mention that the maximum mortality which exhibited by the pre treatment with the lowest concentration 4×10^3 of each of *B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae* that exposed to the UV for the lowest exposure time 30 min. and post treatment with the lowest concentration 0.5% of ammonium nitrate were only 16.66 and 20% after 14 days of the experiment, respectively.

Generally, the pre treatment of snails with each of *B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae* at the highest concentration that exposed to UV radiation for 90 min. and then treated with ammonium nitrate at the highest concentration were the most effective treatments against snails. But, the treatment which contained *B. thuringiensis* was clearly outweighs the other which contains *M. anisopliae* during the experiment period. Moreover, the means of snails' mortality were significantly higher in comparison with the untreated snails.

Data in support to the results of Tables 2. and 3. are limited. While, in this trend Ragab and Shoukry (2006) reported that the pre- exposure of *Lymnaea natalensis* snails to each of ammonium nitrate and urea for 24 hr. caused an additive action to niclosamide against snails. In a similar report, Hussein *et al.* (2016) stated that the pre treatment of *Biomphalaria alexandrina* snails with the inorganic fertilizer NPK increased the infection severity by *Schistosoma mansoni* against treated snails. The pre-exposure of the same snail species to anilofos, butachlor and isoprothiolane showed a synergistic effect to uccmaluscide. While, the treatment with isoprothiolane and

butachlor gave additive effect to copper sulphate and niclosamide against snails (Zidan *et al.*, 2002). The pre-exposure of the other snail species, *Theodoxus fluviatilis* to metals due to its originating from a metal contaminated habitat increased tolerance at the post-exposure with metals from antifouling paints compared to snails exposed to metals for one time (Maria *et al.*, 2017). On the other hand, Drauzio *et al.* (2015) revealed that UV radiation induce the production of *Metarhizium robertsii* conidia. It causes a production of resistant mycellium used as formulation to control pests. In a related study, Ariel *et al.* (2017) reported that the blue and red light increased also the production speed and germination of conidia for the same fungus and killed the pests faster. Similarly, Henrique *et al.* (2015) confirmed that UV radiation increased the production of *Colletotrichum acutatum* fungus conidia. Colonies exposed to this radiation produced 1.7 times more conidia than colonies which not exposed and this contributed strongly to increasing the activity of fungus. On the contrary, Khorramvatan (2014) showed that UV radiation obviously reduced the potency of *B. thuringiensis* against the pests. While, Rodrigues *et al.* (2016) stated that preparation of biopesticides as formulation protect the microorganism structure from the damage by UV radiation. Effect of radiation on molds depend on the wave length of the photons which cells are exposed (Fuller *et al.*, 2013). Moderate exposure to the visible light (400 – 700 nm) encourages the production of conidial spores and the harmful secondary metabolites as aflatoxin (Henrique *et al.*, 2015). This toxin has a high lethal effect against animals and humans (Yan *et al.*, 2008).

4. Effect of the biopesticides and ammonium nitrate on the biological behavior of *Eobania vermiculata* snail:

The effect of all study treatments including irradiated and non irradiated biopesticides (*B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae*), ammonium nitrate individually and pre treatment with biopesticides and then treatment with ammonium nitrate on the biological behavior of *E. vermiculata* snails was observed for a year starting from 15 November 2019 to 20 November 2020. The results showed that all treatments had a noticeable and clear negative impact on the biological behavior of treated snails in comparing with the untreated individuals in the control. All study treatments completely prevented the egg laying of snails during the experiment period for a year, except one replicate in the treatment with the recommended concentration 8×10^3 spores/ml of *M. anisopliae* exposed to UV radiation for 90 min. At the end of January 2020, the snails in this replicate laid only one abnormal oval and transparent egg compared to the normal spherical white eggs that were laid by untreated snails in the control (Photo 1). At observing this egg, it is noticed that it completely burst after only five days of it's laying. A month after laying this egg, the snails in the same replicate laid two normal (non-transparent) eggs, but they were also burst after 11 days of their laying. In comparison with the control replicates, the untreated snails laid 18 egg clutches during two months from December 2019 to February 2020. The number of eggs per clutch ranged between 10 and 48 eggs. On the other hand, the hatchability ranged from 93.75 to 100%. While, the mean of incubation and hatching periods was 23.7 and 4.6 days, respectively.

Photo (1 A , B): *Eobania vermiculata* eggs. A, view of abnormal oval and transparent egg laid by *E. vermiculata* snails treated with irradiated *M. anisopliae*. B, view of normal eggs laid by untreated *E. vermiculata* snails.

These results are in agreement with Ragab and Ismail (2001) indicated that the fungal strains; *Trichoderma viride*, *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*, *Coriolus versicolor* and *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* were highly reduced the egg laying capacity of *B. alexandrina* snail. Moreover, the fungus *Aspergillus fumigatus* completely prevent the eggs hatching of the same snail species (Gamalat *et al.*, 2013). In the same trend, Hend (2007) confirmed that *Fusarium oxysporum* and *Fusarium semitectum* were strongly decreased the number of eggs laid by *Cochlicella acuta* snail. While, *Trichoderma harzianum* completely prevent the egg laying of both of *C. acuta* and *Theba pisana* snails. The same author added that *Aspergillus ochraceus* caused observed burst of *T. pisana* eggs after three days of their laying. On the other hand, the ultraviolet radiation reduced also the reproduction capacity of snails (Ragheb *et al.*, 2018). Consequently, it is highly decreased the number of eggs laid by the land snail, *Cornu aspersum* and prevent the hatching of these eggs (Hallman, 2016). Moreover, it is rapidly killed the embryos of *Planorbarius* snail (Martin, 2008). It is worth noting that ammonium nitrate also has strong negative effect on the biological behavior of snails. It is prevented the egg hatching of *E. vermiculata* and *Monacha cartusiana* snails at the tested concentrations of 0.5, 1, 1.5 and 2% (Hend, 2013). This finding also parallels

the report of Gomaa *et al.* (2008) assured that ammonium nitrate has a potent toxic effect against the *E. vermiculata* eggs. Additionally, bayluscide and hydrothol 191 cause high reduction of the egg laying capacity of *B. alexandrina* snail at the sublethal concentration as earlier reported by Abd El-Latif *et al.* (1987).

5. Biochemical impact of some irradiated biopesticides on *Eobania vermiculata* snail:

Some treatments were chosen for this assay, which is *B. thuringiensis* at 4×10^3 spores/ml exposed to UV radiation for 60 min. as one from the *B. thuringiensis* treatments which prevented egg laying during the study period, *M. anisopliae* at 16×10^3 spores/ml exposed to UV for 60 min. as one from the *M. anisopliae* treatments which prevented egg laying also and *M. anisopliae* at 8×10^3 spores/ml exposed to UV for 90 min. as treatment including snails showed noticeable and strange phenomenon, that laid one transparent egg which burst after laying. The effect of these treatments on the activity of enzymes that strongly related with the biological behavior of snails is investigated.

As illustrated in Table (4), *B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae* exposed to UV for 60 min. caused observed decrease in the activity of alkaline phosphatase enzyme to 684 and 662 U/g, respectively in comparing with 837 U/g in the control. Whereas, the treatment of snails with *M.*

anisopliae exposed to UV for 90 min. showed slightly increase in the activity of the same enzyme to 843 U/g. *B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae* exposed to UV for 60 and 90 min. induced observed increase in the activity of acid phosphatase enzyme from

1095.66 U/g in the control to 1124.33 and 1215.33 U/g, respectively. Conversely, *M. anisopliae* exposed to UV for 60 min. reduced the activity of the same enzyme to 1043.66 U/g.

Table (4): Effect of some irradiated biopesticides on the enzymes activity of *Eobania vermiculata* snail.

Biopesticides Conc. (spores/ml)	Exposure times to UV radiation (min.)	ALP (wt.b.g/mU)	ACP (wt.b.g/mU)	AMY (wt.b.g/min/ glucose ug)	PRO (wt.b.g/min/ alanine-L,D ug)	LIP (wt.b.g/mU)
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i> 4×10^3	60	684.00 ± 2.89	1124.33 ± 1.76	36.83 ± 1.30	63.60 ± 1.20	99.00 ± 2.51
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i> 16×10^3	60	662.00 ± 2.51	1043.66 ± 3.28	43.33 ± 1.08	68.73 ± 1.56	131.00 ± 2.08
<i>Metarhizium anisopliae</i> 8×10^3	90	843.00 ± 2.52	1215.33 ± 2.03	68.23 ± 1.42	49.33 ± 1.31	122.66 ± 1.20
Control		837.00 ± 1.15	1095.66 ± 2.96	84.73 ± 2.34	57.56 ± 1.62	125.00 ± 3.22

ALP = Alkaline phosphatase

ACP = Acid phosphatase

AMY = Amylase PRO = Protease

LIP = Lipase

Regarding amylase enzyme, all treatments caused clear decline in the activity of it to 36.83, 43.33 and 68.23 U/g by *B. thuringiensis*, *M. anisopliae* exposed to UV for 60 min. and *M. anisopliae* exposed to UV for 90 min., respectively compared with 84.73 U/g in the control. While, *B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae* exposed to UV for 60 min. increase the activity of protease enzyme from 57.56 U/g in the

control to 63.60 and 68.73 U/g, respectively. On the other hand, *M. anisopliae* exposed to UV for 90 min. caused clear reduction in the activity of the same enzyme to 49.33 U/g. Highly decrease in the activity of lipase enzyme was achieved by *B. thuringiensis* exposed to UV for 60 min. which recorded 99 U/g followed by *M. anisopliae* exposed to UV for 90 min. which reduced it to 122.66 U/g in comparison with 125 U/g in the

control. Whereas, *M. anisopliae* exposed to UV for 60 min. increase the activity of the same enzyme to 131 U/g. These results are in harmony with those obtained by Kandil *et al.* (2014) showed that abamectin reduced the activity of alkaline and acid phosphatase enzymes in *E. vermiculata* snail from 768.3 and 3.37 U/L in the control to 373.3 and 1.05 U/L, respectively. Similarly, it is decreased also the total lipid of the same snail species to 2.16 g/dl in comparison with 7.03 g/dl in the control. Whereas, it is increased the total protein from 0.17 g/dl in the control to 2.83 g/dl. On the contrary, Emamectin benzoate 0.5% EC and 1.92% EC caused observed reduction in the total protein of *E. vermiculata* individuals but spinetoram 12% SC highly enhanced it. All these biopesticides induced an increasing in the level of alkaline and acid phosphatase enzymes of the same snail species after 48 hrs. of the treatment (Khidr, 2015). El-Halim *et al.* (1990) had earlier reported that most parasites reduced the level of total proteins and free amino acids of snails which may cleared that the parasite obtains its protein requirements and amino acid from the host. Disturbance in the functions of the internal organs of snails may lead to alterations in the protein functions and metabolic processes was strongly depending on the tested compound and concentration (Tolba *et al.*, 1997). On the other hand, UV exposure caused also abnormal biochemical and physiological processes in invertebrates (Misra *et al.*, 2005). The abnormal depression in the total lipid may be due to the decrease of lipid synthesis capacity or attribute to an increase in the hydrolysis of hepatic lipid due to the stress conditions (Saxena *et al.*, 1989). Moreover, an increase in the total protein could be due to an increasing of biosynthesis process occurred by high enzyme stress (Khater *et al.*, 1990).

In summary, this study supported the use of ammonium nitrate fertilizer at low

concentrations as effective molluscicide against *E. vermiculata* snail. This was also the first report on the effect of UV radiation on the activity of *B. thuringiensis* and *M. anisopliae* biopesticides against this snail species. The post treatment of snails with ammonium nitrate at the highest concentration after the treatment with the highest concentration of each biopesticide exposed to UV for 90 min. has the most ability to kill snails. Moreover, all treatments of this study prevent the egg laying of snails and have observed negative impact on the enzymes activity of snails. So, these compounds could be developed as promising molluscicide candidates which additionally are much safer than existing molluscicides for control land snails. In addition, due to its ability to reduce the egg laying of snails it can be considered future compounds have a superior ability to reduce large numbers and many generations of *E. vermiculata* snails in the fields.

References

- Abbott, W. S. (1925):** A method computing the effectiveness of an insecticide. J. Econ. Entomol., 18 : 265-267.
- Abd El-Aal, S. M. (2001):** Studies on certain land snails at Sharkia Governorate. M. Sc. Thesis, Fac. Agric., Zagazig University.
- Abd El-Latif, M. F.; Ali, F. A.; El-Gendy, M. S. and Ahmed, A. H. (1987):** The effect of sublethal concentrations of three pesticides on fecundity and egg viability of *Biomphalaria alexandrina* snail. Al-Azhar J. Agric. Res., 7: 170-176.
- Adedire, C. O.; Imevbore, E. A.; Eyide, E. O. and Ayodele, W. I. (1999):** Aspects of digestive physiology and the complementary roles of the microbial enzymes in the intestinal tract of the giant land snail, *Archachatina marginata* (Swainson). J. Technosci., 3: 6-13.

- Ademolu, K. O.; Fakeye, O. D.; Dedeke, G. A. and Idowu, A. B. (2009):** Activities of glycolysidases in the foot muscles of African Giant land snail, *Archachatina marginata* during aestivation. Ethiopian J. Biol. Sci., 8 : 16-21.
- Ademolu, K. O.; Taiwo, B. E.; Jayeola, O. A. and Ajayi, O. (2013):** Egg laying and albumen gland composition of *Archachatina marginata* during growth phases. Arch. Zootec., 62 (240) : 603-606.
- Ariel, S. O.; Drauzio, E. N. R. and Gilberto, U. L. B. (2017):** *Metarhizium robertsii* illuminated during mycelial growth produces conidia with increased germination speed and virulence. Fungal Biol., 122 (6) : 555-562.
- Azzam, K. M. and Belal, M. H. (2003):** Effect of temperature on the molluscicidal activity of vicyoback12AS against *Eobania vermiculata* Muller. J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 28 (3): 2343-2348.
- Bahy El-Din, I. A.; Kares, E. A. and El-Khawas, M. A. M. (2016):** Bioassay of three biopesticides against *Hypera brunneipennis* (Boheman) (Coleoptera : Curculionidae) and *Monacha obstructa* Ferussac. (Mollusca : Helicidae) in the laboratory. Annals of Agric. Sci., Moshtohor, 54 (3) : 669-676.
- Barker, G. M. (2002):** Molluscs as crop pests. CAB, International, Wallingford Oxon 108 DE. U.K., 468.
- Batista, F. A.; Alves, S. B.; Alves, L. F. A.; Pereira, R. M. and Augusto, N. T. (1998):** Formulation of entomopathogens. In: Alves, S. B., Ed., Controle Microbiano de Insetos, 2nd Edition, Fealq, Piracicaba, 917-965.
- Burges, H. D. (1998):** Formulation of microbial pesticides. Springer, Dordrecht.
- Butt, T.; Jackson, C. and Magan, N. (2001):** Fungi as biocontrol agents. CAB International, London, UK, 24-48.
- Clelland, E.; Di Renna, T. and Saleuddin, A. S. M. (2001):** The structure of the bursa Copulatrix in virgin and mated snails, *Helisoma duryi* (Mollusca): Role of acid phosphatase in reproduction. Invert. Biol., 120 (1): 1-12.
- Cortezao, M.; Fuchs, F. M. and Moeller, R. (2019):** *Bacillus subtilis* spore resistance to simulated mars surface conditions. Front Microbiol., 10 : 333.
- Costat (2005):** Version 6.311, Copyright(c), CoHort Software, 798 Lighthouse Ave. PMB 320, Monterey, CA, 93940, USA.
- Drauzio, E. N. R.; Gilberto, U. L. B.; Everton, K. K. F. and Chad, A. K. (2015):** Stress tolerance and virulence of insect pathogenic fungi are determined by environmental conditions during conidial formation. Current Genetics, 61 (3): 383-404.
- El-Halim, A.; Saad, A. and Mohamed, S. H. (1990).** The relation between infection of *S. mansoni* and free amino acids and total proteins of *B. alexandrina*. J. Egypt Soc. Parasitol., 20 (1) : 411-415.
- El-Metwally, M.M.; Ghanim, N.M. and El-Kady, S.M. (2010):** Local bacterial isolates of entomopathogenic agents against the citrus flower moth, *Prays citri* Miller (Lepidoptera: Hyponomeutidae) in lime orchards at North Delta region, Egypt. Bull. Ent. Soc. Egypt, Econ. Ser., 36:171-184.
- El-Wakil, H. B. (2009):** Molluscicidal activity and repellency of some

- inorganic fertilizers against terrestrial snail, *Theba pisana* (Muller). infesting citrus trees in Northern areas, Egypt. Science J., 11 (1) : 1-11.
- Eshra, E. H. (2013):** Survey and distribution of terrestrial snails in fruit orchards and ornamental plants at Alexandria and EL-Beheira Governorate, Egypt. Alexan. Sci. Exch. J., 34 (2): 242-248.
- Eshra, E. H. (2014):** Toxicity of methomyl, copper hydroxide and urea fertilizer on some land snails. Annals of Agric. Sci., 59 (2) : 281-284.
- Foster, R. N.; Reuter, K. C.; Bradley, C. A. and Wood, P. P. (1991):** Preliminary investigations on the effect of *Beauveria bassiana* on several species of rangeland grasshoppers. In: Cooperative Grasshopper Integrated Pest Management Project, 1991 Annual Report. Boise, ID: U.S. Department of Agriculture, Animal and Plant Health Inspection Service, 203-208.
- Fuller, K. K.; Ringelberg, C.; Loros, J. J. and Dunlap, J. C. (2013):** The fungal pathogen *Aspergillus fumigatus* regulates growth, metabolism and stress resistance in response to light. mBio, 4 (2) : 1-11.
- Gabr, W. M.; Fatma, K. K. and Youssef, A. S. (2006):** Effect of spinosad biocide as a bait and contact applications against three land snail species. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 84 (5) : 1403-1409.
- Gamalat, Y. O.; Mohamed, A. M.; Kader, A. A. and Mohamed, A. A. (2013):** Biological and biochemical impacts of the fungal extract of *Aspergillus fumigatus* on *Biomphalaria alexandrina* snails infected with *Schistosoma mansoni*. Res. and Rev. in Bio Sci., 7 (12) : 473-484.
- Gao, M.; Li, R.; Dai, S.; Wu, Y. and Yi, D. (2008):** Diversity of *Bacillus thuringiensis* strains from soil in China and their pesticidal activities. Biological Control, 44 : 380-388.
- Genena, M. A. M. and Mostafa, F. A. M. (2010):** Biological control of the clover land snail, *Monacha cantiana* (Montagu) using the Rhabditid nematode, *Phasmarhabditis hermaphrodita* (Schneider) under mini-plot field conditions. Egypt. J. Agronematol., 9 (2) : 149-156.
- Genena, M. A. M.; Mohamed, G. and Mostafa, F. A. M. (2008):** Impact of eight bacterial isolates of *Bacillus thuringiensis* against the two land snails *Monacha cantiana* and *Eobania vermiculata* (Gastropoda: Helicidae). J. Agric. Sci. Mansoura Univ., 33 (7): 2853-2861.
- Gomaa, E. A.; Omar, A. E.; El-Sisi, A. G. and Eskander, M. A. (2008):** Screening of different materials for ovicidal effect on the land snail *Eobania vermiculata* (Muller). Zag. J. Agric. Res., 35 (1) : 113-122.
- Hallman, G. J. (2011).** Phytosanitary applications of irradiation. Comprehensive Rev. of Food Sci. and Technol., 10: 143-151.
- Hallman, G. J. (2016).** Phytosanitary irradiation of the invasive herbivorous terrestrial snail *Cornu aspersum* (Stylommatophora: Helicidae). Florida Entomologist, 99 (2): 156-158.
- Hathout, Y.; Setlow, B.; Cabrera-Martinez, R. M.; Fenselau, C. and Setlow, P. (2003):** Small, acid-soluble proteins as biomarkers in mass spectrometry analysis of *Bacillus* spores. Appl. Environ. Microbiol., 69 : 1100–1107.
- Hend, Sh. G. (2007):** Studies on certain external and internal parasites

- infesting some land snails. M. Sc. Thesis, Fac. of Sci., Benha University .
- Hend, Sh. G. (2013):** Efficiency of some biological and chemical compounds and their combinations for control some land snails. Ph. D. Thesis, Fac. of Sci., Benha University.
- Hendawy, A. S.; El-Fakhanny, S. K. and Samy, M. A. (2015):** Laboratory and field evaluation of molluscicidal activity of native biological isolates compared to an insecticide against the land snails, *Monacha* spp. on lettuce and cabbage plantations. Egypt. J. Biol. Pest Control, 25 (3) : 675-678.
- Henrique, D. M.; Stephan, D. F.; Nelson, M. and Geraldo, J. S. (2015):** Growth under visible light increases conidia and mucilage production and tolerance to UV-B radiation in the plant pathogenic fungus *Colletotrichum acutatum*. Photochem. and Photobiol., 91 (2) : 397-402.
- Hussein, R. M.; Marie, M. A. S.; El-Deeb, F. A. and Sayed, S. S. M. (2016):** Effects of three inorganic fertilizers on the biology and histopathology of infected *Biomphalaria alexandrina* snails. Res. J. of Pharmac., Biol. and Chem. Sci., 7 (4) : 2564-2574.
- Kandil, M. A.; El-Deeb, H. I.; Eweis, E. A.; Gabr, W. M. and Soha, A. M. (2014):** Effect of acetylsalicylic acid on the physiological role of mucus gland of land snail species. Egypt. J. Agric. Res., 92 (1) : 53-73.
- Kares, E. A.; El- Khawas, M. A. M. and Ebaid, G. H. (2012):** Efficacy of a bacterial insecticide, on unparasitized and parasitized lesser cotton leafworm *Spodoptera exigua* Hbn. larvae by the endoparasitoid *Microplitis rufiventris* Kok. Annals of Agric. Sci. Moshtohor, 50 (4) : 497-502.
- Khater, A. A.; El-Sheakh, A. A.; El-Sheamy, M. K. and Hussein, M. Z. (1990):** Biochemical effects of lannate and larvin on *Tilapia nilotica* fingerlings. Egypt. J. Appl. Sci., 5 (8) : 227-235.
- Khidr, E. K. (2015):** Effect of some environmentally safety biopesticides on some land molluscs species in Qalubia and Sharkia Governorates. Ph. D. Thesis, Ain Shams University .
- Khorramvatan, S.; Marzban, R.; Ardjmand, M.; Safekordi, A. and Askary, H. (2014):** The effect of polymers on the stability of micro encapsulated formulations of *Bacillus thuringiensis* subsp. Kurstaki (Bt-KD2) after exposure to ultraviolet radiation. Biocont. Sci. Technol., 24 : 462-472.
- Kind, P. R. N. and King, E. J. (1954):** Estimation of plasma phosphatase by determination of hydrolysed phenol with amino antipyrine. J. Clin. Path., 7: 322-326.
- Kong, X. F.; Vogt, G.; Chapgier, A.; Lamaze, C.; Bustamante, J.; Prando, C.; Fortin, A.; Puel, A.; Feinberg, J.; Zhang, X. X.; Gonnord, P.; Pihkala, U. M.; Arola, M.; Moilanen, P.; Abei, L.; Korppi, M.; Boisson, D.S. and Casanova, J. L. (2010):** A novel form of cell type-specific partial IFN-gamma R1 deficiency caused by a germ line mutation of the IFNGR1 initiation codon. Hum. Mol. Genet., 19 (3) : 434-444.
- Kramarz, P. E.; Vaufleury, A.; Zygmunt, P. M. and Verdun, C. (2007):** Increased response to cadmium and *Bacillus thuringiensis* maize toxicity in the snail, *Helix aspersa* infected by

- the nematode, *Phasmarhabditis hermaphrodita*. Environ. Toxicol. Chem., 26 (1) : 73-79.
- Mahmoud, M. F. (1994):** Ecological, biological and toxicological studies on land snails. M. Sc. Thesis, Fac. Agric. Cairo University.
- Maria, A. B.; Burkard, W.; Xueli, G. and Bethanie, C. A. and Ann-Kristin, E. W. (2017):** Mortality and histopathological effects in harbour-transplanted snails with different exposure histories. Aquatic Toxicol., 190 : 11-20.
- Marques, E. J.; Alves, S. B. and Marques, I. M. R. (2000):** Virulence of *Beauveria bassiana* (Bals.) Vuill. To *Diatraea saccharalis* (F.) (Lepidoptera : Crambidae) after conidia storage in low temperature. Anais da Sociedade Entom. do Brasil, 29 : 303-307.
- Martin, W. (2008):** Ecological modulation of environmental stress: interactions between ultraviolet radiation, epibiotic snail embryos, plants and herbivores. J. of Animal Ecol., 77 (3) : 549-557.
- Martyn, M. C.; Carlos, L. B.; Janet, F.B.; Stephan, D. F.; Lars, O. B.; Alan, H. T.; Kulandaivelu, G. and Manfred, T. (2003):** Terrestrial ecosystems, increased solar ultraviolet radiation and interactions with other climatic change factors. Photochem. Photobiol. Sci., 2 : 29-38.
- Misra, R.B.; Lal, K.; Farooq, M. and Hans, R.K. (2005):** Effect of solar UV radiation on earthworm (*Metaphire posthuma*). Ecotoxicology and Environmental Safety, 62(3): 391-396.
- Moussa, S.; Abouelmaaty, H.G.; Hamada, H. A. and Hemieda, E. A. (2014):** Evaluation of *Bacillus thuringiensis* Cry 1 ca strain and *Metarhizium anisopliae* fungus against potato tuber moth, *Phthorimaea operculella* (Zeller) (Lepidoptera : Gelechiidae). Egypt. J. Biol. Pest Control, 24 (2) : 515-521.
- Ragab, F. and Ismail, H. (2001):** Biological activity of certain fungal extracts against *B. alexandrina* snails. 1st Conf. of safe alternative of pesticides for pest management. Assiut Univ., Egypt, 28-29, 273-284.
- Ragab, F. and Shoukry, N. M. (2006):** Influence of certain fertilizers on the activity of some molluscicides against *Biomphalaria alexandrina* and *Lymnaea natalensis* snails. J. Egypt. Soc. Parasitol., 36 (3) : 959-977.
- Ragheb, M.; El-Tayeb, T. A.; El-Emam, A. and Amer, M. A. (2018):** Fecundity, sex hormones and release of cercariae of *Schistosoma mansoni* in *Biomphalaria alexandrina* treated with copper and magnesium chlorophyllin. Folia Malacol., 26 (1) : 17-24.
- Rangel, D. E. N.; Anderson, A. J. and Roberts, D. W. (2008):** Evaluating physical and nutritional stress during mycelial growth as inducers of tolerance to heat and UV-B radiation in *Metarhizium anisopliae* conidia. Mycological Res., 112 : 1362-1372.
- Rodrigues, I. M.; Forim, M. R.; Silva, M. F.; Fernandes, J. B. and Filho, A. B. (2016):** Effect of ultraviolet radiation on fungi *Beauveria bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae*, pure and encapsulated and bio-insecticide action on *Diatraea saccharalis*. Advances in Entomol., 4 : 151-162.
- Saxena, P. K.; Singh V. P.; Kondal J. K. and Soni G. L. (1989):** Effect of some pesticides on *in vitro* lipid and protein synthesis by the liver of the

- freshwater teleost, *Channa punctatus* (BL.). Environ. Pollut., 58 : 273-276.
- Scott, G. and Crunkilton, R. L. (2000):** Acute and chronic toxicity of nitrate to fathead minnows (*Pimephales promelas*), *Ceriodaphnia dubia* and *Daphnia magna*. Environ. Toxicol. Chem., 19 : 2918-2922.
- Segun, A.O. (1975):** The giant land snail *Archachatina marginata*, Swainson. Ethiopic Publishing House and Mid West Communication Corporation. Benin City. Nigeria. pp. 1-9.
- Speiser, B. and Kistler. C. (2002):** Field tests with a molluscicides containing iron phosphate. Crop Protection, 21 : 389-394.
- Tolba, M. R.; Mohamed, B. and Mohamed, M. (1997) :** Effect of some heavy metals on respiration, mean enzyme activity and total protein of the pulmonate snails *B. alexandrina* and *B. truncatus*. J. Egypt Ger. Soc. Zool., 24 (D) : 17-35.
- Vu, V. H.; Hong, S. I. and Kim, K. (2007):** Selection of Entomopathogenic fungi for aphid control. J. Biosci. and Bioengin, 104 (6) : 498-505.
- Yan, Y.; Lei, Y. and Zhong, M. (2008):** Biological control of aflatoxin contamination of crops. J. of Zhejiang Univ. Sci. B.; 9 (10) : 787-792.
- Zappelini, L. O.; Almeida, J. E.; Batista, F. A. and Giometti, F. H. C. (2010):** Isolates selection of entomopathogenic fungus *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Metsch.) Sorok. Aiming control of sugarcane borer *Diatraea saccharalis* (Fabr., 1794). Arquivos do Instituto Biol., 77 : 75-82.
- Zedan, H. A. A. (2004):** Fungicidal activity of *Metarhizium anisopliae* against some land snail species under laboratory conditions. J. of Agric. Sci., Mansoura Univ., 29 (5) : 54.
- Zidan, Z. H.; Ragab, F. M. and Mohamed K. H. (2002):** Molluscicidal activities of certain pesticide and their mixtures against *Biomphalaria alexandrina*. J. Egypt. Soc. Parasitol., 32 (1) : 285-296.

Egyptian Journal of Plant
Protection Research Institute

www.ejprii.eg.net

Genetic profile characterization of *Earias insulana* (Lepidoptera:Noctuidae) in Egypt

Hemat, Z. Moustafa; Mervat, A. Kandil and El-Bassouiny, H. M.

Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Dokki, Giza, Egypt.

ARTICLE INFO

Article History

Received: 28/4/2021

Accepted: 29/ 6 /2021

Keywords

Earias insulana, genetic profile, SCoT, ISSR, peroxidase and polyphenyl-oxidase isozymes.

Abstract:

Genetic profile of *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera:Noctuidae) larvae was identified by two genetic techniques (SCoT and ISSR) using PCR. Seven SCoT primers (SCoT1, SCoT2, SCoT4, SCoT7, SCoT11, SCoT12 and SCoT15) resulted in twelve different bands with molecular weight between 975 and 165bp, while, five ISSR primers (49A, 49B, HB-10, HB-11 and HB-12) resulted in fifteen different bands with molecular weight between 1630 and 175 bp. The genome profile characterization using SCoT technique for *E. insulana* was studied for the first time in the present work. *E. insulana* field strains were collected from five okra fields in different Governorates ; Behera, Alexandria, Menofia, Qaluobya and Sharkeya during season 2019 compared to the reared laboratory strain to investigate genetic study. Results of isozymes showed differences among larvae in five Governorates , polyphenyl oxidase was different in all tested larvae. Whereas, two bands were appeared in larvae from Alexandria governorate of peroxidase, while, larvae from Qaluobya and Sharkeya Governorates have only light different band as control (Laboratory).

Introduction

The spiny bollworm (SBW) *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is one of the most dangerous pests attacking many plants of Malvaceae family, especially okra *Abelmos esculentaus*. It's one of the most important vegetable crops (Kandil, 2013), larvae of *E. insulana* feeds on terminal shoots, flower buds and fruits. It has been recorded for several countries of Asia and Africa and is also known as a cotton pest (Kumar *et al.*, 2014).

In recent years, many new marker techniques have been developed for genomic research (Gupta and Rustgi, 2004). A novel

marker system called Start Codon Targeted (SCoT) Polymorphism (Collard and Mackill, 2002) was developed based on the short conserved region. SCoT markers are generally reproducible, and it is suggested that primer length and annealing temperature are not the sole factors determining reproducibility, SCoT markers have been used to evaluate genetic polymorphism, identify genotypes, and DNA fingerprinting in various species.

Inter simple sequence repeat (ISSR) markers are considered very useful in in distinguishing, fingerprint and assessment genetic diversity studies of genetic diversity, phylogeny, genomics and evolutionary biology

(Reddy *et al.*, 2002 and Havlíčková *et al.*, 2014). ISSR-PCR was already known as a very effective method to understand intra-specific and genetic structure of populations (Fang and Roose, 1997; Ge and Sun, 1999; Zhou *et al.*, 1999 and Nagaraju *et al.*, 2001) to generate species-specific genomic fingerprints (Gupta *et al.*, 1994 and Huang and Sun, 2000). Levy *et al.* (1992) reported that strain identification of *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J.E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) larvae is helpful in developing effective and specific pest management plans to control these insects. Field trapped moths from various geographical locations could also be assessed by this method.

Imbalance between the production of (ROS) and antioxidant processes cause rapid increase in reactive oxygen species ROS levels in tissues causes oxidative stress (OS) and damage to DNA, lipids, or proteins (Zhang *et al.*, 2015 and Matsumura *et al.*, 2017). Generating ROS in the body occurs naturally as a product of many metabolic processes. ROS can be produced by plants as protection against phytophagous insects (Krishnan *et al.*, 2007). Organisms have also evolved antioxidant enzymes that catalyze the removal of ROS, thereby preventing damage to tissues (Cadenas, 1989). (Polyphenoloxidase) PPO and POD (Peroxidase) oxidoreductases are involved in the metabolism of plant phenolic compounds. They play a key role in the aphid's digestion process (Chrzanowski *et al.*, 2012). Polyphenol oxidase (PPO) enzyme catalyzes the hydroxylation of monophenols to o-diphenols through monophenol oxidase activity and a subsequent oxidation of these o-diphenols to the corresponding o-quinones by a catecholase/diphenolase activity in the presence of its cosubstrate oxygen Polyphenol oxidase (1,2-benzenediol:oxygen oxidoreductase; EC 1.10.3.1) In insects, it is involved in sclerotization of the insect cuticle. A remarkably large number of reactions occur, and polyphenol oxidase appears to be involved in more than just the initial oxidation of the o-diphenol to quinone methide or quinone (Sugumaran, 1988).

Peroxidases (EC number 1.11.1.7) are a large group of enzymes which play a role in various biological processes. They have antioxidant features that catalyzed the reactive oxygen species (ROS) using

hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) generated during metabolism and are converted into harmless molecules (Foyer and Harbinson, 1994). They are named after the fact that they commonly break up peroxides (Torres *et al.*, 2002) expressed and purified peroxidase isozyme C as a fusion protein in *S. frugiperda*.

According to the importance of the biochemical genetic basis it had been found that there were variabilities between isozymes activity in two populations of the *Pectinophora gossypiella* and *E. insulana* (Bartlett, 1981 and Sayed and EL-Ghobary, 2019).

Our work aimed to identify the genetic profile of *E. insulana* genome by using two techniques; SCoT and ISSR and study the isoforms of some enzymes electrophoretically detected by native gel electrophoresis of spiny bollworm strains from five Governorates compared to laboratory strain.

Material and methods

1. Insect field collection:

Field strains of *E. insulana* were collected from okra field from five different Governorates Behera, Alexandria, Menofia, Qaluobya and Sharkeya during season 2019 compared to the reared laboratory strain for isozymes study. The collected okra was dissected carefully, and the obtained larvae were kept in test tubes to perform the isozymes or DNA analysis.

2. Insect laboratory rearing:

Larvae of *E. insulana* used in this experiment was obtained from laboratory colony of Bollworm Department, Plant Protection Research Institute; Agricultural Research Center (ARC), reared for several generations under constant condition of 26 ± 2 °C and 65±5 % RH. on an artificial diet that previously described by (Amer, 2015).

3. DNA isolation procedure:

The bulked DNA extraction was performed using DNeasy insect Mini Kit (Qiagen). Larvae tissues were ground using liquid nitrogen to a fine powder, then, 400 µl of buffer AP1, 5 µl of proteinase k and 5 µl of

Lysozyme were added to a maximum of 100 mg of extracted larvae then vortexed vigorously. Mixture was incubated for 10 min at 65°C and mixed 2-3 times during incubation by inverting tube. PCR was performed in 30-µl volume tubes according to Williams *et al.* (1990).

4. Polymerase chain reaction (PCR) condition for SCoT and ISSR:

The DNA amplifications were performed in an automated thermal cycle (Model Techno

512) programmed for one cycle at 94° C for 4 min followed by 45 cycles of 1 min at 94° C, 1 min at 57° C, and 2 min at 72° C. the reaction was finally stored at 72° C for 10 min and the used primers for SCoT were mentioned in Table (1) and primers used for ISSR were mentioned in Table (2).

Table (1): List of the primer names and their nucleotide sequences used in the study for SCoT procedure

No.	Name	Sequence
1	SCoT 1	5` ACG ACA TGG CGA CCA CGC 3`
2	SCoT 2	5` ACC ATG GCT ACC ACC GGC 3`
3	SCoT 4	5` ACC ATG GCT ACC ACC GCA 3`
4	SCoT 7	5` ACA ATG GCT ACC ACT GAC 3`
5	SCoT 11	5` ACA ATG GCT ACC ACT ACC 3`
6	SCoT 12	5` CAA CAA TGG CTA CCA CCG 3`
7	SCoT 15	5` CCA TGG CTA CCA CCG GCT 3`

Table (2): List of the primer names and their nucleotide sequences used in the study for ISSR procedure

No.	Name	Sequence
1	49A	5` CAC ACA CAC ACA AG 3`
2	49B	5` CAC ACA CAC ACA GG 3`
3	HB-10	5` GAG AGA GAG AGA CC 3`
4	HB-11	5` GTG TGT GTG TGT TGT CC 3`
5	HB-12	5`CAC CAC CAC GC 3`

Isozymes electrophoresis

Analysis of samples for isozyme expression by native gel electrophoresis. Native-polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis (Native-PAGE) was conducted to identify isozyme variations among studied strains according to Stegemann *et al.* (1985).

5. Extraction of isozymes:

Isozymes extraction from larvae of the tested five Governorates homogenizing 0.5 g fresh leaves samples in 1 ml extraction buffer (10% glycerol) using a mortar and pestle. The extract was then transferred into clean eppendorf tubes and centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 5 minutes. The supernatant was transferred to new clean eppendorf tubes and kept at -20°C until use for electrophoretic analysis. *E. insulana* larvae samples were used separately for isozymes extraction. The utilized isozymes are

polyphenyl oxidase (PPO) and peroxidase (Px).

6. Data analysis:

Gels were photographed scanned, analyzed using Gel Doc VILBER LOURMAT system (Yang and Quiros, 1993).

Results and discussion

1. SCoT analysis:

Seven SCoT primers and their nucleotide sequences (SCoT1, SCoT2, SCoT4, SCoT7, SCoT11, SCoT12 and SCoT15) illustrated in Table (1) were used in this technique to identify *E. insulana* genome profile, the laboratory strain showed different bands ranged between 4 to 9 bands, varying from 165 to 975 base pairs for each primer showed in Table (3) and Figure (1).

Table (3): Numbers and DNA bands molecular weight by the seven SCOT primers for *Earias insulana* larvae.

Band No	M.W Bp	SCOT Primers						
		SCOT 1	SCOT 2	SCOT 4	SCOT 7	SCOT 11	SCOT 12	SCOT 15
		1	975	-	-	-	-	-
2	845	-	-	-	-	1	-	1
3	800	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
4	730	1	1	-	-	1	-	1
5	600	-	1	1	-	-	-	1
6	530	-	1	1	1	1	-	1
7	500	1	1	1	1	1	1	-
8	435	-	1	1	-	-	1	-
9	345	-	1	1	-	-	1	1
10	280	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
11	220	1	-	1	1	1	1	1
12	165	1	-	-	-	-	1	1
Total		5	7	7	4	6	8	9

Figure (1): SCOT patterns of the *Earias insulana* larvae revealed by seven primers.

There were five bands in primer SCoT1 by molecular weight ranged between 730 to 165bp. SCoT2 and SCoT4 primers had seven bands with molecular weight ranged between 730 to 280bp and from 600 to 220bp. whereas, SCoT7 had four bands varied from 530 to 220bp. while, SCoT11 had six bands with molecular weight varied between 845 to 220bp., also, SCoT12 and 15 were eight and nine bands with molecular weight varied between 165 to 975bp., a unique band appeared in SCoT12 primer with 800bp, while, two monomorphic bands were appeared with primers (SCoT12 and SCoT15) by 975bp and (SCoT11 and SCoT15) by 845bp., whereas, nine polymorphic bands between all tested primers.

2. ISSR analysis:

Data illustrated in Table (2) showed five ISSR primers and their nucleotide

Table (4): Number and DNA bands molecular weight by the five ISSR primers for *Earias insulana* larvae.

Band No	M.W Bp	ISSR Primers				
		49A	49B	HB-10	HB-11	HB-12
1	1630	-	-	-	-	1
2	1375	-	1	1	-	1
3	1050	1	-	1	-	1
4	940	-	1	-	1	1
5	820	-	-	1	-	1
6	780	1	1	1	-	-
7	700	-	1	1	-	1
8	600	-	1	1	-	1
9	530	-	-	1	-	1
10	460	-	-	-	-	1
11	400	-	-	1	1	-
12	320	-	-	-	-	1
13	270	-	-	1	-	1
14	250	-	-	1	-	1
15	175	-	-	-	1	1
Total		2	5	10	3	13

sequences (49A, 49B, HB-10, HB-11 and HB-12) used to identify the *E. insulana* genome profile, these five primers resulted in different bands between 2 and 13, varying from 1630 to 175 base pairs for each primer. There were two bands in primer 49A by molecular weight ranged between 1050 to 780bp., while, primer 49B had five bands with molecular weight ranged between 1375 to 600bp. whereas, HB-10 primer had ten bands varied from 1375 to 250bp., also, primer HB-11 had three bands varied from 940 to 175bp., finally, primer HB-12 had thirteen bands ranged between 1630 to 175bp. showed in Table (4) and Figure (2).

Fifteen primers appeared in all primers between 2 and 13 different bands, varying from 175 to 1630 base pairs, were obtained by five primers screened of ISSR technique presented in Table (4).

Figure (2): ISSR patterns of the *Earias insulana* larvae revealed by five primers.

A unique band appeared in ISSR (HB-12) primer with band number 1 and 10 by 1630 and 460bp., respectively, while, three monomorphic bands were appeared with primers (HB-10 and HB-12) by 820, 270 and 250 bp. respectively, and (HB-10 and HB-11) by 400bp and (HB-11 and HB-12) by 175bp. Three polymorphic bands with primers (49B, HB-10 and HB-12) by 1375, 700 and 600bp. respectively whereas, polymorphic bands with primers (49A, 49B and HB-10) by 780bp., and primers (49B, HB-11 and HB-12) by 940 bp. and polymorphic bands with primers (49A, HB-10 and HB-12) by 1050 bp.

After identification of *E. insulana* genome profile, the electrophoretic

separation analysis of isozymes was done to identify the variations among studied strains. Native gel electrophoresis can detect enzymes such as polyphenyl oxidase and peroxidase.

3. Polyphenyl oxidase:

Polyphenyl oxidase activity of *E. insulana* from laboratory strain and different Governorates was electrophoretically showed in Table (5) and Figure (3). All larvae showed different bands; control (laboratory) larvae strain, Behera, Alexandria and Qaluobya Governorates showed two bands with different densities, whereas, Menofia and Sharkeya Governorates have only light band.

Table (5): Distribution of polyphenyl oxidase isozyme groups of *Earias insulana* populations according to their relative mobility's and densities.

Poly Phenol Oxidase	Relative mobility	Control laboratory	Behera	Alexandria	Menofia	Qaluobya	Sharkeya
PPO1	0.216	-	++	-	-	-	-
PPO2	0.258	-	-	++	-	-	-
PPO3	0.394	-	-	++	-	-	-
PPO4	0.474	-	-	-	-	+	-
PPO5	0.484	-	+++	-	-	-	-
PPO6	0.488	-	-	-	-	-	++
PPO7	0.531	-	-	-	+	-	-
PPO8	0.577	+	-	-	-	-	-
PPO9	0.606	-	-	-	-	++	-
PPO10	0.212	++	-	-	-	-	-

+ +Moderate density Band + Low density band - No Band. +++ High density Band

C: Control (Laboratory), 1:Behera, 2: Alexandria, 3:Menofia, 4:Qaluobya, 5: Sharkeya

Figure (3): Electrophoretic separation of polyphenyl oxidase isoforms from laboratory and different Governorates strain of *Earias insulana*.

4. Peroxidase:

Peroxidase enzyme of *E. insulana* from laboratory strain and different Governorates were electrophoretically showed in Figure (4) and Table (6), two bands were appeared in Alexandria governorate larvae with heavy density, while Behera governorate have one heavy band and Menofia Governorate have one moderate band, whereas, control (Laboratory),

Qaluobya and Sharkeya Governorates have only one band with low density. Two analysis methods were implemented to identify the *E. insulana* genome profile of laboratory strain for the first time in Egypt using two different techniques; SCoT and ISSR. Recognition of most parts of the *E. insulana* genome was achieved as the SCoT technique linked with genes on the other hand, ISSR technique linked among sequences.

Table (6): Distribution of peroxidase isozyme groups of *Earias insulana* populations according to their relative mobility's and densities.

Peroxidase	Relative mobility	Control Laboratory	Behera	Alexandria	Menofia	Qaluobya	Sharkeya
PX1	0.284	-	-	+++	-	-	-
PX2	0.512	-	-	-	-	-	-
PX3	0.517	-	+++	-	++	-	-
PX4	0.612	-	-	++	-	-	-
PX5	0.667	-	-	-	-	+	-
PX6	0.672	-	-	-	-	-	+
PX7	0.687	+	-	-	-	-	-

+ +Moderate density Band + Low density band - No Band. +++ High density Band

C: Control (Laboratory), 1:Behera, 2: Alexandria, 3:Menofia, 4:Qaluobya, 5: Sharkeya

Figure (4): Electrophoretic separation of peroxidase isoforms from laboratory and different Governorates strain of *Earias insulana*.

Using different techniques like SCoT, ISSR, RFLP or RAPD in genetic profile identification of an insect differs according to the purpose of the study. In this respect, many authors showed different genetic studies to identify insect genotypes or to evaluate genetic polymorphism, Levy *et al.* (1992) applied a simple method to analyze the two morphologically indistinguishable host associated strains of *S. frugiperda* using fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) marker, few nanograms of total DNA are needed to yield clear and accurate strain identification of individual insects. Also, Yuan *et al.* (2014) identified reference genes which should be used for accurate elucidation of the expression profiles of functional genes of *Nilaparvata lugens*. Whereas, Yanhong *et al.* (2018) identified some proteins might be directly correlated to the biological characteristics of the *Ericerus pela* eggs at the stage at which they were examined. In the population genetic study of *H. armigera* populations, (Endersby *et al.*, 2007) excluded 3 pairs of SSR markers with the greatest null allele frequencies (i.e., 19.2%, 31.6% and 47.4%). Luque *et al.* (2002) shown that some ISSR amplifications are possible and demonstrate their applicability in studying intra- and inter-specific variation in some Noctuidae populations they found that: (i)

(CA)_n primer gives the most informative profiles; (ii) DNA profiles between species differ substantially; (iii) comparison of ISSR profiles can be successfully applied to study intra-specific variation.

The genetic characterization of the gypsy moth from China (*Lymantria dispar*) provided by (Fang *et al.*, 2013), using five polymorphic Inter simple sequence repeat markers which produced reproducible banding patterns and revealed that ISSR markers are a highly informative and efficient tool for estimating the genetic variation and structure of the insect. Experiment of isozymes study were evaluated on spiny bollworm *E. insulana* field strains from five Governorates in Egypt (Behera, Alexandria, Menoufia, Qalyoubia and Sharkeya) compared with laboratory strain for their molecular diversity to identifying differences between field strains from different Governorates by isozymes as a molecular tool. In this respect, Sayed and El-Ghobary (2019) found that *E. insulana* populations were similar in the distribution and intensity of the peroxidase and polyphenol oxidase isoenzymes. On the other hand, many authors studied many other isozymes like, Scarpassa and Hamada (2003) found that the genetic relationships suggested by the comparison of 11 isozyme loci in four

species of the *Simulium perflavum* group indicate that these species are closely related.

It could be concluded that the identification of *E. insulana* genome with SCoT analysis technique for the first time in Egypt and ISSR analysis technique, using these two techniques had been recognized the most parts of the *E. insulana* genome, our findings may be helpful in genetic and genomic studies.

References

- Amer, A.E.A. (2015):** Economic artificial diets for rearing spiny bollworm, *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Journal of Plant Protection and Pathology, Mansoura University, 6 (3):527-534. <https://dx.doi.org/10.21608/JPPP.2015.53336>.
- Bartlett, A.C. (1981):** Isozyme polymorphism in populations of the pink bollworm. Ann. Entomol. Soc. Americ., 79:9-13. <https://doi.org/10.1093/aesa/74.1.9>.
- Cadenas, E. (1989):** Biochemistry of oxygen toxicity. Annu Rev Biochem, 58:79–110.
- Chrzanowski, G.; Leszczyński, B.; Czerniewicz, P.; Sytykiewicz, H.; Matok, H.; Krzyzanowski, R. and Sempruch, C. (2012):** Effect of phenolic acids from black currant, sour cherry and walnut on grain aphid (*Sitobion avenae* F.) development. Crop Prot., 35: 71–77.
- Collard, B.C.Y. and Mackill, D.J. (2009):** Start Codon Targeted (SCOT) Polymorphism: a simple novel DNA marker technique for generating gene-targeted markers in plants. Plant Mol. Biol. Rep., 27:86–93. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11105-008-0060-5>.
- Endersby, N.M.; Hoffmann, A.A.; McKechnie, S.W. and Weeks, A.R. (2007):** Is there genetic structure in populations of *Helicoverpa armigera* from Australia? Entomol. Exp. Appl., 122: 253–263. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0053448>.
- Fang, Chen; Juan, Shi; You-Qing, Luo; Shuang-yan, Sun and Min, Pu. (2013):** Genetic Characterization of the moth from China (Lepidoptera, Lymantriidae) Using Inter Simple Sequence Repeats Markers. PLoS One. 7:8(8): e73017. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0073017>.
- Fang, D. and Roose, M. (1997):** Identification of closely related citrus cultivars with inter-simple sequence repeat markers. Theoret. Appl. Genet. 95: 408–417. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s001220050577>.
- Foyer, C. H. and Harbinson, J. (1994):** Oxygen metabolism and the regulation of photosynthetic electron transport,” in Causes of Photo-oxidative Stresses and Amelioration of Defense Systems in Plants, C. H. Foyer and P. Mullineaux, Eds., pp. 1–42, CRC Press, Boca Raton, Fla, USA.
- Ge, X.J. and Sun, M. (1999):** Reproductive biology and genetic diversity of a cryptoviviparous mangrove *Aegiceras corniculatum* (Myrsinaceae) using allozyme and intersimple sequence repeat (ISSR) analysis. Mol. Ecol. , 8: 2061–2069. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-294x.1999.00821>.
- Gupta, M.; Chyi, Y.S.; Romero-Severson, J. and Owen, J.L. (1994):** Amplification of DNA markers from evolutionarily diverse genomes using single primers of simple sequence repeats. Theoret. Appl. Genet., 89:

- 998–1006.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00224530>.
- Gupta, P.K. and Rustgi, S. (2004):** Molecular markers from the transcribed /expressed region of the genome in higher plants. *Funct. Integr. Genomics.* 4:139–162. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10142-004-0107-0>.
- Havlíčková, L.; Jozová, E.; Rychlá, A.; Klima, M.; Kučera, V. and Čurn, V. (2014):** Genetic diversity assessment in winter oilseed rape (*Bras-sicanapus* L.) collection using AFLP, ISSR and SSR markers. *Czech Journal of Genetics and Plant Breeding,* 50: 216-225. <https://doi.org/10.17221/16/2015-CJGPB>.
- Huang, J. and Sun, M. (2000):** Genetic diversity and relationships of sweet potato and its wild relatives in *Ipomoea series* Batatas (Convolvulaceae) as revealed by inter-simple sequence repeat (ISSR) and restriction analysis of chloroplast DNA. *Theoret. Appl. Genet.,* 100: 1050–1060. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s001220051386>.
- Kandil, M.A.A. (2013):** Relationship between temperature and some biological aspects and biochemical of *Earias insulana* (Boisd.) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). *Egypt. Acad. J. Biolog. Sci.,* 6(1): 11-20.
- Krishnan, N.; Kodrík, D.; Turanli, F. and Sehnal, F. (2007):** Stage-specific distribution of oxidative radicals and antioxidant enzymes in the midgut of *Leptinotarsa decemlineata*. *J. Insect Physiol.,* 53: 67–74.
- Kumar, U.; Singh, D.V.; Sachan, S.K.; Bhatnagar, A. and Singh, R. (2014):** Insect pest complex of okra and biology of shoot and fruit borer, *Earias vittella* (F.). *Indian Journal of Entomology.* 76:29-31. <https://doi.org/10.5958/0974-8172.2018.00238.9>.
- Levy, Hazel C.; Garcia-Maruniak, Alejandra and Maruniak, James, E. (1992):** Strain identification of *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) insects and cell line: PCR-RFLP of cytochrome oxidase C subunit I gene. *Florida Entomologist,* 85(1): 186-190. <https://doi.org/10.1653/0015-4040>.
- Luque, C.; Legal, L.; Staudter, H.; Gers, C. and Wink, M. (2002):** ISSR (Inter Simple Sequence Repeats) as genetic markers in Noctuids (Lepidoptera). *Hereditas,* 136: 251–253. <https://doi.org/10.1034/j.1601-5223>.
- Matsumura, T.; Matsumoto, H. and Hayakawa, Y. (2017):** Heat stress hardening of oriental armyworms is induced by a transient elevation of reactive oxygen species during sublethal stress. *Arch. Insect Biochem. Physiol.,* 96:1–10.
- Nagaraju, J.; Reddy, K.; Nagaraja, G. and Sethuraman, B. (2001):** Comparison of multilocus RFLPs and PCR-based marker systems for genetic analysis of the silkworm, *Bombyx mori*. *Heredity,* 86: 588–597. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1365-2540.2001.00861.x>.
- Reddy, M. P.; Sarla, N. and Siddiq, E. A. (2002):** Inter simple sequence repeat (ISSR) polymorphism and its application in plant breeding. *Euphytica,* 128(1): 9-17. <https://doi.org/10.1023/A:1020691618797>.
- Sayed, R.M. and EL-Ghobary , A. M.A. (2019):** Molecular diversity in *Earias insulana* populations from different Egyptian Governorates . *International*

- Journal of Entomology Research., 4(3):10-15.
- Stegemann, H.; Afify, A. M. R. and Hussein, K. R. F. (1985):** Cultivar identification of dates (*Phoenix dactylifera*) by protein patterns. In 2nd international symposium of biochemical approaches to identification of cultivars. Braunschweig, West Germany (44).
- Scarpassa, V.M. and Hamada, N. (2003):** Isozyme variation in four species of the *Simulium perflavum* species group (Diptera: Simuliidae) from the Brazilian Amazon. Genetics and Molecular Biology, 26(1): 39-46. <https://doi.org/10.1590/S1415-47572003000100007>.
- Sugumaran, M. (1988):** Molecular mechanisms for cuticular sclerotization. Adv. Insect Physiol., 21(9): 179-231.
- Torres, M. A.; Dangel, J. L. and Jones, J. D. G. (2002):** Arabidopsis homologues AtrbohD and AtrbohF are required for accumulation of reactive oxygen intermediates in the plant defense response. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America, 99(1): 517–522.
- Williams, J. G. K.; Kubelk, A. R.; Livak, K. J.; Rafalski, J. A. and Tingey, S. V. (1990):** DNA polymorphisms amplified by arbitrary primers are useful as genetic markers. Nucl. Acid Res, 18: 6231-6235. <https://doi.org/10.1093/nar/18.22.6531>.
- Yanhong, Hu.; Xiaoming, Chen. and Pu, Yang. (2018):** Protein Profile Analysis of *Ericerus pela* (Hemiptera: Coccoidea) Egg. Journal of Insect Science, 18(1): 6:1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jisesa/iex107>.
- Yang, X. and Quiros, C.F. (1993):** Identification and classification of celery cultivars with RAPD markers. Theoretical and Applied Genetics, 86:205-212. <https://doi.org/10.1007/BF00222080>.
- Yuan, M.; Lu, Y.; Zhu, X.; Wan, H.; Shakeel, M.; Zhan, S.; Jin, B. and Li, J. (2014):** Selection and evaluation of potential reference genes for gene expression analysis in the brown planthopper, *Nilaparvata lugens* (Hemiptera: Delphacidae) using reverse-transcription quantitative PCR. Plos one, 9(1):1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0086503>.
- Zhang, S.; Fu, W.; Li, N.; Zhang, F.; Liu, T.X. (2015):** Antioxidant responses of *Propylaea japonica* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae) exposed to high temperature stress. J. Insect Physiol., 73: 47–52.
- Zhou, Z.; Miwa, M. and Hogetsu, T. (1999):** Analysis of genetic structure of a *Suillus grevillei* population in a *Larix kaempferi* stand by polymorphism of inter-simple sequence repeat (ISSR). New Phytol., 144: 55–63. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1469-8137.1999.00504.x>.

Instruction to authors

Original articles are full length papers describing original research. The paper should not exceed 15 pages of double-spaced typed text (including abstract, tables, figures and references). One double-spaced typed page contains approximately 300-350 words. Reviews are normally by invitation from the Editor-in-Chief. However, authors are encouraged to submit a tentative title and a table of contents of a proposed review for consideration. These reviews should not exceed 20 pages of double-spaced typed text (including abstract, tables, figures and references). Scientific notes and short communications to the Editor usually on matters of general concern to plant protection, are welcome but should not exceed 4 typed pages. The decision to publish submitted scientific notes and short communications with the Editor-in-Chief.

Manuscripts should be written in clear, concise, and grammatically correct English. Submission of a manuscript implies: that the work described has not been published before; that it is not under consideration for publication anywhere else. Authors should submit their manuscripts online. To the Email: shaabanabdrabou59@yahoo.com

Manuscript preparation

Title: The title should reflect the most important aspects of the article, in a preferably concise form of not more than 150 characters and spaces. By-line The authors' names should be followed by affiliations and addresses.

Abstracts are required for all the manuscripts. They should be typed in one paragraph and limited to max.150- 200 words. The abstract should not contain any undefined abbreviations or unspecified references.

Keywords: Most important words of paper. Should be from 4 to 6 words.

Text: Main text should contain (1) an Introduction (2) a Material and Methods (3) a Results (4) a Discussion (5) a Conclusion (6) a References

Text formatting: Use a normal, plain font (e.g., 14 Point Times Roman) for text.

Abbreviations should be defined at first mention and used consistently thereafter. Authors should adhere to the rules governing scientific nomenclature to the International Code of Zoological Nomenclature. All biotica (crops, plants, insects, birds, mammals, etc.) should be identified by their scientific names including authors (and Order: Family) when the English term is first used in the main text, with the exception of common domestic plants and animals. Scientific names should be as follows: In the Title only give the Latin name but No authority or (Order: Family); in the Abstract all Latin names should be accompanied with the correct authority and with (Order: Family); in addition, at the first mention in the body of the text - and only then - these data should be given; authority, the order, family, should also go in the Key Words list.

Footnotes

Footnotes on the title page are not given reference symbols. Footnotes to the text are numbered consecutively; those to tables should be indicated by superscript lower-case letters (or asterisks for significance values and other statistical data).

References

The list of References should only include works that are cited in the text and that have been published or accepted for publication. Personal communications and unpublished works should only be mentioned in the text.

Cite references in the text by name and year in parentheses. Some examples:

- Negotiation research spans many disciplines (Abd-Rabou, 1996).
- This result was later contradicted (Simmons and Abd-Rabou, 2009).
- This effect has been widely studied (Abd-Rabou, 1998; Simmons *et al.*, 2002; Evans and Abd-Rabou, 2005 and Abd-Rabou *et al.*, 2005).

List style

Reference list entries should be alphabetized by the last names of the first author of each work.

Journal article

Abd-Rabou, S. (1998): The efficacy of indigenous parasitoids in the biological control of *Siphoninus phillyreae* (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) on pomegranate in Egypt. Pan-Pacific Entomologists, 74 (3): 169-173.

Evans and Abd-Rabou (2005): Two new species and additional records of Egyptian Aphelinidae. Zootaxa, 833:1-7.

Simmons, A. and Abd-Rabou, S. (2006): Whitefly populations in vegetables crops with different fertilizers. 52nd Annual meeting of the South Carolina Entomological Society, Mc Cormick, Sc., October 19-20.

Abd-Rabou, S. and Simmons, A. M. (2012): *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) whitefly as a pest in Egypt. Advances In Agricultural Research In Egypt, 10 (1): 1-82.

Figures Line-drawing should be clear and of high quality. Cite all figures in numerical order in the manuscript.

Tables The title should be self-explanatory and include enough information so that each table is intelligible without reference to the text or other tables. The title should summarize the information presented in the table without repeating the subheadings. Subheadings should be brief, nonstandard ones can be explained in footnotes. Cite tables in numerical order in the manuscript. Information presented in a table should agree with that in the text.